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Schéma Théorique pour Détecter la Nature Quantique des Ondes Gravitationnelles Primordiales en Sondant les Caractéristiques Quantiques des Ondes Électromagnétiques

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Fateme SHOJAEI ARANI

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Thèse dirigée par

Alain BLANCHARD et Malek Bagheri HAROUNI

Composition du jury

M. Jean-Philippe UZAN, Président, CNRS Paris-Centre

M. Vincent VENNIN, Rapporteur, CNRS Paris-Centre

M. Behrouz MIRZA, Rapporteur, Isfahan University of Technology

M. Rasoul ROKNIZADEH, Examineur, University of Isfahan

Mme Ruth DURRER, Examinatrice, Université de Genève

M. Alain BLANCHARD, Directeur de thèse, Université Toulouse III - Paul Sabatier

M. Malek BAGHERI HAROUNI, Co-directeur de thèse, University of Isfahan

M. Brahim LAMINE, Co-directeur de thèse, Université Toulouse III - Paul Sabatier

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M. Ali MAHDIFAR, University of Isfahan

UNIVERSITÉ
TOULOUSE III
PAUL SABATIER Université
de Toulouse

University of Isfahan

Faculty of physics

Department of physics

and

Université Toulouse III - Paul Sabatier

Département de physique

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Theoretical Schema for Detecting Quantum Nature of Primordial Gravitational Waves by Probing the Quantum Features of Electromagnetic Waves

Supervisors:

Dr. Malek Bagheri Harouni

Dr. Brahim Lamine

Prof. Alain Blanchard

By:

Fateme Shojaei Arani

December 2024

Declaration of Authorship

I, Fateme Shojaei Arani, declare that this thesis titled, “Theoretical Schema for Detecting Quantum Nature of Primordial Gravitational Waves by Probing the Quantum Features of Electromagnetic Waves” and the work presented in it are my own. I confirm that:

- This work was done wholly or mainly while in candidature for a research degree at this University.
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- I have acknowledged all main sources of help.
- Where the thesis is based on work done by myself jointly with others, I have made clear exactly what was done by others and what I have contributed myself.

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made this work possible.*

Abstract

One of the fundamental outcomes of inflationary cosmology is that tensorial perturbations of spacetime, similar to the large-scale structure of our Universe, originate from quantum fluctuations during the inflationary epoch. Creation and amplification of inflationary-generated primordial gravitational waves lie in the middle of the crossroad where quantum mechanics meet cosmology. Thus, detecting their quantumness, especially their squeezed nature, not only paves the way to search for the quantum essence of gravitational waves but also may provide a hitherto inaccessible source of information about the early Universe. In this dissertation, we present a comprehensive investigation of the interaction between quantum gravitational waves and electromagnetic fields that are supposed to probe quantum spacetime. Using the optical medium analogy framework, we not only recover the usual results of a typical interferometer detector in terms of the phase shift, but we may also promote the investigation to a fully quantum mechanical one, where the application of the well-known quantum optical language in analog systems, helps understand the electromagnetic-gravitational wave interaction in a close-up. In particular, we assess the quadrature variance of the electromagnetic field and demonstrate the impossibility of witnessing the quantum nature of gravitational waves based on the revivals of optical squeezing. On the contrary, we show that primordial gravitational waves induce decoherence of the electromagnetic field and ruin temporal correlations after a characteristic time scale, which depends on the cosmological parameters, namely the inflationary index and the tensor-to-scalar ratio. Moreover, the apparition of sidebands in the optical spectrum may be viewed as a signature of the squeezed nature of relic gravitational waves. Moreover, we investigate the effect of quantum background of GWs on the phase correlations of EM field emitted from distant sources. We show that primordial gravitational waves placed in two-mode squeezed state could ruin van Citter-Zernike correlations, an effect called as the blurring of the visibility. Although the effect crucially depends on the value of tensor-to-scalar ratio, it turns out that for the current upper-bounds on this parameter, the incoherence effect is too feeble that can not ruin electromagnetic phase correlations. Nevertheless, we promote the idea of using spatial correlations of light as a new tool to explore the primordial gravitational background.

Key words: Primordial gravitational waves, Optical medium analogy, inflation cosmology, Gravitational decoherence, tensor to scalar ratio.

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Publications

During my PhD, I have had the opportunity to contribute to scientific research through the following publications:

Published

- [1] Arani, F. Shojaei, et al. "Sensing quantum nature of primordial gravitational waves using electromagnetic probes." *Physica Scripta* 98.5 (2023): 055004.

Results and materials presented in Chapter 7 is submitted to JCAP:

Submitted

- [2] Arani, Fateme Shojaei, et al. "Constraining tensor-to-scalar ratio based on VLBI observations: PGWs induced-incoherence approach." arXiv preprint arXiv:2312.00474 (2023).

In addition to the above, I am currently working on the following paper, which is in progress:

In Preparation

- Phase diffusion of light immersed in a quantum spacetime reservoir: open quantum system approach , in preparation

These publications reflect the main findings of my PhD research, and I look forward to further developing and expanding upon these contributions in the future.

Symbols and notation

Throughout the manuscript, we reserve the big Latin indices (Ω_K, \mathbf{K}) to denote the GW's frequency and wave vector, and the small Latin indices (ω_k, \mathbf{k}) to denote the EM frequency and wave vector. The squeezing amplitude of the PGWs mode K is denoted by r_K . To be consistent with the literature as much as possible, we reserve the index r_{k_0} to denote the tensor-to-scalar ratio at the pivot scale k_0 .

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Résumé français

1 Préface

Les prédictions réussies de la théorie de la relativité générale sont une preuve solide que les phénomènes gravitationnels peuvent être correctement compris et décrits en prenant en compte la courbure de l'espace-temps. En relativité générale, les effets gravitationnels de la matière se manifestent sous forme de courbure de l'espace-temps, et la propagation des particules et des champs se produit dans ce contexte courbé. À ce niveau d'examen, le champ gravitationnel est considéré classiquement, et les méthodes habituelles de la théorie quantique des champs dans l'espace-temps de Minkowski sont étendues autant que possible. Cette généralisation directe a conduit à la prédiction de phénomènes physiques riches et intéressants qui ont élargi notre vue sur la nature de la gravitation.

L'un des résultats physiques les plus importants de cette intégration est la création de particules dans les espaces-temps cosmologiques. Autrement dit, il est prévu que le champ gravitationnel très fort de l'espace-temps en expansion conduit à la production de gravitons, des paquets d'énergie de champ gravitationnel quantifiés. Dans ce processus, les fluctuations quantiques du vide sont étirées et finalement conduisent à la production de particules dans un état excité à deux modes. De plus, il est montré que les gravitons créés sont fortement intriqués. Ainsi, il est prévu qu'un fond d'ondes gravitationnelles anciennes, depuis le temps de l'expansion inflationniste jusqu'à aujourd'hui, soit répandu à travers l'univers, qui devrait maintenant être trouvé dans un état excité. En outre, ces ondes gravitationnelles anciennes montrent les caractéristiques des ondes gravitationnelles aléatoires. La production et l'évolution des ondes gravitationnelles primitives qui se sont formées pendant la période inflationniste dépendent de facteurs tels que le moment de la sortie de l'horizon pendant la période inflationniste, le moment de l'entrée dans l'horizon dans les périodes post-inflationnistes et la manière dont l'univers lui-même a évolué entre les deux. Par conséquent, ce que nous obtenons aujourd'hui de ces ondes gravitationnelles peut fournir des informations précieuses sur les conditions de l'époque inflationniste et l'évolution de l'univers après cela. En particulier, les ondes gravitationnelles aléatoires primitives fournissent des informations uniques sur la physique des énergies très élevées pendant la période

inflationniste, car contrairement à d'autres particules, les gravitons se sont rapidement désaccouplés des autres champs et se sont répandus librement dans l'univers primitif peu après leur naissance. Ainsi, ils portent des informations d'avant le moment de désaccouplement du rayonnement de fond cosmique.

Ainsi, la détection des ondes gravitationnelles aléatoires anciennes est activement recherchée et constitue l'une des principales lignes d'objectifs des détecteurs d'ondes gravitationnelles actuels et en développement, chacun dans sa propre fenêtre de fréquence : L'Observatoire d'ondes gravitationnelles par interférométrie laser LIGO, VIRGO, GEO, AIGO, LCGT, et ET, qui sont tous actifs dans la gamme de fréquences ($10^2 - 10^3$) Hz, les interféromètres spatiaux tels que l'antenne spatiale à interféromètre laser LISA, qui est sensible dans la gamme de fréquences ($10^{-4} - 10^{-1}$) Hz, l'observatoire Big Bang BBO et l'observatoire d'ondes gravitationnelles par interféromètre décimétrique DECIGO, qui sont tous deux actifs dans la gamme de fréquences (0.1 – 10) Hz, et l'ensemble de chronométrage de pulsars qui comprend PPTA et SKA, qui fonctionnent tous deux dans la plage de fréquences ($10^{-9} - 10^{-6}$) Hz. En outre, plusieurs plans ont été proposés pour détecter les ondes gravitationnelles anciennes à haute fréquence, basés sur des détect

eurs à ondes guidées, des détecteurs à faisceau maser Gaussien dans la gamme de gigahertz et de 100 mégahertz. D'autre part, la plage de fréquences extrêmement courte des ondes gravitationnelles anciennes, qui correspond à des dimensions de 10 à 10^4 mégaparsecs, est responsable de l'anisotropie et de la polarisation du rayonnement de fond cosmique, qui devraient être enregistrées par le satellite Wilkinson Microwave Anisotropy Probe, le satellite Planck, le satellite LiteBIRD et le télescope cosmologique Atacama.

La détection des ondes gravitationnelles anciennes, non seulement confirme la véracité de la théorie inflationniste, mais pourrait également valider la description quantique du champ gravitationnel à des échelles plus grandes que la longueur de Planck. En cosmologie standard, on pense que la période inflationniste a suivi la période de gravitation quantique, cependant, il n'existe encore aucune preuve expérimentale directe pour confirmer cette affirmation. En outre, la validité de la théorie de la gravitation quantique n'a pas encore été testée expérimentalement. De ce point de vue, les ondes gravitationnelles anciennes issues des fluctuations quantiques du vide pendant la période inflationniste constituent un laboratoire expérimental unique pour valider ces théories. Dans ce contexte, plusieurs plans pour détecter la nature quantique des ondes gravitationnelles anciennes, basés sur la nature excitée de ces ondes, sont examinés par les détecteurs d'ondes gravitationnelles terrestres et spatiaux, ainsi que par le suivi des traces gravées sur l'anisotropie et la polarisation du rayonnement de fond cosmique. Cependant, la détection de la nature quantique de ces ondes reste hors de portée expérimentale.

Inspiré par les sujets mentionnés ci-dessus, cette thèse aborde la question de

comment la nature quantique des ondes gravitationnelles anciennes peut être révélée par des détecteurs basés sur des ondes électromagnétiques, tels que les interféromètres laser et les interféromètres à très longue base. Pour atteindre cet objectif, nous commençons d'abord par établir un cadre théorique pour décrire l'interaction entre les ondes électromagnétiques et les ondes gravitationnelles. L'utilisation du concept de constance de l'environnement optique dans ce contexte facilite la résolution des équations de Maxwell et permet également de comprendre les phénomènes gravitationnels en termes de concepts optiques familiers. De plus, la transition au niveau quantique se fait simplement en mettant à niveau l'hamiltonien classique en quantique. En particulier, il est démontré que l'hamiltonien qui décrit l'interaction entre les ondes électromagnétiques et gravitationnelles est constant dans l'interaction cavité optomécanique, ouvrant ainsi une nouvelle voie pour découvrir la nature quantique des ondes gravitationnelles, à travers la constance avec son analogue optomécanique. Un examen détaillé de ce sujet révèle que les ondes gravitationnelles anciennes causent une cohérence (disparition des corrélations temporelles) de l'onde électromagnétique, ce qui à son tour affecte la détection des évolutions cohérentes du champ électromagnétique résultant des propriétés quantiques des ondes gravitationnelles. Cependant, nous montrons que les corrélations spatiales du rayonnement électromagnétique émis par des sources très éloignées, telles que le rayonnement micro-ondes des pulsars lointains, peuvent fournir des informations précieuses sur les ondes gravitationnelles anciennes qui sont présentes dans l'arrière-plan de la propagation des ondes électromagnétiques.

Dans la suite de cette section, nous commencerons d'abord par un bref aperçu des ondes gravitationnelles anciennes issues des fluctuations du vide pendant la période inflationniste et présenterons des caractéristiques telles que l'amplitude du spectre de ces ondes en fonction de la fréquence et l'amplitude de l'excitation des différents modes, au moment présent. Dans la section suivante,

des concepts tels que la constance de l'environnement lumineux, l'hamiltonien d'interaction, et la dynamique du champ électromagnétique en présence d'un fond d'ondes gravitationnelles quantifiées seront examinés, ce qui constitue la pierre angulaire des calculs ultérieurs. Les sujets tels que la cohérence et l'incohérence résultant de la gravité dans les sections suivantes seront examinés. Cette résumé se termine par un accent sur les résultats novateurs obtenus à partir de la recherche actuelle et une perspective pour des études plus approfondies.

2 Ondes gravitationnelles anciennes issues des fluctuations quantiques de la période inflationniste

Les ondes gravitationnelles sont des perturbations $h_{\mu\nu}(\mathbf{x})$ de la métrique de l'espace-temps

$$g_{\alpha\beta} = \bar{g}_{\alpha\beta} + h_{\alpha\beta}, \quad |h_{\alpha\beta}| \ll 1, \quad \alpha, \beta = 0, 1, 2, 3 \quad (1)$$

Dans l'expression ci-dessus, $g_{\mu\nu}$ représente la métrique de l'espace-temps non perturbée, qui peut être, par exemple, la métrique de Minkowski ou la métrique d'un univers en expansion. En écrivant les équations d'Einstein, il peut être démontré que les perturbations de la métrique suivent l'équation de d'Alembert. La théorie de la relativité générale d'Einstein prédit ainsi l'existence des ondes gravitationnelles, qui sont des perturbations de l'espace-temps se propageant à la vitesse de la lumière. En examinant les détails plus précisément, il peut être montré que les ondes gravitationnelles, en tant que champ tensoriel de rang deux, possèdent deux modes de polarisation distincts, correspondant à deux degrés de liberté dans la théorie des champs quantiques. Dans la jauge transverse-traceless, les ondes gravitationnelles peuvent être exprimées en termes d'ondes planes comme suit :

$$h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta) = \sum_{\gamma=+, \times} \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{K}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} e_{ij}^{\gamma}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] (h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma}(\eta) e^{i\mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x}} + h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma*}(\eta) e^{-i\mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x}}). \quad (2)$$

Dans l'expression ci-dessus, $i, j = 1, 2, 3$ sont les indices spatiaux, \mathbf{K} est le vecteur d'onde gravitationnelle et $\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}$ est la fréquence de l'onde gravitationnelle. Le tenseur spatial $e_{ij}^{\gamma}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}]$ est le tenseur de polarisation de l'onde gravitationnelle avec une polarisation $\gamma = +, \times$. La quantité $h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma}(\eta)$ est appelée l'amplitude du champ de Fourier, qui est liée au spectre de puissance de l'onde gravitationnelle. Ici, η représente les coordonnées temporelles. Si les perturbations de la métrique de l'espace-temps de Minkowski sont considérées, η est la même que la coordonnée temporelle t . Si les perturbations de la métrique d'un univers en expansion sont considérées, η pourrait être le temps conforme. Pour décrire les perturbations métriques dans un univers homogène et isotrope en expansion, la métrique de Friedmann-Robertson-Walker perturbée est introduite comme suit :

$$ds^2 = a^2(\eta) \left[-d\eta^2 + (\delta_{ij} + h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta)) dx^i dx^j \right]. \quad (3)$$

où $a(\eta)$ est appelé le facteur d'échelle et fournit une mesure de la taille de l'univers, et la dynamique de l'expansion de l'univers est liée à la dynamique de ce facteur. La quantité $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta)$ représente les perturbations tensorielles de jauge-invariantes qui

possèdent des propriétés transversales sans trace, c'est-à-dire $\partial^i h_{ij} = 0$ et $\delta^{ij} h_{ij} = 0$. L'expansion générale de l'équation (2) peut décrire les perturbations tensorielles de la métrique de Friedmann. Dans ce cas, les équations d'Einstein-Friedmann qui déterminent l'évolution de la métrique et ses perturbations requièrent que :

$$h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma\prime\prime}(\eta) + 2\frac{a'(\eta)}{a(\eta)}h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma\prime}(\eta) + K^2 h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma}(\eta) = 0. \quad (4)$$

Ainsi, en plus du facteur oscillatoire déterminé par le coefficient K^2 , l'expansion de l'univers, qui est représentée ici par le facteur $\mathcal{H} \equiv a'(\eta)/a(\eta)$, peut globalement modifier la dynamique de l'amplitude des ondes gravitationnelles. Le terme \mathcal{H} n'est rien d'autre que le paramètre de Hubble en coordonnées conformes. Les ondes sub-Hubble, pour lesquelles $\mathcal{H} \ll K$, subissent leur évolution normale dans un univers en expansion, accompagnée d'une diminution de l'amplitude de l'onde gravitationnelle proportionnelle à $1/a(\eta)$. Pour les ondes super-Hubble $\mathcal{H} \gg K$, l'amplitude du champ gravitationnel non seulement ne diminue pas, mais reste constante tant que le régime super-Hubble persiste. Il peut être démontré que l'équation (4) décrit un oscillateur forcé dont la fréquence est dépendante du temps. Du point de vue classique, cela signifie un échange d'énergie entre le système, ici l'onde gravitationnelle, et son environnement, ici l'espace-temps en expansion. Du point de vue de la mécanique quantique, cela est directement lié à la production de particules d'ondes gravitationnelles, c'est-à-dire des gravitons, par le moteur de pompage de l'univers en expansion. Cet événement, qui est examiné en détail sous le nom de 'production de particules dans des espaces-temps cosmologiques', est ici uniquement discuté en termes de ses résultats et de son application à nos problèmes d'intérêt, et les détails des calculs sont laissés au texte principal de la thèse.

Une autre quantité souvent considérée dans la littérature sur les ondes gravitationnelles primordiales est appelée l'amplitude spectrale, notée $h(K, \eta)$, qui est proportionnelle à l'amplitude du champ $h_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)$. Ainsi, il peut être montré que l'amplitude spectrale des ondes gravitationnelles primordiales d'origine quantique serait aujourd'hui comme suit :

$$h(K, \eta_H) = \begin{cases} A \left(\frac{K}{K_H}\right)^{2+\beta} & , \quad K \leq K_E \\ A \left(\frac{K}{K_H}\right)^{\beta-\gamma} \zeta_E^{-\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}} & , \quad K_E \leq K \leq K_H \\ A \left(\frac{K}{K_H}\right)^{\beta} \zeta_E^{-\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}} & , \quad K_H \leq K \leq K_2 \\ A \left(\frac{K}{K_H}\right)^{1+\beta} \left(\frac{K_H}{K_2}\right) \zeta_E^{-\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}} & , \quad K_2 \leq K \leq K_s \\ A \left(\frac{K}{K_H}\right)^{1+\beta-\beta_s} \left(\frac{K_s}{K_H}\right)^{\beta_s} \left(\frac{K_H}{K_2}\right) \zeta_E^{-\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}} & , \quad K_s \leq K \leq K_1. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

où les nombres d'onde caractéristiques K_E, K_H, K_2, K_s, K_1 sont entièrement définis et spécifiés dans le texte principal. Ainsi, en disposant du spectre actuel des ondes gravitationnelles primordiales, nous pouvons obtenir l'amplitude de compression,

r_K associée à chaque mode K des ondes gravitationnelles primordiales. Il est démontré que l'amplitude de polarisation est conforme à la relation suivante :

$$e^{r_K} = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{K}{K_1}\right)^{1+\beta} \left(\frac{K_2}{K_E}\right)^2 \left(\frac{K_s}{K_1}\right)^{-\beta_s} \left(\frac{K_1}{K_2}\right) \left(\frac{K_H}{K_E}\right)^\gamma, & K \leq K_E \\ \left(\frac{K}{K_1}\right)^{1+\beta} \left(\frac{K_1}{K_H}\right) \left(\frac{K_2}{K_H}\right) \left(\frac{K_E}{K_H}\right)^{-(2+\gamma)} \left(\frac{K_s}{K_1}\right)^{-\beta_s}, & K_E \leq K \leq K_H \\ \left(\frac{K}{K_2}\right)^{\beta-1} \left(\frac{K_2}{K_1}\right)^\beta \left(\frac{K_s}{K_1}\right)^{-\beta_s}, & K_2 \leq K \leq K_H \\ \left(\frac{K}{K_s}\right)^\beta \left(\frac{K_s}{K_1}\right)^{\beta-\beta_s}, & K_s \leq K \leq K_2 \\ \left(\frac{K}{K_1}\right)^{\beta-\beta_s}, & K_1 \leq K \leq K_s \\ 1, & K \geq K_1. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

En ayant cette quantité, nous pouvons obtenir le nombre moyen de gravitons produits dans chaque mode K via $\bar{n}(K) = \sinh^2 r_K \simeq e^{2r_K}/4$. Notez que l'expression ci-dessus est valide pour les modes qui ont vécu dans le régime super-Hubble et pour lesquels l'amplitude de compression $r_K \gg 1$ est.

3 Cadre théorique pour la description de l'interaction électromagnétique-gravitationnelle

Dans la présente étude, un cadre de constance de l'environnement matériel a été utilisé pour décrire l'interaction des ondes électromagnétiques et gravitationnelles. Dans ce cadre, les effets gravitationnels apparaissent efficacement sous la forme d'un milieu magnéto-diélectrique hétérogène et anisotrope, où les tenseurs de perméabilité électrique et magnétique sont déterminés par les composants métriques de l'espace-temps. Ainsi, pour l'espace-temps de Minkowski perturbé, qui décrit la propagation des ondes gravitationnelles, les tenseurs électriques et magnétiques sont égaux et sont égaux à

$$\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)/\varepsilon_0 = \mu_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)/\mu_0 = g_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t). \quad (7)$$

Dans cela, $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ a une expansion similaire à l'équation (2). Avec cette interprétation, la prochaine étape consiste à trouver les réponses propres des équations de Maxwell dans ce milieu matériel, créées par les ondes gravitationnelles $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$. Dans ce contexte, l'utilisation de l'approximation de la variation lente est très utile pour simplifier les équations. Cette approximation repose sur le fait physique que le taux de changement de l'onde électromagnétique, qui est déterminé par la fréquence de l'onde électromagnétique ω_0 , est beaucoup plus élevé que le taux de changements du fond des ondes gravitationnelles, qui est déterminé par la fréquence de l'onde gravitationnelle Ω_K . En d'autres termes, le temps caractéristique de l'évolution du champ électromagnétique est beaucoup plus court que le temps caractéristique de l'onde gravitationnelle et dans l'intervalle de temps

où le champ électromagnétique oscille, le champ gravitationnel est pratiquement constant. Étant donné la limite supérieure sur la fréquence des ondes gravitationnelles primordiales, c'est-à-dire $f_1 \lesssim 4 \times 10^{10}$ Hz, cette approximation est applicable aux ondes électromagnétiques dans la gamme optique. Cependant, il convient de noter que l'amplitude spectrale des ondes gravitationnelles primordiales diminue avec l'augmentation de la fréquence (ou du nombre d'onde), de sorte que la majorité des effets restants sur le champ électromagnétique provient de la partie à très haute fréquence des ondes gravitationnelles primordiales, qui contient également un très grand nombre de contenus gravitoniques. Par conséquent, l'approximation de la variation lente peut également être généralisée à la partie des ondes radio avec des fréquences de l'ordre du gigahertz.

Ainsi, la résolution des équations de Maxwell se réduit à résoudre une équation de Fresnel généralisée, dont la réponse donne l'indice de réfraction du milieu comme suit :

$$n_k(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sqrt{\frac{\det(\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t))}{\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j}}. \quad (8)$$

Dans cette relation, le tenseur de permittivité électrique est donné par les équations (2,7), et $\hat{\mathbf{k}}_i$ représente la composante i du vecteur d'onde électromagnétique \mathbf{k} . Ainsi, les fonctions propres des modes spatiaux et temporels sont obtenues comme suit :

$$\begin{aligned} v_k(\mathbf{x}, t) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t)}} e^{\pm i \int_0^t \omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t') dt'}, \\ \mathbf{F}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) &= \frac{\hat{\mathbf{u}} e^{i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}}}{(2\pi)^{3/2} \sqrt{m(t)}}, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

dans laquelle, la fréquence dépendante du temps du champ électromagnétique est définie comme suit :

$$\omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t) = \omega_k \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j \right), \quad (10)$$

et ω_k est la fréquence initiale de l'onde électromagnétique, en l'absence de fond d'ondes gravitationnelles. Avec cette interprétation, la présence des ondes gravitationnelles provoque une modification de la fréquence de l'onde électromagnétique comme indiqué ci-dessus, et cela modifie les fonctions propres temporelles et spatiales comme indiqué dans la relation (9). En l'absence d'ondes gravitationnelles, ces relations se réduisent aux réponses attendues dans l'espace vide. Par conséquent, l'examen des effets gravitationnels au niveau de la description classique est facilité par les relations précédentes. Par exemple, des effets tels que le "déplacement résiduel", qui signifie le déplacement de la fréquence de l'onde électromagnétique en présence d'ondes gravitationnelles et qui a été précédemment obtenu dans

la littérature sur les ondes gravitationnelles dans le cadre de l'optique géométrique et des équations de géodésie, sont maintenant récupérés dans le cadre de l'optique ondulatoire en utilisant le cadre de constance de l'environnement optique. De plus, des caractéristiques telles que la polarisation de l'onde électromagnétique sont également examinables dans le cadre actuel. Par exemple, il peut être démontré que le milieu effectif des ondes gravitationnelles se comporte comme un milieu biréfringent, et selon la polarisation de l'onde incidente, l'indice de réfraction du milieu sera différent.

Avec les réponses propres des équations de Maxwell en présence d'ondes gravitationnelles, la construction du lagrangien du système et le hamiltonien correspondant sont effectués de manière standard. En particulier, au niveau quantique, il peut être montré que le hamiltonien décrivant l'interaction d'un champ électromagnétique monomodal avec un continuum d'ondes gravitationnelles est donné par la relation suivante :

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}_{\text{int}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)/\hbar &= -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}} \right) \frac{\sqrt{16\pi c^3}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \sum_{\gamma=+,x} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \frac{F_\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}})}{\sqrt{2\Omega_K}} \\ &\times \left(\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K},\gamma} e^{-i\Omega_K t} g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) + \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K},\gamma}^\dagger e^{i\Omega_K t} g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) \right) \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

dans laquelle les opérateurs bosoniques $(\hat{a}_k, \hat{a}_k^\dagger)$ et $(\hat{b}_K, \hat{b}_K^\dagger)$ représentent respectivement les opérateurs d'échelle pour le champ électromagnétique monomodal, avec le vecteur d'onde et la polarisation $k \equiv (\sigma, \mathbf{k})$ et également pour l'onde gravitationnelle avec le vecteur d'onde et la polarisation $K \equiv (\gamma, \mathbf{K})$. De plus, la fonction de motif du détecteur est définie comme suit :

$$F_\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) \equiv e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j, \quad (12)$$

ce qui inclut l'orientation et la configuration du système électromagnétique par rapport aux ondes gravitationnelles en propagation. Comme le montre la forme hamiltonienne de la relation (11), le couplage électromagnétique-gravitationnel dépend de l'intensité, c'est-à-dire de l'opérateur du nombre de photons $\hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k$. De plus, ce couplage, en raison de la présence de termes tels que $\hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k \hat{b}_K$ et $\hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{a}_k$, est similaire au phénomène de mélange tri-ondulatoire en optique non linéaire et rappelle aussi le couplage en optomécanique de cavité. En optomécanique de cavité, la pression de radiation du champ électromagnétique à l'intérieur de la cavité provoque un mouvement oscillatoire du miroir arrière de la cavité, et ce mouvement module à son tour les fréquences propres de la cavité. Ainsi, le champ électromagnétique est intensément couplé avec le miroir de masse microscopique, influençant mutuellement leur évolution. Dans le cas du couplage électromagnétique-gravitationnel de la relation (11), les ondes gravitationnelles agissent efficacement comme le miroir arrière mobile d'une cavité, provoquant la modulation de la fréquence de l'onde

électromagnétique. De ce point de vue, la correspondance suivante peut être établie entre l'onde gravitationnelle et le miroir arrière mobile de la cavité optomécanique :

L'amplitude du champ oscillatoire de l'onde gravitationnelle \longleftrightarrow L'amplitude de déplacement de l'oscillateur mésoscopique dans la cavité optomécanique

Inspiré par les efforts antérieurs dans le domaine de l'optomécanique pour accéder au comportement quantique de l'oscillateur mésoscopique, il est maintenant possible d'espérer que cette correspondance ouvre une nouvelle voie pour la détection du comportement quantique des ondes gravitationnelles. Comme exemple spécifique pour le système de cavité optomécanique, cette proposition a été examinée et envisagée que le couplage du champ de radiation avec l'oscillateur mésoscopique ne peut provoquer la révivification de la chiralité des composantes de quadrature du champ électromagnétique que si l'oscillateur mésoscopique possède une nature quantique et que son comportement est décrit et analysé dans le cadre de la mécanique quantique. Sinon, la révivification de la chiralité des composantes de quadrature du champ électromagnétique ne se produira pas. Ainsi, il est suggéré que si ce comportement du champ électromagnétique peut être validé expérimentalement, alors la nature quantique de l'oscillateur mésoscopique sera confirmée. Pour enquêter et généraliser ce point au cas du couplage électromagnétique-gravitationnel, nous devons révéler la dynamique du champ électromagnétique.

Avec l'aide de l'Hamiltonien de la relation (11) et en résolvant les équations de Heisenberg, il est découvert que l'opérateur d'échelle destructeur du champ électromagnétique est déterminé par la relation suivante

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= \left[\prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathcal{R}^{3+}} \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa_{\gamma}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k})\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \right. \\ &\quad \otimes \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa_{\gamma}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k})\eta_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))] \\ &\quad \times e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^{\dagger} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} + \frac{1}{2})} e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} t} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Dans la relation ci-dessus, l'opérateur $\hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\zeta)$ représente l'opérateur de déplacement pour le mode $K \equiv (\gamma, \mathbf{K})$ du champ des ondes gravitationnelles, et d'autres quantités telles que $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$, $\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ et $\kappa_{\gamma}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k})$ sont définies dans la section 5.2.2 du texte principal de la thèse. Ainsi, alors que la dernière phrase de l'expression (13) indique l'évolution libre du champ électromagnétique en l'absence d'ondes gravitationnelles, les autres phrases contiennent les effets de l'interaction entre les ondes gravitationnelles et le champ électromagnétique. Le résultat du calcul des observables du champ électromagnétique dépend de l'état initial du champ des ondes gravitationnelles. Dans la présente recherche, nous avons calculé ces quantités pour différents états du champ des ondes gravitationnelles, y compris : le vide continu du champ gravitationnel, les ondes gravitationnelles dans un état

cohérent, les ondes gravitationnelles dans un état de compression monomodal et bimodal, ainsi que dans un état thermique.

Par exemple, la variance des composantes de quadrature du champ électromagnétique dans un cas où les ondes gravitationnelles sont dans un état de compression bimodal et le champ électromagnétique est dans un état cohérent $|\alpha\rangle$, est donnée par la relation suivante

$$\begin{aligned}
[\Delta\hat{\chi}_\vartheta(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]_{\text{ts}}^2 &= 1 + 2|\alpha|^2 \left\{ e^{-|\alpha|^2(1-\cos 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{-4(\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + \mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \right. \\
&\times \cos[-2\vartheta + 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + |\alpha|^2 \sin 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + 2\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)] \\
&- e^{-2|\alpha|^2(1-\cos 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{-2(\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + \mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \\
&\times \cos[-2\vartheta + 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + 2|\alpha|^2 \sin 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)] \\
&\left. + 1 - e^{-4|\alpha|^2 \sin^2 E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} e^{-2(\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + \mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \right\}, \quad (14)
\end{aligned}$$

dans laquelle ϑ est le paramètre de réglage de phase des composantes de quadrature, et les autres fonctions sont définies comme suit :

$$\begin{aligned}
E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &\equiv \sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa_\gamma^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 (\Omega_K t - \sin(\Omega_K t)), \quad (15) \\
\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_\gamma \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa_\gamma^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) (4 \sin^2(\frac{\Omega_K t}{2})) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2, \\
\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= \sum_\gamma \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa_\gamma^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \left\{ (4\bar{n}_{\text{ts}}(K) \sin^2(\frac{\Omega_K t}{2})) \right. \\
&\left. + \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K (\cos[2\phi_K] - 2 \cos[2\phi_K - \Omega_K t] + \cos[2\phi_K - 2\Omega_K t]) \right\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Dans les relations ci-dessus, $E_{\text{Pl}} = 1.9561 \times 10^9 \text{J}$ est l'énergie de Planck, r_K et $2\phi_K$ représentent respectivement l'amplitude et la phase de la compression des ondes gravitationnelles primordiales. Le rapport déterminant $(\hbar\omega_k/E_{\text{Pl}})^2$ (qui est à l'intérieur du coefficient κ_γ) définit la force de l'interaction. Pour des fréquences optiques $\omega_k \sim 10^{15} \text{Hz}$, ce rapport est de l'ordre de 10^{-58} , ce qui est extrêmement négligeable. Par conséquent, la détection des effets quantiques des ondes gravitationnelles par des capteurs électromagnétiques dépend de conditions où le couplage électromagnétique-gravitationnel très faible est efficacement amplifié. Bien que pour des fréquences plus élevées du champ électromagnétique, ce couplage soit plus fort, il reste cependant très faible. Comme il ressort des relations ci-dessus, les fonctions $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ et $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ contribuent toutes deux aux évolutions cohérentes et incohérentes du champ électromagnétique, tandis que la fonction $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ provoque uniquement un comportement de décroissance du champ électromagnétique. Plus précisément, le facteur qui pourrait influencer le comportement oscillatoire et la révivification de la variance de chiralité est défini par les fonctions $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ et $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$, qui sont malheureusement très insignifiantes

dans le système électromagnétique-gravitationnel et sont en pratique négligeables. En revanche, la fonction $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$, qui représente la contribution de la nature bimodale comprimée des ondes gravitationnelles primordiales à la variance du champ, pourrait avoir un effet observable sur la variance du champ, à condition que le nombre moyen de gravitons soit suffisamment élevé pour améliorer un couplage autrement insignifiant. Autrement dit, lorsque $\bar{n}_{\text{ts}}(K) \sim 10^{58}$, les effets des ondes gravitationnelles primordiales sur le champ seront visibles, bien que ces effets provoquent en réalité la décohérence du champ électromagnétique. Il apparaît également dans la relation (15) que, outre le nombre moyen de gravitons, les corrélations quantiques entre les gravitons dans l'état comprimé bimodal, de type $\langle \hat{b}_K \hat{b}_K \rangle$ et $\langle \hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{b}_K^\dagger \rangle$ et proportionnelles à $\sinh 2r_K$, jouent un double rôle dans la décohérence. Enfin, en négligeant les effets insignifiants dus au vide du champ gravitationnel fournis par les deux fonctions $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ et $D^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$, la variance de la relation (14) peut être réécrite comme suit

$$[\Delta \hat{\chi}_{1,\theta}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]_{\text{ts}}^2 = 1 + 2|\alpha|^2 (e^{-2\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} - 1)^2, \quad (16)$$

Ainsi, la variance du champ commence à partir d'une valeur initiale de $[\Delta \hat{\chi}_{1,\theta}(t=0)]_{\text{ts}}^2 = 1$, augmente avec le temps jusqu'à atteindre une valeur finale de $1 + 2|\alpha|^2$, et reste stable dans cet état permanent. De manière équivalente, dans un système de cavité optomécanique, ce comportement est similaire à celui où l'oscillateur méso-scopique est dans un état thermique avec un nombre moyen de phonons thermiques \bar{n}_{th} et le champ électromagnétique est dans un état cohérent $|\alpha\rangle$. Là aussi, la variance du champ augmente à partir d'une valeur initiale de $[\Delta \hat{\chi}_{1,\theta}(t=0)]_{\text{th}}^2 = 1$ pour rester à la valeur finale de $1 + 2|\alpha|^2$. Ainsi, la variance adopte toujours une valeur supérieure à 1, et la possibilité de compression, qui correspond à $[\Delta \hat{\chi}_{1,\theta}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]_{\text{ts}}^2 < 1$, est exclue. Par conséquent, il semble que la détection de la nature quantique des ondes gravitationnelles anciennes en établissant une correspondance avec un système de cavité optomécanique ne sera pas fructueuse.

4 Décohérence causée par les ondes gravitationnelles

Un des aspects inévitables de l'interaction électromagnétique-gravitationnelle est la décohérence causée par la gravité. En d'autres termes, comme discuté en détail dans le texte de la thèse, l'interaction du champ électromagnétique avec un continuum d'ondes gravitationnelles quantiques entraîne la perte de corrélations temporelles du champ électromagnétique. En général, les corrélations spatio-temporelles du champ électromagnétique en présence d'un fond d'ondes gravitationnelles dépendent non seulement de l'état quantique du champ d'ondes gravi-

tationnelles mais héritent également des caractéristiques statistiques et des corrélations spatio-temporelles du champ d'ondes gravitationnelles. Par exemple, si le champ d'ondes gravitationnelles présente statistiquement les caractéristiques d'un champ aléatoire, c'est-à-dire que les perturbations de l'espace-temps sont statistiquement homogènes, isotropes et non polarisées, ces caractéristiques seront mappées sur les fonctions de corrélation du champ électromagnétique.

Par exemple, les ondes gravitationnelles anciennes qui sont dans un état de compression bimodal montrent les caractéristiques d'ondes aléatoires. Dans ce cas, nous montrons que la fonction de corrélation temporelle du premier ordre du champ électromagnétique (dans la limite de coïncidence spatiale) en présence d'ondes gravitationnelles anciennes dans un état de compression bimodal est déterminée par la relation suivante

$$g_{\text{ts}}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) = g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau)}, \quad (17)$$

dans laquelle $g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau)$ englobe les effets des fluctuations quantiques du champ d'ondes gravitationnelles, qui sont en pratique très négligeables et peuvent être ignorés. La seconde partie de la relation ci-dessus indique un comportement de décroissance des corrélations temporelles dues à la nature des ondes gravitationnelles dans un état de compression bimodal, qui est défini par la relation suivante

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) &= \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \left\{ \sinh^2 r_K \left(4 \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Omega_K \tau}{2} \right) \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K (\cos[2\phi_K] - 2 \cos[2\phi_K - \Omega_K \tau] + \cos[2\phi_K - 2\Omega_K \tau]) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

en considérant $\phi_K = 0$, la relation ci-dessus se simplifie comme suit

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\tau) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar \omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}} \right)^2 \int d\Phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) \sin^4 \Theta_K \\ &\quad \times \int_{K_E}^{K_1} \frac{dK}{K} \frac{e^{2r_K}}{4} \left(8 \sin^4 \left(\frac{\Omega_K \tau}{2} \right) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

dans lequel l'intégration sur les angles polaires et azimutaux du vecteur d'onde gravitationnelle a été effectuée, et seule l'intégration sur la partie radiale reste. Pour calculer cette intégrale, la relation (6) est utilisée pour substituer l'expression e^{2r_K} . De plus, pour estimer l'intégrale et obtenir le résultat analytique, on peut tirer parti du fait que la contribution majeure de l'intégrale ci-dessus provient des fréquences très basses ou des longueurs d'onde très longues qui contiennent d'énormes quantités de contenu gravitonique et peuvent donc laisser des effets observables. Le calcul précis de l'expression (19) donne le résultat que les corrélations temporelles existent pour des délais $\tau \lesssim 10^4$ s et qu'il n'y a pas de corrélations pour des délais plus longs que cela. Par conséquent, l'approximation $\Omega_K \tau \ll 1$ signifie choisir

une limite supérieure de fréquence $\Omega_K \lesssim 10^{-4}\text{s}^{-1}$. En utilisant cette approximation, l'expression ci-dessus se simplifie comme suit

$$\mathcal{D}_{\phi_K=0}^{\text{ts}}(\tau) \simeq \left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_{\text{ts}}}\right)^4, \quad (20)$$

dans lequel le temps de décohérence causé par les ondes gravitationnelles anciennes dans un état comprimé bimodal est défini comme suit

$$\tau_{\text{ts}} = \left[\frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}} \right)^2 \int d\Phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) \sin^4 \Theta_K \int_{K_E}^{K_1} \frac{dK}{K} \frac{e^{2r_K \Omega_K^4}}{8} \right]^{-1/4}. \quad (21)$$

Dans l'équation ci-dessus, la valeur numérique est obtenue en substituant l'expression e^{2r_K} de la relation (19). L'amplitude de compression r_K des ondes gravitationnelles anciennes est déterminée par des paramètres de l'époque inflationniste, tels que le rapport tensoriel à scalaire r_{k_0} (ne pas confondre avec l'amplitude de compression) et l'indice inflationniste β . Pour sondes à petite échelle $KL \ll 1$, temps de décohérence pour une valeur de $\beta = -2$, qui décrit l'espace-temps de de Sitter pendant l'inflation, et pour les valeurs $r_{k_0} = 10^{-2}$ et $r_{k_0} = 10^{-3}$ est respectivement de $\tau_{\text{ts}} = 1.07 \times 10^4$ s et $\tau_{\text{ts}} = 1.9 \times 10^4$ s. Ainsi, une augmentation du rapport tensoriel à scalaire entraîne une réduction du temps de décohérence. Ce résultat est attendu, car une augmentation du rapport tensoriel à scalaire signifie une augmentation de l'amplitude du champ des ondes gravitationnelles anciennes, ce qui entraîne une interaction plus forte avec le champ électromagnétique. Par conséquent, les effets de décohérence dus à l'interaction gravitationnelle se produisent également plus rapidement.

Il est donc attendu que si une expérience interférométrique peut être conçue avec une source de champ cohérent laser ayant un temps de cohérence supérieur à 10^4 s, et que cet explorateur balaye l'espace pendant 10^4 s puis mesure les corrélations du champ entre les moments initial et final, il serait en principe possible de détecter les traces des ondes gravitationnelles anciennes comme un facteur de décohérence du champ électromagnétique. Toutefois, ce résultat est conditionné par le fait que le champ électromagnétique soit isolé de toutes autres sources de décohérence pendant toute la durée.

D'autre part, la décohérence gravitationnelle provoque également un élargissement de la largeur de ligne du laser. Cet élargissement est inversement proportionnel au temps de décohérence et, pour un $\tau_{\text{ts}} \sim 10^4$ s, il prend une valeur de l'ordre de $\gamma_{\text{ts}} \sim 10^{-4}$ Hz, ce qui est très faible. La détection d'un tel élargissement minime nécessite des instruments de haute précision. En plus de l'élargissement spectral, un autre effet caractéristique des ondes gravitationnelles anciennes qui sont dans un état de compression bimodal est l'apparition de bandes latérales dans le spectre électromagnétique. L'emplacement approximatif de ces bandes latérales est donné

par la relation suivante

$$\omega_{\text{side}} \sim \omega_k \pm 1.2\gamma_{\text{ts}}. \quad (22)$$

Ainsi, le paramètre $\Delta\omega \equiv |\omega_{\text{side}} - \omega_k| \sim \gamma_{\text{ts}}$, qui détermine la séparation des bandes latérales avec le pic central du spectre, augmente avec la diminution du temps de décohérence. Cependant, comme mentionné précédemment, la plage de variations du temps de décohérence dépend de la plage de variations des paramètres inflationnistes tels que le rapport tensoriel à scalaire r_{k_0} et l'indice inflationniste β . Toutefois, la plage de variations de ces paramètres n'est pas très large et, dans l'ensemble, ne change le temps de décohérence que d'un ordre de grandeur au maximum. Cependant, la recherche de bandes latérales dans le spectre électromagnétique par des lasers ultra-stables capables de résoudre une fraction de fréquence aussi petite que $\Delta\omega/\omega_k = (\gamma_{\text{ts}}/\omega_k) \sim 10^{-19}$ sera possible à l'avenir.

5 Décohérence causée par les ondes gravitationnelles

Comme mentionné ci-dessus, la détection de la nature quantique des ondes gravitationnelles anciennes basée sur l'idée de rétablissement de la compression des composants de quadrature du champ électromagnétique est pratiquement impossible, et sa détection repose principalement sur les effets de la décohérence des corrélations temporelles ou par l'élargissement du spectre de puissance ou en révélant des bandes latérales dans le spectre de puissance, principalement dépendante des technologies avancées et des conditions de laboratoire contrôlées pour isoler le système des autres sources de décohérence environnementale. D'un autre côté, les corrélations spatiales du champ électromagnétique ont cette propriété unique qu'elles sont non seulement résistantes aux bruits environnementaux, mais qu'elles se propagent également à mesure que la distance de la source émettrice augmente.

Dans le cadre de la théorie de la cohérence en optique, le théorème de Van Cittert-Zernike a été développé pour décrire les corrélations spatiales du champ électromagnétique. En conséquence, le rayonnement électromagnétique de différentes parties d'une source étendue, initialement incohérent et en déphasage, conduit à la formation d'un motif interférentiel à de grandes distances. Le théorème de Van Cittert-Zernike fournit une formulation précise et formalisée des corrélations du champ électromagnétique en deux points spatiaux (mais simultanément) dues aux ondes émises par une source étendue située à distance qui n'ont initialement aucune corrélation entre elles. Sur cette base, dans des régions éloignées et près de la direction perpendiculaire à la surface de la source, la lumière émise par une source discale de rayon a , dans une région d'environ $d_{\text{coh}} \simeq 2/(k\theta)$ est appe-

lée cohérente. Dans cette relation, k est la longueur d'onde centrale de la source quasi-monochromatique et $\theta = 2a/R$ est le diamètre angulaire de la source vu de la Terre, avec R étant la distance de la source à la Terre. En conséquence, si le rayonnement électromagnétique se propage librement dans l'espace et atteint la Terre sans subir de changement ou d'interaction qui affaiblit les corrélations, un motif interférentiel est visible.

L'utilisation des corrélations spatiales a été initialement employée pour mesurer le diamètre angulaire de Sagittarius lors de l'expérience interférométrique de Hanbury Brown et Twiss. Aujourd'hui, les interféromètres à très longue base sont utilisés pour mesurer les caractéristiques apparentes d'objets célestes très éloignés comme les quasars, en fonction des corrélations spatiales des ondes électromagnétiques radio émises par ces derniers. Au-delà, ces dernières années, l'utilisation des techniques d'imagerie par interférométrie à très longue base a également trouvé une place spéciale dans les discussions cosmologiques. Par exemple, le télescope Event Horizon, conçu pour imager les trous noirs supermassifs, mesure précisément la métrique de Kerr, testant les écarts par rapport à la relativité générale. D'autre part, le projet cosmologique MEGAMASER, qui utilise la technologie d'interférométrie à très longue base pour cartographier la position des objets compacts dans le ciel avec une précision sub-milliseconde d'arc, offre un nouveau laboratoire, parallèlement aux autres levés basés sur le rayonnement de fond cosmique, pour contraindre la constante de Hubble ainsi que pour mettre à jour les contraintes actuelles sur la masse des trous noirs supermassifs. En particulier, la capacité minutieuse de l'interférométrie à très longue base à mesurer la relation angulaire-rougeur ($\theta - z$) des quasars a mené à ce résultat surprenant que les noyaux galactiques actifs peuvent être considérés comme des règles standard avec des dimensions intrinsèques $\ell_m \sim 11.03\text{pc}$, qui à leur tour sont utiles pour contraindre les paramètres cosmologiques tels que la constante de Hubble, le paramètre de densité de la matière noire et de l'énergie noire. Cependant, jusqu'à présent, aucune tentative n'a été faite pour utiliser les données de mesure de la taille angulaire-rougeur des quasars obtenues par les interféromètres à très longue base pour contraindre les ondes gravitationnelles anciennes. Cela est particulièrement important car le rayonnement radio de ces objets a été suffisamment exposé à l'interaction avec le champ d'ondes gravitationnelles en arrière-plan et, par conséquent, les effets de cette interaction devraient être enregistrés dans les corrélations spatiales du rayonnement électromagnétique enregistré.

Ainsi, en utilisant le cadre que nous avons établi pour décrire l'interaction électromagnétique-gravitationnelle, nous examinons les corrélations spatiales du rayonnement des objets lointains et montrons que les ondes gravitationnelles anciennes dans un état de compression bimodal peuvent causer la perte de ces corrélations. Ce phénomène est appelé décohérence causée par les ondes gravitationnelles.

En effectuant des calculs, nous montrons que la fonction d'exposition diminue exponentiellement avec la distance entre deux détecteurs, comme déterminé par la relation suivante

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{V}_{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}_C, t) &= 2 \Re \left\{ \int_0^1 du u e^{-\left(\frac{v^2}{2(k\xi_{\text{ts}})^2} u^2\right)} \left(J_0(vu) J_0\left(i \frac{v^2}{2(k\xi_{\text{ts}})^2} u^2\right) \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-i)^n J_{2n}(vu) J_n\left(i \frac{v^2}{2(k\xi_{\text{ts}})^2} u^2\right) \right) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

où $v = kd\theta/2$, d représente la distance entre les deux détecteurs, θ est le diamètre angulaire de l'étoile, et ξ_{ts} désigne la longueur de décohérence induite par les ondes gravitationnelles primordiales dans l'état comprimé bimodal, définie comme suit :

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_{\text{ts}}(R, t) &= \left[\frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}} \right)^2 \int dK \left(\frac{K e^{2r_K}}{4} \right) \left(8 \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Omega_K t}{2} \right) \sin^2 \left(\frac{2\phi_K - \Omega_K t}{2} \right) \right) \right. \\ &\quad \times \int_0^{2\pi} d\Phi_K \int_0^\pi d(\cos \Theta_K) \sum_{\lambda=+, \times} \left| \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} (i^\ell) \frac{2\ell+1}{2\pi} \left(\int d\Omega_{\hat{r}} e_{ij}^\lambda[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j P_\ell(\cos \gamma) \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. \times \left(\frac{j_\ell(KR)}{(KR)} - \frac{\int_0^{KR} j_\ell(u) du}{(KR)^2} \right) \right|^2 \right]^{-1/2}, \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Ainsi, le nombre moyen de gravitons ainsi que les corrélations quantiques du type $\langle \hat{b}_K \hat{b}_K \rangle$ et $\langle \hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{b}_K^\dagger \rangle$ dans l'état comprimé bimodal interviennent dans le processus de décohérence. Comme il est évident, cette longueur caractéristique dépend du temps d'interaction entre l'onde électromagnétique et les ondes gravitationnelles. Pour les objets situés à des distances cosmiques, tels que les pulsars et les noyaux actifs de galaxies, nous pouvons exprimer le temps et la distance en fonction du décalage vers le rouge de l'étoile z , comme suit :

$$\begin{aligned} t(z) &= H_0^{-1} \int_0^z \frac{dz'}{\sqrt{(1 - \Omega_m)(1 + z')^2 + \Omega_m(1 + z')^5}}, \\ R(z) &= \frac{c}{H_0(1 + z)} \left(\int_0^z \frac{dz'}{\sqrt{\Omega_m(1 + z')^3 + (1 - \Omega_m)}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Dans cette relation, Ω_Λ et Ω_m représentent respectivement la fraction de densité de l'énergie noire et de la matière noire. Par conséquent, la longueur de décohérence ξ_{ts} peut être exprimée en fonction du décalage vers le rouge de la source.

La détection réussie d'objets lointains par des méthodes interférométriques témoigne du fait que l'interaction avec les ondes gravitationnelles de fond n'a pas pu détruire les corrélations spatiales du champ sur une échelle spatiale d_{coh} . En d'autres termes, comme il ressort de l'équation (23), les effets de décohérence induits par les ondes gravitationnelles primordiales sont observables si et seulement

si :

$$k \xi_{\text{ts}}(z) \gtrsim \nu = k d \theta / 2. \quad (26)$$

La longueur caractéristique de décohérence $\xi_{\text{ts}}(z)$ est liée au rapport tenseur-sur-scalaire r_{k_0} , qui régule en réalité l'intensité du couplage avec les ondes gravitationnelles primordiales. Compte tenu de la limite supérieure de cette quantité, $r_{k_0} \lesssim 0.032$, enregistrée par le satellite Planck, il apparaît que la valeur de la quantité sans dimension $k \xi_{\text{ts}}$ dans la plage de décalage vers le rouge $0 \leq z \leq 5$ prend toujours une valeur supérieure à $\sim 10^6$. Par conséquent, l'effet de décohérence des ondes gravitationnelles primordiales est si faible qu'il est impossible de les détecter avec les interféromètres à très longue base.

Cependant, il convient de noter que, dans l'étude actuelle, l'effet de décohérence induit par les perturbations scalaires de l'espace-temps sur les corrélations spatiales du champ électromagnétique a été négligé. Cela pourrait modifier les résultats obtenus, car il est attendu que la convergence gravitationnelle induite par les fluctuations de matière agisse comme un mécanisme de déphasage du champ électromagnétique. Dans cette optique, le cadre actuel peut être directement généralisé pour inclure le déphasage induit par les perturbations de densité primordiales.

D'autre part, l'interaction des ondes gravitationnelles primordiales avec les champs de matière durant les époques postérieures à leur génération pendant l'inflation peut modifier leur état quantique et les transformer en états cohérents. Par conséquent, l'effet de décohérence ou des interactions ultérieures sur les ondes gravitationnelles primordiales mérite une étude plus approfondie, qui peut être abordée dans le cadre de la présente formalisation.

Conclusions français

En résumé, dans cette thèse, nous étudions la possibilité de détecter la nature quantique des ondes gravitationnelles primordiales générées par l'inflation, en utilisant un schéma interférométrique avec une sonde électromagnétique.

Après une revue complète de la littérature dans le Chapitre 1, le Chapitre 2 introduit de manière générale le concept de création de particules dans un Univers en expansion, avant de se concentrer sur le cas des perturbations tensorielles $\hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta)$. Cette procédure est réalisée dans un cadre combinant la théorie quantique des champs d'une part, et la théorie générale de la relativité d'autre part, avec l'aide de la prescription du couplage minimal. Ce cadre nous permet de traiter les perturbations métriques comme une théorie quantique des champs vivant sur la variété FLRW classique. De cette manière, l'équation de mouvement de Heisenberg pour l'amplitude de champ de Fourier a été obtenue et deux limites asymptotiques, correspondant aux échelles sous-Hubble et super-Hubble, ont été spécifiées. Pour une phase d'expansion DS durant l'inflation, nous avons montré que les échelles super-Hubble, déterminées par la condition $K\eta \ll 1$, subissent une amplification super-adiabatique. Cela signifie que l'énergie gravitationnelle de l'expansion rapide de l'Univers se transforme en paires de particules de champ tensoriel de moments opposés. Ce mécanisme conduit le vide du champ tensoriel à évoluer vers un vide fortement peuplé à deux modes comprimés, où les moments opposés du champ deviennent fortement intriqués. Une autre quantité d'intérêt est la fonction de corrélation à deux points des perturbations tensorielles $\langle \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta) \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\ell}, \eta) \rangle$, qui est la principale quantité utilisée pour parler de la détection des PGWs, que ce soit par des détecteurs d'ondes gravitationnelles ou par des enquêtes sur les anisotropies et la polarisation du CMB. Comme nous l'avons étudié en détail dans la thèse, la même quantité apparaît également dans les fonctions de corrélation du champ EM. Des caractéristiques telles que l'homogénéité et l'isotropie des corrélations EM sont héritées de la fonction de corrélation des ondes gravitationnelles.

Dans le Chapitre 3, nous avons considéré l'expansion successive de l'Univers FLRW, modélisée par un facteur d'échelle en loi de puissance $a(\eta) \propto \eta^\alpha$. Les paramètres du modèle pertinents ont été identifiés et les contraintes théoriques et observationnelles sur ceux-ci ont été discutées. L'évolution de l'indice spectral tensoriel $h(K, \eta)$ (qui détermine essentiellement le spectre de puissance des PGWs)

a été étudiée dans le cadre du modèle d'expansion successive. Une solution approximative pour $h(K, \eta)$ ainsi que pour les paramètres de compression r_K, ϕ_K dans le régime super-adiabatique (échelles \sim super-Hubble) a été obtenue, en partant de la condition de normalisation quantique qui détermine l'amplitude spectrale initiale. Finalement, le spectre actuel des perturbations tensorielles, identifié par $h(K, \eta_H)$ et $r_K(\eta_H)$, a été dérivé en termes de quatre paramètres libres du modèle $\beta, \beta_s, T_{\text{reh}}, r_{k_0}$, qui déterminent l'indice inflationnaire, l'indice de réchauffement, la température de réchauffement et le rapport tensoriel-à-scalar. Ces résultats sont utilisés dans les Chapitres suivants.

Après avoir fourni une revue détaillée de la génération des PGWs dans un Univers en expansion, le Chapitre 4 formule l'interaction entre une sonde EM générique et un continuum générique d'ondes gravitationnelles, dans le cadre de l'analogie du milieu optique. Des subtilités telles que la fixation de jauge pour les deux champs EM et GWs ont été discutées en détail. De cette manière, les équations de Maxwell généralisées ont été résolues en présence d'un milieu magnétodialectique inhomogène, anisotrope et dépendant du temps, imité par les GWs. Nous avons appliqué l'approximation adiabatique, qui implique $\omega_k \ll \Omega_K$ et $\lambda_k \ll \lambda_K$, de sorte que l'approximation de l'enveloppe à variation lente a été utilisée pour trouver les fonctions de mode temporelles et spatiales du champ EM. Finalement, nous avons dérivé l'équation de Fresnel générale, régissant l'indice de réfraction du milieu effectif. Il s'avère que l'indice de réfraction du milieu hérite de l'inhomogénéité et de l'anisotropie des ondes gravitationnelles. Des sujets tels que la biréfringence et l'angle de dérive du vecteur de Poynting ont été discutés. Finalement, il a été réalisé que l'approche actuelle basée sur l'OMA non seulement reproduit les résultats de l'optique géométrique, mais est également capable d'être promue à une description entièrement quantique de l'interaction EM-GWs.

Le Chapitre 5 de la thèse traite de la quantification de l'interaction EM-GWs. Cette procédure commence par l'établissement d'une densité d'énergie lagrangienne qui pourrait reproduire les équations de Maxwell en présence des GWs, dans l'approche OMA. De cette manière, la dynamique hamiltonienne du système a été dérivée, à partir de laquelle les observables quantiques du champ EM peuvent être suivies. Nous avons décrit en détail l'analogie entre l'Hamiltonien d'interaction EM-GWs et celui de l'optomécanique en cavité et avons tenté d'extraire les similitudes autant que possible. À première vue, cette analogie pourrait faire croire que les GWs induisent des récurrences de compression optique, ce qui est une caractéristique purement quantique en optomécanique de cavité. Cependant, nous montrons que, en raison du couplage extrêmement faible EM-GWs, le temps nécessaire pour observer l'effet est astronomiquement long, à condition que le champ optique maintienne sa cohérence, ce qui est pratiquement impossible.

D'un autre côté, nous avons montré que les fluctuations quantiques amplifiées

dans les PGWs détruisent la cohérence optique après une échelle de temps caractéristique $\tau^{\text{ts}} \sim 10^4$ s, ce qui rend impossible la détection de toute récurrence de compression optique. Ainsi, nous concluons que témoigner de la nature quantique des PGWs basée sur les récurrences de compression optique est exclu, et dans le meilleur des cas, on ne pourrait pas distinguer entre un fond de PGWs classique ou quantique, en raison de la stabilisation de la compression de quadrature, qui est une caractéristique commune aux GWs classiques et quantiques. Pour comparaison, nous calculons la variance optique lorsque les GWs sont supposées être dans des états de vide, cohérents, comprimés à un mode et thermiques. Il a été réalisé que les fluctuations quantiques des GWs s'incorporent dans la dynamique décohérente du champ EM. Pour un état cohérent des GWs, qui n'est qu'un déplacement des fluctuations du vide dans l'espace de phase, la décohérence induite est identique à celle des fluctuations du vide. Les états comprimés ou thermiques, pour lesquels les fluctuations sont amplifiées, laissent une décohérence accrue sur le champ EM, qui bien sûr dépend du nombre moyen de gravitons (qui détermine essentiellement la dispersion de l'ellipse de bruit dans l'espace de phase). Dans tous les cas, le nombre moyen de gravitons doit être aussi grand que $\sim E_{\text{pl}}/(\hbar\omega_k)$ pour compenser la faible force de couplage et laisser un effet observable sur la dynamique EM.

Le Chapitre 6 est consacré à l'étude de la décohérence du champ électromagnétique induite par les ondes gravitationnelles (GWs). Pour ce faire, nous avons d'abord obtenu l'expression générale de la fonction de corrélation à deux points d'un champ électromagnétique monomode à polarisation linéaire en présence d'ondes gravitationnelles dans différents états. Nous nous sommes ensuite concentrés sur les corrélations temporelles en supposant la condition de stationnarité pour les ondes gravitationnelles. Il a été démontré que les corrélations du champ électromagnétique peuvent être homogènes ou inhomogènes, héritées des corrélations des ondes gravitationnelles. De manière générale, les fluctuations quantiques des GWs induisent une décohérence, tandis que le déplacement du bruit quantique dans l'espace des phases peut uniquement modifier la périodicité du motif d'interférence. Par conséquent, les états comprimés et thermiques des ondes gravitationnelles induisent une décohérence, tandis que l'état cohérent des gravitons induit une modification de la périodicité de l'interférence. Les états comprimés monomodes et bimodes partagent la propriété commune d'induire des corrélations de type $\langle \hat{b}_K \hat{b}_K \rangle$ et $\langle \hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{b}_K^\dagger \rangle$ entre gravitons, lesquelles sont absentes dans l'état thermique. D'un autre côté, dans la représentation en espace des phases, l'ellipse de bruit est orientée selon une direction spécifique, déterminée par l'angle de compression ϕ_K . Ceci contraste avec le bruit des gravitons thermiques, qui forme un cercle dans l'espace des phases avec une dispersion de $1 + 2\bar{n}_{\text{th}}$, résultant de la phase indéterministe dans l'état thermique. Cependant, les corrélations

spatiales dans l'état comprimé monomode sont inhomogènes, tandis qu'elles sont homogènes dans l'état comprimé bimode en raison des corrélations entre moments opposés dans ce dernier cas. De plus, dans l'état thermique des ondes gravitationnelles, les corrélations spatiales sont automatiquement homogènes. Finalement, ces caractéristiques – à savoir l'homogénéité ou l'inhomogénéité des corrélations des GWs ainsi que la nature déterministe ou indéterministe de la phase dans l'état – déterminent le comportement final des corrélations du champ électromagnétique.

Dans le Chapitre 7, les corrélations spatiales du champ électromagnétique en présence d'ondes gravitationnelles (GWs) dans différents états sont étudiées au cas par cas. En l'absence d'ondes gravitationnelles, lorsque le champ électromagnétique se propage librement dans l'espace, les corrélations spatiales sont décrites par le théorème de van Cittert-Zernike, qui exprime les corrélations du champ entre deux points distincts de l'espace. Il s'avère que, pour une source étendue de rayon a située à une grande distance R de la Terre, le champ électromagnétique reste cohérent sur une région circulaire de rayon $d_{\text{coh}} = 2/(k\theta)$ transverse à la direction de propagation. Ici, $\theta = 2a/R$ définit le diamètre angulaire de la source vue depuis la Terre. Cependant, nous montrons que les fluctuations quantiques des ondes gravitationnelles tendent à réduire les corrélations de van Cittert-Zernike et à induire une incohérence (perte de corrélation spatiale). Cet effet est appelé flou de la visibilité induit par les fluctuations quantiques des ondes gravitationnelles primordiales (PGWs). D'autre part, les ondes gravitationnelles dans un état cohérent peuvent modifier la longueur de cohérence transverse d_{coh} , l'ampleur de cet effet dépendant cruciallement du contenu en gravitons dans l'état cohérent. Les ondes gravitationnelles dans des états comprimés et thermiques, lorsqu'elles contiennent un grand nombre de gravitons (et donc un bruit fluctuant important), entraînent également un flou de la visibilité. Ainsi, les fluctuations des ondes gravitationnelles dans ces états agissent comme un mécanisme d'incohérence. Dans ces cas, nous avons déterminé une échelle caractéristique de longueur ξ_{gr} , qui dépend des propriétés des ondes gravitationnelles, notamment leur homogénéité, le nombre moyen de gravitons, les corrélations de phase et les corrélations entre différents modes. Entre autres, la longueur d'incohérence induite par les PGWs comprimées bimodes, ξ_{ts} , dépend fortement du rapport tenseur-sur-scalaire. Afin que la visibilité soit préservée, comme le suggèrent les expériences actuelles d'interférométrie à très longue base (VLBI), le paramètre sans dimension doit satisfaire la condition $k\xi_{\text{ts}} \geq kd\theta/2$. Nous avons constaté que, pour la gamme de paramètres des PGWs contrainte par les relevés actuels, ce critère est automatiquement respecté. Cela signifie que les observations VLBI actuelles sont compatibles avec la contrainte actuelle sur le rapport tenseur-sur-scalaire, $r_{k_0} \leq 0.032$, obtenue à partir des données Planck PR4 [124].

Chapter 1

Introduction

This chapter provides a brief history of gravitational wave detection and a qualitative discussion of the theoretical and observational efforts regarding primordial gravitational waves (PGWs) that were inevitably generated during the inflationary era. After introducing various motivations for PGWs detection, we provide a qualitative summary of the dissertation objectives, which primarily rely on theoretical and observational schemes to detect the squeezed essence of PGWs, based on electromagnetic interferometric setups.

1.1 A brief history of gravitational wave detection

The quest for gravitational waves (GWs) has been a true scientific adventure since the 20th century, following their prediction by Albert Einstein, continuing up to the present day. By the end of the 1950s, after four decades of debate, the first attempts were made by Joseph Weber to discover GWs through the minute vibrations of massive aluminum cylinders [3, 4]. Reviews of this early work are provided in [5, 6]. His major contribution to science was initiating the exciting field of GW detection by constructing the first resonant-mass antenna, influencing Robert Forward (his Ph.D. thesis student) to build the first free-mass antenna with laser interferometry [7, 8]. The development of Weber bar-type detectors continued with significant emphasis on cooling to reduce noise levels. Afterward, the idea of using large interferometers to detect such feeble ripples in the fabric of spacetime was independently proposed. The sensitivity of km -scale interferometric gravitational wave detectors began to surpass the peak sensitivity of these cryogenic bar detectors. The early prototype of the Michelson interferometric GW observatory has been under continuous improvement. At the current stage, a network of laser interferometer GW detectors built in various places around the world has offered an outstanding facility to look at the gravitational Universe; the LIGO project led by a Caltech/MIT consortium in the USA [9, 10]; the Virgo project, a joint Italian/French venture [11, 12]; the GEO600 project in Germany [13, 14]; and the TAMA300 project in Japan [15, 16]. While ground-based GW interferometers are usually used to observe sources whose radiation is emitted at frequencies above a few Hz, the space-born missions such as LISA, as originally envis-

aged by Peter Bender and Jim Faller [17, 18], are developed for implementation at lower frequencies.

1.2 Characterising primordial gravitational waves

During the last few years, witnessing successive transient GW signals produced by binary black holes (BBH) [19, 20, 21] and binary neutron star mergers [22] has significantly deepened our insights into general relativity (GR) and its predictions. However, there are a wide variety of other astrophysical and cosmological mechanisms that produce a stochastic gravitational wave background (SGWB) [23], that can be isotropic, stationary, and unpolarized perturbations in space-time. Although present GW experiments have not been designed specifically for the detection of SGWB, there are chances that in their frequency window, there might be a cosmological signal [24, 25, 26, 27]. Nevertheless, the detection of an SGWB of cosmological origin is considered a remarkable tool to probe the infant Universe, i.e., inflationary and post-inflationary epochs.

The main reason why stochastic primordial gravitational waves (PGWs) carry unique information on very high-energy physics during inflation is that, contrary to other particles, gravitons decoupled from other fields below the Planck scale and propagated freely in the early Universe after they were generated [26]. To be more precise, the condition for thermal equilibrium is that the rate Γ that maintains thermal equilibrium be larger than the rate of expansion of the Universe, as measured by the Hubble parameter H . The weaker the interaction of a particle, the higher the energy scale when it drops out of thermal equilibrium. For gravitons, with an extremely small cross-section of interaction $\sigma \propto G_N = 1/M_{Pl}^2$, with G_N being the Newton constant and the Planck mass is $M_{Pl} \sim 10^{19}$ GeV, one may find [28]

$$\left(\frac{\Gamma}{H}\right)_{\text{gravitons}} \sim \left(\frac{T}{M_{Pl}}\right)^3, \quad (1.1)$$

In order to obtain this estimation, the Hubble parameter H during the radiation-dominated era is assumed. By decoupling, one usually refers to a situation where the interaction becomes negligible or irrelevant, thus reaching equilibrium. Hence, gravitons are decoupled below the Planck scale and can probe deeper into the very early Universe. Consequently, their detection opens up a new window on high-energy physical processes that are unavailable by other means. The most general mechanism that generates a relic SGWB is the inevitable amplification of vacuum fluctuations during the inflationary and subsequent evolutionary stages of the Universe [29, 30], first discussed in a cosmological setting in [31, 32] and then in many other papers, see e.g. [33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41]. This phenomenon lies at the heart of “particle creation in an expanding Universe,” which plays a vital role in our understanding of the structure formation of the Universe [42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47].

The generation and evolution of the primordial tensor modes are predominantly determined by the first horizon crossing during inflation, the horizon reentry after inflation, and by the evolution itself of the Universe and its matter content. Dynamical equations governing the tensorial part of the metric perturbations during the expansion of the Universe imply that the amplitude of perturbations (whether scalar or tensor perturbations) may get amplified when the mode is in the super Hubble regime, i.e., when [48]

$$K \ll 2\pi\mathcal{H}, \quad (1.2)$$

where K stands for the GW's wave number and $\mathcal{H} \equiv a'(\eta)/a(\eta)$ is the conformal Hubble parameter and $a(\eta)$ denotes the scale factor of the Universe in terms of the conformal time η . From the physical point of view, there are two characteristic lengths to be compared, namely the wavelength of GW, λ_K , which propagates through the expanding Universe, and the length scale at which the underlying background changes noticeably, say \mathcal{H}^{-1} (with a dimensionality of length). Now, if the spatial extension of the wave is small compared to \mathcal{H}^{-1} , i.e., the *sub-Hubble regime*, the wave evolves ordinarily. That is, the amplitude of the perturbation decays as $a^{-1}(\eta)$ and its frequency experiences a redshift, as time elapses. On the other hand, if the wavelength exceeds the characteristic length scale \mathcal{H}^{-1} , i.e., the *super-Hubble regime*, it is possible that the wave gains energy from the underlying expanding background that prohibits the decaying behavior of the perturbation amplitude. One may show that the tensorial amplitude stays approximately constant when the wave is in the super Hubble regime. However, the latter case (the super-Hubble regime) describes an oscillator with time-dependent frequency, which basically does not oscillate anymore, but rather undergoes *super-adiabatic* amplification due to the exchange of energy with the underlying pumping field of the expanding Universe. This interaction leads the initial vacuum state of the oscillator to evolve into a two-mode highly-squeezed, highly-entangled, and highly-populated-graviton state [41].

In the quantum phase space description, in the super-Hubble regime, the quantum fluctuations of the GW mode K are stretched in one direction and compressed along the orthogonal direction. Their variances for two conjugate variables, say q and p are significantly unequal and are described by an ellipse. The ellipse rotates around the origin of the (q, p) diagram as time evolves, and the numerical values of the variances oscillate too. The Heisenberg uncertainty principle requires that the variance of the oscillator's phase in the squeezed vacuum state be very small (the origin of the name *squeezed*), while the uncertainty in the graviton number gets extremely large. Phase space representation of this highly-squeezed state is graphically shown in Fig. 1.1, where the ellipse is very thin so that the uncertainty in the angle between the horizontal axis and the orientation of the ellipse is very small. This highly elongated ellipse can be regarded as a portrait of the gravitational wave quantum state that is inevitably generated by parametric amplification of the oscillator frequency [49]. On the other hand, due to the conservation of linear and angular momentum in the course of the evolution of the Universe, gravitons

Figure 1.1: Phase space representation of the vacuum and highly-squeezed states. The angle 2ϕ is called the squeezing angle, and $\Delta\phi$ shows the uncertainty in the determination of ϕ .

generated from vacuum come in pairs, with opposite momenta and vanishing net polarization. Moreover, the generated PGWs inherit the homogeneity and isotropicity of the underlying background. As a result, the inflationary-generated PGWs exhibit the features of a homogeneous, isotropic, and unpolarized SGWB.

1.3 Motivations for primordial gravitational waves detection

With the stochastic PGWs, which are nothing but the super-adiabatic amplified zero-point fluctuations of the gravitational field, the physics of the inflationary and post-inflationary early Universe, hitherto unknown to us, might be touched. Due to their specific generating mechanism, the PGWs spectrum spans a full range of frequencies, corresponding to wavelengths much larger than the Planck scale. Thereupon, the quest for PGWs has become one of the main targets of today's and upcoming GW detectors in different frequency bands [50]. The ground-based detector communities, among which is the LIGO-Virgo interferometer, have put continued effort into detecting a stochastic GW background between $\sim 10 - 10^3$ Hz [51]; The space-based interferometers, including the future LISA is sensitive in the frequency range ($10^{-4} - 10^{-1}$) Hz [52] and the Deci-hertz Interferometer Gravitational-Wave Observatory (DECIGO) that is the future Japanese mission in space, sensitive in the frequency range 0.1 – 10 Hz [53]; the Big Bang Observatory (BBO) works in a frequency band 0.1 – 10 Hz [54]; and the pulsar timing arrays (PTA), including North American Nanohertz Observatory for Gravitational Waves (NANOGrav) works in the frequency window $10^{-9} - 10^{-6}$ Hz [55].

Besides, there are potential proposals able to detect the very-high-frequency part of PGWs, among which are the waveguide detector [56, 57, 58, 59], the proposed Gaussian maser beam detector around GHz [60, 61, 62], and the 100 MHz detector [63]. Moreover, the very low-frequency portion of PGWs, corresponding to scales between 10 Mpc and 10^4 Mpc, contribute to the anisotropy and polarization of cosmic microwave background (CMB) at large angular scales (equivalent to low-multipoles $\ell \leq 10$) [64, 65, 66, 67, 68, 69, 70], yielding a cross-type polarization of CMB as a distinguished signal of PGWs, which would possibly be sensed by means of WMAP [71, 72, 73, 74, 75], Planck [76, 77], liteBIRD [78], the ground-based ACTPol [79] and the proposed CMBpol [80].

Detection of PGWs would not only confirm the inflationary scenario but also validate the quantum description of gravity at scales much larger than the Planck length. On one hand, it is conceived that the inflationary epoch occurred after the quantum gravity era of our Universe, and from the beginning of the inflationary era the Universe is assumed to be four-dimensional and to be described by the standard cosmology. The inflation paradigm provides a mechanism for generating large-scale fluctuations that fits the data very well [81, 82]. However, direct verification that the inflation had ever occurred has not been accomplished yet. On the same foot, we lack any observational data to support quantum gravity effects. Hence, the quest for PGWs can pave the way toward direct perception of the quantum nature of gravity, at least in post-Planckian epochs of the Universe. In short, the motivation for cosmologists' search to detect inflationary-generated PGWs can be summarized as follows:

1. Verifying the theory of inflation as a standard model of cosmology.
2. Testing inflationary models. Detecting the amplitudes and spectral index of PGWs puts constraints on inflationary models which will in turn narrow down the inflationary models.
3. Understanding the physics behind inflation and beyond the standard model. PGW detection along with any information about their quantum mechanical origin may hint at how the fundamental theories of gravity and quantum mechanics could congregate.

1.4 Dissertation objectives

Various theoretical schemes have been proposed to search for the non-classical nature of gravity based on electromagnetic correlations [83, 84, 85, 86, 87]. In particular, several schemes are considered to reveal the squeezed essence of PGWs by using either ground- and space-based gravitational wave interferometers [88, 89], by observing the imprint of squeezed PGWs on the CMB temperature fluctuations and polarization [90, 91] and by performing a Hanbury Brown–Twiss (HB-T) interferometry on the squeezed PGWs [92, 93, 94]. Moreover, the implications of the quantumness of primordial cosmological

fluctuations and its detectability by means of CMB anisotropies is investigated in [95]. A more recent proposal offers the possibility of testing the quantum origin of cosmological perturbations based on Bell inequalities [96]. On the experimental side, however, the search for demonstrations of the quantum nature of PGWs is still challenging.

Motivated by these aspects, this dissertation aims at:

1. Establish a comprehensive framework to address the interaction of a typical electromagnetic (EM) probe with a continuum of gravitational waves, within the familiar language of quantum optics.
2. Apply the theoretical framework to realizable experimental situations that work based on electromagnetic spatio-temporal correlations.
3. Identify the signatures of the quantumness of PGWs at these detectors or put constraints on the relevant quantities of PGWs, such as tensor-to-scalar ratio and the inflationary index.

To achieve the first objective, we develop a theoretical framework to describe the coupling between a generic EM radiation field and a continuum of GWs based on the optical medium analogy (OMA). Wherever possible, we try to assimilate the concepts and quantities to the quantum optical language so that it is more easy to construct analogies between gravitational phenomena and the well-known discipline of quantum optics. Specifically, it turns out that the EM-GWs interaction resembles the cavity opto-mechanics interaction. Hence, one may find a new avenue to explore quantum gravitational effects, inspired by tabletop opto-mechanical experiments already established to expose the quantum behavior of mesoscopic objects. Within the OMA context, the main formulas of typical laser interferometer GW observatories are reproduced automatically. However, we will not limit ourselves to the case of current or planned GW observatories: we try to seek other observables of the EM field that can reveal the existence of PGWs. Indeed, the present framework seems fruitful when the EM-GWs coupling is promoted to the quantum mechanical level. As a result of interaction with the so-called two-mode squeezed PGWs, the EM field undergoes non-intuitive dynamics. Of central importance are the spatial and temporal correlations of the EM field which exhibit unique behavior when interacting with PGWs. In particular, decoherence and incoherence of the EM field injected by the PGWs are among the inevitable consequences that carry information about them. While temporal correlations of the EM field are very sensitive to environmental effects, robust spatial correlations of distant emitters seem to be a promising tool for studying the imprints of PGWs on them. On top of that, scrutinizing spatial correlations of the EM field illuminates a new tool to constrain the underlying PGWs background with the help of spatial correlations of the emitted EM radiation coming from most distant objects, located at cosmological distances, measured by means of Very Long Baseline interferometric (VLBI) methods.

1.5 The structure of the dissertation

The structure of this thesis is organized as follows. In Chapter 2, we provide an introduction to the PGWs production as a result of the amplification of quantum fluctuations during the inflationary era. Subjects such as quantum field theory in curved spacetime, adiabatic vacuum, particle creation, super-adiabatic amplification, and horizon-crossing are touched upon. We will determine the stochastic nature of PGWs with the help of their correlation functions. The results of this section will be used in subsequent chapters when considering PGWs in the two-mode squeezed state.

Chapter 3 deals mainly with the spectrum of the inflationary-generated PGWs at the present. This will be done by identifying the expanding Universe with a power-law scale factor and definition of the related parameters and quantities. The approximate solution of dynamical equations for tensor perturbations is obtained in the limit where the modes are in super-Hubble regime. This will let us determine analytic solutions for the squeezing amplitude of the two-mode squeezed PGWs, which is almost the main quantity that eventually determines the order of magnitude of observable effects of the electromagnetic probe.

In Chapter 4, the interaction between EM field propagating through a generic GWs spacetime is formulated within the OMA framework. The effective refractive index of the medium, residual Doppler shift of the frequency, and mode expansion of the EM field in the presence of GWs are among the main results of this chapter. For the sake of completeness, we touch upon quantities such as the Stokes parameters of the EM field, as well as the walk-off angle, which stems from the fact the effective GWs medium acts as a birefringence media that shows different refractive index for different polarizations of the EM field.

In Chapter 5, we promote the description of EM-GWs coupling to the quantum mechanical level, where both EM and GWs fields are treated as quantum entities. Quantum dynamics of the EM observables are derived within the Heisenberg picture. This is achieved by evaluating the time evolution operator of the total system. It turns out that EM-GWs interaction modifies the dynamics of the EM field ladder operators by a multiplicative factor that includes the displacement operator of the GWs. Although the magnitude of the displacement depends on the EM-GWs coupling strength, which is extraordinarily small, a highly-populated state of GWs may give rise to a sensible non-vanishing effect in the field observables. We then try to physically understand the appearance of the displacement operator of GWs in the EM field dynamics with the help of analogy with the cavity opto-mechanical system. We then initialize different quantum states for the GWs, namely vacuum, coherent, one-mode squeezed, two-mode squeezed, and thermal states, and try to assess the optical quadrature variance, case by case. We argue why it seems impossible to exhibit the quantum nature of GWs based on optical squeezing.

Chapter 6 addresses the approach of sensing quantum nature of PGWs based on the

decoherence of the EM field (\sim disappearing temporal correlations of the EM field). As a general consequence, it turns out that two-point correlations of GWs, namely $\langle \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_1, t_1) \hat{h}^{ij}(\mathbf{x}_2, t_2) \rangle$ which carry information about statistical properties of GWs as well as their quantum state, are essentially mapped into the two-point correlation functions of the EM field, expressed in terms of $\langle \hat{E}(\mathbf{x}_1, t_1) \hat{E}(\mathbf{x}_2, t_2) \rangle$. Thus, our main strategy to search for quantum effects of GWs is organized upon EM correlations. The coherent and decoherent dynamics of temporal correlations of the EM field are investigated and compared when GWs are considered to be in a continuum of vacuum, coherent, one-mode squeezed, and thermal states. In the case of two-mode squeezed PGWs, there exists a characteristic time-scale τ^{ts} that signifies the ultimate decoherence time of a coherent laser field, which solely depends on the PGWs-related quantities such as the tensor-to-scalar ratio and the inflationary index. In this way, two-mode squeezed PGWs introduce a line-width broadening in the optical spectrum, given by $\gamma^{\text{ts}} \sim (\tau^{\text{ts}})^{-1}$. Moreover, the appearance of secondary peaks in the spectrum of the laser field could be regarded as an exclusive signature of the two-mode squeezed nature of PGWs.

Chapter 7 provides an analysis of the spatial correlation function of the EM field propagating through the GW background. The incoherence (\sim disappearing spatial correlations of the EM field) induced by GW background strongly depends on the given state of PGWs. We show how constraints on the PGWs can be inferred from current precise measurements of the angular-size redshift of distant radio emitters, such as quasars, by VLBI means. The dissertation is concluded in Chapter 8 with presenting summary and conclusions followed by a comprehensive appendix on the derivation of the main formulas of the text.

Chapter 2

Inflationary-generated gravitational waves

The existence of relic gravitational waves is a consequence of quite general assumptions. Essentially, it relies only on the validity of general relativity and basic principles of quantum field theory at scales much larger than Planck's length. The strong and variable gravitational field of the early Universe acts as a pumping field that amplifies the inevitable zero-point quantum fluctuations of the gravitational field. This phenomenon, known as the super-adiabatic or parametric amplification of vacuum fluctuations, can be viewed as the gravitational counterpart of the optical parametric down-conversion [97]. In the latter, a photon of frequency ω_c is converted into two photons of lower frequencies ω_a and ω_b , such that $\omega_c = \omega_a + \omega_b$ (due to energy conservation) in the presence of a crystal with non-linear susceptibility. In the former case, the intense, homogeneous, and isotropic, varying gravitational field of the inflation itself acts as a pumping field that couples each pair of waves with opposite momenta (due to momentum conservation) and leads their vacuum state to evolve into a two-mode squeezed state.

To illuminate this analogy better, let us use the conformal coordinates (to be introduced in Sec. 2.1.2) to specify the conformal Hubble expansion rate $\mathcal{H} = a'/a$, which shows the rate of change of scale factor in conformal time η . Also, the inverse of \mathcal{H} determines the characteristic length at which the background pumping field of the expanding Universe changes significantly. Thus, in order to have a parametric down-conversion, the rate \mathcal{H} of changing gravitational field should be comparable to the frequency of the generated gravitons, e.g., $K \sim \mathcal{H}$. Since $\mathcal{H}(\eta)$ is time-dependent, a broad spectrum of relic gravitational waves is being formed.

In this chapter, we formulate the problem of graviton creation in the expanding Universe, starting from the action $S[h_{ij}]$ governing the tensor metric perturbations h_{ij} . To do so, we discuss general aspects of quantum field theory (QFT) in curved spacetime in a nutshell, where mode function expansion, definition of the vacuum state, and Bogoliubov transformations are of central focus. This approach lets us quantize the perturbation field h_{ij} as a rank-2 tensor field, using standard QFT methods in an expanding Universe.

Heisenberg equations of motion governing the tensor field \hat{h}_{ij} and its conjugate momenta are derived. In particular, we shall see how the squeezing operator naturally manifests itself in the time evolution of field operators. Furthermore, the introduction of the squeezing parameters will be useful for our later use when we consider the interaction of an electromagnetic probe with squeezed GWs. In the case of the exact de Sitter expansion, we find the solution to the Heisenberg equations and derive analytical expressions for the squeezing parameters. At last, characteristic features of the inflationary-generated PGWs, including quantum correlations and spectral amplitude, are determined.

2.1 General aspects of field quantization in curved spacetime

At energies well below the Planck scale, the combination of gravity with other quantum fields is accomplished by describing the propagation of quantum fields in a curved spacetime having a metric described by Einstein's gravitational field equations with additional higher-order curvature corrections. Within quantum field theory in curved spacetime, which is a generalization of the well-established theory of quantum fields in Minkowski spacetime, local entities such as the field equations and commutation relations are to a large extent determined by the principle of general covariance and the principle of equivalence. However, global entities, which are unique in Minkowski spacetime lose that uniqueness in curved spacetime. For example, the vacuum state, which in Minkowski spacetime is determined by Poincaré invariance, is not unambiguously determined in curved spacetime. This ambiguity is closely tied to the phenomenon of particle creation by certain gravitational fields, as in the expanding Universe or near a black hole [98]. In other words, the choice of the mode functions that are used to perform the quantization procedure is not unique. In Minkowski spacetime, one requires that the modes are of *positive energy* with respect to time t , i.e., that they are positive eigenvalues of the operator $i\partial/\partial t$, where $i\partial/\partial t$ is the Killing vector associated with the invariance of Minkowski space under time translations. This selects mode functions proportional to $e^{-i\omega t}$ (together with $\omega > 0$). In curved space, there is no such unambiguous definition, since the invariance under diffeomorphisms does not allow us to select a preferred definition of time. Modes that are “positive frequency” with respect to a variable t are in general a mixture of positive and negative frequencies with respect to another variable $t'(t)$. The Fourier expansion of $e^{-i\omega t'(t)}$ involves both positive and negative frequencies with respect to t , and in a general spacetime, there is no Killing vector associated with time translations that could provide a privileged definition of time. As a consequence, there is no unique choice of the mode functions. In the following, we consider the propagation of a massless scalar field in a general curved spacetime and find some generic results. In Sec. 2.1.2, we shall discuss the ambiguity of the vacuum and its implications in detail for the specific case of the Friedmann-Lemaître-Robertson-Walker (FLRW) Universe.

2.1.1 Quantization of massless scalar field in curved spacetime

The above general statements can be understood by considering a massless real scalar field $\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ in curved spacetime, determined by the metric $g_{\mu\nu}(x)$. This helps us better grasp different aspects of field quantization procedure in the curved spacetime and its consequences. To do so, one follows the minimal coupling prescription, based on the equivalence principle, and the following replacements are inserted in the action of a free massless scalar field in Minkowski spacetime,

$$\partial_\mu \rightarrow \nabla_\mu \quad , \quad \eta_{\mu\nu} \rightarrow g_{\mu\nu} \quad , \quad d^n x \rightarrow d^n x \sqrt{-g}. \quad (2.1)$$

This results in the following action for the field in the curved spacetime

$$S = -\frac{1}{2} \int d^4 x \sqrt{-g} g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu \Phi \partial_\nu \Phi, \quad (2.2)$$

where the signature $(-, +, +, +)$ is chosen and $g < 0$ is the determinant of the metric. Variation of the action with respect to the field gives rise to the Klein-Gordon (KG) equation in curved spacetime

$$\square \Phi = \nabla_\mu \nabla^\mu \Phi = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}} \partial_\mu (\sqrt{-g} g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\nu \Phi) = 0. \quad (2.3)$$

In flat spacetime, the solutions are plane waves $e^{\pm i k x}$, and one can define the following mode functions

$$u_{\mathbf{k}}(x) \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\omega_{\mathbf{k}}}} e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} t + i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}}, \quad (2.4)$$

and the classical field is expanded as follows

$$\Phi(x) = \int \frac{d^3 \mathbf{k}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} [a_{\mathbf{k}} u_{\mathbf{k}}(x) + a_{\mathbf{k}}^* u_{\mathbf{k}}^*(x)]. \quad (2.5)$$

Having obtained the mode functions Eq. (2.4), in flat Minkowski spacetime one proceeds with defining a time-independent scalar product [99]

$$\langle u_1 | u_2 \rangle = i \int d^3 \mathbf{x} [u_1^*(x) \partial_0 u_2(x) - (\partial_0 u_1^*(x)) u_2(x)], \quad (2.6)$$

for two given solutions u_1 and u_2 of the KG equation in flat space. This construction can be generalized to the curved space, where the use of the conserved scalar product is convenient, especially in the context of the Bogoliubov transformations, as shall be seen below. In this case, again one may use the field expansion Eq. (2.5) where the mode functions $u_{\mathbf{k}}(x)$ are determined by the curved-space KG equation Eq. (2.3). The construction of the scalar product Eq. (2.6) can be generalized to curved spacetime by choosing a spatial

hypersurface Σ with unit normal n^μ , and writing

$$\langle u_{\mathbf{k}} | u_{\mathbf{k}'} \rangle = i \int_{\Sigma} d\Sigma^\mu J_\mu(x), \quad (2.7)$$

where

$$J_\mu(x) = u_{\mathbf{k}}^*(x) \partial_\mu u_{\mathbf{k}'}(x) - (\partial_\mu u_{\mathbf{k}}^*(x)) u_{\mathbf{k}'}(x). \quad (2.8)$$

The analog of the fact that in Minkowski space the scalar product Eq. (2.6) does not depend on t is now the statement that the scalar product Eq. (2.7) is independent of the hypersurface Σ , whose position in space is labeled by time coordinate t (see [100] for details). Moreover, the mode functions $u_{\mathbf{k}}(x)$ can be chosen so that they are orthonormal with respect to the scalar product Eq. (2.7),

$$\begin{aligned} \langle u_{\mathbf{k}} | u_{\mathbf{k}'} \rangle &= (2\pi)^3 \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}'), \\ \langle u_{\mathbf{k}} | u_{\mathbf{k}'}^* \rangle &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

Passing to a quantum description, the quantum field is expanded as

$$\Phi(x) = \int \frac{d^3 \mathbf{k}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} [\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} u_{\mathbf{k}}(x) + \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger u_{\mathbf{k}}^*(x)], \quad (2.10)$$

where the bosonic commutation relation between the ladder operators $\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}$ and $\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger$ is imposed. However, as a consequence of the diffeomorphism-invariance of the theory, there is no preferred time and no privileged choice of mode functions. Given complex mode functions $u_{\mathbf{k}}(x)$, one may construct the following quantity

$$U_{\mathbf{k}}(x) = \int \frac{d^3 \mathbf{k}'}{(2\pi)^3} [\alpha_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'} u_{\mathbf{k}'}(x) + \beta_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'} u_{\mathbf{k}'}^*(x)]. \quad (2.11)$$

Clearly, $U_{\mathbf{k}}(x)$ is also a solution of the curved-space KG equation. Moreover, one can require that the new mode functions $U_{\mathbf{k}}(x)$ satisfy the following orthonormality condition

$$\begin{aligned} \langle U_{\mathbf{k}} | U_{\mathbf{k}'} \rangle &= (2\pi)^3 \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}'), \\ \langle U_{\mathbf{k}} | U_{\mathbf{k}'}^* \rangle &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (2.12)$$

The transformation Eq. (2.11) together with the coefficients $\alpha_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'}$ and $\beta_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'}$ is called a *Bogoliubov transformation*. Now the quantum field expansion in terms of the new mode functions becomes

$$\hat{\Phi}(x) = \int \frac{d^3 \mathbf{k}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} [\hat{A}_{\mathbf{k}} U_{\mathbf{k}} + \hat{A}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger U_{\mathbf{k}}^*], \quad (2.13)$$

A straightforward algebra would determine the following relations between the old and

new operators,

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{A}_{\mathbf{k}} &= \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{k}'}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \left[\alpha_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'}^* \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'} - \beta_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'}^* \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'}^\dagger \right], \\ \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} &= \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{k}'}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \left[\alpha_{\mathbf{k}'\mathbf{k}} \hat{A}_{\mathbf{k}'} + \beta_{\mathbf{k}'\mathbf{k}}^* \hat{A}_{\mathbf{k}'}^\dagger \right].\end{aligned}\quad (2.14)$$

and the new commutators turn out as

$$[\hat{A}_{\mathbf{k}}, \hat{A}_{\mathbf{k}'}^\dagger] = (2\pi)^3 \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}') \quad \text{and} \quad [\hat{A}_{\mathbf{k}}, \hat{A}_{\mathbf{k}'}] = [\hat{A}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger, \hat{A}_{\mathbf{k}'}^\dagger] = 0. \quad (2.15)$$

Finally, one may observe that the Bogoliubov coefficients can be compactly written as

$$\alpha_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'} = \langle u_{\mathbf{k}'} | U_{\mathbf{k}} \rangle \quad \text{and} \quad \beta_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'} = -\langle u_{\mathbf{k}'}^* | U_{\mathbf{k}} \rangle, \quad (2.16)$$

which highlights the role of the introduction of the scalar product Eq. (2.7) in the characterization of the Bogoliubov coefficients. The annihilation operator $\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}$ defines the vacuum state $|0_a\rangle$ by the condition that, for all \mathbf{k} , $\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}|0_a\rangle = 0$ and the Fock space is constructed in the standard manner. Similarly, another vacuum state $|0_A\rangle$ can be defined, requiring that for all \mathbf{k} , $\hat{A}_{\mathbf{k}}|0_A\rangle = 0$ and the corresponding Fock space is constructed by acting on $|0_A\rangle$ with $\hat{A}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger$. If the Bogoliubov coefficients $\beta_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'}$ are non-vanishing, the vacuum states $|0_a\rangle$ and $|0_A\rangle$ and the corresponding definitions of particles of kind a and A are different. Indeed, with the help of Eq. (2.14) one may check that

$$\hat{A}_{\mathbf{k}}|0_a\rangle = - \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{k}'}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \beta_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'}^* \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'}^\dagger |0_a\rangle. \quad (2.17)$$

If $\beta_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'} \neq 0$, the r.h.s is non-zero, so the vacuum with respect to one observer that defines $\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}$ operator is not a vacuum state with respect to another observer with annihilation operator $\hat{A}_{\mathbf{k}}$. Rather, $|0_a\rangle$ is a multi-particle state with respect to the particles of kind A , with occupation number

$$\langle 0_a | \hat{A}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{A}_{\mathbf{k}} | 0_a \rangle = \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{k}'}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} |\beta_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'}|^2. \quad (2.18)$$

2.1.2 The case of spatially-flat FLRW

A homogeneous, isotropic, expanding Universe can be described by the Friedmann-Lemaître-Robertson-Walker (FLRW) metric which respects all symmetries while allowing for expansion in time. The above discussion on the quantization of fields in curved spacetime can be specialized to the case of a massless scalar field in spatially-flat FLRW metric, as follows. The general form of FLRW metric is conventionally expressed by [101]

$$ds^2 = a^2(\eta) \left(-d\eta^2 + \delta_{ij} dx^i dx^j \right), \quad (2.19)$$

where $a(\eta)$ is called scale factor, η is the conformal time, which relates to the cosmic time t through $cdt \equiv a(\eta)d\eta$, and x^i , are the spatial coordinates with $i = 1, 2, 3$. Thus, the FLRW spacetime is conformally flat when written in conformal coordinates. The dynamics of the scale factor are determined by Friedmann equations, which relate the matter-energy content of the Universe to the evolution of the scale factor.

Equivalently, the massless scalar field Φ in the FLRW Universe may be described by the action Eq. (2.2) where the metric $g_{\mu\nu}$ is identified by Eq. (2.19). It seems more easy to work with the auxiliary field $\chi(\mathbf{x}, \eta) \equiv a(\eta)\Phi(\mathbf{x}, \eta)$ which, in the conformal coordinates $x \equiv (\mathbf{x}, \eta)$, obeys the following action (see [100] for details)

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \int d\eta d^3\mathbf{x} \left(\chi'^2 - \partial_i \chi \partial_i \chi + \frac{a''}{a} \chi^2 \right), \quad (2.20)$$

where $'$ denotes derivative with respect to the conformal time η . Due to the invariance of the FLRW spacetime under spatial transformations, one may expand the fields in terms of the plane wave modes $e^{\pm i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}}$ with \mathbf{k} being the conformal wave vector, as follows

$$\chi(\mathbf{x}, \eta) = \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{k}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \chi_{\mathbf{k}}(\eta) e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}} \quad (2.21)$$

where the expansion coefficients are η -dependent. Here, because $\chi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is real, one has $\chi_{-\mathbf{k}} = \chi_{\mathbf{k}}^*$. Inserting Eq. (2.21) into Eq. (2.20), one obtains

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \int d\eta d^3\mathbf{k} \left[\chi'_{\mathbf{k}} \chi'^*_{\mathbf{k}} - \left(k^2 - \frac{a''}{a} \right) \chi_{\mathbf{k}} \chi_{\mathbf{k}}^* \right]. \quad (2.22)$$

Under the subtraction of the total derivative $\frac{(\chi_{\mathbf{k}} \chi_{\mathbf{k}}^* a')}{2}$ in the Lagrangian, which leaves the action Eq. (2.22) unchanged, Eq. (2.22) becomes

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \int d\eta d^3\mathbf{k} \left[\chi'_{\mathbf{k}} \chi'^*_{\mathbf{k}} - \frac{a'}{a} (\chi'_{\mathbf{k}} \chi_{\mathbf{k}}^* + \chi_{\mathbf{k}} \chi'^*_{\mathbf{k}}) - \left(k^2 - \frac{a''}{a^2} \right) \chi_{\mathbf{k}} \chi_{\mathbf{k}}^* \right], \quad (2.23)$$

which yields the following Euler-Lagrange equation

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{d\eta} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \chi'^*_{\mathbf{k}}} \right) - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \chi_{\mathbf{k}}^*} &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\chi''_{\mathbf{k}}(\eta) + \left(k^2 - \frac{a''}{a} \right) \chi_{\mathbf{k}}(\eta) \right] = 0, \\ \Rightarrow \chi''_{\mathbf{k}}(\eta) + \omega_{\mathbf{k}}^2(\eta) \chi_{\mathbf{k}}(\eta) &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (2.24)$$

The time-dependent frequency is defined by $\omega_{\mathbf{k}}^2(\eta) \equiv k^2 - a''/a$. More generally, the variable $\chi_{\mathbf{k}}(\eta)$ could be either the so-called Mukhanov-Sasaki variable which describes the scalar sector perturbations [95, 102], or the tensor sector perturbations that are our main interest. Hence, the following discussion applies in both cases. To construct the scalar product Eq. 2.7, first we promote the field expansion Eq. (2.21) to quantum field

operator as follows

$$\hat{\chi}(\mathbf{x}, \eta) = \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{k}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} [\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} u_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}, \eta) + \text{h.c.}] \quad (2.25)$$

where the mode functions $u_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}, \eta)$ are identified by the following separable form

$$u_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}, \eta) = \chi_k(\eta) e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}}. \quad (2.26)$$

Here, the invariance under spatial rotations ensures that $\chi_k(\eta)$ depends only on the magnitude of momentum $k = |\mathbf{k}|$, i.e., to the energy of the mode. Now, the scalar product defined by Eq. (2.7) and Eq. (2.8) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} \langle u_{\mathbf{k}} | u_{\mathbf{k}'} \rangle &= i \int d^3\mathbf{x} e^{-i(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}')\cdot\mathbf{x}} (\chi_k^* \chi_{k'}' - \chi_k' \chi_{k'}^*) \\ &= -i(2\pi)^3 \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}') (\chi_k \chi_{k'}^* - \chi_k' \chi_{k'}^*). \end{aligned} \quad (2.27)$$

Thus, in order for $u_{\mathbf{k}}(x)$ to be a mode function, $\chi_k(\eta)$ must satisfy the following condition

$$W[\chi_k, \chi_k^*] \equiv \chi_k \chi_k'^* - \chi_k' \chi_k^* = i. \quad (2.28)$$

where $W[\chi_k, \chi_k^*]$ is the Wronskian of χ_k and χ_k^* that are solutions of the linear second-order differential equation Eq. (2.24).

To construct the Bogoliubov transformation Eq. (2.11) in FLRW, one may consider the following expressions for the coefficients $\alpha_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'}$ and $\beta_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'}$

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'} &= \alpha_k (2\pi)^3 \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}'), \\ \beta_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'} &= \beta_k (2\pi)^3 \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}'). \end{aligned} \quad (2.29)$$

These expressions for $\alpha_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'}$ and $\beta_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'}$ ensure a separable form of the new mode functions $U_{\mathbf{k}}(x)$, according to Eq. (2.11). Physically, the old mode functions $u_{\mathbf{k}}(x)$ were separable due to the homogeneity and isotropic nature of FLRW. After some time, the universe expands and the scale factor changes, but spatial symmetry is conserved. Hence, in the field expansion of $\chi(\mathbf{x}, \eta)$ in terms of the new mode functions $U_{\mathbf{k}}(x)$, the same spatial behavior is expected. In this way, Eq. (2.11) implies that only the temporal mode functions are mixing while spatial mode functions are unchanged. This is why the + sign is inserted in the second equation of Eq. (2.29). Otherwise, if the above expressions for the Bogoliubov coefficients do not hold, there would be also a mixing of spatial mode functions as a result of the Universe expansion, which is inconsistent with the FLRW symmetries. Now combining Eq. (2.29) with Eq. (2.14) gives the physical interpretation of Eq. (2.29): the *initial* annihilation operator of a given mode \mathbf{k} with frequency ω_k consists of a combination of the *late* annihilation operator of the mode \mathbf{k} and the creation operator of the opposite mode $-\mathbf{k}$. In this way, the two modes \mathbf{k} and $-\mathbf{k}$ get correlated (entangled) in the course of the

particle creation mechanism. Basically, this is a consequence of the linear-momentum conservation during the course of the expansion of the Universe, as a result of the symmetries of the FLRW. Thus, the new mode functions $U_{\mathbf{k}}(x)$ possess the following separable form

$$U_{\mathbf{k}}(x) = F_k(\eta)e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}}, \quad (2.30)$$

where the mixing relation between temporal mode functions is determined by

$$F_k(\eta) = \alpha_k f_k(\eta) + \beta_k f_k^*(\eta). \quad (2.31)$$

With the help of Eqs. (2.9, 2.11, 2.12), one may show that

$$|\alpha_k|^2 - |\beta_k|^2 = 1. \quad (2.32)$$

Moreover, Eq. (2.18) gives the number density of particles of type A with momentum \mathbf{k} , in the vacuum of the particles of type a , as follows

$$n_{\mathbf{k}}^{(A)} \equiv \frac{N_{\mathbf{k}}^{(A)}}{V} = |\beta_k|^2. \quad (2.33)$$

where we have used $(2\pi)^3 \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k}) = V$. It is evident that $|\beta_k|^2$ is indeed the occupation number per cell of phase space. This can be seen from the *total number* of particles of type A in the state $|0_a\rangle$,

$$\begin{aligned} N^{(A)} &= V \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{k}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} |\beta_k|^2 \\ &= \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{x} d^3\mathbf{k}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} |\beta_k|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (2.34)$$

One may show that the explicit relation between the vacuum states $|0_A\rangle$ and $|0_a\rangle$ is given by [100]

$$\begin{aligned} |0_a\rangle &= \exp\left[-\int \frac{d^3\mathbf{k}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \frac{\beta_k^*}{2\alpha_k} \hat{A}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{A}_{-\mathbf{k}}^\dagger\right] |0_A\rangle \\ &= \prod_{\mathbf{k}} \frac{1}{|\alpha_k|^{1/2}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\beta_k^*}{2\alpha_k}\right)^n |n_{\mathbf{k}_A}, n_{-\mathbf{k}_A}\rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (2.35)$$

where the vacuum state $|0_A\rangle$ represents the two-mode vacuum state $|0_{\mathbf{k}_A}, 0_{-\mathbf{k}_A}\rangle$. Note that we shifted from the continuum notation to a discrete notation using the convention $\int d^3\mathbf{k}/(2\pi)^{3/2} \rightarrow \sum_{\mathbf{k}}$. Broadly speaking, Eq. (2.35) represents a continuum of two-mode squeezed state, also introduced in the context of quantum optics [103]. Consequently, Eq. (2.35) implies that as a result of linear momentum-conservation, the particles come in pairs with opposite momenta \mathbf{k} and $-\mathbf{k}$. The state Eq. (2.35) is called a two-mode squeezed state in which gravitons in the opposite momenta are highly entangled. This state also describes the state

of photons in the parametric down-conversion [97], which explicitly shows the analogy with the particle creation in an expanding Universe.

2.1.3 Ambiguity of the vacuum state

We have seen that in a general curved spacetime, there is no unique way to define the time coordinate, the mode functions of the field theory, the corresponding vacuum state, and particles. All the mode functions related by Eq. (2.11) are on the same foot, and this raises the question of which kind of vacuum and particles are physical. To better understand the question, let's describe the situation in more detail. When we study the propagation of a field in a general gravitational background, two natural length-scales (or equivalent time-scales) appear: the first one is the wavelength $\lambda \propto k^{-1}$ which shows the length at which the field configuration changes, and a relevant cosmological length-scale R which shows the length-scale of variation of the background gravitational field. Practically, R could be given by $\mathcal{R}^{-1/2}$ where \mathcal{R} is the Ricci scalar. In the Minkowski spacetime, we usually describe fields by expanding them in terms of plane waves $e^{-i(\omega t + \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x})}$. For each mode, the momentum is well-defined only if $\Delta k \ll k$ with Δk being the momentum spread, and this gives rise to the spatial size of the wave packet to be large, i.e., $\Delta x \gg k^{-1}$. However, when the geometry of spacetime varies significantly across a region of size Δx , the plane waves are not a good approximation to the solution of the wave equation, and the concept of a particle with momentum k fails. Indeed, the Fourier decomposition technique is meaningful only when $k^{-1} < \Delta x < R$, where R shows the curvature scale (the distance below which the spacetime can be approximated by Minkowski spacetime).

In the cosmological setup of spatially-flat FLRW, the Ricci scalar is given by $\mathcal{R} = \frac{6}{a^2}(\mathcal{H}' + 2\mathcal{H}^2)$ in conformal coordinates, which indicates that the inverse Hubble parameter \mathcal{H}^{-1} can be regarded as the relevant length-scale R . According to Eq. (2.24), modes with squared frequency $\omega_k^2(\eta) \equiv k^2 - a''/a \leq 0$ do not oscillate and for them, the harmonic oscillator analogy breaks down. Moreover, it can be shown that, when quantizing this harmonic oscillator, the lowest energy state that minimizes the Hamiltonian does not exist [104]. As we shall see in detail in Sec. 3.2, the condition $\omega_k^2(\eta) \leq 0$ is equivalent to the criteria $k \leq 2\pi\mathcal{H}$ that is accompanied by the *particle creation* fueled by the intense varying gravitational field. For these *super-Hubble modes*, with wavelengths exceeding the Hubble scale $\lambda \geq \mathcal{H}^{-1}$, the energy is unbounded from below due to the interaction with the external gravitational background, which acts as a mechanism to transform the gravitational energy of the expanding Universe into the field particles. It can be seen from Eq. (2.24) that for *sub-Hubble* modes with $k \geq a''/a$, the mode functions coincide with Minkowski solutions (in conformal coordinates) $\chi_k(\eta) \sim \frac{1}{\sqrt{k}}e^{-ik\eta}$, while for super-Hubble modes with $k \leq a''/a$ the solutions differ from the Minkowski solutions, and hence become a superposition of the *in* and *out* mode functions and the corresponding Bogoliubov coefficient β appears as a signature of particle creation. Formally, even for $\omega_k^2 \leq 0$ mode expansions still make sense, but the interpretation of the corresponding states

in Hilbert space in terms of physical particles is problematic. However, this does not lead to ambiguities in physical predictions, since one has to consider the detector response which can be unambiguously determined for a given quantum state of the field.

2.2 Cosmological tensor perturbations

Inflation is the standard paradigm for the early Universe and describes an accelerated expansion epoch that occurred before the hot Big Bang phase [29]. Besides offering simple and elegant solutions to the hot big bang puzzles, it naturally provides a mechanism for generating large-scale fluctuations. According to cosmic inflation, primordial perturbations originated from the quantum fluctuations of the gravitational and inflation fields. In this manner, inflation links the large-scale structure of the Universe to its microphysics by stretching the quantum fluctuations from scales close to the Planckian length to galactic scales. Technically, the amplification of quantum fluctuations of the inflation field could give rise to two types of perturbations: scalar fluctuations and gravitational waves. As the main objective of the present study, we focus only on the tensor sector. At the linear level, the tensor sector of the perturbed FLRW spacetime is defined by

$$ds^2 = a^2(\eta) \left[-d\eta^2 + (\delta_{ij} + h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta)) dx^i dx^j \right]. \quad (2.36)$$

Here, h_{ij} is the gauge invariant tensor perturbation that is Transverse-Traceless (TT), with the properties $\partial^j h_{ij} = \delta^{ij} h_{ij} = 0$ ($i, j = 1, 2, 3$). In the literature, it is convenient to work in natural units where $\hbar = c = 1$. In the natural units, the Einstein-Hilbert action $S_{\text{EH}} = \frac{c^3}{16\pi G} \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} \mathcal{R}$ takes the form $S_{\text{EH}} = \frac{M_{\text{Pl}}^2}{2} \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} \mathcal{R}$ where $M_{\text{Pl}} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c}{8\pi G}}$ is the reduced Planck mass and \mathcal{R} is the Ricci scalar. In order to recover the expressions in terms of physical units, one has to substitute $M_{\text{Pl}}^2 \rightarrow M_{\text{Pl}}^2 c^2 / \hbar$. Given the action S_{EH} , Einstein equations governing the evolution of tensor perturbations $h_{ij}(\eta, \mathbf{x})$ can be derived by expanding the $S_{\text{EH}} = \frac{M_{\text{Pl}}^2}{2} \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} \mathcal{R}$ to quadratic order in h_{ij} around a FLRW background. Skipping the details (see [100, 101] for derivation), this gives rise to the following action quadratic in the field h_{ij} ,

$$S^{(2)}[h_{ij}] \approx \frac{M_{\text{Pl}}^2}{8} \int d\eta d^3\mathbf{x} a^2(\eta) \left(h^{ij'} h'_{ij} - \partial^k h^{ij} \partial_k h_{ij} \right) \quad (2.37)$$

, where ' denotes the derivative with respect to conformal time and spatial indices, are raised and lowered with the help of the unit tensor δ_{ij} . To decouple time and spatial variables, it is convenient to introduce the Fourier transform of the metric perturbation $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta)$ by

$$h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta) = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{M_{\text{Pl}}} \sum_{\gamma=+, \times} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \frac{d^3\mathbf{K}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} e_{ij}^{\gamma}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma}(\eta) e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}}, \quad (2.38)$$

where the vector $\mathbf{K} \equiv K\hat{\mathbf{K}}$ denotes the comoving wave vector, $\gamma = +, \times$ denote the polarization state of the field and $e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}]$ represents the polarization tensor. Note that, throughout the subsequent chapters, we use upper-case letters $K \equiv (\Omega_K/c, \mathbf{K})$ to show the GWs four-momentum, while the lower-case letters $k \equiv (\omega_k/c, \mathbf{k})$ are used to denote the EM four-momentum. The normalization factor $\sqrt{2}/M_{\text{Pl}}$ in Eq. (2.38) is chosen so that the action takes a canonical form (see Eq. (2.42)). Note that the tensor field $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta)$ is a dimensionless quantity.

Since the tensor field $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta)$ is real, one has $e_{ij}^\gamma[-\hat{\mathbf{K}}] = e_{ij}^{*\gamma}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}]$ and $h_{-\mathbf{K}}^\gamma = h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma*}$. This property implies that, in the Fourier space, all degrees of freedom are not independent. This is of course expected since we describe the metric perturbations in terms of real quantities while $h_{\mathbf{K}}^\gamma(\eta)$ is complex. The polarization tensor $e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}]$ fulfills the following conditions [91]

$$K^i e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] = 0 \quad , \quad e_{ii}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad e_{ij}^{\gamma*}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] e_{ij}^{\gamma'}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] = 2\delta_{\gamma\gamma'}. \quad (2.39)$$

stemming from TT gauge conditions. The two independent polarization states $\gamma = +, \times$ can be expressed in terms of two unit vectors $(\hat{\mathbf{n}}, \hat{\mathbf{m}})$ orthogonal to the propagation direction $\hat{\mathbf{K}}$ and to each other. In terms of the Euler's angles (Θ_K, Φ_K) one may specify $(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{n}}, \hat{\mathbf{m}})$ by

$$\hat{\mathbf{K}} = \begin{pmatrix} \sin \Theta_K \cos \Phi_K \\ \sin \Theta_K \sin \Phi_K \\ \cos \Theta_K \end{pmatrix}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{n}} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \Theta_K \cos \Phi_K \\ \cos \Theta_K \sin \Phi_K \\ -\sin \Theta_K \end{pmatrix}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{m}} = \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \Phi_K \\ \cos \Phi_K \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.40)$$

and the polarization tensors are written as

$$\begin{cases} \hat{e}_{ij}^+[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] = \hat{n}_i \hat{n}_j - \hat{m}_i \hat{m}_j, \\ \hat{e}_{ij}^\times[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] = \hat{m}_i \hat{n}_j + \hat{n}_i \hat{m}_j, \end{cases} \quad (2.41)$$

which satisfy the conditions Eq. (2.39). Inserting Eq. (2.38) into the action Eq. (2.37) and rearranging the terms one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} S^{(2)}[h_{ij}] &= \frac{1}{4} \sum_{\gamma, \gamma'} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d\eta d^3 \mathbf{K} a^2(\eta) \left(e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] e_{ij}^{\gamma'}[-\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \right. \\ &\quad \times \left. \left(h_{\mathbf{K}}^\gamma(\eta) \right)' \left(h_{-\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma'}(\eta) \right)' - K^2 h_{\mathbf{K}}^\gamma(\eta) h_{-\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma'}(\eta) \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma = +, \times} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d\eta d^3 \mathbf{K} a^2(\eta) \left(h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma'}(\eta) h_{-\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma'}(\eta) - K^2 h_{\mathbf{K}}^\gamma(\eta) h_{-\mathbf{k}=\mathbf{K}}^\gamma(\eta) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (2.42)$$

where in the last line we have used Eq. (2.39). Hence, the Euler-Lagrange equations imply that the Fourier field amplitude $h_{\mathbf{K}}^\gamma(\eta)$ satisfy the following equation of motion

$$h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma''}(\eta) + 2\mathcal{H}(\eta) h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma'}(\eta) + K^2 h_{\mathbf{K}}^\gamma(\eta) = 0, \quad (2.43)$$

where $\mathcal{H}(\eta) \equiv \frac{a'(\eta)}{a(\eta)}$ denotes the Hubble parameter in conformal coordinates. It can be

seen that both polarizations satisfy the same equation of motion, have similar statistical properties, and have equal contributions to the PGWs background. This means that the generated PGWs background is unpolarized. Hence, the superscript γ is dropped in the following equations. Eq. (2.43) can be solved for a given $a(\eta)$. This procedure has been extensively studied in the literature to obtain an analytical expression for the tensor perturbations (for instance see [105]). Specially, the solution of Eq. (2.43) in two asymptotic regimes is interesting: $K \gg 2\pi\mathcal{H}$ and $K \ll 2\pi\mathcal{H}$, corresponding to short-wavelength (sub-Hubble) and long-wavelength (super-Hubble) regimes, respectively. In the former case, the amplitude of the wave experiences a decay according to $h_{\mathbf{k}}^\gamma(\eta) \propto 1/a(\eta)$, while in the latter case, the amplitude stays constant during the whole long-wavelength regime [49]. We are specifically interested in long-wavelength regimes, where the modes are amplified. Thus, an approximate solution to Eq. (2.43) is provided in Chapter 3, when we consider power-law expansion of the Universe.

For the current purpose of PGWs quantization in the FLRW, it is convenient to work with the auxiliary field $\chi_{\mathbf{k}}(\eta)$ defined by

$$\chi_{\mathbf{k}}(\eta) \equiv a(\eta)h_{\mathbf{k}}(\eta). \quad (2.44)$$

The action Eq. (2.42) in terms of the auxiliary field can be rewritten as

$$S^{(2)} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathcal{R}^3} d\eta d^3\mathbf{K} \left[\chi'_{\mathbf{k}} \chi'^*_{\mathbf{k}} - \frac{a'}{a} (\chi_{\mathbf{k}} \chi'^*_{\mathbf{k}} + \chi'_{\mathbf{k}} \chi_{\mathbf{k}}^*) + \left(\left(\frac{a'}{a} \right)^2 - K^2 \right) \chi_{\mathbf{k}} \chi_{\mathbf{k}}^* \right]. \quad (2.45)$$

which is basically the same as the action of the massless scalar field, given by Eq. (2.23), and gives rise to the same equation of motion, given by Eq. (2.24), i.e.,

$$\chi''_{\mathbf{k}}(\eta) + \left(K^2 - \frac{a''}{a} \right) \chi_{\mathbf{k}}(\eta) = 0. \quad (2.46)$$

Hence, the evolution of the auxiliary field $\chi_{\mathbf{k}}(\eta)$ in conformal time η is formally the same as that of a scalar field in Minkowski spacetime, with a time-dependent mass $m_\chi^2 \equiv -a''/a$. In other words, Eq. (2.46) describes the evolution of a parametric oscillator with time-dependent frequency. The time dependence is due to the interaction with the (classical) background gravitational field accompanied by the *pump field* $a(\eta)$.

Before quantization of tensor perturbations, it is useful to make an analogy with the quantum mechanical motion of a particle in the presence of a potential barrier $V(x)$. The stationary Schrödinger equation for a particle in one-dimensional potential $V(x)$ is

$$\frac{d^2\psi}{dx^2} + (E - V(x))\psi = 0, \quad (2.47)$$

which is similar to the *mode equation* Eq. (2.46) when one replaces the spatial coordinate x by time η and $K^2 - a''/a \rightarrow E - V(x)$. Hence, there would be a formal analogy between the notion of *particle creation* and the problem of quantum mechanical penetra-

Figure 2.1: Quantum mechanical analogy : motion in a potential $V(x)$.

tion through a potential barrier. Consider the barrier shown in Fig. 2.1, where an incident plane wave with an amplitude α is propagating towards it: if $E \geq V(x)$, the wave does not feel the barrier and transmits without reflection. However, if the barrier potential exceeds the energy of the wave, the wave splits into reflected and transmitted waves with corresponding amplitudes β and γ . Due to the energy conservation, the conservation of probability follows as $|\alpha|^2 = |\beta|^2 + |\gamma|^2$. Normalizing the amplitude of the transmitted wave to unity, one has $|\alpha|^2 = |\beta|^2 + 1$. If no barrier exists, the wave transmits without reflection, and $|\beta| = 0$. However, in the presence of the barrier, some part of the incident wave reflects back. The incident wave in this situation plays the role of the initial vacuum fluctuations in the particle creation problem, while the reflected wave is analogues to the produced particles.

2.3 Quantization of tensor perturbations in FLRW spacetime

In this section, we are especially interested in the quantization of tensor perturbations during the long-wavelength regime. In the following discussion, we chose the formalism and notation that is previously introduced for the quantization of scalar perturbations in [41, 95].

2.3.1 Quantum Hamiltonian of tensor perturbations

In order to find the classical Hamiltonian of the system in terms of the auxiliary field $\chi_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)$, we first split the integral in the action Eq. (2.45) into two parts corresponding to $\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}$ and $\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3-}$, and change $\mathbf{K} \rightarrow -\mathbf{K}$ in the second part. Hence, the action is given by the following expression

$$\begin{aligned}
 S^{(2)} &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} d\eta d^3\mathbf{K} \left[\chi'_{\mathbf{K}} \chi'^*_{\mathbf{K}} + \chi^*_{\mathbf{K}} \chi'_{\mathbf{K}} - 2 \frac{a'}{a} (\chi'_{\mathbf{K}} \chi^*_{\mathbf{K}} + \chi_{\mathbf{K}} \chi'^*_{\mathbf{K}}) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \left(\left(\frac{a'}{a} \right)^2 - K^2 \right) (\chi_{\mathbf{K}} \chi^*_{\mathbf{K}} + \chi^*_{\mathbf{K}} \chi_{\mathbf{K}}) \right], \tag{2.48}
 \end{aligned}$$

where each term is explicitly written in a commutative format. Also, note that the integral over whole Fourier space $\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3$ is now performed in half Fourier space, $\mathbf{k} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}$. The integrand in the action defines the Lagrangian density of the system, hence one may define the conjugate momentum of the classical variables. Note that, here we have two independent variables $(\chi_{\mathbf{K}}, \chi_{\mathbf{K}}^*)$ with their corresponding conjugate momenta

$$\begin{aligned} p_{\mathbf{K}} &\equiv p_{\chi_{\mathbf{K}}^*} = \frac{\delta \mathcal{L}}{\delta \chi_{\mathbf{K}}^*} = \chi'_{\mathbf{K}} - \frac{a'}{a} \chi_{\mathbf{K}}, \\ p_{\chi_{\mathbf{K}}} &= \frac{\delta \mathcal{L}}{\delta \chi'_{\mathbf{K}}} = \chi_{\mathbf{K}}^* - \frac{a'}{a} \chi_{\mathbf{K}}^* = p_{\mathbf{K}}^*. \end{aligned} \quad (2.49)$$

The Hamiltonian of the system is thus given by

$$H = \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} d^3 \mathbf{K} (p_{\mathbf{K}} \chi'_{\mathbf{K}} + p_{\mathbf{K}}^* \chi'_{\mathbf{K}} - L). \quad (2.50)$$

where the Lagrangian L is given by the Kernel of the action Eq. (2.48). Note that, basically the Lagrangian is defined by $S = \int dt L$, while in Eq. (2.48) it is of the form $S = \int d\eta L$, thus the two Lagrangians differ by a multiplicative factor c so that the correct dimensionality of S is achieved. As a result, the following Hamiltonian must also be multiplied by a factor c to represent the energy of the field. Inserting Eq. (2.49) into the Hamiltonian Eq. (2.50) and eliminating $\chi'_{\mathbf{K}}$ using Eq. (2.49), one obtains

$$H = \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} d^3 \mathbf{K} \left[p_{\mathbf{K}} p_{\mathbf{K}}^* + \frac{a'}{a} (p_{\mathbf{K}} \chi_{\mathbf{K}}^* + p_{\mathbf{K}}^* \chi_{\mathbf{K}}) + K^2 \chi_{\mathbf{K}} \chi_{\mathbf{K}}^* \right]. \quad (2.51)$$

The quantization procedure consists of the introduction of the ladder operators $\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}$ and $\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger$, obeying the bosonic commutation relations $[\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}'}^\dagger] = \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}')$ (note that, the dimensionality of the ladder operators must be as $\dim[\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}] = V^{1/2}$, so that the integration over $d^3 \mathbf{K}$ gives rise to energy in Eq. (2.51)). Thus, the Mukhanov-Sasaki variable and its conjugate momentum will be expressed as a combination of these operators. However, one should use the correct combination so that the property $\hat{\chi}_{-\mathbf{K}} = \hat{\chi}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger$ is fulfilled. The following expansions

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\chi}_{\mathbf{K}} &= \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2K}} (\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} + \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}^\dagger), \\ \hat{p}_{\mathbf{K}} &= -i \sqrt{\frac{\hbar K}{2}} (\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} - \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}^\dagger), \end{aligned} \quad (2.52)$$

not only ensures $\hat{\chi}_{-\mathbf{K}} = \hat{\chi}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger$ but also gives rise to the correct commutation relations between the field variables $(\hat{\chi}_{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\chi}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger)$ and their corresponding conjugate momenta. According to

Eq. (2.52) one has

$$\begin{aligned} [\hat{\chi}_{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{p}_{\chi_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger}] &= [\hat{\chi}_{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{p}_{\mathbf{K}}] = \frac{-i\hbar}{2} [\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} + \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}^\dagger, \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} - \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}^\dagger] = 0, \\ [\hat{\chi}_{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{p}_{\chi_{\mathbf{K}}}] &= [\hat{\chi}_{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{p}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger] = \frac{i\hbar}{2} [\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} + \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}^\dagger, \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger - \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}] = i\hbar. \end{aligned} \quad (2.53)$$

The first formula assures that the variable $\chi_{\mathbf{K}}$ commutes with the corresponding conjugate momenta of $\chi_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger$, i.e., $\hat{p}_{\chi_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger}$, while the second formula shows the standard commutation relation between the variable $\hat{\chi}_{\mathbf{K}}$ and its conjugate momenta $\hat{p}_{\chi_{\mathbf{K}}}$. Plugging Eq. (2.52) into the Hamiltonian Eq. (2.51) results in the following expression for the Hamiltonian of tensor perturbations in terms of the creation and annihilation operators,

$$\hat{H} = \hbar \int_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} d^3\mathbf{K} [K(\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger + \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}\hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}^\dagger) - i\frac{a'}{a}(\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}\hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}} - \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger\hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}^\dagger)]. \quad (2.54)$$

Here, we have substituted the conformal Hubble parameter $\mathcal{H} = a'/a$. The first term in Eq. (2.54) represents the energy of a collection of free oscillators with frequency $\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} = cK$, while the second one describes the interaction between perturbation modes with opposite momenta, mediated by the classical pumping field of the FLRW background. The dynamical evolution of the tensor perturbations is governed by the Hamiltonian Eq. (2.54). Of course, if the scale factor is constant (i.e., the Minkowski spacetime), then this interaction disappears. The Hamiltonian Eq. (2.54) realizes the two-mode squeezing operation and is analogous to optical parametric down-conversion [97], where an incoming intense optical pump field is converted to *signal* and *idler* fields that form a highly entangled state. Indeed, this interaction is responsible for the creation of pairs of particles, as is discussed in detail below.

2.3.2 Evolution of tensor perturbations in expanding Universe and squeezing representation

We now discuss the equation of motion governing the evolution of tensor perturbations. Given the Hamiltonian Eq. (2.54), the Heisenberg equation of motion, namely $d\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}/d\eta = -i/\hbar[\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{H}]$, leads to

$$i\frac{d\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}}{d\eta} = K\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} + i\mathcal{H}\hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}^\dagger. \quad (2.55)$$

The first term represents the free evolution of mode \mathbf{K} of the perturbations, while the second term shows the fact that the creation of a particle in mode $-\mathbf{K}$, mediated by the expanding FLRW background, is accompanied by annihilation of a particle in mode \mathbf{K} . The solution of this equation can be written as

$$\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta) = u_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_{\text{ini}}) + v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)\hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}^\dagger(\eta_{\text{ini}}), \quad (2.56)$$

with the initial conditions $u_K(\eta_{\text{ini}}) = 1$ and $v_K(\eta_{\text{ini}}) = 0$. Here, η_{ini} represents an initial time (during the inflationary epoch) before the mode \mathbf{K} enters the super-Hubble regime. Combining Eq. (2.55) and Eq. (2.56), time evolution of the functions $(u_K(\eta), v_K(\eta))$ are determined by

$$\begin{aligned} i \frac{du_K(\eta)}{d\eta} &= K u_K(\eta) + i \mathcal{H} v_K^*(\eta), \\ i \frac{dv_K(\eta)}{d\eta} &= K v_K(\eta) + i \mathcal{H} u_K^*(\eta), \end{aligned} \quad (2.57)$$

together with the condition $|u_K(\eta)|^2 - |v_K(\eta)|^2 = 1$ in order the bosonic commutation relation, $[\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}'}^\dagger] = \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}')$, to hold. Hence, solving the Bogoliubov system Eq. (2.57) is equivalent to solving the time-dependent Heisenberg equation (2.55). It is convenient to express (u_K, v_K) in terms of three parameters $(r_K(\eta), \phi_K(\eta), \theta_K(\eta))$ defined by [41, 95]

$$\begin{aligned} u_K(\eta) &\equiv e^{i\theta_K} \cosh r_K, \\ v_K(\eta) &\equiv e^{-i\theta_K + 2i\phi_K} \sinh r_K. \end{aligned} \quad (2.58)$$

Now, we define the *squeezing parameter* according to $\zeta_K \equiv r_K e^{2i\phi_K}$, with (r_K, ϕ_K) being the squeezing amplitude and squeezing angle respectively. Moreover, we define two unitary operators. The first one is the two-mode squeezing operator $\hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}(\zeta_K)$ defined by

$$\hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}(\zeta_K) \equiv \exp \left[\zeta_K^* \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}(\eta_{\text{ini}}) \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_{\text{ini}}) - \zeta_K \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}^\dagger(\eta_{\text{ini}}) \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger(\eta_{\text{ini}}) \right], \quad (2.59)$$

with the property $\hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger(\zeta_K) = \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}^{-1}(\zeta_K) = \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}(-\zeta_K)$. The second operator is the rotation operator $\hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}(\theta_K)$ defined by

$$\hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}(\theta_K) \equiv \exp \left[-i\theta_K \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger(\eta_{\text{ini}}) \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_{\text{ini}}) - i\theta_K \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}^\dagger(\eta_{\text{ini}}) \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}(\eta_{\text{ini}}) \right], \quad (2.60)$$

with the property $\hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger(\theta_K) = \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}^{-1}(\theta_K) = \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}(-\theta_K)$. In the next step, one may compute the quantity $\hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_{\text{ini}}) \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}} \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}$, using the formula $e^{-\hat{O}} \hat{A} e^{\hat{O}} = \hat{A} + [\hat{O}, \hat{A}] + [\hat{O}, [\hat{O}, \hat{A}]]/2! + \dots$. One ends up with the following expressions

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_{\text{ini}}) \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}} \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}} &= e^{i\theta_K} \cosh r_K \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_{\text{ini}}) + e^{-i\theta_K + 2i\phi_K} \sinh r_K \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}^\dagger(\eta_{\text{ini}}), \\ \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}(\eta_{\text{ini}}) \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}} \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}} &= e^{i\theta_K} \cosh r_K \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}(\eta_{\text{ini}}) + e^{-i\theta_K + 2i\phi_K} \sinh r_K \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger(\eta_{\text{ini}}). \end{aligned} \quad (2.61)$$

By comparing Eq. (2.56) and Eq. (2.61), it can be seen that the two functions (u_K, v_K) defined by Eq. (2.58) truly realize the time evolution Eq. (2.56), and

$$\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta) = \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_{\text{ini}}) \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}} \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}, \quad (2.62)$$

Note that, (u_K, v_K) automatically satisfy the condition $|u_K(\eta)|^2 - |v_K(\eta)|^2 = 1$. Hence, the inevitable appearance of a two-mode squeezing operator in the problem is evident, as we

have previously described qualitatively in Sec. 2.1.1.

It can be seen from Eq. (2.58) that in the course of the expansion of the Universe, the corresponding Bogoliubov function $v_k(\eta)$ which indicates the mixing of opposite modes \mathbf{K} and $-\mathbf{K}$ is non-vanishing provided that $r_K \neq 0$. As we will see in the following, the squeezing amplitude r_K is directly related to the number of e-folds during the time interval that the mode \mathbf{K} is in the super-Hubble regime, hence proportional to the increase of scale factor during that time interval. Once a given mode \mathbf{K} leaves the Hubble horizon, two waves are spontaneously generated with opposite momenta and graviton creation occurs in pairs. Naturally, quantum fluctuations of tensor perturbations also get subjected to the process of particle creation. Consequently, the two super-Hubble modes \mathbf{K} and $-\mathbf{K}$ initially at the vacuum state $|0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}}\rangle$ evolve into a two-mode squeezed state that is an entangled state. The total Hilbert space of the system can be factorized into direct product of the Hilbert spaces of the two modes \mathbf{K} and $-\mathbf{K}$ according to $\mathcal{E} = \prod_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \mathcal{E}_{\mathbf{K}} \otimes \mathcal{E}_{-\mathbf{K}}$, with the initial vacuum state $|\{0\}\rangle \equiv \prod_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} |0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}}\rangle$. In the Heisenberg picture, the field operator evolves with time, while the state of the system does not. The field operator Eq. (2.38) thus becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta) &= \frac{C}{a(\eta)} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \frac{d^3\mathbf{K}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \frac{e_{ij}^{\gamma}(\hat{\mathbf{K}})}{\sqrt{2\Omega_K}} \left\{ \left(\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K},\gamma}(\eta) + \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K},\gamma}^{\dagger}(\eta) \right) e^{i\mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \left(\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K},\gamma}^{\dagger}(\eta) + \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K},\gamma}(\eta) \right) e^{-i\mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x}} \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.63)$$

where we have used Eq. (2.44) and Eq. (2.52). We have also assumed real polarization tensor with the property $e_{ij}^{\gamma}[-\hat{\mathbf{K}}] = e_{ij}^{\gamma*}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] = e_{ij}^{\gamma}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}]$. Also note that, the time behavior of $\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K},\gamma}(\eta)$ is identical for both polarization degrees of freedom $\gamma = +, \times$, as specified by Eq. (2.56). This implies that for each tensor mode \mathbf{K} , both polarization states are necessarily generated with equal amplitudes. Consequently, the inflationary-generated PGWs is statistically *unpolarized*. Moreover, rewriting everything in physical units, one can show that the coefficient C is determined by $C = \sqrt{16\pi c \ell_{Pl}}$ as previously obtained in [49]. We will re-derive this coefficient later in Chapter 5 when quantizing GWs in Minkowski spacetime (in Chapter 5, we give an equivalent way of quantizing GWs which is slightly different from the present procedure, but of course the results are the same). It will turn out that the coefficient C determines the coupling strength of EM-GWs interaction.

On the other hand, one could equivalently consider the Schrödinger picture in which the quantum field operators stay constant while the evolution of the initial state of the system is governed by the Hamiltonian Eq. (2.54), which is the generator of the two-mode squeezed (TS) states. The evolution of the initial vacuum state into the TS state takes place according to

$$|\text{TS}_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)\rangle \equiv |\psi_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)\rangle = \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}(r_K, \phi_K) \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}(\theta_K) |0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}}\rangle. \quad (2.64)$$

Using the operator ordering lemma one may establish the following normal-ordered form

Figure 2.2: Two-dimensional Wigner function, $W(x, v)$, representation of a typical two-mode squeezed state based on Eq. (2.67). Here, $r_K = 1$ and $\phi_K = 0$ are chosen.

for the squeezing operator [106]

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}(r_K, \phi_K) &= \exp \{ e^{-2i\phi_K} \tanh r_K \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}^\dagger(\eta_{\text{ini}}) \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger(\eta_{\text{ini}}) \} \\ &\times \exp \{ -\ln(\cosh r_K) [\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger(\eta_{\text{ini}}) \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_{\text{ini}}) + \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}(\eta_{\text{ini}}) \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}^\dagger(\eta_{\text{ini}})] \} \\ &\times \exp \{ -e^{2i\phi_K} \tanh r_K \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}(\eta_{\text{ini}}) \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_{\text{ini}}) \}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.65)$$

Moreover, one may easily check that the vacuum state is rotationally invariant as it should be, i.e., $\hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}(\theta_K)|0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}}\rangle = |0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}}\rangle$. This implies that the parameter θ_K will be irrelevant in all physical quantities, as long as we are interested in amplified vacuum fluctuations. Straightforward calculations lead to

$$\begin{aligned} |\text{TS}_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)\rangle &= \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}(r_K, \phi_K) \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}(\theta_K) |0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}}\rangle \\ &= \frac{1}{\cosh r_K} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} e^{-2in\phi_K} \tanh^n r_K |n_{\mathbf{K}}, n_{-\mathbf{K}}\rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (2.66)$$

and the presence of particle pairs is more evident in this form (compare with Eq. (2.35)). Hence, $|\text{TS}_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)\rangle$ which describes quantum state of tensor perturbation of mode \mathbf{K} at time η , is a two-mode squeezed state that is also well-known as a highly entangled state in the context of quantum optics since it cannot be written in a separable form as $|\psi_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)\rangle \otimes |\psi_{-\mathbf{K}}(\eta)\rangle$. Hence, we are facing a highly non-classical gravitational wave background that is basically the remnant of very early epochs of the Universe. To illustrate the phase-space representation of the TS state, one may calculate the Wigner function, $W_{\text{ts}}(\alpha, \alpha^*, \beta, \beta^*)$, which is essentially a four-dimensional probability distribution in four-dimensional space $(\Re(\alpha), \Im(\alpha), \Re(\beta), \Im(\beta))$. It is straightforward to show that the Wigner function for the

two-mode squeezed vacuum is (see [97] for details of calculations)

$$\begin{aligned}
W_{\text{ts}}(\alpha, \alpha^*, \beta, \beta^*) &= \frac{4}{\pi^2} \exp(-2|\alpha \cosh r_K - \beta^* \sinh r_K e^{i\phi_K}|^2 \\
&\quad - 2|-\alpha^* \sinh r_K e^{i\phi_K} + \beta \cosh r_K|^2) \\
&= \frac{4}{\pi^2} \exp(-2|(x + iy) \cosh r_K - (v - iw) \sinh r_K e^{i\phi_K}|^2 \\
&\quad - 2|-(x - iy) \sinh r_K e^{i\phi_K} + (v + iw) \cosh r_K|^2) \\
&\equiv W(x, y, v, w).
\end{aligned} \tag{2.67}$$

In the last equality, the four parameters $(\alpha, \alpha^*, \beta, \beta^*)$ are expressed in terms of four parameters x, y, v, w where $\alpha \equiv x + iy$ and $\beta \equiv v + iw$ are defined. To obtain a visualization, we may set $y = w = 0$, i.e., consider real α and β . The Wigner function $W(x, v)$ is shown in Fig. 2.2 for chosen values of $r_K = 1$ and $\phi_K = 0$. It shows a Gaussian distribution in two-dimensional space (x, v) . By definition, it shows the probability of finding the mode \mathbf{K} and $-\mathbf{K}$ in the point (x, y) in the phase space, respectively. Clearly, it shows the squeezing in a certain direction. It turns out that the major axis of the elliptic contours makes an angle $\theta = n\pi/4$ with the x -axis, where $n \in \mathcal{Z}$.

In the following, we mainly work with the squeezing parameters (r_K, ϕ_K) . Using Eq. (2.57) and Eq. (2.58), one may show that the squeezing parameters (r_K, ϕ_K) and the rotation angle θ_K , which basically specify the final state of the system at a given instant of time η , are governed by

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{dr_K}{d\eta} &= \frac{a'}{a} \cos(2\phi_K), \\
\frac{d\phi_K}{d\eta} &= -K - \frac{a'}{a} \coth(2r_K) \sin(2\phi_K), \\
\frac{d\theta_K}{d\eta} &= -K - \frac{a'}{a} \tanh(r_K) \sin(2\phi_K).
\end{aligned} \tag{2.68}$$

It can be seen that the evolution of the squeezing parameters is decoupled from the evolution of the rotation parameter. Consequently, solving the first two equations for the squeezing parameters determines the time behavior of the rotation parameter as well. The system of Eqs. (2.68) will be solved in Chapter 3 for a cosmological model which includes successive stages of the expansion: quasi de Sitter, radiation dominated (RD), matter-dominated (MD) and dark energy dominated (ΛD). For the purpose of illustration, here we consider the exact de Sitter (DS) case for which the conformal scale factor is characterized by $a(\eta) \propto -\eta^{-1}$ and $\eta < 0$ during inflation. In this case, the conformal Hubble parameter is given by $\mathcal{H} = a'/a = |\eta|^{-1}$, and the solution of Eq. (2.68) turns out to be

Figure 2.3: Typical behavior of parameters (r_K, ϕ_K, θ_K) versus the dimensionless parameter $K\eta$ in the exact de Sitter expansion, based on Eq. (2.69), shown by blue, orange and green curves, respectively.

given by [95]

$$\begin{aligned}
 r_K(\eta) &= -\operatorname{arcsinh}\left(\frac{1}{2K\eta}\right), \\
 \phi_K(\eta) &= -\frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{1}{2} \arctan\left(\frac{1}{2K\eta}\right), \\
 \theta_K(\eta) &= -K\eta - \arctan\left(\frac{1}{2K\eta}\right).
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.69}$$

Consequently, the behavior of the squeezing parameters strongly depends on the dimensionless parameter $K\eta$. Sub-Hubble scales are determined by the condition $K \geq \mathcal{H}$ or $K\mathcal{H}^{-1} = K|\eta| \geq 1$. Fig. 2.3 shows the typical behavior of the parameters (r_K, ϕ_K, θ_K) versus the dimensionless parameter $K\eta$ in case of exact de Sitter expansion, in blue, orange, and green curves. For super-Hubble scales ($K|\eta| \ll 1$) at the end of inflation, one has $r_K \rightarrow +\infty$, $\phi_K \rightarrow 0$ and $\theta_K \rightarrow \pi/2$ which remains true for quasi de Sitter expansion as well. On the other hand, for sub-Hubble scales ($K|\eta| \geq 1$) one has $r_K \rightarrow 0$, $\phi_K \rightarrow -\pi/4$. In this case, $\theta_K \propto -K\eta$ indicates free evolution of each tensor mode in the absence of the underlying gravitational field of FLRW. From this example, one may understand that the inflationary stage acts as a pumping mechanism that enforces the vacuum of tensor modes into the highly-squeezed state, which possesses a high number of gravitons. This process is called *super-adiabatic amplification*, which lies at the heart of particle creation in the expanding Universe.

Eq. (2.69) implies that, at sub-Hubble scales, $\phi_K(\eta) \simeq -K\eta$, hence $r'_K \simeq \frac{a'}{a} \cos(2K\eta)$. If $a(\eta)$ varies over a time-scale H^{-1} that is much larger than K^{-1} , i.e., for the sub-Hubble

scales, then the integral $\int \frac{a'}{a} \cos(2K\eta) d\eta$ can be WKB expanded as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 r_K(\eta) &= \int \frac{a'}{a} \cos(2K\eta) d\eta = \int_{\eta_{**}}^{\eta} \mathcal{H}(\eta) \cos(2K\eta) d\eta \quad (2.70) \\
 &\simeq \mathcal{H}(\eta_{**}) \int_{\eta_{**}}^{\eta} \cos(2K\eta) d\eta \\
 &= \mathcal{H}(\eta_{**}) \frac{\sin(2K\eta) - \sin(2K\eta_{**})}{2K} \\
 &\propto \frac{\mathcal{H}(\eta_{**})}{K} = \frac{a(t_{**})H(t_{**})}{K_{\text{phy}}} \ll 1.
 \end{aligned}$$

Here, η_{**} stands for the conformal time at which the mode K re-enters the Hubble horizon. Hence, the first nonvanishing term is suppressed by $(\frac{a(t_{**})H(t_{**})}{K_{\text{phy}}})$. On the other hand, super-hubble scales are specified by the condition $K \ll \mathcal{H}$ or $K|\eta| \ll 1$.

2.4 Characteristic features of inflationary-generated primordial gravitational waves

For our later destinations, it seems necessary to investigate the correlation functions of the PGWs background. These correlations are reflected in the behavior of the EM field observables and determine the ultimate behavior of the EM probe. In this section, we derive auto-correlation and two-point correlations of the inflationary-generated PGWs, and define the power spectrum $P(K, \eta)$ and the spectral amplitude $h(K, \eta)$ of PGWs. In Chapter 3 we shall obtain explicit expressions for spectral amplitude by solving dynamical equations governing PGWs.

2.4.1 Quantum correlations of PGWs

We may proceed in the Heisenberg picture and assume that the initial quantum state of the field is the continuum of the vacuum state. Statistical properties of the tensor field $\hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta)$ at later times are determined by the expectation values of the ladder operators $\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K},\gamma}(\eta)$ and $\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K},\gamma}^\dagger(\eta)$. While the mean values of the ladder operators are zero at any time, $\langle 0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}} | \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K},\gamma}(\eta) | 0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle = 0$ and $\langle 0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}} | \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K},\gamma}^\dagger(\eta) | 0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle = 0$, the mean values of the quadratic combinations of the ladder operators are non-zero, and are determined by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle 0_{\mathbf{p}}, 0_{-\mathbf{p}} | \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\eta) \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}', \gamma'}(\eta) | 0_{\mathbf{q}}, 0_{-\mathbf{q}} \rangle &= u_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta) v_{\mathbf{K}'}(\eta) \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}') \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K}' - \mathbf{q}) \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{p}) \\
 &= -e^{2i\phi_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)} \sinh r_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta) \cosh r_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta) \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \\
 &\times \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}') \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K}' - \mathbf{q}) \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{p}), \\
 \langle 0_{\mathbf{p}}, 0_{-\mathbf{p}} | \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}^\dagger(\eta) \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}', \gamma'}^\dagger(\eta) | 0_{\mathbf{q}}, 0_{-\mathbf{q}} \rangle &= v_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta) u_{\mathbf{K}'}^*(\eta) \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}') \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K}' - \mathbf{q}) \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{p}) \\
 &= -e^{-2i\phi_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)} \sinh r_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta) \cosh r_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta) \delta_{\gamma\gamma'}, \\
 &\times \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}') \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K}' - \mathbf{q}) \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{p}) \quad (2.71) \\
 \langle 0_{\mathbf{p}}, 0_{-\mathbf{p}} | \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\eta) \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}', \gamma'}^\dagger(\eta) | 0_{\mathbf{q}}, 0_{-\mathbf{q}} \rangle &= u_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta) u_{\mathbf{K}'}^*(\eta) \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}') \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K}' - \mathbf{q}) \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{p}) \\
 &= \cosh^2 r_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta) \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}') \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K}' - \mathbf{q}) \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{p}), \\
 \langle 0_{\mathbf{p}}, 0_{-\mathbf{p}} | \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}^\dagger(\eta) \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}', \gamma'}(\eta) | 0_{\mathbf{q}}, 0_{-\mathbf{q}} \rangle &= v_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta) v_{\mathbf{K}'}(\eta) \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}') \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K}' - \mathbf{q}) \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{p}) \\
 &= \sinh^2 r_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta) \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}') \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K}' - \mathbf{q}) \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{p}).
 \end{aligned}$$

The first two relations explicitly show that the modes with opposite momenta are not independent, but, on the contrary, are strongly correlated. The last two correlations are proportional to the mean number of generated gravitons in the TS state. As we expected, the parameter $\theta_{\mathbf{K}}$ does not appear in the correlations as long as we assume the vacuum state as the initial state of the field. One may note that Eq. (2.70) holds also for the correlations in one-mode squeezed state, with a difference that the delta function $\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}')$ is replaced by $\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}')$, stemming from the independency of the opposite momenta. Consequently, correlations between opposite momenta in the TS state lead to the *homogeneity* of the two-point spatial correlations of the tensor field, while these features are absent in a generic one-mode squeezed state in which different momenta are independent.

2.4.2 Spectral amplitude of PGWs

The power spectrum $P(K, \eta)$ and dimensionless spectral amplitude $h(K, \eta)$ are defined based on the auto-correlation of the field. In order to find the field correlation functions, first note that the quantized tensor field $\hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta)$ is given by Eq. (2.63). The mean value of the field $\hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta)$ is zero at every moment of time η and in every spatial point \mathbf{x} : $\langle \{0\} | \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta) | \{0\} \rangle = 0$. The auto-correlation of the field, also known as the variance, is defined by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle \{0\} | \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta) \hat{h}^{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta) | \{0\} \rangle &= \frac{16\ell_{Pl}^2}{\pi a^2(\eta)} \int \frac{d\mathbf{K}}{K} K^2 \\
 &\times \left(|u_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)|^2 + |v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)|^2 + u_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta) v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta) + u_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta) v_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta) \right), \quad (2.72)
 \end{aligned}$$

where Eq. (2.70) is used. In terms of the squeezing parameters, this expression can be

written as

$$\langle \{0\} | \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta) \hat{h}^{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta) | \{0\} \rangle = \frac{16\ell_{Pl}^2}{\pi a^2(\eta)} \int \frac{dK}{K} P(K, \eta), \quad (2.73)$$

where the *power spectrum* of the field is defined by [41]

$$P(K, \eta) \equiv K^2 (\cosh(2r_K(\eta)) + \sinh(2r_K(\eta)) \cos(2\phi_K(\eta))). \quad (2.74)$$

It is seen from Eq. (2.72) that the variance of the inflationary-generated PGWs does not depend on the spatial coordinate \mathbf{x} , which signifies the homogeneity of PGWs. An important property due to squeezing is that the power spectrum $P(K, \eta)$ is oscillating and vanishes many times [41]. This can be seen if one considers the modes that are well inside the present Hubble scale. We may denote by $\eta_*(K)$ and $\eta_{**}(K)$ the instants of time that a given mode \mathbf{K} left the Hubble horizon during inflation and reentered it during subsequent epochs, respectively (see Figure. 3.1 for more details). As we explained, Eq. (2.68) implies that after reentering the horizon, the squeezing parameter stays practically constant $r_K(\eta_{**}) \gg 1$, and the squeezing angle evolves as $\phi_K(\eta) = -K(\eta - \eta_{**}(K))$. For these modes, one has $P(K, \eta) \sim K^2 e^{2r_K(\eta)} \cos^2[K(\eta - \eta_{**}(K))]$, which vanishes for a series of modes whenever $K(\eta - \eta_{**}) \propto (2n + 1)\frac{\pi}{2}$. The dimensionless spectral amplitude of PGWs, $h(K, \eta)$, (also called as spectrum in some references [107]) is defined by

$$\int_0^\infty h^2(K, \eta) \frac{dK}{K} \equiv \langle \{0\} | \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta) \hat{h}^{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta) | \{0\} \rangle, \quad (2.75)$$

where the r.h.s is the variance of the field in vacuum state. Comparing Eq. (2.72) with Eq. (2.75), one reads the spectral amplitude as

$$h(K, \eta) = \frac{4\ell_{Pl}}{\sqrt{\pi}a(\eta)} K \left(|u_K(\eta)|^2 + |v_K(\eta)|^2 + u_K(\eta)v_K(\eta) + u_K^*(\eta)v_K^*(\eta) \right)^{1/2}, \quad (2.76)$$

where the functions $u_K(\eta)$ and $v_K(\eta)$ are given by Eq. (2.58) with the initial conditions $u_K(\eta_{ini}) = 1$ and $v_K(\eta_{in}) = 0$. Remind that, η_{ini} denotes a time instant before the outset of super-adiabatic amplification during the inflation epoch, and is indeed K -dependent. Using the expression Eq. (2.76), one may find the evolution of the spectral amplitude $h(K, \eta)$ readily, as soon as the evolution of the functions $u_K(\eta)$ and $v_K(\eta)$ are determined.

2.4.3 Spatial correlations of PGWs and stochasticity

Similar conclusions hold for the two-point spatial correlation function,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \{0\} | \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta) \hat{h}^{ij}(\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\ell}, \eta) | \{0\} \rangle &= \frac{16\ell_{Pl}^2}{\pi a^2(\eta)} \int dK K \frac{\sin(K\ell)}{K\ell} \\ &\times \left(1 + 2 \sinh^2 r_K(\eta) + \sinh(2r_K(\eta)) \cos(2\phi_K(\eta)) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.77)$$

Again, the spatial correlation function depends only on the separation between two points, l , but not on their coordinates, which reflects the homogeneity and isotropy of the PGWs background. Later in Sec. 5.3.4, we consider a hypothetical situation of a generic GWs background of one-mode squeezed state, which basically consists of independent harmonic oscillators, each of which is placed in squeezed state, so that there is absolutely no correlation between different modes \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' , in contrary to the two-mode squeezed state. The two-point correlation function of GWs $\langle \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\ell}, t) \rangle$ calculated in one-mode squeezed state is given by Eq. (5.64), which shows explicit dependence on \mathbf{x} and $\boldsymbol{\ell}$ and is basically inhomogeneous. For our later use, we calculate in App. A the expression of two-point correlations of GWs in various states, namely vacuum, coherent, one-mode squeezed, and thermal states. As we shall see in detail in Chapter 5, Chapter 6, and Chapter 7, the inhomogeneity of the two-point correlation function of GWs is directly imprinted on the two-point correlation functions of the EM field.

Another point about the correlation function Eq. (2.77) is that, although the field correlations strongly depend on the squeezing angle ϕ_K , the energy density of the field, which also includes the kinetic energy term in addition to Eq. (2.74), is smooth and the contribution of the oscillating factor $\cos(2\phi_K(\eta))$ cancels out [41].

To conclude this chapter, we touch upon the stochasticity of the inflationary-generated PGWs. In general, early Universe sources lead to the production of stochastic backgrounds of GWs today. The *stochasticity* points to the fact that the amplitude of tensor perturbations, $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta)$, is a random variable, and can be characterized only statistically, by means of ensemble averages. These gravitational waves could arise from a large number of random, independent events combined to create a cosmic gravitational wave background. For a stochastic gravitational wave background (SGWB), the ergodic hypothesis can be invoked so that the ensemble averages are replaced by either spatial and/or temporal averages [26]. The reason why the inflationary-generated GW signal is a stochastic background resides in the intrinsic quantum nature of the generating process. As we have seen in Sec. 2.3, inflationary PGWs are nothing but amplified quantum fluctuations of the tensorial FLRW metric perturbations, $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta)$. The amplified tensor perturbations are therefore random variables, due to intrinsically random initial conditions.

For an stochastic GW background, the following assumptions can be made. Firstly, the background is stationary. This means that all the correlators depend only on time difference and not on the absolute value of time. This assumption can be justified as follows: for a background created at cosmological epochs, the typical time-scale on which it can change substantially is of the order of the age of the Universe. Consequently, during typical experiments, which is at most a few year, the properties of the background could not change appreciably.

Moreover, the SGWB from early Universe sources is assumed to be *statistically homogeneous and isotropic, unpolarised and Gaussian*[26]. Here, we explain these features in the specific case of inflationary-generated PGWs. The statistical homogeneity and isotrop-

icity are inherited from the symmetries of the FLRW metric, whether during inflation or subsequent eras. Indeed, as can be seen from the interaction Hamiltonian Eq. (2.54), both modes \mathbf{K} and its opposite $-\mathbf{K}$ are generated at the same time, leading the Fourier amplitude $h_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)$ to be only K -dependent, $h_K(\eta)$. As we described in Sec. (2.1.2), this is a direct consequence of the linear-momentum conservation during the course of Universe expansion. As a result of homogeneity and isotropy, the two-point correlation function fulfills the general form of

$$\langle h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta_1) h_{lm}(\mathbf{y}, \eta_2) \rangle = \xi_{ijlm}(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|, \eta_1, \eta_2), \quad (2.78)$$

which can be easily verified by comparing it to Eq. (2.76). On the other hand, as we discussed in Sec. (2.2), the equation of motion for the generated tensor perturbations is identical for both polarization states of the field $\gamma = +, \times$, and the generated spectrum contains, on average, equal contributions of both polarizations. Hence, the inflationary-generated PGWs are unpolarized. Gaussianity also follows from the fact that the present PGWs signal is placed in a two-mode squeezed state which is a Gaussian state, in the sense that the Wigner function displayed in Fig. 2.2 is Gaussian. Alternatively, in the Schrödinger picture, the wavefunction is a Gaussian function. This is not manifest from Eq. (2.66), which is written in the Fock basis, but when written in the configuration representation it becomes explicit. Fundamentally, the reason is that the vacuum state is a Gaussian state, and linear evolution preserves Gaussianity (non-Gaussian statistics would arise at a higher order in cosmological perturbation theory).

Further detailed issues concerning generating mechanisms, characterization, and detection methods of stochastic GWs are vastly discussed in the literature. However, during the dissertation, we rarely need to work with those concepts. Instead, we mainly deal with the present spectrum $h(K, \eta_H)$ and the associated squeezing parameters $r_K(\eta_H)$ and $\phi_K(\eta_H)$, which consist the subject of the next chapter.

2.5 Summary and conclusions

In this chapter, we investigated the amplification of tensor perturbation in the FLRW Universe. Concepts such as the super-adiabatic amplification of vacuum perturbations, particle creation in an expanding Universe, and the existence of PGWs in a two-mode squeezed state are discussed. Some of the main findings are as follows:

- Combining general rules of the QFT and general relativity, quantization of tensor perturbation of the FLRW metric can be done in the standard manner. Following the Heisenberg equations of motion, the expression of the quantized field $\hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta)$ is given by Eq. (2.63).
- Dynamics of quantized tensor perturbations can be expressed in terms of the so-called squeezing parameters (r_K, ϕ_K) defined by Eq. (2.58), which determine the

spectrum of PGWs today.

- Two-point correlation function of the TS PGWs is obtained in Eq. (2.77) which is expressed in terms of the squeezing parameters. It shows homogeneity and isotropy, stemming from the existence of strong correlations between opposite momenta \mathbf{K} and $-\mathbf{K}$. Due to the absence of correlations between opposite momenta in a generic one-mode squeezed state, the corresponding two-point correlation function lacks homogeneity and isotropic, as we will discuss in detail in Sec. 5.3.4.

Chapter 3

PGWs spectrum in expanding Universe

As we have seen in Chapter 2, inflationary models generally predict the existence of a stochastic background of relic gravitational waves (RGWs). The resulting spectrum of generated tensor perturbations is not only important in cosmological computations, such as calculations of CMB anisotropies and polarizations induced by PGWs, but it is also crucial to be compared with sensitivity curves of ongoing and forthcoming GW detectors. On top of that, in the next chapters, we shall consider the interaction between the EM field and GWs, and propose experimental schemas to track the imprint of PGWs on the EM observables. It turns out that expectation values of EM observables drastically depend on the present state of PGWs, hence on the spectral amplitude $h(K, \eta)$. Thus, we need to find the present spectral amplitude of the inflationary-generated PGWs, so that physical observables of the EM probe can be characterized based on that. Generally, the spectral amplitude of PGWs depends on several physical processes. Firstly, it depends on the specific inflationary model, during which the PGWs are generated. After being generated, the spectrum undergoes further modifications during the subsequent expansion of the Universe, which typically causes redshift suppression of the generated spectrum. On the other hand, as we are going to see in this chapter, characteristic frequencies of the generated PGWs strongly depend on the cosmological model describing the Universe expansion. We shall see in subsequent chapters, that the whole spectrum of PGWs contributes to the behavior of the EM field correlation functions. This leads us to obtain the expression of the PGWs spectrum, from which other physical quantities such as the squeezing amplitude and fractional energy density can be obtained. To do so, we first describe the expanding Universe within the standard Λ CDM model and introduce various model parameters. Next, we obtain approximate solutions for the spectrum $h(K, \eta)$ of the generated PGWs assuming a highly-squeezed regime. The generated spectrum turns out to be sensitively dependent on the inflation and cosmological model parameters, such as the inflationary and reheating indices, the reheating temperature, and the tensor-to-scalar ratio. Subtleties involving parameter fixing based on current observational data are discussed. Eventually, we are equipped with the essential quantities to characterize PGWs, which will be employed in subsequent chapters of the thesis, when discussing the EM-

GWs interaction.

3.1 Expanding Universe

The expansion of a spatially flat Universe ($\Omega_\Lambda + \Omega_m + \Omega_r = 1$) from the inflationary stage up to the current (late) accelerating stage can be described by the FLRW metric Eq. (2.19). Note that, in our notation we mainly use $\Omega_K = c|\mathbf{K}|$ to express the frequency of mode \mathbf{K} of PGWs, not to be confused with the fractional energy densities ($\Omega_r, \Omega_m, \Omega_\Lambda$) corresponding to radiation, matter and dark energy respectively. The specific form of the scale factor $a(\eta)$ determines the dynamics of the Universe as well as tensor perturbation spectral amplitude. It is convenient to consider a power-law behavior $a(\eta) \propto \eta^\alpha$ for the scale factor where the parameter α is a real number, positive or negative, and is different for each successive expansion stage [49, 105]. One may easily show that a power-law scale factor in cosmic time $a(t) \propto t^n$ yields a power-law scale factor in conformal time of the form $a(\eta) \propto \eta^{\frac{n}{1-n}}$. In cosmology, it is more often assumed that the expansion of the Universe at each evolutionary stage is accomplished by a perfect fluid that possesses the equation of state (EoS) $p = w\rho$ with p and ρ being its pressure and energy density, respectively. The dimensionless parameter w determines the properties of the perfect fluid in each stage and is called the EoS parameter. For spatially flat FLRW with $w \neq -1$, the solution of the Friedmann equation for the scale factor is determined by $a(t) \propto t^{\frac{2}{3(1+w)}}$, equivalent to $a(\eta) \propto \eta^{\frac{2}{1+3w}}$ (note that $w \neq -1/3$ in the last equation). In case of $w = -1$, which may correspond to Λ -dominated (Λ D) or de Sitter (DS) expansion stages, one has $a(t) \propto e^{Ht}$ and $a(\eta) \propto -\frac{1}{H\eta}$. In the following discussion, we consider the power-law expansion for each successive stage and assign to each stage an index α , and try to determine the spectrum of generated PGWs.

3.1.1 Successive epochs of expanding Universe

The history of the overall expansion of the Universe can be modeled as a sequence of successive epochs of power-law expansion. When considering the power-law model $a(\eta) \propto \eta^\alpha$, some confusion concerning the dimensionality of $a(\eta)$ may arise since $\dim[\eta] = L$. So if α is a fractional number for a specific expansionary stage, $a(\eta)$ finds odd dimensionality. To avoid this problem, we may proceed by assuming a system of units in which η and x are assumed as dimensionless parameters, while $a(\eta)$ has a length dimension. This freedom comes from the fact that (\mathbf{x}, η) are just coordinates not physical quantities. The physical quantity is, for instance, the physical length $\mathbf{x}^{\text{ph}} = a(\eta)\mathbf{x}$. Now, the physical length must have the length dimensionality, while generally, one is free to attribute length to the coordinates \mathbf{x} or the scale factor $a(\eta)$. Hence, throughout this chapter, we adopt the notation which is primarily used in the literature, by taking the following dimensionality for the quantities [49, 59, 107]: $\dim[a(\eta)] = L$, $\dim[\eta] = \dim[x] = 1$ and $\dim[t] = \dim[\int d\eta a(\eta)/c] = T$. For instance, in this units, the present scale factor is spec-

ified by $a(\eta_H) = \ell_H$ with ℓ_H being the present Hubble radius. We consider the sequential expansionary stages as follows:

- The initial (inflationary) stage:

$$a(\eta) = \ell_0 |\eta|^{1+\beta}, \quad -\infty \leq \eta \leq \eta_1, \quad (3.1)$$

where the inflation index β is a model parameter satisfying $1 + \beta < 0$ and $\eta < 0$ during inflation (to ensure the accelerated expansion $\ddot{a} > 0$). The special case of $\beta = -2$ corresponds to the exact DS expansion $a(t) \propto e^{Ht}$. Observations imply that the value of β is slightly different from -2 [108].

- The preheating stage (or reheating stage or z -stage):

$$a(\eta) = a_z |\eta - \eta_p|^{1+\beta_s}, \quad \eta_1 \leq \eta \leq \eta_s, \quad (3.2)$$

Where the parameter β_s describes the expansion behavior of the preheating stage from the end of inflation to the beginning of the radiation-dominated (RD) stage. As we shall see, β_s affects the PGWs spectrum only at very high frequencies. In the literature, β_s is occasionally set to be 1 [48] or -0.3 [109]. We mainly take β_s as a free parameter and usually set it to 1 when calculating physical observables.

- The radiation-dominated (RD) stage:

$$a(\eta) = a_e (\eta - \eta_e), \quad \eta_s \leq \eta \leq \eta_2. \quad (3.3)$$

- The matter-dominated (MD) stage

$$a(\eta) = a_m (\eta - \eta_m)^2, \quad \eta_2 \leq \eta \leq \eta_E, \quad (3.4)$$

where η_E is the time when the dark energy density ρ_Λ equals to the matter energy density ρ_m . The value of the redshift at the time η_E , z_E is determined by $(1 + z_E) = a(\eta_H)/a(\eta_E)$, where η_H denotes the present time. Since ρ_Λ is constant and $\rho_m \propto a^{-3}$, one has

$$1 = \frac{\rho_\Lambda}{\rho_m(\eta_E)} = \frac{\rho_\Lambda}{\rho_m(\eta_H)(1 + z_E)^3}, \quad (3.5)$$

which gives rise to

$$1 + z_E = \left(\frac{\Omega_\Lambda}{\Omega_m} \right)^{1/3} \sim 1.33, \quad (3.6)$$

given the current values $\Omega_\Lambda \sim 0.7$ and $\Omega_m \sim 0.3$ [108].

- The accelerating stage up to the present (Λ):

$$a(\eta) = \ell_H |\eta - \eta_a|^{-\gamma}, \quad \eta_E \leq \eta \leq \eta_H, \quad (3.7)$$

where the index γ is a Ω_Λ -dependent parameter. For a pure DS phase (a Universe dominated by dark energy as a cosmological constant), one would have $\gamma = 1$. However, since the matter component today is not yet completely negligible, the scale factor $a(t)$ does not evolve as a pure exponential DS phase. Nevertheless, the evolution of $a(\eta)$ can be approximated by a power-law with a value of γ that only slightly differs from 1 [105, 110, 111]. By numerically solving the Friedmann equation, one finds $\gamma \simeq 1.06$ for $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.65$, $\gamma \simeq 1.05$ for $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$ and $\gamma \simeq 1.044$ for $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.75$ [109]. Throughout the present study, we write explicit γ -dependence of the quantities, however, we finally fix $\gamma = 1$ taking $\Omega_\Lambda \sim 0.7$ and $\Omega_m \sim 0.3$.

3.1.2 Model parameters

In the above specification of $a(\eta)$, there are a total number of 17 parameters, including five instants of time $\eta_1, \eta_s, \eta_2, \eta_E$ and η_H , which separate different stages. It is convenient to express four of these time instants in terms of (dimensionless) *increase parameters* that quantify how much $a(\eta)$ increases in each stage. We take the following specification for the increased parameters

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_1 &= \frac{a(\eta_s)}{a(\eta_1)}, & \text{for the preheating stage} \\ \zeta_s &= \frac{a(\eta_2)}{a(\eta_s)}, & \text{for the radiation stage} \\ \zeta_2 &= \frac{a(\eta_E)}{a(\eta_2)} = \frac{a(\eta_H) a(\eta_E)}{a(\eta_2) a(\eta_H)} = (1 + z_2) \zeta_E^{-1}, & \text{for the matter stage} \\ \zeta_E &= \frac{a(\eta_H)}{a(\eta_E)} = \left(\frac{\Omega_\Lambda}{\Omega_m} \right)^{1/3}, & \text{for the late accelerating stage.} \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

Here, z_2 stands for the redshift at radiation-matter transition, which is assumed to be equal to the redshift at the radiation-matter equality [110], i.e., $z_2 = z_{\text{eq}} = 3387$ [112]. Hence, by imposing observational considerations, one has $\zeta_E = 1.33$ and $\zeta_2 \sim 2547$. On the other hand, the increase parameters during the reheating and RD stages, namely ζ_1 and ζ_s , generally depend on the reheating temperature T_{reh} at which the radiation stage begins. For the radiation stage, one has [113]

$$\zeta_s(T_{\text{reh}}) = \frac{T_{\text{reh}}}{T_{\text{CMB}}(1 + z_{\text{eq}})} \left(\frac{g_{*s}}{g_{*\text{s}}} \right)^{1/3}, \quad (3.9)$$

where $T_{\text{CMB}} = 2.348 \times 10^{-13}$ GeV [114] (note that, in cosmology it is convenient to express the energy scales in terms of the temperature. In this way, $k_B T$ is used as the unit of temperature. Thus, the CMB temperature in Kelvin is obtained by $T_K = T_{\text{CMB}}/k_B =$

$2.348 \times 10^{-13} \text{ GeV}/(8.617 \times 10^{14})$ ($\text{GeV/K} \sim 2.88 \text{ K}$). In Eq. (3.9), g_{*s} and $g_{\star s}$ count the effective number of relativistic species contributing to the entropy during the reheating and recombination, respectively, and will be taken $g_{*s} \simeq 200$ and $g_{\star s} = 3.91$ [115], as was also employed in [113]. Lower and upper bounds on T_{reh} come from the Big Bang Nucleosynthesis (BBN) $T_{\text{reh}} \geq 10 \text{ MeV}$ ($\sim 10^{10} \text{ K}$) and the energy scale at the end of inflation $T_{\text{reh}} \leq 10^{16} \text{ GeV}$ ($\sim 10^{30} \text{ K}$), respectively. However, CMB data modify the lower bound on the reheating temperature $T_{\text{reh}} \geq 6 \times 10^3 \text{ GeV}$ [116], and gravitinos generation has given the upper bound $T_{\text{reh}} \leq 10^8 \text{ GeV}$ [107]. As we are going to see in this chapter, T_{reh} , as well as β_s , determine the behavior of the Universe expansion during the reheating stage and affect only the high-frequency part of the PGWs spectrum, and this part of the PGWs spectrum does not play significant role in the behavior of EM field observables (see Chapter 6 and Chapter 7). However, the value of T_{reh} could affect the range of other parameters, including β, β_s and ζ_1 , when considering specific inflationary scenarios (see [107] for example). For practical illustration, we mainly adopt $T_{\text{reh}} = 10^8 \text{ GeV}$ throughout our calculations as it is most favored in the literature [112].

So far, four-time instants η_1, η_s, η_2 and η_E are expressed in terms of four independent increase parameters, that are reduced to two parameters T_{reh} and ζ_1 by imposing observational values of $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$ and $z_2 = z_{\text{eq}} = 3387$. The remaining time instant η_H is fixed by an overall normalization, assuming $a(\eta_H) = \ell_H$, which leads to

$$|\eta_H - \eta_a| = 1. \quad (3.10)$$

So the value of η_H is fixed once the value of η_a is determined. Moreover, the constant ℓ_H is fixed by the following calculation

$$\frac{1}{H_0} \equiv \frac{a}{c\mathcal{H}} \Big|_{\eta=\eta_H} = \frac{\ell_H |\eta - \eta_a|^{-\gamma+1}}{c\gamma} \Big|_{\eta=\eta_H} = \frac{\ell_H}{c\gamma} \quad (3.11)$$

where H_0 is the present Hubble constant. There remain 12 constants in the expressions of $a(\eta)$, among them β, β_s , and γ are considered as the model parameters, describing inflation, reheating, and late accelerated expansion eras. Considering $\gamma = 1$ gives $\ell_H = c/H_0$ which is the Hubble radius at present, and the constant ℓ_H is fixed by imposing the observational value of $H_0 = 67.4 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ from Planck 2018 [117]. Thus, subtracting 5 condition results in 12 parameters. We shall treat $\beta, \beta_s, T_{\text{reh}}$ and ζ_1 as free parameters of the model. The remaining 8 parameters can be fixed by the conditions of continuity of $a(\eta)$ and $a'(\eta)$ at four jointing points η_1, η_s, η_2 and η_E . Consequently, all parameters are written in terms of the increase parameters $\zeta_1, \zeta_s, \zeta_2$ and ζ_E and the parameters β, β_s and γ (note that, γ is fixed as soon as the value of Ω_Λ is fixed, however we proceed by writing γ explicitly in

subsequent equations) [109],

$$\begin{aligned}
\eta_a - \eta_E &= \zeta_E^{1/\gamma}, \\
\eta_E - \eta_m &= \frac{2}{\gamma} \zeta_E^{1/\gamma}, \\
\eta_2 - \eta_m &= \frac{2}{\gamma} \zeta_2^{-1/2} \zeta_E^{1/\gamma}, \\
\eta_2 - \eta_e &= \frac{1}{\gamma} \zeta_2^{-1/2} \zeta_E^{1/\gamma}, \\
\eta_s - \eta_e &= \frac{1}{\gamma} \zeta_s^{-1} \zeta_2^{-1/2} \zeta_E^{1/\gamma}, \\
\eta_s - \eta_p &= \frac{1}{\gamma} (1 + \beta_s) \zeta_s^{-1} \zeta_2^{-1/2} \zeta_E^{1/\gamma}, \\
\eta_1 - \eta_p &= \frac{1}{\gamma} (1 + \beta_s) \zeta_1^{-1/(1+\beta_s)} \zeta_s^{-1} \zeta_2^{-1/2} \zeta_E^{1/\gamma}, \\
\eta_1 &= \frac{1}{\gamma} (1 + \beta) \zeta_1^{-1/(1+\beta)} \zeta_s^{-1} \zeta_2^{-1/2} \zeta_E^{1/\gamma},
\end{aligned} \tag{3.12}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
a_m &= \frac{\ell_H}{4} \gamma^2 \zeta_E^{-(1+2/\gamma)}, \\
a_e &= \ell_H \gamma \zeta_2^{-1/2} \zeta_E^{-(1+1/\gamma)}, \\
a_z &= \ell_H \gamma^{1+\beta_s} |1 + \beta_s|^{-(1+\beta_s)} \zeta_s^{\beta_s} \zeta_2^{(\beta_s-1)/2} \zeta_E^{-(1+(1+\beta_s)/\gamma)}, \\
\ell_0 &= \ell_H \gamma^{1+\beta} |1 + \beta|^{-(1+\beta)} \zeta_1^{(\beta-\beta_s)/(1+\beta_s)} \zeta_s^\beta \zeta_2^{(\beta-1)/2} \zeta_E^{-[1+(1+\beta)/\gamma]}.
\end{aligned} \tag{3.13}$$

These relations help us to find the characteristic wave numbers in Sec. (3.2.2) and are useful in the definition of the quantum normalization condition in Sec. (3.3.1).

3.2 Spectral amplitude of PGWs

In this section, we derive an approximate expression for the spectral amplitude $h(K, \eta)$, given the expansionary model described in Sec. 3.1.1. The dimensionless spectral amplitude $h(K, \eta)$ is defined by Eq. (2.76), i.e.,

$$h(K, \eta) = \frac{4\ell_{Pl}}{\sqrt{\pi}a(\eta)} K \left(|u_K(\eta)|^2 + |v_K(\eta)|^2 + u_K(\eta)v_K(\eta) + u_K^*(\eta)v_K^*(\eta) \right)^{1/2}. \tag{3.14}$$

where the functions $u_K(\eta)$ and $v_K(\eta)$ are defined in Eq. (2.58) with the initial conditions $u_K(\eta_{ini}) = 1$ and $v_K(\eta_{ini}) = 0$. Here, η_{ini} denotes a time before the outset of super-adiabatic amplification during inflation epoch and is indeed K -dependent. Using the expression Eq. (3.14), one may find the evolution of the spectral amplitude $h(K, \eta)$ readily as soon as the evolution of the functions $u_K(\eta)$ and $v_K(\eta)$ are determined.

The other application of Eq. (3.14) is to build the relationship between the squeezing parameters (r_K, ϕ_K) and the spectral amplitude. Especially, by substitution of Eq. (2.58) for

the functions u_K and v_K into Eq. (3.14) and assuming $r_K \gg 1$ for super-Hubble modes ($K \leq 2\pi\mathcal{H}$), one obtains the following relationship

$$h(K, \eta) = 8 \sqrt{\pi} \left(\frac{\ell_{Pl}}{\ell_H} \right) \left(\frac{K}{K_H} \right) e^{r_K(\eta)} \cos \phi_K(\eta). \quad (3.15)$$

Eq. (3.15) is in accordance with Eq. (31) of [49]. Note that, according to Eq. (2.68), the variable ϕ_K is not an independent variable, and its dynamics are determined once the dynamics of r_K are specified. Hence, the evolution of $h(K, \eta)$ can be solely given by the evolution of the squeezing amplitude r_K . Even more, for super-Hubble scales, the squeezing amplitude r_K is very large, so that $\coth(2r_K) \rightarrow 1$. Hence, Eq. (2.68) for ϕ_K yields the following solution

$$\phi'_K(\eta) = -\frac{a'}{a} \sin(2\phi_K) \Rightarrow \tan(\phi_K) \propto \frac{1}{a^2(\eta)}, \quad (3.16)$$

which implies $\tan(\phi_K) \rightarrow 0$ during the long-wavelength regime. The squeezing angle ϕ_K tends to either values 0 or π , both resulting in $\cos(2\phi_K) \rightarrow 1$. In this case, the oscillatory factor $\cos \phi_K$ tends to 1, yielding

$$e^{r_K(\eta)} = \frac{1}{8 \sqrt{\pi}} \left(\frac{\ell_H}{\ell_{Pl}} \right) \left(\frac{K_H}{K} \right) h(K, \eta) \quad , \quad \text{super-Hubble scales.} \quad (3.17)$$

Although we shall derive an explicit expression for the squeezing amplitude r_K in Sec. 3.3, Eq. (3.17) offers an equivalent way to obtain it from $h(K, \eta)$.

On the other hand, one may show that $h(K, \eta)$ is related to the Fourier field amplitude $h_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)$ (defined in Eq. (2.38)) by the following relation

$$h(K, \eta) = \frac{4\ell_{Pl}K}{\sqrt{\pi}} \sqrt{\frac{2K}{\hbar}} |h_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)|. \quad (3.18)$$

Note that, definition of $h_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)$ is occasionally different from Eq. (2.38) in a $\sqrt{2K}$ factor. In some references, the prefactor $1/\sqrt{2K}$ is included in the field expansion, while in others this prefactor is implicitly included in the temporal mode functions $h_{\mathbf{K}}^\gamma(\eta)$. Here, we adopted the second notation. As a result, Eq. (3.18) for $h(K, \eta)$ may differ by a factor $\sqrt{2K}$ with some references in the literature. Consequently, our convention for $h(K, \eta)$ given by Eq. (3.18) is in accordance with Eq. (24) of [110] by the replacement $h_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta) \rightarrow h_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)/\sqrt{2K}$ in Eq. (3.18). Final expressions for $h(K, \eta)$ and spectral energy density (see Sec. 3.2.4) are of course invariant. Ultimately, the spectral amplitude $h(K, \eta)$ can also be specialized by solving the equation of motion for $h_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)$ given by Eq. (2.43).

3.2.1 Initial spectral amplitude of primordial gravitational waves

The initial spectral amplitude of the inflationary generated PGWs (before the horizon-crossing during the inflation) can be found by setting $u_K(\eta_{ini}) = 1$ and $v_K(\eta_{ini}) = 0$ in

Eq. (3.14) and replacing $\lambda_{\text{ini}} = 2\pi a(\eta_{\text{ini}})/K_{\text{ini}}$. This results in

$$h(K, \eta_{\text{ini}}) = 8 \sqrt{\pi} \frac{\ell_{\text{Pl}}}{\lambda_{\text{ini}}}, \quad (3.19)$$

where λ_{ini} denotes the *physical* wavelength of mode K at time η_{ini} (which is time-dependent in an expanding Universe). Eq. (3.19) expresses the so-called *quantum normalization* of the spectral amplitude of PGWs [49, 107]. From Eq. (3.19) it is obvious that the initial spectral amplitude of mode K is proportional to the ratio $\frac{\ell_{\text{Pl}}}{\lambda_{\text{ini}}}$ which is negligibly small for waves with typical length-scales of Hubble radius during inflation. Moreover, in the absence of amplification, the quantum normalization condition implies that the tensor amplitude is inversely proportional to its wavelength; hence, it shrinks as the Universe expands.

For a given (comoving) wave number K , its wavelength crossed the Hubble horizon at a time η_{ini} , when $\lambda^{\text{com}}(\eta_{\text{ini}}) = \mathcal{H}^{-1}(\eta_{\text{ini}})$, where λ^{com} denotes the comoving wavelength and $\lambda = a\lambda^{\text{com}}$ is the physical wavelength. In physical quantities, this criteria is equivalent to $\lambda(\eta_{\text{ini}}) = cH^{-1}(\eta_{\text{ini}})$. Hence, using the relation $\mathcal{H} = Ha/c$ and $\mathcal{H}(\eta_{\text{ini}}) = a'(\eta_{\text{ini}})/a(\eta_{\text{ini}}) = K/(2\pi)$ one may obtain following relations

$$\begin{aligned} H(\eta_{\text{ini}}) &= \frac{|1 + \beta|c}{\ell_0 |\eta_{\text{ini}}|^{2+\beta}}, \\ |\eta_{\text{ini}}| &= \frac{2\pi|1 + \beta|}{K} = \frac{K_H |1 + \beta|}{K \gamma}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.20)$$

In the last line of the second equality, we used $K_H = 2\pi\gamma$ (see Sec. 3.1.1 about dimensionality of the quantities. In the present chapter, we use the convention $\dim[x] = \dim[\eta] = \dim[K] = 1$). Here, K_H denotes the characteristic (comoving) wave number at the present, i.e.,

$$K_H \equiv K(\eta_H) = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda^{\text{com}}(\eta_H)} = 2\pi\mathcal{H}(\eta_H) = 2\pi \frac{H_0 a(\eta_H)}{c} = 2\pi\gamma, \quad (3.21)$$

where $a(\eta_H) = \ell_H$ and Eq. (3.11) is used. Assuming $\gamma = 1$ gives rise to $K_H = 2\pi$, however, to be as general as possible we keep explicit γ -dependence of the formulas throughout the chapter. Substituting $\lambda(\eta_{\text{ini}}) = cH^{-1}(\eta_{\text{ini}})$ into Eq. (3.19) and using Eq. (3.20), the initial spectral amplitude of PGWs is obtained

$$h(K, \eta_{\text{ini}}) = A \left(\frac{K}{K_H} \right)^{2+\beta}, \quad (3.22)$$

where the constant A is defined by

$$A = 8 \sqrt{\pi} \left(\frac{\ell_{\text{Pl}}}{\ell_0} \right) \gamma^{2+\beta} |1 + \beta|^{-(1+\beta)}. \quad (3.23)$$

Once the initial spectral amplitude at a given moment η_{ini} is specified, the spectrum at

later times can be derived straightforwardly. In particular, the present spectral amplitude $h(K, \eta_H)$ is the main quantity that appears in practical observational situations. In the following, we derive approximate expression of the present spectral amplitude of tensor perturbations. Before doing that, it is essential to define characteristic wave numbers.

3.2.2 Characteristic wave numbers

The physical wave number at present is related to the comoving wave number K according to the relation $K^{\text{ph}} = K/a(\eta_H) = K/\ell_H$ (note that here the physical wave number has the correct dimensionality of L^{-1}), where $\ell_H = c\gamma/H_0$ is the present Hubble radius. For a given mode K , its wavelength exceeded the Hubble horizon when the criteria $K = 2\pi\mathcal{H}$ fulfills for the first time during the inflationary epoch, at a specific time $\eta_*(K)$. Then, the wave may re-enter the Hubble horizon at a later time $\eta_{**}(K)$ (at subsequent epochs), when the same criteria is fulfilled again. It is useful to define the characteristic wave numbers as $K_x \equiv K(\eta_x) = 2\pi\mathcal{H}(\eta_x)$ where η_x denotes the four transition times η_1, η_s, η_2 and η_E . Hence, characteristic wave numbers signify the waves that crossed the Hubble horizon at the jointing times. Figure. 3.1 illustrates the schematic view of this situation: the curve shows the conformal Hubble parameter \mathcal{H} (multiplied by 2π) versus the conformal time η , where different expansion epochs are distinguished by different colors. Moreover, characteristic wave numbers K_x are shown on the vertical axis, together with their corresponding exit times η_x shown on the η -axis. Whenever the mode K is inside the Hubble horizon, it behaves as a normal harmonic oscillator and the spectral amplitude suffers a decay with the expansion of the Universe. In this case, the energy of the oscillator, indicated by K , is larger than the Hubble rate, and the wave behaves normally. On the other hand, when the mode is outside of the Hubble horizon, the harmonic oscillator description is not valid, and the wave undergoes super-adiabatic amplification as a result of particle production. In this case, the energy of the oscillator is smaller than the Hubble rate.

One can show that characteristic wave numbers at different jointing points η_1, η_s, η_2 and η_E are related to the increase parameters according to [107]

$$\frac{K_E}{K_H} = \zeta_E^{-1} \quad , \quad \frac{K_2}{K_E} = \zeta_2^{1/2} \quad , \quad \frac{K_s}{K_2} = \zeta_s \quad , \quad \frac{K_1}{K_s} = \zeta_1^{\frac{1}{1+\beta_s}} . \quad (3.24)$$

Thus, characteristic wave numbers are determined as soon as the increase parameters together with β and β_s are chosen. From the discussion in Sec. 3.1.2, it turns out that there are only four independent parameters, namely $\beta, \beta_s, T_{\text{reh}}, \zeta_1$, that determine the values of all relevant quantities. As we described in Sec. 3.2.1, we proceed by $\zeta_E = 1.33$, $\zeta_2 \sim 2547$, $T_{\text{reh}} = 10^8$ GeV and $\beta_s = 1$. Hence, the following values for *physical* characteristic wave

Figure 3.1: Illustration of the Hubble-crossing of mode K . The curve shows the conformal Hubble parameter versus the conformal time η , during each expansionary stage shown by colored regions. Characteristic wave numbers K_x at jointing times η_x are shown on the vertical axis. Hubble-crossing occurs whenever $K = 2\pi\mathcal{H}$.

numbers turn out:

$$\begin{aligned}
 K_H &= \frac{2\pi\gamma}{\ell_H} \simeq 4.5 \times 10^{-26} \text{ m}^{-1} = 0.0013 \text{ Mpc}^{-1}, \\
 K_E &= \frac{K_H}{\zeta_E} \simeq 3.4 \times 10^{-26} \text{ m}^{-1} = 0.001 \text{ Mpc}^{-1}, \\
 K_2 &= K_E \zeta_2^{1/2} = 1.71 \times 10^{-24} \text{ m}^{-1} = 0.053 \text{ Mpc}^{-1}, \\
 K_s &= K_2 \zeta_s \simeq 8 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^{-1} = 2.45 \times 10^1 6 \text{ Mpc}^{-1}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.25}$$

where $\ell_H \simeq 1.4 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}$. The value of K_1 depends on the increase parameter ζ_1 , which can take a wide range of values from $\zeta_1 \sim 1$ up to $\zeta_1 \sim 10^{16}$ [107]. However, it has been argued that the rate of the primordial nucleosynthesis (PN) exerts a constraint on the maximum possible frequency of PGWs as $\nu_{\text{max}} \lesssim 4 \times 10^{10} \text{ Hz}$ [113]. Note that the frequency ν_K is related to the comoving wave number according to $\nu_K = \frac{cK}{2\pi a(\eta_H)} = \frac{cK}{2\pi \ell_H} = \left(\frac{K}{K_H}\right)H_0$, where Eq. (3.11) and Eq. (3.21) are used. Thus, the PN constraint $\nu_1 \lesssim 4 \times 10^{10} \text{ Hz}$ is equivalent to $K_1 \lesssim 837.7 \text{ m}^{-1}$, and Eq. (3.24) implies that $K_s \zeta_1^{\frac{1}{1+\beta_s}} \lesssim 837.7 \text{ m}^{-1}$. In this way, the PN constraint limits the possible range of the parameters ζ_1 and T_{reh} , and for a given value of T_{reh} , the range of ζ_1 is limited by this constraint.

On the other hand, the introduction of primordial perturbations adds new parameters to the four aforementioned parameters, namely the scalar and tensor power spectrum, $A_{s,T}$,

and the scalar and tensor spectral indices, $n_{s,T}$. These parameters are usually constrained by means of observations at some pivot scale k_0 . Among these, we only treat A_T (or equivalently the tensor-to-scalar ratio r_{k_0} to be defined in Sec. (3.3.1)) as free parameter and use the current constraints on A_s and n_s made by *Planck2018* observations to fix A_s and n_s . As we shall discuss in Sec. 3.3.1, the quantum normalization condition Eq. (3.22) combined with observational constraint on A_s at the pivot scale $k_0 = 0.002 \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, exerts a constraint between different parameters (see Eq. (3.64)). This will, in turn, lead to a theoretical expression for the parameter ζ_1 in terms of the four parameters $(\beta, \beta_s, \zeta_s, r_{k_0})$. Throughout the dissertation, we adopt this constraint to determine the value of ζ_1 as well as K_1 .

3.2.3 Approximate expression for spectral amplitude in the long wavelength regime

Time evolution of the spectral amplitude $h(K, \eta)$ may be determined from the Fourier field amplitude $h_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)$ from Eq. (3.18), where $h_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)$ satisfies Eq. (2.43). It can be shown that, the analytic solution of Eq. (2.43) assuming a general scale factor of power-law form $a(\eta) \propto \eta^\alpha$ is a linear combination of Bessel and Neumann functions [113]

$$h_K(\eta) = \eta^{\frac{1}{2}-\alpha} \left[C_1 J_{\alpha-\frac{1}{2}}(K\eta) + C_2 N_{\alpha-\frac{1}{2}}(K\eta) \right], \quad (3.26)$$

where the constants C_1 and C_2 for each stage are determined by the continuity of $h_K(\eta)$ and $h'_K(\eta)$ at the jointing points η_1, η_s, η_2 and η_E . In the current setup, we are considering cosmological model which consists of different phases with constant EoS parameters. Since the tensor wave equation is sourced by a''/a term, and since the EoS parameter is discontinuous at transition points, a''/a contains Dirac terms (centered at transition times). These may leave finite contributions when integrated around the transition times. As a result, the continuity of $h_K(\eta)$ and $h'_K(\eta)$ may be spoiled. The reason why this is not so is that, when applying Israel matching conditions (continuity of the extrinsic curvature) to such a setup, one finds that $h_K(\eta)$ and $h'_K(\eta)$ remain continuous [118]. This is also what ensures the continuity of the squeezing parameters.

Moreover, due to the homogeneity and isotropicity of the FLRW Universe, the Fourier field amplitude $h_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)$ is written as $h_K(\eta)$. Therefore, all the coefficients in the solutions of PGWs can be completely found, once the initial condition is given. This procedure is done for example in [105, 109] where analytical expression for $h_K(\eta)$ or the auxiliary variable $\chi_K(\eta)$ (defined by Eq. (2.44)) is found. However, approximate evaluation of the spectral amplitude can be obtained by considering the following limiting cases:

- sub-Hubble scales $K \gg \frac{a'}{a}$ (equivalent to $K^2 \gg \frac{a''}{a}$) where the mode is in the short-wavelength regime;
- super-Hubble scales $K \ll \frac{a'}{a}$ (equivalent to $K^2 \ll \frac{a''}{a}$) where the mode is in the

long-wavelength regime (see Figure. 3.1).

For sub-Hubble modes $K \gg \frac{a'}{a}$, the solution of Eq. (2.43) is approximately given by

$$h_K(\eta) \rightarrow A_K \frac{e^{iK\eta}}{a(\eta)} + B_K \frac{e^{-iK\eta}}{a(\eta)}, \quad (3.27)$$

which is analogous to the Minkowski solutions, albeit having a decreasing amplitude $h_K(\eta) \propto 1/a(\eta)$ due to the Universe expansion. On the other hand, for super-Hubble modes $K \ll \frac{a'}{a}$ the solution of Eq. (2.43) is approximately given by

$$h_K(\eta) \rightarrow C_K + D_K \int^{\eta} \frac{d\eta'}{a^2(\eta')}. \quad (3.28)$$

The second term is decaying and is small for the power-law model described in Sec. 3.1.1. Hence during the long-wavelength regime, the field amplitude $h_K(\eta)$ remains approximately constant while the auxiliary field $\chi_K(\eta)$ is getting amplified. When the wave re-enters the Hubble horizon, it decreases as $1/a(\eta)$. Note that, the approximate solutions Eq. (3.27) and Eq. (3.28) could also be obtained from Eq. (3.26) in two asymptotic cases (see [105]). Indeed, it can be shown that the analytic solution Eq. (3.26) in the sub-Hubble limit ($K\eta \gg 1$) reduces to the adiabatic vacuum (positive frequency mode) $e^{-iK\eta}$ [105], while in the super-Hubble limit $K\eta \ll 1$, it reduce to the approximate solution Eq. (3.28) [105].

In the following, we shall use the fact that during the long-wavelength regime the field amplitude $h_K(\eta)$ is constant, likewise the spectral amplitude $h(K, \eta)$. This helps us to find the present spectrum of PGWs in a straightforward manner. During the short-wavelength regime however, the field amplitude $h_K(\eta)$ and the spectral amplitude $h(K, \eta)$ undergo decreasing as $\propto 1/a(\eta)$ according to Eq. (3.27). To better follow subsequent calculations, the schematic illustration Figure. 3.1 can be helpful.

3.2.3.1 $K \leq K_E$

For $K \leq K_E$, the corresponding wavelength $\lambda_K = \frac{2\pi a(\eta_H)}{K}$ in this range is even greater than the present Hubble radius, which is determined by $\lambda_H = \frac{2\pi a(\eta_H)}{K_H} = \frac{\ell_H}{\gamma}$ (note that $a(\eta_H) = \ell_H$ and $K_H = 2\pi\gamma$). These modes have been in the super-Hubble regime $K < 2\pi\mathcal{H}$ throughout the whole expansion up to the present, so the amplitude remains the same constant as the initial one in Eq. (3.22),

$$h(K, \eta_H) = A \left(\frac{K}{K_H} \right)^{2+\beta}, \quad K \leq K_E. \quad (3.29)$$

3.2.3.2 $K_E \leq K \leq K_H$

The spectral amplitude $h(K, \eta)$ remains approximately constant during the long-wavelength period until the mode enters the Hubble horizon and begins to decrease as $1/a(\eta)$. For a

given mode K , let $a_{**}(K) \equiv a(\eta_{**}(K))$ be the scale factor at the moment the mode enters the Hubble horizon (see Figure. 3.1). For those very long wavelength modes with $K_E \leq K \leq K_H$, the modes left the horizon at some instant of time $\eta_*^{(1)}(K)$ for the first time during the inflationary epoch, then they had entered the Hubble horizon at some later time $\eta_{**}(K)$ during MD era, and have left the horizon again in a later time $\eta_*^{(2)}(K)$ during the current epoch of accelerating expansion, $\eta_E \leq \eta_*^{(2)}(K) \leq \eta_H$. The amount of decrease in $h(K, \eta)$ is determined by the prefactor $\frac{a_{**}(K)}{a(\eta_*^{(2)}(K))}$. Hence, one has

$$h(K, \eta_H) = A \left(\frac{K}{K_H} \right)^{2+\beta} \frac{a_{**}(K)}{a(\eta_*^{(2)}(K))}, \quad K_E \leq K \leq K_H, \quad (3.30)$$

where $\eta_{**}(K)$ happens during the MD era and $\eta_*^{(2)}(K)$ during the Λ D era. To calculate the decreasing factor, first note that, generally, for a power-law scale factor $a(\eta) \propto \eta^\alpha$ one has $\mathcal{H} = a'/a \propto \eta^{-1}$, hence the horizon-crossing condition $K = 2\pi\mathcal{H}$ gives rise to $K \propto \eta^{-1} \propto [a(\eta)]^{-1/\alpha}$ or equivalently $a(\eta(K)) \propto K^{-\alpha}$ at each transition time η . Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{a_{**}(K)}{a(\eta_*^{(2)}(K))} &= \frac{a_{**}(K)}{a(\eta_E)} \frac{a(\eta_E)}{a(\eta_*^{(1)}(K))} \\ &= \left(\frac{K}{K_E} \right)^{-2} \left(\frac{K_E}{K} \right)^\gamma = \left(\frac{K_E}{K} \right)^{2+\gamma} = \left(\frac{K_E}{K_H} \frac{K_H}{K} \right)^{2+\gamma} = \zeta_E^{-(2+\gamma)/\gamma} \left(\frac{K_H}{K} \right)^{2+\gamma}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.31)$$

with $\alpha = 2$ for MD era and $\alpha = -\gamma$ for Λ D. Consequently, Eqs. (3.30) and (3.31) give rise to

$$h(K, \eta_H) = A \left(\frac{K}{K_H} \right)^{\beta-\gamma} \zeta_E^{-\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}}, \quad K_E \leq K \leq K_H. \quad (3.32)$$

3.2.3.3 $K_H \leq K \leq K_2$

For modes that entered the horizon during the time interval $\eta_2 \leq \eta_{**}(K) \leq \eta_H$ during the MD era, the corresponding spectral amplitude has decreased all the way up today, according to

$$h(K, \eta_H) = A \left(\frac{K}{K_H} \right)^{2+\beta} \frac{a_{**}(K)}{a(\eta_H)}, \quad K_H \leq K \leq K_2, \quad (3.33)$$

where

$$\frac{a_{**}(K)}{a(\eta_H)} = \frac{a_{**}(K)}{a(\eta_E)} \frac{a(\eta_E)}{a(\eta_H)} = \left(\frac{K}{K_E} \right)^{-2} \zeta_E^{-1}, \quad (3.34)$$

and the spectral amplitude is given by

$$h(K, \eta_H) = A \left(\frac{K}{K_H} \right)^\beta \zeta_E^{-\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}}, \quad K_H \leq K \leq K_2. \quad (3.35)$$

3.2.3.4 $K_2 \leq K \leq K_s$

For modes with wave numbers $K_2 \leq K \leq K_s$, the modes enter the horizon during the RD era and the calculation of the decrease in the spectral amplitude is similar to previous cases, which is determined by

$$\frac{a_{**}(K)}{a(\eta_H)} = \frac{a_{**}(K) a(\eta_2)}{a(\eta_2) a(\eta_H)} = \left(\frac{K}{K_2}\right)^{-1} \left(\frac{K_2}{K_E}\right)^{-2} \zeta_E^{-1}, \quad (3.36)$$

and the value of $a(\eta_2)/a(\eta_H)$ is inserted from Eq. (3.34) with the substitution $K = K_2$. Re-writing everything in terms of K_H and K_2 , one obtains

$$h(K, \eta_H) = A \left(\frac{K}{K_H}\right)^{1+\beta} \left(\frac{K_H}{K_2}\right) \zeta_E^{-\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}}, \quad K_2 \leq K \leq K_s. \quad (3.37)$$

3.2.3.5 $K_s \leq K \leq K_1$

Modes with wave numbers $K_s \leq K \leq K_1$ entered the horizon during the reheating era with power-law index $\alpha = 1 + \beta_s$. The decrease in the spectral amplitude is determined by the factor

$$\frac{a_{**}(K)}{a(\eta_H)} = \frac{a_{**}(K) a(\eta_s)}{a(\eta_s) a(\eta_H)} = \left(\frac{K}{K_s}\right)^{-(1+\beta_s)} \left(\frac{K_2}{K_s}\right) \left(\frac{K_2}{K_E}\right)^{-2} \zeta_E^{-1}, \quad (3.38)$$

where the value of $a(\eta_s)/a(\eta_H)$ is inserted from Eq. (3.36) with the substitution of $K = K_s$. The amplitude of the power spectrum is then given by

$$h(K, \eta_H) = A \left(\frac{K}{K_H}\right)^{1+\beta-\beta_s} \left(\frac{K_s}{K_H}\right)^{\beta_s} \left(\frac{K_H}{K_2}\right) \zeta_E^{-\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}}, \quad K_s \leq K \leq K_1. \quad (3.39)$$

To summarize, the following expression gives the present amplitude of the power spectrum of inflationary-generated PGWs in all frequency bands

$$h(K, \eta_H) = \begin{cases} A \left(\frac{K}{K_H}\right)^{2+\beta}, & K \leq K_E \\ A \left(\frac{K}{K_H}\right)^{\beta-\gamma} \zeta_E^{-\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}}, & K_E \leq K \leq K_H \\ A \left(\frac{K}{K_H}\right)^{\beta} \zeta_E^{-\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}}, & K_H \leq K \leq K_2 \\ A \left(\frac{K}{K_H}\right)^{1+\beta} \left(\frac{K_H}{K_2}\right) \zeta_E^{-\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}}, & K_2 \leq K \leq K_s \\ A \left(\frac{K}{K_H}\right)^{1+\beta-\beta_s} \left(\frac{K_s}{K_H}\right)^{\beta_s} \left(\frac{K_H}{K_2}\right) \zeta_E^{-\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}}, & K_s \leq K \leq K_1. \end{cases} \quad (3.40)$$

The coefficient A which is defined by Eq. (3.23) is nothing but the initial value of the spectral amplitude at Hubble scale $K = K_H$, i.e., $h(K_H, \eta_{\text{ini}})$. The value of A is usually adjusted by observations and is expressed in terms of the tensor-to-scalar ratio r_{k_0} . We will discuss this convention in Sec. 3.3.1. The plot of $h(K, \eta_H)$ is shown in Figure. 3.2, for different set of parameters $(\beta, \beta_s, T_{\text{reh}}/\text{GeV}, r_{k_0})$. The solid line corresponds to $(-2, 1, 10^8, 10^{-2})$.

Figure 3.2: The plot of $h(K, \eta_H)$ versus the physical wave number in m^{-1} , for different values of the parameters $(\beta, \beta_s, T_{\text{reh}}/\text{GeV}, r_{k_0})$. Generally, decreasing β and r_{k_0} leads to decreasing $h(K, \eta_H)$ in the whole range of spectrum, while changing the reheating parameters β_s and T_{reh} only changes the high-frequency part of the spectrum, including $K_s \leq K \leq K_1$.

Increasing β from the value -2 (which corresponds to DS expansion) to -1.8 increases the spectrum in almost the whole frequency range, as shown by the dashed-purple line. Moreover, reducing the tensor-to-scalar ratio from 10^{-2} shifts the whole spectrum down, as shown by the dashed-blue line. On the other hand, changing the reheating parameters such as β_s and T_{reh} only affects the high-frequency part of the spectrum, which possess the tiniest strain amplitude, as shown by the dashed-green and red lines, respectively.

Having obtained $h(K, \eta_H)$, in the following, we find the expression of spectral energy density of inflationary-generated PGWs, which is particularly important when considering sensitivity curves of GW detectors.

3.2.4 Spectral energy density of PGWs

Once the spectral amplitude is specified, it is straightforward to find the present *energy fraction* of PGWs defined by the ratio $\Omega_{\text{pgw}} = \langle \rho_{\text{pgw}} \rangle / \rho_c$, where $\rho_c = 3c^2 H_0^2 / (8\pi G)$ is the critical energy density today. In order to find the energy-momentum tensor of GWs in FLRW spacetime, let us first clarify some fundamental assumptions.

In a general curved background, GWs are perceived as very small fluctuations around the background metric, and in order to study the effect of these perturbations on the curvature of the background, one should define a criterion to separate the “background” from the “perturbations”. This procedure is usually called *short-wave expansion*, in which one assumes that there is a length-scale L_B associated to the background such that the typical length-scale (or time period) of perturbations is smaller than that, i.e., $\lambda_K \ll L_B$. This is only under this circumstance that one may find a wave-equation for GWs (in a suitable gauge). Unless, one may not distinguish the fluctuations from the background, and the

total dynamics of gravitation is determined by the Einstein equations. As a result of this scale-separation, one is able to assign the energy-momentum tensor $t^{\mu\nu} = \frac{c^4}{32\pi G} \langle \partial^\mu h^{\alpha\beta} \partial^\nu h_{\alpha\beta} \rangle$ to GWs (see Chapter 1 of [119]). Also note that, this expression for $t^{\mu\nu}$ is obtained in the TT gauge, where the wave-equation $\square \bar{h}_{\alpha\beta} = 0$ is satisfied. Note that, the quantity $\partial^\mu h^{\alpha\beta} \partial^\nu h_{\alpha\beta}$ which appears inside $t^{\mu\nu}$ is not gauge-invariant; indeed, the equivalence principle tells us that, at a given point we can always find a locally inertial frame, such that at the point in question, gravitational field vanishes. Therefore, any candidate for *local* energy-density can always be set to zero at a given point with a coordinate transformation. However, when we consider waves, all that can be measured is the energy averaged over several wavelengths or periods. Eventually, it turns out that the field theoretical approach based on the Noether's theorem gives us an *unambiguous* recipe for computing a spatial (or temporal) average of the energy-momentum tensor of GWs.

When applied to the FLRW background, one comes up with the result that, it is possible to define the energy-momentum tensor of GWs only for the modes well inside the horizon, for which $K\eta \gg 1$. In this case, one can average the energy-momentum tensor over several wavelengths to obtain a gauge invariant quantity (an operation that no longer makes sense if the wavelength is greater than the Hubble scale).

From the above discussion, it follows that energy density of PGWs is determined by the (0, 0) component of the energy-momentum tensor of PGWs, according to [119]

$$t^{00} = \langle \rho_{\text{pgw}} \rangle = \frac{c^2}{32\pi G} \langle h_{ij,0} h_{,0}^{ij} \rangle \rightarrow \kappa t^{00} = \frac{1}{4c^2} \langle h_{ij,0} h_{,0}^{ij} \rangle = \frac{1}{4a^2(\eta)} \langle h'_{ij} h'^{ij} \rangle, \quad (3.41)$$

where $\kappa \equiv \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}$ and the relation $d\eta = (c/a)dt$ is used. For those modes that are comfortably shorter than the Hubble radius, one can calculate the spectral energy density of PGWs. Using the expression Eq. (2.38) for $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta)$ one has,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta) &= \frac{\sqrt{2}}{M_{Pl}} \sum_{\gamma=+, \times} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \frac{d^3 \mathbf{K}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} e_{ij}^{\gamma}(\hat{\mathbf{K}}) [h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma}(\eta) \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma}(0) e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}} \\ &+ h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma*}(\eta) \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma\dagger}(0) e^{-i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}}]. \end{aligned} \quad (3.42)$$

For sub-Hubble modes the mode functions $h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma}(\eta)$ are simply determined by $e^{\pm iK\eta}$, hence $h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma'} = \pm iK h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma}$. Thus, by inserting the time derivative of Eq. (3.42) into Eq. (3.41) and taking the expectation value with respect to the vacuum state $|\{0\}\rangle$, one obtains

$$\kappa t^{00} = \frac{1}{4a^2(\eta)} \int K^2 h^2(K, \eta) \frac{dK}{K}, \quad (3.43)$$

where Eq. (3.18) has been used, and the reduced Planck mass is expressed in physical units (see discussion after Eq. (2.36)). On the other hand, the critical energy density can

be rewritten as $\kappa\rho_c = 3H_0^2/c^2$. Thus, the present energy fraction is given by

$$\Omega_{\text{pgw}} = \frac{c^2}{12a^2(\eta_H)H_0^2} \int K^2 h^2(\eta_H, K) \frac{dK}{K}. \quad (3.44)$$

Now using the definition of K_H given by Eq. (3.21), Eq. (3.44) can be transformed to

$$\Omega_{\text{pgw}} = \frac{\pi^2}{3} \int \left(\frac{K}{K_H} \right)^2 h^2(K, \eta_H) \frac{dK}{K}, \quad (3.45)$$

and the spectral energy density parameter $\Omega_{\text{pgw}}(K)$ turns out

$$\Omega_{\text{pgw}}(K) = \frac{\pi^2}{3} \left(\frac{K}{K_H} \right)^2 h^2(K, \eta_H). \quad (3.46)$$

The spectral energy is especially important when comparison with the sensitivity curve of GW detectors matters (see Sec. 7.8.1 of [119]). Basically, detection of cosmological gravitational wave background can be done at different frequency bands; in the low-frequency band, constraining a possible tensor-mode contribution to the large-scale temperature and polarization fluctuations in the CMB can provide a constraint on the PGWs energy density. For instance, Planck's 2015 results constrain the PGWs energy density to $\Omega_{\text{pgw}} h^2 < 1.7 \times 10^6$ at 95% [120]. At higher frequencies, GW observatories such as pulsar timing arrays [121], LIGO, and VIRGO [122], have posed upper bounds on the spectral energy density in their working frequency bands. Especially, LIGO observations have made the constraint $\Omega_{\text{pgw}}(K) \lesssim 6.9 \times 10^{-6}$ in a frequency band around 100 Hz [123].

As we shall see in Chapters 6, 7, the decoherence and incoherence of the EM field, induced by PGWs, concerns the whole frequency spectrum of PGWs, and we shall obtain constraint on the tensor-to-scalar ratio r_{k_0} , which can be alternatively translated to a constraint on the total energy density of the PGWs, given by Eq. (3.45). On the other hand, the functions $(u_K(\eta_H), v_K(\eta_H))$ which are defined by Eq. (2.58), or equivalently the squeezing parameters $(r_K(\eta_H), \phi_K(\eta_H))$, manifest themselves in the equations of motion of the EM field, so it is crucial to obtain the present value of these quantities. In the next section, we investigate the squeezing parameters in the long-wavelength regime and, in particular, obtain the present value of the squeezing amplitude.

3.3 Squeezing parameters in the long-wavelength regime

In this section, we derive the squeezing amplitude $r_K(\eta)$ and squeezing angle $\phi_K(\eta)$ in the long-wavelength regime $K \ll 2\pi\mathcal{H}$, that is to say when the modes have been amplified sufficiently so that $r_K \gg 1$. In this approximation, we may find rather simple solutions to Eq. (2.68) governing the squeezing parameters. Note that, the following results for e^{r_K} could be equivalently derived from Eq. (3.17), once $h(K, \eta)$ is known from Eq. (3.40). This equivalence holds, provided that the quantum normalization condition is fulfilled.

We discuss this point later in Sec. 3.3.1. As we have discussed in Sec. 3.2, in the long-wavelength regime, the squeezing angle is governed by Eq. (3.16) which yields $\cos 2\phi_K \rightarrow 1$. Thus, Eq. (2.68) for $r_K(\eta)$ can be approximately written as follows

$$r'_K(\eta) = \frac{a'}{a} \cos(2\phi_K) \simeq \frac{a'}{a}, \quad (3.47)$$

that has the simple solution

$$r_K(\eta) = \ln \frac{a(\eta)}{a_*(K)}, \quad (3.48)$$

where $a_*(K) = a(\eta_*(K))$ denotes the value of the scale factor at the initial moment of horizon-crossing, and the initial value is chosen as $r_K(\eta_*(K)) = 0$ consistent with the quantum normalization condition. At a later time $\eta_{**}(K)$ that the mode enters the Hubble horizon the final value of the squeezing amplitude is determined by

$$e^{r_K} = \frac{a_{**}(K)}{a_*(K)}, \quad (3.49)$$

where $a_{**}(K) = a(\eta_{**}(K))$ denotes the value of scale factor when the mode enters the horizon. Eq. (3.48) and Eq. (3.49) imply that the squeezing amplitude increases proportional to the increase of $\ln(a)$, and the vacuum of the mode K occupies a large number of gravitons (note that the mean number of particles in the TS state is proportional to $\bar{n}_{\text{ts}}(K) = \sinh^2 r_K \simeq e^{2r_K}/4$). This is the reason why the process is called *super-adiabatic (or parametric) amplification of vacuum fluctuations* [49]. After the end of amplification, the accumulated (and typically large) squeezing amplitude r_K stays approximately constant (see Eq. (2.70)). The mode is again in the adiabatic regime, and as we have seen previously, the amplitude of the spectral amplitude $h(K, \eta)$ decays as $\propto 1/a(\eta)$.

Note that, according to Eq. (2.68), the equation of motion for the rotation parameter $\theta_K(\eta)$ can be solved once $r_K(\eta)$ and $\phi_K(\eta)$ are specified. Especially, during the super-adiabatic regime ($r_K \gg 1$), both θ_K and ϕ_K obey similar equation of motion and both decay as $1/a^2(\eta)$. On the other hand, when the adiabatic regime begins, one has $\theta_K(\eta) = \phi_K(\eta) = -K(\eta - \eta_{**}(K))$. However, the parameter $\theta_K(\eta)$ would be canceled in all physical observables of the tensor field $\hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta)$ (such as its two-point correlation given by Eq. (2.73)), since the vacuum perturbations are invariant under a rotation.

From Eq. (3.49), it is straightforward to find the present value of the squeezing factor $e^{r_K(\eta_H)}$. High-frequency modes $K \geq K_1$ have always been inside the horizon (short-wavelength regime) and have never been amplified (see Figure. 3.1). Since they were always in the vacuum state with the initial conditions $u_K(\eta_{\text{ini}}) = 1$ and $v_K(\eta_{\text{ini}}) = 0$, from Eq. (2.58) one has $r_K = 0$, hence

$$e^{r_K} = 1 \quad , K \geq K_1 . \quad (3.50)$$

For modes $K_s \leq K \leq K_1$, the mode leaves the horizon at some time $\eta_*(K)$ during the inflationary epoch and re-enter it at a later time $\eta_{**}(K)$ during the reheating epoch $\eta_1 \leq \eta_{**}(K) \leq \eta_s$. Note that, as we have seen before in Sec. 3.2.3.2, at the horizon-crossing $K = 2\pi\mathcal{H}$ one has $a(\eta(K)) \propto K^{-\alpha}$, thus during inflation $a_*(K) \propto K^{-(1+\beta)}$ at horizon crossing. One has

$$\frac{a_{**}(K)}{a_*(K)} = \frac{a_{**}(K)}{a(\eta_1)} \frac{a(\eta_1)}{a_*(K)} = \left(\frac{K}{K_1}\right)^{-(1+\beta_s)} \left(\frac{K}{K_1}\right)^{1+\beta}, \quad (3.51)$$

and the squeezing factor becomes

$$e^{r_K} = \left(\frac{K}{K_1}\right)^{\beta-\beta_s}, \quad K_s \leq K \leq K_1. \quad (3.52)$$

Similar calculations for other frequency ranges apply. In particular, for those scales corresponding to $K_E \leq K \leq K_H$, one should note that these waves left the horizon for the first time at $\eta_*^{(1)}(K)$ during inflation ($\eta_*^{(1)}(K) \leq \eta_1$), then entered the horizon at $\eta_{**}(K)$ during the MD epoch ($\eta_H^{(1)} \leq \eta_{**}(K) \leq \eta_E$). Here, $\eta_H^{(1)}$ shows the time at which the mode with the present Hubble scale, K_H , entered the horizon during the MD epoch (see Figure. 3.1). These modes have again left the horizon at a subsequent time $\eta_*^{(2)}(K)$ during Λ D epoch, $\eta_E \leq \eta_*^{(2)}(K) \leq \eta_H$, and have been further amplified by now (see the dashed-blue line in Fig. 3.1). Using Eq. (3.48), the total squeezing parameter during the long-wavelength regime is given by $r_K = \ln \frac{a_{**}(K)}{a_*^{(1)}(K)} + \ln \frac{a(\eta_H)}{a_*^{(2)}(K)}$, hence

$$e^{r_K} = \left(\frac{a_{**}(K)}{a(\eta_*^{(1)}(K))}\right) \left(\frac{a(\eta_H)}{a(\eta_*^{(2)}(K))}\right), \quad K_E \leq K \leq K_H, \quad (3.53)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{a_{**}(K)}{a(\eta_*^{(1)}(K))} &= \frac{a_{**}(K) a(\eta_H^{(1)}) a(\eta_2) a(\eta_s) a(\eta_1)}{a(\eta_H^{(1)}) a(\eta_2) a(\eta_s) a(\eta_1) a(\eta_*^{(1)}(K))} \\ &= \left(\frac{K}{K_H}\right)^{-2} \left(\frac{K_H}{K_2}\right)^{-2} \left(\frac{K_2}{K_s}\right)^{-1} \left(\frac{K_s}{K_1}\right)^{-(1+\beta_s)} \left(\frac{K_1}{K}\right)^{-(1+\beta)}, \\ \frac{a(\eta_H)}{a(\eta_*^{(2)}(K))} &= \left(\frac{K_H}{K}\right)^\gamma. \end{aligned} \quad (3.54)$$

This yields the following expression

$$e^{r_K} = \left(\frac{K}{K_1}\right)^{1+\beta} \left(\frac{K_1}{K_H}\right) \left(\frac{K_2}{K_H}\right) \left(\frac{K_1}{K_s}\right)^{\beta_s} \left(\frac{K_H}{K}\right)^{2+\gamma}, \quad K_E \leq K \leq K_H. \quad (3.55)$$

Figure 3.3: The plot of $e^{r_K(\eta_H)}$ versus the physical wave number in m^{-1} , for different values of the parameters $(\beta, \beta_s, T_{\text{reh}}/\text{GeV}, r_{k_0})$. Generally, decreasing β and r_{k_0} leads to decreasing $e^{r_K(\eta_H)}$ in the whole range of the spectrum, while changing the reheating parameters β_s and T_{reh} only changes the high-frequency part of the spectrum, including $K_s \leq K \leq K_s$, for which the squeezing amplitude (and the graviton number) is significantly smaller than the ultra-low frequency part.

We may summarize the full expression of the squeezing factor at present, as

$$e^{r_K(\eta_H)} = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{K}{K_1}\right)^{1+\beta} \left(\frac{K_2}{K_E}\right)^2 \left(\frac{K_s}{K_1}\right)^{-\beta_s} \left(\frac{K_1}{K_2}\right) \left(\frac{K_H}{K_E}\right)^\gamma, & K \leq K_E \\ \left(\frac{K}{K_1}\right)^{1+\beta} \left(\frac{K_1}{K_H}\right) \left(\frac{K_2}{K_H}\right) \left(\frac{K_1}{K_s}\right)^{\beta_s} \left(\frac{K_H}{K}\right)^{2+\gamma}, & K_E \leq K \leq K_H \\ \left(\frac{K}{K_2}\right)^{\beta-1} \left(\frac{K_2}{K_1}\right)^\beta \left(\frac{K_s}{K_1}\right)^{-\beta_s}, & K_H \leq K \leq K_2 \\ \left(\frac{K}{K_s}\right)^\beta \left(\frac{K_s}{K_1}\right)^{\beta-\beta_s}, & K_2 \leq K \leq K_s \\ \left(\frac{K}{K_1}\right)^{\beta-\beta_s}, & K_s \leq K \leq K_1 \\ 1, & K \geq K_1. \end{cases} \quad (3.56)$$

The plot of $e^{r_K(\eta_H)}$ is shown in Figure. 3.3 for different set of parameters $(\beta, \beta_s, T_{\text{reh}}, r_{k_0})$. As in case of $h(K, \eta_H)$, changing the inflationary parameters β and r_{k_0} affects the whole frequency part of the spectrum, while the reheating parameters β_s and T_{reh} only determine the high-frequency part of the spectrum $K_s \leq K \leq K_1$, for which the squeezing amplitude and the mean number of gravitons are significantly smaller than the ultra-low frequency part.

It is worth to note that, Eq. (3.56) coincides with Eq. (3.17) where $h(K, \eta_H)$ is given by Eq. (3.40), provided that the quantum normalization condition Eq. (3.19) is fulfilled (see below). In the following, we discuss the normalization of the constant A based on theoretical and observational constraints.

3.3.1 Normalization of A and definition of the tensor-to-scalar ratio

It is useful to explore some consequences of the quantum normalization condition Eq. (3.19), which relates the magnitude of spectral amplitude $h(K, \eta_{\text{ini}})$ of mode K to its physical wavelength during the inflationary epoch. It implies that the larger the wavelength, the smaller the initial amplitude of tensor perturbations. Note that, this quantity is basically the r.m.s of the tensor perturbation in the vacuum state, and is responsible for the zero-point fluctuations of the PGWs. Just before the horizon-crossing of a typical mode K , this amplitude is determined by Eq. (3.22). Thus, the constant A expresses the initial amplitude of tensor perturbations at Hubble scale $K = K_H$ as Eq. (3.22) implies. Combining Eq. (3.23) with Eq. (3.13), one may easily find the following theoretical expression for A in terms of other parameters of the model, i.e., $(\beta, \beta_s, T_{\text{reh}}, \zeta_1)$,

$$A = 8 \sqrt{\pi} \left(\frac{\ell_{\text{Pl}} H_0}{c} \right) \zeta_1^{\frac{\beta_s - \beta}{1 + \beta_s}} \zeta_s^{-\beta} \zeta_2^{\frac{1 - \beta}{2}} \zeta_E^{1 + \frac{1 + \beta}{\gamma}}. \quad (3.57)$$

In order to set up a normalization on the value of A , it is convenient to define the so-called tensor-to-scalar ratio, r_{k_0} , as the ratio of primordial tensor perturbation power spectrum and primordial scalar perturbation power spectrum at the pivot scale k_0 ,

$$r_{k_0} \equiv \frac{\Delta_h^2(k_0, \eta_i)}{\Delta_{\mathcal{R}}^2(k_0, \eta_i)}, \quad (3.58)$$

where η_i denotes the moment when the mode k_0 exits the horizon during inflation, $\Delta_h^2(k_0, \eta_i) \equiv h^2(k_0, \eta_i)$ and $\Delta_{\mathcal{R}}^2(k_0, \eta_i)$ represent the power spectrum of tensor perturbations and curvature perturbations evaluated at the pivot scale k_0 (remind that, throughout the thesis, we use the convention that r_K denotes the squeezing amplitude of mode K of tensor perturbations, while the symbol r_{k_0} stands for the tensor-to-scalar ratio at the pivot scale k_0 . The reason that we chose lower-case k_0 instead of K_0 is simply because of consistency with the literature). The (conformal) pivot scale k_0 in physical units is given by $k_0^{\text{phy}} = k_0/a(\eta_H)$. We adopt the pivot scale $k_0^{\text{phy}} = 0.002 \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ which is probed by, for instance, the Planck observatory [108]. As a result, a non-zero value of r_{k_0} implies the existence of a gravitational wave background, that is going to be probed by measuring the B-mode CMB polarization. In the literature of WMAP and Planck, the primordial power spectrum is often considered to obey a power-law behavior near the pivot scale, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_h^2(k) &= \Delta_h^2(k_0) \left(\frac{k}{k_0} \right)^{n_T}, \\ \Delta_{\mathcal{R}}^2(k) &= \Delta_{\mathcal{R}}^2(k_0) \left(\frac{k}{k_0} \right)^{n_s - 1}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.59)$$

where n_s, n_T are called scalar and tensorial spectral indexes, respectively. Moreover, deviation from the power-law behavior is accounted for by running indices $\alpha_s \equiv dn_s/d \ln k$ and $\alpha_T \equiv dn_T/d \ln k$ respectively, which leave the room for the spectral indices to be

k -dependent. However, α_s and α_T are second-order small quantities [113]. The impact of a non-vanishing running index α_T on the spectrum of PGWs over the whole range of frequency ($10^{-18} \sim 10^{10}$) Hz has been investigated in [113]. Analytical calculations show that although the low-frequency portion of the PGWs spectrum is less affected by $\alpha_T \neq 0$, the high-frequency part is modified substantially. As we argued in Sec. 3.3 and shown in Figure. 3.3, the high-frequency part of the spectrum leaves insignificant effect on the EM field observables, due to negligible graviton content. Indeed, the quantum mechanical EM-GWs coupling strength effectively depends on the mean number of gravitons in the tensor field of mode K . Hence, for the high-frequency part of the PGWs spectrum, the effective coupling strength would be small, and these modes leave a negligible impact on the EM field observables of our interest. Consequently, throughout the dissertation, we set $\alpha_s = \alpha_T = 0$. However, the effect of non-vanishing running indices may be included in our investigations, straightforwardly.

As discussed in Sec. 3.2.1, the initial spectral amplitude of primordial tensor perturbations is determined by $h(K, \eta_{\text{ini}}) = A(K/K_H)^{2+\beta}$ which yields $n_T = 2\beta + 4$ when combined with Eq. (3.59) (note that, as mentioned in [113], the quantum normalization condition yields exactly $\alpha_T = 0$ since n_T is k -independent). Basically, the definition of tensor-to-scalar ratio in Eq. (3.58) based on the primordial power spectrum gives the *primordial* value of the tensor-to-scalar ratio. For the scales that have not re-entered the horizon by far, i.e., for $K \leq K_E$, the amplitude of the power spectrum has been constant during the whole expansion of the Universe, therefore $h(K, \eta_{\text{ini}}) = h(K, \eta_H)$. However, this is not the case for the pivot scale $k_0 = 0.002 \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, which is the main target of the present CMB measurements. The pivot scale k_0 entered the horizon a little earlier than the present time and has suffered a small decay. This may cause deviation from the primordial value of r_{k_0} . However, one may show that the deviation is negligible and can be safely neglected. Indeed, in order to account for the decay, we use Eq. (3.58) to evaluate the primordial power spectrum at $K = K_E$ as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 r_{K_E} &= \frac{\Delta_h^2(K_E, \eta_{\text{ini}})}{\Delta_{\mathcal{R}}^2(K_E, \eta_{\text{ini}})} = \frac{\Delta_h^2(K_E, \eta_H)}{\Delta_{\mathcal{R}}^2(K_E, \eta_H)} \equiv \frac{\Delta_h^2(K_E)}{\Delta_{\mathcal{R}}^2(K_E)} \\
 &= \frac{\Delta_h^2(k_0)}{\Delta_{\mathcal{R}}^2(k_0)} \left(\frac{K_E}{k_0} \right)^{n_T - n_s + 1}, \\
 &= r_{k_0} \left(\frac{K_E}{k_0} \right)^{n_T - n_s + 1}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.60}$$

where definition Eq. (3.59) is used. Hence, the ratio $(K_E/k_0)^{n_T - n_s + 1}$ accounts for deviation from the actual value of the tensor-to-scalar ratio. To estimate the deviation, one may consider the first-order slow-roll framework of inflation [48]. In this case, the spectral

indices are given by

$$\begin{aligned} n_T &\simeq -2\epsilon, \\ n_s &\simeq 1 - 6\epsilon + 2\eta, \end{aligned} \quad (3.61)$$

where ϵ and η are the first-order slow-roll parameters. For a quadratic scalar inflationary potential of the form $V(\phi) = \frac{1}{2}m\phi^2$, one has $\epsilon = \eta$ and $n_s \simeq 1 - 4\epsilon$. Hence, Eq. (3.60) reduces to

$$r_{K_E} = r_{k_0} \left(\frac{K_E}{k_0} \right)^{\frac{1-n_s}{2}}. \quad (3.62)$$

For $k_0 = 0.002 \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, $K_E = 0.001 \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ and $n_s = 0.966$, one has $(K_E/k_0)^{\frac{1-n_s}{2}} \sim 0.99$. Hence, practically, the definition Eq. (3.58) holds approximately true even for those scales which have entered the horizon recently and suffered a small decay.

Although there is still no direct measurement of $\Delta_h^2(k_0)$, upper bounds on the other parameters, say $\Delta_{\mathcal{R}}^2(k_0) \leq 2.1 \times 10^{-9}$ and $r_{0.002} \lesssim 0.056$ has been made by Planck2018+TT,TE,EE+lowE+lensing+BAO means [112]. An improved constraint on the tensor-to-scalar ratio $r_{k_0} \lesssim 0.032$ has been made with a combination of BICEP and Planck PR4 data [124]. However, throughout the dissertation, we generally treat r_{k_0} as a free parameter of the model.

Since $K_2 \simeq 0.053 \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ and $K_H \simeq 0.0014 \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ (see Eq. 3.25), the pivot scale $k_0 = 0.002 \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ lies in the range $K_H < k_0 < K_2$. The spectrum of tensor perturbations in this frequency range is given by Eq. (3.35), i.e.,

$$h(k_0, \eta_H) = A \left(\frac{k_0}{K_H} \right)^\beta \zeta_E^{-\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}} = \left(\Delta_{\mathcal{R}}^2(k_0) r_{k_0} \right)^{1/2}, \quad (3.63)$$

where in the last equality, Eq. (3.59) is used. Thus, the coefficient A can be normalized for a given set of $\Delta_{\mathcal{R}}^2(k_0)$, r_{k_0} , β and γ , as follows

$$A = \left(\Delta_{\mathcal{R}}^2(k_0) r_{k_0} \right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{K_H}{k_0} \right)^\beta \zeta_E^{\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}}. \quad (3.64)$$

Eq. (3.64) thus provides an observational constraint on the initial amplitude of tensor perturbations A . Even more, by combining the theoretical expression Eq. (3.57) (which is a result of the quantum normalization condition) and observational constraint Eq. (3.64), the following constraint between the model parameters and observational parameters $\Delta_{\mathcal{R}}^2(k_0)$, r_{k_0} outcomes

$$\left(\Delta_{\mathcal{R}}^2(k_0) r_{k_0} \right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{K_H}{k_0} \right)^\beta \zeta_E^{\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}} = 8 \sqrt{\pi} \left(\frac{\ell_{\text{Pl}} H_0}{c} \right) \zeta_1^{\frac{\beta_s - \beta}{1 + \beta_s}} \zeta_s^{-\beta} \zeta_2^{\frac{1-\beta}{2}} \zeta_E^{1 + \frac{1+\beta}{\gamma}}. \quad (3.65)$$

Given the constraint on $\Delta_{\mathcal{R}}^2(k_0)$, Eq. (3.65) implies a constraint between five parameters

$\beta, \beta_s, \zeta_s, \zeta_1$ and r_{k_0} . For instance, the parameter ζ_1 may be expressed in terms of the other parameters according to

$$\zeta_1(\beta, \beta_s, \zeta_s, r_{k_0}) = \left(\frac{c \left(\Delta_{\mathcal{R}}^2(k_0) r_{k_0} \right)^{1/2}}{8 \sqrt{\pi} \ell_{pl} H_0} \right) \left(\frac{K_H}{k_0} \right)^\beta \zeta_s^\beta \zeta_2^{\frac{\beta-1}{2}} \zeta_E^{\frac{1-\beta}{\gamma}} \zeta_E^{\frac{1+\beta_s}{\beta_s-\beta}}, \quad (3.66)$$

assuming $(\beta, \beta_s, \zeta_s, r_{k_0})$ as free parameters of the model. In the subsequent chapters of the thesis, we consider $(\beta, \beta_s, T_{\text{reh}}, r_{k_0})$ as free parameters that determine the spectrum of PGWs and its squeezing parameters. In addition, we consider the theoretical-observational constraint Eq. (3.66) for ζ_1 .

3.4 Summary and conclusions

In this chapter, we investigated the amplification of tensor perturbations in a power-law expansionary model. Relevant quantities and parameters were defined and theoretical and observational constraints were discussed. The following remarks are among the main results of this chapter:

- By considering successive expansionary epochs labeled by different power-law scale factors $a(\eta) \propto \eta^\alpha$, we described the FLRW expanding Universe and determined all relevant parameters of such a cosmological model. In particular, the inflationary epoch was labeled by the power-law index β which, in general, can be linked to a specific inflationary potential.
- Starting from the quantum normalization condition, we initialized the spectral amplitude, i.e., the amplitude of primordial tensor perturbations before the onset of amplification.
- By solving the equation of motion of tensor perturbation in the long-wavelength regime, approximate solutions for the spectral amplitude $h(K, \eta_H)$ and the squeezing parameter $r_K(\eta_H)$ were obtained.
- We defined four independent parameters $\beta, \beta_s, T_{\text{reh}}, r_{k_0}$ that determine the present value of the spectral amplitude $h(K, \eta_H)$ and the squeezing amplitude $r_K(\eta_H)$ of the generated PGWs.
- Results of the present chapter will be used in Chapters 5, 6, 7 to find EM observables in the presence of PGWs.

Chapter 4

Interaction between GWs and EM field: classical version

In this chapter, we consider the EM field propagation through GW background and derive its equation of motion at the classical level. To do so, we apply the Optical Medium Analogy (OMA) concept to visualize the properties of GWs as a bi-anisotropic magneto-dielectric media and determine the EM field solutions inside the medium. Classical quantities of the EM field such as frequency shift and walk-off angle are investigated. Recovering previous results and verifying the consistency between the present approach and the well-established geometrical optics is considered as one of the main goals of this chapter. Moreover, classical solutions of the EM field obtained in this chapter will let us promote the OMA approach to the quantum level, where both of EM field and GWs are treated as quantum entities. The latter will be addressed in the next chapter. The chapter concludes with a discussion on the gauge invariance of the results.

When the EM signal passes through a gravitational field or GW background, the following questions may arise in the realm of the classical theory of waves,

1. How does the frequency of light change?
2. How does the wave vector change, in particular its direction?
3. How the polarization of light is affected by GWs?

For the usual purposes of GW detection by laser interferometers, geometrical optics usually suffices to find out the null geodesics in the presence of GW background. In this way, the frequency shift of light is often obtained within the geometrical optics framework, as we discuss in Sec. 4.1. However, this approach does not allow us to treat the EM field as a quantum mechanical entity. In order to establish the quantum field theory of interaction between the EM and GWs fields, one has to pursue the Hamiltonian formalism. To do so, we describe in Sec. 4.2 the OMA concept, which allocates a bi-anisotropic magneto-dielectric medium to a general curved spacetime. This approach has been vastly used to better grasp the physical aspects of gravitational phenomena at the classical level

[125, 126, 127, 128, 129]. In our context, this framework enables us not only better explore the gravitational phenomena arising from the GWs propagation in terms of the accustomed optical concepts, as we discuss in Sec. 4.3 and Sec. 4.4, but also to construct the Hamiltonian formalism describing the interaction between two tensor fields of rank one and two, corresponding to the EM and GWs fields, as we discuss in Sec. 5.

4.1 EM-GWs interaction within geometrical optics framework

In this section, we present some fundamental formulas regarding the EM-GWs interaction from the geometrical point of view. We describe the EM-GWs interaction assuming a flat Minkowski spacetime. In a typical interferometric probe of GWs, it is crucial to specify the metric perturbations and the coordinate system that we choose for calculations. For our later purposes, it seems easier to choose the transverse-traceless (TT) coordinate system. The TT gauge is a particular coordinate system in which the polarization tensor of a plane gravitational wave assumes a very simple form. As we shall see in the following, this gauge is comoving for freely-falling particles, so it is not the locally Minkowskian coordinate system that would be used by an experimenter to analyze an experiment. However, the benefit of using these coordinates comes back to facts that (a) the form of the metric perturbations in this coordinate system is significantly simplified, (b) two independent polarization states of GWs in the TT gauge naturally appear and (c) the outcoming results in the TT gauge are general, and would be applicable to any beam detector regardless of its physical size with respect to GWs wavelength. In any case, physical observables are gauge invariant and hence can be computed in any coordinate system.

4.1.1 Mathematics of GWs

The metric tensor of a perturbed flat spacetime can be considered as

$$g_{\alpha\beta} = \eta_{\alpha\beta} + h_{\alpha\beta} \quad , \quad |h_{\alpha\beta}| \ll 1 \quad , \quad \alpha, \beta = 0, 1, 2, 3 \quad (4.1)$$

where $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ is the Minkowski metric, which we shall take as $(-1, +1, +1, +1)$ throughout the dissertation, and $h_{\alpha\beta}$ is a small perturbation to the flat spacetime. The inverse metric $g^{\alpha\beta}$ defined by the condition $g^{\alpha\gamma}g_{\gamma\beta} = \delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}$ is determined by $g^{\alpha\beta} = \eta^{\alpha\beta} - h^{\alpha\beta}$ (correct to first order in linearized theory). We define raising and lowering indices of the perturbation with the metric $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$, that is to say $h^{\alpha\beta} \equiv \eta^{\alpha\gamma}\eta^{\beta\delta}h_{\gamma\delta}$. The *trace-reduced* metric is usually defined by $\bar{h}_{\alpha\beta} \equiv h_{\alpha\beta} - \frac{1}{2}\eta_{\alpha\beta}h$, where $h \equiv \eta_{\alpha\beta}h^{\alpha\beta}$ is the trace of the metric perturbation. It follows that Einstein's equation governing the trace-reduced metric takes the form of the famous d'Alembert equation in the *Lorentz (or Hilbert) gauge*, which in the absence of

matter-energy content is given by

$$\square \bar{h}^{\alpha\beta} = \left(-\frac{d^2}{dt^2} + \nabla \right) \bar{h}^{\alpha\beta} = 0. \quad (4.2)$$

Indeed, the freedom to choose the coordinate system lets us define the Lorentz gauge, by imposing

$$\bar{h}^{\alpha\beta}_{,\beta} = 0, \quad (4.3)$$

and the degrees of freedom of the metric perturbations reduce to six (indeed, we chose a coordinate system such that the condition $\partial_\beta \bar{h}^{\alpha\beta} = 0$ is fulfilled in that coordinate system). Thus, the plane-wave solutions $\bar{h}_{\alpha\beta} \propto e_{\alpha\beta} e^{iK_\mu x^\mu}$ describes the propagation of perturbations in the Minkowski background, where $e_{\alpha\beta}$ is called the polarization tensor. The 4-vector K_μ is light-like, i.e., $K^\mu K_\mu = 0$, and the Lorentz gauge condition Eq. (4.3) implies that the wave vector and polarization tensor are orthogonal: $e^{\alpha\beta} K_\beta = 0$. Moreover, one may confirm that the Lorentz gauge does not completely fix the coordinates; If one performs additional infinitesimal coordinate transformation $x^\mu \rightarrow x^\mu + \xi^\mu$ such that $\xi^\mu_{,;\nu} = O(h)$ and $\square \xi^\mu = 0$, one still remains in Lorentz gauge $\bar{h}^{\alpha\beta}_{,\beta} = 0$ (this transformations is called infinitesimal diffeomorphism). This means that one can always find four functions $\xi^\mu(x)$ so as to impose four conditions on $h^{\alpha\beta}$.

In particular, we can choose ξ^0 such that the trace vanishes and one would have $\bar{h} = 0$. One can easily show that $\bar{h} = -h$, hence if $\bar{h} = 0$ then $h = 0$ and $\bar{h}_{\alpha\beta} = h_{\alpha\beta}$. Three functions ξ^i are now chosen so that $h^{0i}(x) = 0$. Then, the Lorentz condition Eq. (4.3) with $\alpha = 0$ results in $\partial_0 h^{00} + \partial_i h^{0i} = 0$. Having fixed $h^{0i} = 0$, this simplifies to $\partial_0 h^{00} = 0$. A time-independent term h_{00} corresponds to the static part of the gravitational interaction, i.e., to the Newtonian potential of the source that generates GWs. The GW itself is the time-dependent part and, as far as GWs are concerned, $\partial_0 h^{00} = 0$ means $h^{00} = 0$. Consequently, we have set four components $h_{0\beta} = 0$ and we are left only with the spatial components h_{ij} , for which the Lorentz gauge condition leads to $h^{ij} K_j = 0$, and the condition of vanishing trace becomes $h_{ii} = 0$. Together, these conditions put the metric into the transverse-traceless (TT) gauge, encapsulated as follows

$$e_{0\beta} = 0 \quad , \quad e_{ii} = 0 \quad , \quad e_{ij} K_j = 0. \quad (4.4)$$

The polarization tensor e_{ij} in the TT gauge is indeed the same that is previously defined by Eq. (2.39). Thus the degrees of freedom are reduced to 2, which are nothing but the two polarization states of GWs (corresponding to two helicity states in the quantum language), and can be determined by $e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}]$, represented by Eq. (2.40) and Eq. (2.41). We will explicitly construct this gauge in our subsequent calculations.

In a real situation, the spacetime hosts a superposition of different GWs, each of which possesses arbitrary propagation direction, polarization tensor, and frequency. The most

general form of GWs may be given by the following expansion

$$h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{\gamma=+, \times} \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{K}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} e_{ij}^{\gamma}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] (h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma} e^{-i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}t - \mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x})} + h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma*} e^{i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}t - \mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x})}), \quad (4.5)$$

which is a result of the d'Alembert equation in TT gauge. This expression can describe the present PGWs background which we studied in detail in Chapter 2 and Chapter 3. Note that, we use upper-case symbols \mathbf{K} and $\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}$ to describe the GWs wave vector and frequency, while the lower-case symbols \mathbf{k} and $\omega_{\mathbf{k}}$ are reserved for the EM wave vector and frequency, respectively. The summation is over different polarization states of the GWs denoted by $\gamma = +, \times$.

For illustration, we may consider a single-mode GW of frequency $\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}$ moving in the z -direction, so that $K_1 = K_2 = 0, K_3 = \Omega_{\mathbf{K}}/c$. The TT gauge conditions Eq. (4.4) leave only two independent components of the polarization tensor, say e_{11} and e_{12} , which are usually denoted by $+$ and \times symbols. For a pure $+$ -polarized wave propagating in the z -direction, the spacetime line element is specified by

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 + (1 + h_+) dx^2 + (1 - h_+) dy^2 + dz^2, \quad (4.6)$$

where $h_+ \equiv h_{\mathbf{K}} e_{11}^+ e^{-i\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}(t - \frac{z}{c})}$. One can show that the effect of GW in TT gauge on a particle initially at rest is such that the particle stays at rest during the passage of the GW. Thus, the TT gauge, to first order in $h_{\alpha\beta}$, corresponds to a coordinate system that is co-moving with freely-falling particles. However, tidal forces show the action of the wave independently of the coordinates. This can be seen from the equation of geodesic deviation, which governs the separation of two neighboring freely-falling test particles. In this case, the separation of the two particles evolves with the oscillating GW. Thus, as far as local mathematics is applicable, a GW behaves like an extra force, called a tidal force, perturbing the proper distance between two test particles.

From experimental aspects, two typical situations can be analyzed: *small detectors* for which the physical length of the detector is small compared to the wavelength of the gravitational waves it is measuring, and *large detectors* which have physical lengths comparable to or larger than GWs wavelength. In the first case, one may use the geodesic deviation equation to represent the wave as a simple extra force on the equipment. Bar detectors can always be analyzed in this way. Laser interferometers on the Earth can be treated this way too, considering their frequency window. In these cases, a gravitational wave simply exerts a force on test masses, to be measured. In large detectors, the geodesic deviation equation is not useful because the 'local physics' concept of geodesic deviation must be replaced with the 'global mathematics' of the TT gauge. In deriving the equation for the geodesic deviation, it is valid as long as the separation between two geodesics is much smaller than the typical scale over which the gravitational field changes substantially. For a GW, this length scale is its wavelength. Thus, if a detector has a characteristic linear size L , we can discuss its interaction with GWs using the equation of the geodesic

deviation, if and only if $L \leq \lambda_{gw}$. In this case, it is possible to study the detector and its interaction with GWs using a simple and intuitive description in terms of Newtonian forces, supplemented by the “GW force”. Otherwise, a full general relativistic description, usually performed in the TT frame, is necessary [119]. Some space-based interferometers like LISA and pulsar timing arrays are of this class. On top of that, we will consider in Chapter 7 propagation of EM field over cosmological distances, where the characteristic length-scale of the detector (the EM probe) is comparable to the GWs wavelength (which is of the order of the Hubble scale). To study these beam detectors it is easier to remain in the TT gauge.

4.1.2 The effect of GWs on light in TT gauge

The TT gauge is the coordinate system in which the spatial coordinates \mathbf{x} stay fixed even after the passage of GWs. In other words, the TT gauge corresponds to freely-falling masses in the presence of GWs. However, this is not the coordinate system that is important, but the proper distance between two points that changes as GWs propagate from one point to another. Thus, from the point of view of the TT observer, the proper distance between two spatial points carries information about GWs. The observable quantity of interest which is usually measured in typical large GW detectors, is *the rate of change of return time* of an EM signal. Let us examine the simplest case of metric from Eq. (4.6) and examine a null geodesic moving in the x -direction. The (coordinate) speed along this curve is:

$$\left(\frac{dx}{cdt}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{1+h_+}. \quad (4.7)$$

That means, the TT observer sees the EM field propagating along a curve described by Eq. (4.7). To understand the way the detector works, we may assume that the GW is propagating in the z -direction and the arm-length of the interferometer lies along the x -axis. Then a photon emitted at time t_s from the source at origin reaches the other end (transponder), at a fixed coordinate $x = L$, at the coordinate time

$$t_t = t_s + \frac{1}{c} \int_0^L \sqrt{1+h_+(t(x))} dx, \quad (4.8)$$

where the argument $t(x)$ denotes the fact that it takes a time $t(x) = t_s + x/c$ for the EM field to reach the position x along the x -axis. Since h_+ is small, one may use the first-order approximation. The result is

$$t_t = t_s + \frac{L}{c} + \frac{1}{2c} \int_0^L h_+(t_s + x/c) dx. \quad (4.9)$$

In an interferometer, the light is reflected back to be detected at the receiver, so the return

trip takes the form

$$t_r = t_s + \frac{L}{c} + \frac{1}{2c} \left[\int_0^L h_+(t_s + x/c) dx + \int_0^L h_+(t_s + L/c + x/c) dx \right]. \quad (4.10)$$

If there were no GWs, t_r would be constant since L is fixed. What one monitors is changes in the time taken by a round trip as a function of start time at the origin, i.e.,

$$\frac{dt_r}{dt_s} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} [h_+(t_s + 2L/c) - h_+(t_s)]. \quad (4.11)$$

which depends only on the GW amplitude at the initial time and receiving time. Practically, dt_s can be the oscillatory period T_s of an EM field which after the round trip takes a new value T_r , due to the existence of GWs.

4.1.3 The residual shift \mathcal{Z}_h

Another way around to explore the formula Eq. (4.11), is to consider a general situation consisting of a source of EM waves ('s'), a transponder ('t') located on a spacecraft, and a receiver ('r'). Here we take into account only the effect of GWs on the Doppler shift of the EM field and neglect the Doppler shift caused by the motion of these instruments (see [127] for a more general case where the motion of source, transponder and receiver are taken into account). We assume that all instruments are in freely-falling motion (are comoving). At a given moment t_s , an EM beam is directed to the spacecraft (containing the transponder) in the direction \hat{n} , then it is conducted from the transponder to the receiver, in the direction \hat{m} , as shown in Figure 4.1. We denote by ω_s , ω_t and ω_r the frequency of the beam as measured at the source, transponder, and receiver, respectively. Following the geometrical optics, one may find an expression for $\frac{\omega_r}{\omega_s}$ [127]. If in the absence of an external GW, this expression is $\frac{\omega_r^0}{\omega_s}$, then the ratio

$$\frac{\omega_r}{\omega_r^0} \equiv 1 + \mathcal{Z}_h, \quad (4.12)$$

is a measure of the influence of the GW on the Doppler shift (there would also be a second residual shift due to the change in the velocity of the instruments accompanied by the incidence of GWs. An analysis of this effect is provided in [127]). In Eq. 4.12, ω_r^0 and ω_r denote the EM frequency at the receiver, in the absence and presence of the GWs, correspondingly. It follows that the residual shift \mathcal{Z}_h is given by [127]

$$\mathcal{Z}_h = \frac{1}{2} \frac{n^i n^j (h_{ij}^s - h_{ij}^t)}{1 - \hat{K} \cdot \hat{n}} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{m^i m^j (h_{ij}^t - h_{ij}^r)}{1 - \hat{K} \cdot \hat{m}}. \quad (4.13)$$

Figure 4.1: Schematic diagram of the sender-transponder-receiver configuration.

Here, n^i and m^i represent spatial components of the unit vectors \hat{n} and \hat{m} , and \hat{K} shows the propagation direction of GWs. Moreover, $h_{ij}^s = e_{ij}^\gamma h_{K,\gamma}(q_s)$, etc., with

$$\begin{aligned} q_s &= t_s - \hat{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}_s, \\ q_t &= q_s + (1 - \hat{K} \cdot \hat{n})(t_t - t_s), \\ q_r &= q_t + (1 - \hat{K} \cdot \hat{m})(t_r - t_t), \end{aligned} \quad (4.14)$$

and \mathbf{x}_s being the position of sender. If GW propagates in the same direction as the initial beam, $\hat{K} = \hat{n}$, then $q_t = q_s$ and $h_{ij}^t = h_{ij}^s$ so that the contribution of the first term in Eq. (4.13) vanishes. In other words, since $e_{ij}K^j = 0$ in TT gauge, the first expression in Eq. (4.13) vanishes automatically when we replace $n^i n^j$ by $K^i K^j$. In this case the residual shift is given by

$$\mathcal{Z}_h = \frac{1}{2} \frac{m^i m^j (h_{ij}^t - h_{ij}^r)}{1 - \hat{n} \cdot \hat{m}}. \quad (4.15)$$

Moreover, if $\hat{m} = -\hat{n}$, then again one has $e_{ij}m^i m^j = e_{ij}K^i K^j = 0$ and it follows from Eq. (4.15) that the residual shift is zero, $\mathcal{Z}_h = 0$. Consequently, if the EM beam is transmitted and received parallel to the GW propagation direction, the residual shift vanishes. On the other hand, if \hat{K} is orthogonal to \hat{n} and $\hat{n} = -\hat{m}$, then the residual shift is given by

$$\mathcal{Z}_h = \frac{1}{2} n^i n^j (h_{ij}^s - h_{ij}^r). \quad (4.16)$$

Thus, the residual shift Eq. (4.16) together with the definition Eq. (4.12) provides the Doppler shift experienced by the EM field, from the point of view of the TT observer. That is, the frequency of light after a round trip in GW background (measured by an observer located at the origin) differs from the frequency in the absence of GWs. This result was

obtained by many authors, see for instance Estabrook and Wahlquist [130]. Indeed, the residual shift Eq. (4.16) is a generalization of the quantity that appears in Eq. (4.11); in that case, we discussed the change in the arrival time of the signal in the presence of a pure +polarized single-mode GW propagating in z -direction where the EM field propagates in the x -direction. With the help of Eq. (4.16), one can simply show that in this simplified case the residual shift becomes

$$\mathcal{Z}_h = \frac{1}{2}(h_+(t_s) - h_+(t_s + 2L/c)). \quad (4.17)$$

Now we may replace dt_s and dt_r respectively by T_s and T_r which represent the oscillation period of the EM field measured at the source and at the receiver, correspondingly. Eq. (4.11) then becomes

$$\frac{dt_s}{dt_r} \rightarrow \frac{T_s}{T_r} = \frac{\omega_r}{\omega_s} = 1 + \mathcal{Z}_h, \quad (4.18)$$

with \mathcal{Z}_h given by Eq. (4.17). On top of that, we recover this formula later in Sec. (4.4.1) when we compute the refractive index of the GWs medium in the context of OMA. In this way, we shall establish the connection between geometrical optics and wave optics points of view.

When we discuss quantum mechanical EM-GWs interaction in Chapter 5, we shall see that the EM-GWs coupling strength is proportional to the quantity $F_\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) \equiv e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j$ with $\hat{\mathbf{K}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ being the unit GWs and EM field wave vectors. This quantity also appears in the residual shift Eq. (4.13) and, later in Sec. 4.3.3 we shall explore the same quantity in the expression of the refractive index given by Eq. (4.48) within the OMA framework. Indeed, the function $F_\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}})$ is closely related to the *detector pattern function* introduced in the literature (see Eq. (7.21) in Chapter 7 of [119]). In that context, in general, the input of a detector has the form $h(t) = D^{ij}h_{ij}$, where D^{ij} is a constant tensor which depends on the detector geometry and is known as the *detector tensor*. For instance, for a detector that is driven only by the (x, x) component of h_{ij} (such as a resonant bar or an EM field oriented along the x axis), $D^{11} \neq 0$ and other components vanish (see Chapter 7 of [119]). Here, we may define the detector tensor as $D^{ij} \equiv \hat{\mathbf{k}}^i \hat{\mathbf{k}}^j$. For instance, if the EM probe propagates along the x axis one has $\hat{\mathbf{k}} = (1, 0, 0)$, $D^{11} = 1$ and other components vanish.

In the following, we address the optical medium analogy approach, which enables us not only to investigate the effect of GWs on the EM phase but also discuss its effect on the external degrees of freedom of the EM field, say its polarization and orbital angular momentum as well. However, a detailed investigation of these quantities is out of the scope of this thesis.

4.2 Optical medium analogy (OMA) framework

The analogy between gravity and optics was first introduced by J. Plebanski [125] to study the scattering of plane EM waves by the gravitational field of an isolated physical system, and to calculate a generalized formula for the Einstein deflection of light rays. The optical medium analogy (OMA) also proves helpful to simply capture some interesting effects of photon propagation in a gravitational radiation field [129, 131]. Here, we shall use OMA to describe the interaction between EM and the GW background in a general manner. Let $F^{\mu\nu}$ be the anti-symmetric tensor of the EM field propagating in a gravitational field. The following equations govern the EM field in a Riemannian space

$$F^{\mu\nu}_{;\nu} = 4\pi J^\mu \quad , \quad F_{\mu\nu;\sigma} + F_{\sigma\mu;\nu} + F_{\nu\sigma;\mu} = 0, \quad (4.19)$$

where J_μ stands for the 4-current vector and the semicolon refers to covariant differentiation. For our purpose, it will be convenient to rewrite these basic equations in a non-covariant notation, in which they will be formally equivalent to the equations of electrodynamics in a macroscopic medium in the fabric of flat spacetime. By defining the dual tensor $H^{\mu\nu} \equiv \sqrt{-g}F^{\mu\nu}$ and $I^\mu = \sqrt{-g}J^\mu$, the Maxwell's equation takes the form $H^{\mu\nu} = 4\pi I^\mu$ and $F_{\mu\nu;\sigma} + F_{\sigma\mu;\nu} + F_{\nu\sigma;\mu} = 0$, where a comma stands for ordinary differentiation. A space and time decomposition in a Cartesian coordinate system such that $F_{\mu\nu} \rightarrow (\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{B})$, $H^{\mu\nu} \rightarrow (-\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{H})$ and $I^\mu \rightarrow (\rho, \mathbf{J})$ yields

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} &= 0 \quad , \quad \nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\partial_t \mathbf{B} \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} &= 0 \quad , \quad \nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \partial_t \mathbf{D} + 4\pi \mathbf{J}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.20)$$

in the absence of external free charges. Here, $t = x^0$, $\mathbf{x}_i = x^i$ and $\partial\rho/\partial t + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{J} = 0$. These equations look like Maxwell's equations in a flat space-time. The "constitutive equations" $H^{\mu\nu} = \sqrt{-g}g^{\mu\rho}g^{\nu\sigma}F_{\rho\sigma}$ can be written as [126, 125]

$$D_i = \varepsilon_{ij}E_j - (\mathbf{G} \times \mathbf{H})_i \quad , \quad B_i = \mu_{ij}H_j + (\mathbf{G} \times \mathbf{E})_i. \quad (4.21)$$

with $\bar{\varepsilon}$ and $\bar{\mu}$ being the permittivity and permeability tensors defined by

$$\frac{\varepsilon_{ij}}{\varepsilon_0} = \frac{\mu_{ij}}{\mu_0} = -\sqrt{-g} \frac{g^{ij}}{g_{00}} \quad , \quad G_i = -\frac{g_{0i}}{g_{00}}. \quad (4.22)$$

and double bar entails the tensor nature of permittivity and permeability tensors. Here, $i, j = 1, 2, 3$ are spatial indices, $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the spacetime metric, $g^{\mu\nu}$ is the inverse metric and g denotes its determinant. For GWs, one may apply the TT gauge conditions which lead to $g = -1$, $g_{00} = -1$, $g^{0i} = 0$, $g_{ij} = \delta_{ij} + h_{ij}$ and $g^{ij} = \delta_{ij} - h_{ij}$ (δ_{ij} being the Kronecker symbol). Considering the perturbed flat spacetime in TT gauge, one may specify the characteristic

tensors of the medium according to

$$\frac{\varepsilon_{ij}}{\varepsilon_0} = \frac{\mu_{ij}}{\mu_0} = g_{ij} = \delta_{ij} - h_{ij}. \quad (4.23)$$

The bi-anisotropic nature of GW medium can be best seen as follows. Generally, one may rewrite Eq. (4.21) for \mathbf{D} and \mathbf{H} in an equivalent form

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{r}, t) &= \bar{\varepsilon}^{(1)} \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, t) + \bar{\varepsilon}^{(2)} \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{r}, t), \\ \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{r}, t) &= \bar{\mu}^{(1)} \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, t) + \bar{\mu}^{(2)} \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{r}, t). \end{aligned} \quad (4.24)$$

The bi-anisotropic nature, i.e., the dependency of (\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{H}) to (\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{B}) , is evident in the *constitutive relations* Eq. (4.24). Now one may easily show that the tensors $\bar{\varepsilon}^{(1,2)}$ and $\bar{\mu}^{(1,2)}$ defined in Eq. (4.24) are given by [132]

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{ij}^{(1)}/\varepsilon_0 &= -\sqrt{-g} \frac{g^{ij}}{g_{00}} - \epsilon_{i\alpha\beta} \epsilon_{mnj} \frac{g_{0\alpha} g_{0n} g_{\beta m}}{g_{00} \sqrt{-g}}, \\ \varepsilon_{ij}^{(2)}/\varepsilon_0 &= -\epsilon_{imn} \frac{g_{nj} g_{0m}}{\sqrt{-g}}, \\ \mu_{ij}^{(1)}/\mu_0 &= -\epsilon_{mnj} \frac{g_{0n} g_{im}}{\sqrt{-g}}, \\ \mu_{ij}^{(2)}/\mu_0 &= -\frac{g_{00}}{\sqrt{-g}} g_{ij}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.25)$$

Thus the form of Maxwell's equations in the curved spacetime in the absence of an external responsive medium is similar to the form of Maxwell's equations in the flat spacetime in the presence of a bi-anisotropic magneto-dielectric medium characterized by Eq. (4.25). For GWs in the TT gauge, Eq. (4.25) can be further simplified into the following relations

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{ij}^{(1)}/\varepsilon_0 &= -\mu_{ij}^{(2)}/\mu_0 = \varepsilon_{ij}/\varepsilon_0 = \mu_{ij}/\mu_0 = \delta_{ij} - h_{ij}, \\ \varepsilon_{ij}^{(2)}/\varepsilon_0 &= \mu_{ij}^{(1)}/\mu_0 = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4.26)$$

Thus, in the TT gauge, \mathbf{D} depends only on \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{H} depend only on \mathbf{B} .

4.3 Plane wave expansion of the EM field in the presence of GW background

In order to apply the OMA framework to the case of GWs, we consider a general GWs background which can be described by Eq. (4.5), namely

$$h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{\gamma=+, \times} \int \frac{d^3 \mathbf{K}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} e_{ij}^{\gamma}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] (h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma} e^{-i(\Omega t - \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x})} + h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma*} e^{i(\Omega t - \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x})}).$$

With the help of Eq. (4.23), the corresponding permittivity and permeability tensors are specified by

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)/\epsilon_0 = \bar{\mu}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)/\mu_0 &= \delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \\ &= \delta_{ij} - \sum_{\gamma=+, \times} \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{K}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} e_{ij}^{\gamma}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] (h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma} e^{-i(\Omega t - \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x})} + h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma*} e^{i(\Omega t - \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x})}).\end{aligned}\quad (4.27)$$

In the following, we solve Maxwell's equations Eq. (4.20) in the presence of a time-dependent magneto-dielectric medium specified by Eq. (4.27).

4.3.1 Wave equation in the adiabatic approximation

In order to find the wave equation, we proceed by defining the scalar and vector potentials, which are the components of the 4-potential $A_{\mu} = (\phi/c, \mathbf{A})$ and are related to the EM tensor according to $F_{\mu\nu} = A_{\nu,\mu} - A_{\mu,\nu}$. Thus, we may rewrite the fields in terms of the scalar and vector potentials as $\mathbf{E} = -\nabla\phi - \partial_t\mathbf{A}$ and $\mathbf{B} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A}$. Maxwell's equations lead to the following wave equation for the vector potential

$$\nabla \times [\bar{\mu}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) \nabla \times \mathbf{A}] = -\dot{\bar{\epsilon}}(\mathbf{x}, t)(\nabla\phi + \partial_t\mathbf{A}) - \bar{\epsilon}(\nabla\dot{\phi} + \partial_t^2\mathbf{A}). \quad (4.28)$$

4.3.1.1 Adiabatic approximation

The first term on the r.h.s of Eq. (4.28) is proportional to $\dot{\bar{\epsilon}}$, which is directly proportional to the rate of change of gravitational field, or the GWs frequency Ω_K . For typical GWs which we are interested in, one has $\Omega_K \ll \omega_k$. Consequently, one may apply the *adiabatic approximation* and assume that the medium is slowly varying. Therefore we will neglect the first term in Eq. (4.28) with respect to the second one. The same argument also applies to the spatial change of the vector field, that is to say, $\lambda_K \gg \lambda_k$. In the following, we use the adiabatic approximation in temporal and spatial domains, in order to simplify the equation of motion of the EM field.

4.3.1.2 Gauge fixing

In order to exclude the extra degree of freedom, i.e., to have $\phi = 0$, it is enough to fix the gauge by imposing the condition $\nabla \cdot [\bar{\epsilon}(\mathbf{x}, t)\dot{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}, t)] = 0$. To prove that, consider the Gauss' law:

$$\nabla \cdot (\bar{\epsilon}(\mathbf{x}, t)\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}, t)) = 0 \quad \rightarrow \quad \nabla \cdot (-\bar{\epsilon}(\mathbf{x}, t)\partial_t\mathbf{A} - \bar{\epsilon}(\mathbf{x}, t)\nabla\phi) = 0 \quad (4.29)$$

This means that ϕ and \mathbf{A} satisfy following equation

$$\int \nabla \cdot (\bar{\epsilon}(\mathbf{x}, t)\nabla\phi) d^3\mathbf{x} = - \int \nabla \cdot (\bar{\epsilon}(\mathbf{x}, t)\partial_t\mathbf{A}) d^3\mathbf{x}. \quad (4.30)$$

We now consider the following solution for $\phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$,

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}, t) := \int d^3\mathbf{x}' G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') \nabla' \cdot (\bar{\epsilon}(\mathbf{x}', t) \dot{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}', t)). \quad (4.31)$$

By plugging Eq. (4.31) into Eq. (4.30) we get

$$\int \nabla \cdot (\bar{\epsilon}(\mathbf{x}, t) \nabla \phi) d^3\mathbf{x} = \int d^3\mathbf{x}' \int d^3\mathbf{x} \nabla \cdot (\bar{\epsilon}(\mathbf{x}', t) \nabla G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')) \nabla' \cdot (\bar{\epsilon}(\mathbf{x}', t) \partial_t \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}', t)). \quad (4.32)$$

Hence, provided that the function $G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$ satisfy the following point-source equation

$$\nabla \cdot (\bar{\epsilon}(\mathbf{x}, t) \nabla G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')) = -\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'), \quad (4.33)$$

Eq. (4.32) fulfills Eq. (4.29) and Eq. (4.31) is a solution for $\phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$. In order to have $\phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0$, we demand

$$\nabla \cdot (\bar{\epsilon}(\mathbf{x}, t) \partial_t \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}, t)) = 0. \quad (4.34)$$

The condition Eq. (4.34) is called the gauge condition. By choosing this gauge condition, one has $\phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0$ and the wave equation Eq. (4.28) in the adiabatic approximation (neglecting the first term on r.h.s) reduces to

$$\nabla \times [\bar{\mu}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) \nabla \times \mathbf{A}] = -\bar{\epsilon}(\mathbf{x}, t) \partial_t^2 \mathbf{A}. \quad (4.35)$$

In the next step we solve the above wave equation. Although the medium is intrinsically time-dependent, inhomogeneous and anisotropic, we profit from some features of GWs to reduce the complexity of the equations.

4.3.2 Plane wave expansion

In order to solve the wave equation Eq. (4.35), let us expand the field $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ over a complete set of mode functions $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ as [133, 132]

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_k \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2}} (\alpha_k \nu_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) + \alpha_k^* \nu_k^*(\mathbf{x}, t) \mathbf{f}_k^*(\mathbf{x}, t)). \quad (4.36)$$

Here, $k \equiv (\sigma, \mathbf{k})$ denotes different modes of the EM field with wave vector \mathbf{k} and polarization σ . Although the quantum pre-factor \hbar is included intentionally, at the classical level one can substitute $\alpha_k \sqrt{\hbar} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_k$ where \mathcal{A}_k stands for a constant amplitude. The time-harmonic behavior of $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is included in the temporal mode function $\nu_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ which recasts to $e^{\pm i\omega_k t}$ in the vacuum case, i.e., when there is no gravitational background. However, we let this function to be \mathbf{x} -dependent as well, since the gravitational background is \mathbf{x} -dependent through $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$. That means, $\nu_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is a slowly varying function of \mathbf{x} . The spatial mode function $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ contains the spatial factor which recasts to the plane modes

$e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}}$ in absence of GWs, and again we let it to have a slowly varying envelope as well since the gravitational medium is time-dependent. Thus we may consider $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \equiv \hat{\mathbf{u}}_k f(t) e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}}$ with $f(t)$ being a slowly varying function of time and $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_k$ a unit vector. The slowly varying envelope approximation (SVEA) implies that [134]

$$\left| \frac{\dot{\mathbf{f}}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)} \right| \ll \left| \frac{\dot{\mathbf{f}}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)} \right| \ll \omega_k \quad , \quad \left| \frac{\nabla^2 v_k(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\nabla v_k(\mathbf{x}, t)} \right| \ll \left| \frac{\nabla v_k(\mathbf{x}, t)}{v_k(\mathbf{x}, t)} \right| \ll k s. \quad (4.37)$$

That means, temporal change of the spatial mode function due to the existence of GWs happens in a time scale much larger than the characteristic oscillatory behavior of the EM wave. Similarly, spatial change of the temporal mode functions induced by GW medium happens at scales much larger than the typical wavelength of the EM field. Inserting the field expansion Eq. (4.36) into the wave equation Eq. (4.35) results in

$$\left[\nabla \times (\bar{\mu}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) \nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)) \right] v_k(\mathbf{x}, t) = -\dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \bar{\epsilon}(\mathbf{x}, t) \mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t). \quad (4.38)$$

In derivation of Eq. (4.38), we have neglected spatial derivative of $\bar{\mu}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $v_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$, as well as time derivative of $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ under the adiabatic approximation Eq. (4.37). Thus, Eq. (4.38) contains the second-order spatial derivative of $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ on the l.h.s, and second-order time derivative of $v_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ on the r.h.s. To solve Eq. (4.38), we proceed by assuming the following time behavior for the temporal mode functions,

$$\dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \equiv -\omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) v_k(\mathbf{x}, t). \quad (4.39)$$

Firstly, note that the \mathbf{x} -dependence of temporal mode function $v_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ must satisfy the SVEA condition Eq. (4.37). In the following, we shall see that this is indeed the case. On the other hand, in the proposed form Eq. (4.39) a friction term is absent in the time evolution of the EM field, while its frequency may be affected by the underlying GWs background. This assumption is consistent with the fact that the GW background does not produce or annihilate photons, under the adiabatic approximation where $\Omega_K \ll \omega_k$.

Let us take a look at the optical medium analogy. In this framework, the dielectric field $\mathbf{D} = \bar{\epsilon} \mathbf{E}$ can be re-written as $\mathbf{D} = \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{P}$, where the first term indicates the contribution of the vacuum (as if there is no medium). The second term which contains the polarization vector \mathbf{P} is related to the electric field through $P_i \equiv \chi_{ij} E_j$, where $\chi_{ij} \propto h_{ij}$ denotes the susceptibility tensor of the effective medium. Consequently, the response function of the medium to the incident EM field can be obtained from the (temporal) Fourier transformation of the permittivity and permeability tensors Eq. (4.27), namely $\tilde{\epsilon}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \Omega') \sim \int dt e^{i\Omega' t} \epsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ that are proportional to delta function $\delta(\Omega' \pm \Omega_K)$. This means that the GW medium is not dispersive and absorptive in the optical range since the EM-GWs interaction is off-resonant. In the corresponding quantum field theory (to be addressed in Chapter 5), this assumption implies that EM-GWs interaction does not create or annihilate photons, and the mean number of photons in the EM field is conserved. This

point was first noted by Kip. Thorne [135] in case of slowly varying GW background.

Now, inserting Eq. (4.39) into the wave equation Eq. (4.38) yields

$$\nabla \times (\bar{\mu}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) \nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)) = \omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) \bar{\epsilon}(\mathbf{x}, t) \mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad (4.40)$$

which is an eigen-equation for $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ with eigen-values $\omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$. In the presence of anisotropic media, it is convenient to define the orthogonality equation of the spatial mode functions $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ according to

$$\int_V d^3\mathbf{x} \bar{\epsilon}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{\sigma,ki}^*(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{\sigma',k'j}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}') \delta_{\sigma,\sigma'}, \quad (4.41)$$

which is a generalization of the orthogonality condition defined in [133, 132] to the case that the medium is time-dependent and anisotropic. Here, $f_{\sigma,ki}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ denote the i -th component of the vector $\mathbf{f}_{\sigma,\mathbf{k}}$ where the polarization state σ and the wave vector \mathbf{k} are written explicitly. Note that since the medium is spacetime-dependent, in general, the integration in Eq. (4.41) does not produce the Dirac delta function $\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}')$ on the r.h.s. However, it is straightforward to show that in the adiabatic limit $K \ll k$ the orthonormality relation Eq. (4.41) holds correct (see Appendix B.1). Thus, the normalized spatial mode function $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is determined by

$$\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}} e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}}}{\sqrt{(2\pi)^3 \epsilon_0 m(t)}}, \quad (4.42)$$

Here, $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}}$ denotes the unit polarization vector of the electric field and $m(t) \equiv \bar{\epsilon}_{ij}(t) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k},i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k},j} = (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(0, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k},i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k},j}$ is a slowly varying function since its time behavior is governed by the metric perturbations $h_{ij}(0, t)$, the time-derivative of which is proportional to Ω_K . Here, $h_{ij}(0, t)$ is obtained by setting $\mathbf{x} = 0$ in Eq. (4.5). The mode function Eq. (4.42) satisfies the orthogonality condition Eq. (4.41) as well as the SVEA condition Eq. (4.37). Putting plane wave solutions Eq. (4.42) into the eigenvalue equation Eq. (4.40) results in the following algebraic equation between $\omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$, \mathbf{k} and $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}}$

$$\mathbf{k} \times (\bar{\mu}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) \mathbf{k} \times \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}}) = -\omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) \bar{\epsilon}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}}. \quad (4.43)$$

In the next section, we try to find the eigenvalues $\omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and their relation to the refractive index of the medium. Before that, let us discuss some remarks about the plane wave solutions Eq. (4.42). In the present context, the EM-GWs interaction is considered in the ‘‘adiabatic regime’’, implying that the characteristic time-scale of variation of GWs, determined by Ω_K^{-1} is much larger than the oscillation time of the EM field, ω_k^{-1} . The same holds for the corresponding characteristic length scales λ_K and λ_k . Under these circumstances, we applied the SVEA and ignored spatial derivatives of GWs with respect to the EM spatial variations (see Sec. 4.3). The solution to the mode functions given by Eq. (4.42) thus implies that the wave vector of the EM field, \mathbf{k} , does not change while the

effect of GWs is reflected in the phase velocity of the wave as determined by the refractive index $n(\mathbf{x}, t)$.

4.3.3 Refractive index of the GWs' effective medium

Eq. (4.43) can be cast to the following algebraic eigenvalue equation

$$\left[\omega_k^2 \varepsilon_{il} + \epsilon_{ijr} \epsilon_{sul} k_j k_u \mu_{rs}^{-1} \right] \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k},l} = 0. \quad (4.44)$$

This is evidently an eigen equation, with $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k},l}$ and ω_k being the eigenvectors and eigenvalues, respectively. Here, k_i is the i -th component of the EM wave vector and $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k},l}$ is the l -th component of the electric field polarization. Note that, here we have dropped the spacetime dependence of the quantities for the sake of abbreviation. To discover the link between this formula and the previous results in the literature, we define the quantity

$$n_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \equiv \frac{\omega_k}{\omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t)}, \quad (4.45)$$

where $\omega_k = ck$ is the EM frequency in the vacuum (in the absence of GWs). Combining Eq. (4.44) and Eq. (4.45) gives

$$\left[\varepsilon_{il}(\mathbf{x}, t) + \frac{n_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t)}{c^2} \epsilon_{ijr} \epsilon_{mnl} \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j \hat{\mathbf{k}}_n \mu_{rm}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) \right] \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k},l} = 0, \quad (4.46)$$

where we have substituted $k_j = |\mathbf{k}| \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j = (\omega_k/c) \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j$. Eq. (4.46) is also obtained in [136] where the quantity $n_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is nothing but the refractive index of the GWs medium. The existence of eigen-solutions for $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}}$ leads to the *generalized Fresnel equation*

$$n_k^2 \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j - \det(\bar{\varepsilon}) = 0. \quad (4.47)$$

Eq. (4.47) determines the refractive index of the GWs effective medium according to

$$n_k(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sqrt{\frac{\det(\bar{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}, t))}{\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j}}, \quad (4.48)$$

which is consistent with Eq. (14) of [136]. Consequently, the EM frequency in the presence of GW background is determined by Eq. (4.45), and the temporal mode functions $v_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ are specified by Eq. (4.39). The refractive index $n_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ depends on the EM propagation direction $\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ through the contraction of $\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ and the permittivity tensor $\bar{\varepsilon}$, induced by GWs. Thus the effective medium is birefringence since it exhibits different refractive indices depending on the EM propagation direction. One can check that $\det(\bar{\varepsilon}) = 1$ in the linear

order $O(h)$, and Eq. (4.48) simplifies to

$$\begin{aligned} n_k(\mathbf{x}, t) &= \left(\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j \right)^{-1/2} = \left(1 - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j \right)^{-1/2} \\ &= 1 + \frac{1}{2} h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j. \end{aligned} \quad (4.49)$$

where we have used Eq. (4.23) for the permittivity tensor $\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$. For a mono-chromatic pure +polarized GW propagating in the z -direction described by the spacetime metric Eq. (4.6) and a single-mode EM field propagating in a direction that makes angle θ_k with z -axis, one may show that the refractive index is determined by

$$n_k(\mathbf{x}, t) = 1 + \frac{1}{2} h_+(\mathbf{x}, t) \sin^2 \theta_k, \quad (4.50)$$

which depends on the angle θ_k between the EM wave vector $\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ and the GW wave vector $\hat{\mathbf{K}} \equiv \hat{z}$.

4.3.4 Temporal mode functions

Before proceeding, here we obtain the solution of the temporal mode functions $\nu_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$. Eq. (4.39) indicates that, under the adiabatic approximation, the EM field behaves as a time-dependent harmonic oscillator. This may give rise to possible *photon production* by the gravitational field, which in the corresponding quantum field theory leads to the ambiguity in defining the vacuum state of the EM field [104]. However one may check that, the corresponding Bogoliubov coefficient of particle creation is zero and the particle production is negligible *in the adiabatic regime*. It follows that the WKB prescription can be used to determine the adiabatic vacuum, that is given by (see [104] for details)

$$\nu_k(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t)}} e^{\pm i \int_0^t \omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t') dt'}. \quad (4.51)$$

where the space-time dependent frequency $\omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is given by

$$\omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t) = \omega_k \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j \right), \quad (4.52)$$

where Eq. (4.45) and Eq. (4.49) are used to specify $\omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$. In the case of vacuum, where $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ vanishes, one recovers the time-harmonic solutions $e^{\pm i \omega_k t}$. Given the specific form of $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, the explicit time behavior of the EM field is obtained based on Eq. (4.51).

4.4 Classical fingerprints : residual shift and walk-off angle

4.4.1 Refractive index and residual shift

In this section, we check the consistency of the obtained results in the OMA framework with already established formula in geometrical optics. Precisely, we show that the mode functions Eq. (4.42) and Eq. (4.51), obtained in the adiabatic approximation, truly describe the residual shift \mathcal{Z}_h introduced in Sec. 4.1.2.

Eq. (4.52) for the EM frequency implies that the effect of GWs on the EM field is similar to a parametric change of its frequency, though in the adiabatic regime, it leaves the energy content (\sim mean number of photons) of the EM field conserved. This effect is expected, as we already discussed about the residual shift in TT gauge in Sec. 4.1.2. In order to clarify the link between the refractive index in the OMA context and previous results about the residual shift, one may start from the total phase of the EM field. The expression of the vector potential $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ given by Eq. (4.36) for a single-mode EM field can be re-written as follows

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2(2\pi)^3 m(\mathbf{x}, t) \omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t)}} \left(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}} \alpha_k e^{i(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x} - \int_{t_0}^t \omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t') dt')} + c.c. \right), \quad (4.53)$$

where Eq. (4.42) and Eq. (4.51) are used. Thus, the total phase of the EM wave is determined by $\varphi_k^{\text{em}}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x} - \int_{t_0}^t \omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t') dt'$. We may consider the observation point \mathbf{x} to be located on the way of the EM field so that $\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x} = kr$ where $\mathbf{x} = r\hat{\mathbf{x}}$. The phase velocity of light is defined as the velocity of the wavefront of constant phase, i.e., the speed at which the phase of a wave propagates through space. One has

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \varphi^{\text{em}}}{\partial r} &= k - \int_{t_0}^t \frac{\partial \omega(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial r} \simeq k, \quad (\text{adiabatic approximation } K \ll k), \\ \frac{\partial \varphi^{\text{em}}}{\partial t} &= -\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left[\int_{t_0}^t \omega(\mathbf{x}, t') dt' \right] = -\omega(\mathbf{x}, t) = -\frac{\omega_k}{n(\mathbf{x}, t)}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.54)$$

For a constant phase $\varphi_{\text{cte}}^{\text{em}}$, one has $r = \frac{\varphi_{\text{cte}}^{\text{em}}}{k} + \frac{\int_{t_0}^t \omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t') dt'}{k}$ and the phase velocity is obtained as

$$v_p \equiv \frac{dr}{dt} = \frac{\partial r}{\partial \varphi^{\text{em}}} \frac{\partial \varphi^{\text{em}}}{\partial t} = \frac{\omega_k}{kn(\mathbf{x}, t)} = \frac{c}{n(\mathbf{x}, t)}. \quad (4.55)$$

This is the velocity of the propagation of constant phase through the medium. By integrating both parts we obtain

$$\int_{t_0}^{t_1} dt = t_1 - t_0 = \frac{1}{c} \int_{r_1}^{r_2} n(\mathbf{x}, t) dr, \quad (4.56)$$

where t_0 is the sending time of signal, t_1 is the arrival time of the signal at the fixed position r_2 . For simplicity and for the sake of illustration, we consider a monochromatic +polarized GW propagating in the z -direction, and the EM propagation direction makes angle θ_k with z -axis. In this case one has $n(\mathbf{x}, t) = n(z, t) = 1 + \frac{1}{2}h_+(t - z/c) \sin^2 \theta$ (see Eq. (4.50)). Since $z = c(t - t_0) \cos \theta$ one has $h_+(t - z/c) = h_+[t(1 - \cos \theta) + t_0 \cos \theta]$. The quantity of interest is the rate of change of arrival time of the EM signal, which according to Eq. (4.56) is determined by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dt_1}{dt_0} &= 1 + \frac{1}{2} \sin^2 \theta \frac{d}{dt_0} \left[\int_{t_0}^{t_0+L/c} h_+(t(1 - \cos \theta) + t_0 \cos \theta) dt \right] \\ &= 1 + \frac{1}{2} \sin^2 \theta \left\{ h_+(t_0 + L/c - L/c \cos \theta) - h_+(t_0) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \int_{t_0}^{t_0+L/c} \frac{\partial h_+(t(1 - \cos \theta) + t_0 \cos \theta)}{\partial t_0} dt \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.57)$$

Here, we have used the Leibniz integral rule

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(\int_{a(x)}^{b(x)} f(x, t) dt \right) = f(x, b(x)) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} b(x) - f(x, a(x)) \frac{d}{dx} a(x) + \int_{a(x)}^{b(x)} \frac{d}{dx} f(x, t) dt. \quad (4.58)$$

We may write $u \equiv t(1 - \cos \theta) + t_0 \cos \theta$, and

$$\frac{\partial h_+(u)}{\partial t_0} = \frac{\partial h_+(u)}{\partial t} \frac{\partial t}{\partial u} \frac{\partial u}{\partial t_0} = \frac{\cos \theta}{1 - \cos \theta} \frac{\partial h_+(u)}{\partial t}. \quad (4.59)$$

Plugging Eq. (4.59) into Eq. (4.57) and re-arranging the terms yields

$$\frac{dt_1}{dt_0} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} (1 + \cos \theta) (h_+(t_0 + L/c(1 - \cos \theta)) - h_+(t_0)). \quad (4.60)$$

Eq. (4.60) has been already derived following the geometrical approach in general relativity, by specifying the light-like geodesics of the perturbed flat space-time metric in the TT gauge [137, 130], which is widely used in GW detectors involving time delay interferometry (TDI), such as LISA or PTA. Basically, Eq. (4.60) is a generalization of Eq. (4.11) which was obtained based on geometrical optics for EM field propagating in x -direction, i.e., when $\theta_k = \pi/2$. Moreover, we may check that for the special case of parallel propagation ($\theta_k = 0$) the change in the arrival time vanishes.

Consequently, the mode functions $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $\nu_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ can properly recover the already-established results of geometrical optics. Thus, the mode expansion Eq. (4.36) together with the proposed mode functions Eq. (4.42) and Eq. (4.51) and definition of the refractive index Eq. (4.45) provide a correct description for the EM field propagation through GWs background. Thus the OMA formalism not only recovers the previous results for the residual phase shift but also lets us investigate other classical and quantum observables of the EM field in a neat way.

As pointed out in section 4.3.3, the GWs medium is birefringent, i.e., the EM field ex-

Figure 4.2: Illustration of the ordinary and extraordinary wave propagation through a uni-axial crystal.

periences different refractive indices depending on its propagation direction. This causes an interesting physical effect, namely birefringent walk-off, which we discuss below.

4.4.2 Walk-off angle

In an anisotropic medium, the refractive index depends on the relative orientation of the electric field vector with respect to the crystal axes. Birefringence is one of the most prominent optical properties of anisotropic crystals. For example in uni-axial media in which the symmetry axis is called the optical axis (OA), the birefringency, i.e., the dependence of the refractive index to the incident electric field direction, is usually expressed in terms of the angle between the propagation direction of the EM field and the OA. If the light ray is polarized perpendicular to the OA (\mathbf{k} parallel to OA and \mathbf{E} perpendicular to it) then only the ordinary index of refraction plays a role and the ordinary light ray obeys the ordinary Snell's law. If the polarization lies within the plane of propagation and optical axis (\mathbf{k} has component perpendicular to OA and \mathbf{E} has component parallel to it), then different indices of refraction affect the components of the field parallel and perpendicular to the OA, and the light ray now propagates as an extra-ordinary light ray, as illustrated in Figure 4.2. For a laser beam propagating in an isotropic medium, the transverse intensity distribution propagates along the beam axis as defined by the medium wave vector \mathbf{k} . In anisotropic (and thus birefringent) crystals, this is not necessarily the case: it can occur that the intensity distribution drifts away from the direction defined by the wave vector. In Fig. 4.2, it is seen that the electric field \mathbf{E} has a component parallel to OA which experiences the extraordinary refractive index. This phenomenon, called as *spatial walk-off*, *birefringent walk-off* or *Poynting vector walk-off*, is associated with some finite angle, called walk-off angle, between the Poynting vector and the wave vector. The Poynting vector defines the direction of energy transport, whereas the wave vector is normal to the wavefronts [138].

The GW analogue medium (within the OMA framework) is intrinsically anisotropic and birefringency can be addressed within this framework. As a consequence of bire-

fringe, the electric field \mathbf{E} and the displacement field \mathbf{D} are no longer parallel when propagating through the medium. More precisely, this leads the wave vector \mathbf{k} and the Poynting vector, defined by $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{H}$, to have different directions.

Given the solution Eq. (4.53) for the vector potential of single-mode $k = (\sigma, \mathbf{k})$, the spatio-temporal dependence of the EM field is determined by mode functions $e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x} - \int_0^t \omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t') dt'}$, neglecting the slowly varying envelope. In order to proceed, for simplicity we take the electric field as $\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{E}_0 e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x} - \int_0^t \omega(\mathbf{x}, t') dt'}$ with \mathbf{E}_0 being a vector satisfying the SVEA (see Sec. 4.3.2). Similar expressions hold for \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{H} and \mathbf{D} . Replacing the temporal and spatial derivatives according to $\partial_t \rightarrow \partial_t \left(e^{-i \int_0^t \omega(\mathbf{x}, t') dt'} \right) = -i\omega(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $\nabla \rightarrow i\mathbf{k}$ (in the adiabatic approximation where temporal and spatial derivatives of the slowly varying functions can be neglected), Maxwell's equations Eq. (4.20) yield

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{D} &= 0, \\ \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{B} &= 0, \\ \mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{E} &= \omega(\mathbf{x}, t)\mathbf{B}, \\ \mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{H} &= -\omega(\mathbf{x}, t)\mathbf{D}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.61)$$

In order to find the components of \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{H} in the presence of GWs, the standard technique is to solve the last two equations in Eq. (4.61), i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{E} &= \omega\mathbf{B}, \\ \mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{H} &= -\omega\mathbf{D}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.62)$$

together with the constitutive equations $\mathbf{D} = \bar{\epsilon}\mathbf{E}$ and $\mathbf{H} = \bar{\mu}^{-1}\mathbf{B}$. This way, the total six components of the electric field \mathbf{E} and magnetic field \mathbf{H} are determined. Some rough investigations show that the walk-off angle is proportional to $O(h)$, however, to our best knowledge, this procedure is not yet investigated in the literature. Nevertheless, we shall not discuss this effect further, but a full investigation of the effect can be addressed within the present formalism, in a separate study.

4.4.3 Some remarks on the gauge invariance

At the end of this section, it is useful to discuss the gauge invariance of the presented formula, since in the next chapter we are going to use these results to establish the quantum mechanical approach.

4.4.3.1 Field Theoretical point of view

From the field theoretical point of view, quantization of gauge fields, such as radiation field or gravitational field, must be carried out with special care, due to the fictitious degrees of freedom stemming from the underlying gauge symmetry. In this case, it is already shown by Dirac and later by Gupta, that the quantization procedure can be done in the

usual way by ignoring the gauge degrees of freedom. However in order to be consistent, there would be some supplementary conditions to define the subspace of physical states in the Fock state representation. In the case of the EM field (as a gauge field), it is known that time-photons and longitudinal photons are not real physical photons, and may only enter the virtual photon processes. In the case of the free gravitational field, it is shown that the supplementary conditions rule out 8 extra degrees of freedom, leaving only two polarization states for the gravitons. Gupta has shown that for the EM-GWs interactions up to leading order $O(h)$, the GW field possesses only two different polarization states, and the time-like and longitudinal degrees of freedom $g^{0\nu}$ are eliminated. However, this is not the case when higher-order interactions $O(h^2)$, such as the self-gravity of a detector is under consideration [139, 140]. Thus in order to study the EM-GWs interaction at the linear order, it suffices to pick up the TT gauge and be sure that the physical gravitons have only two polarization states $\gamma = +, \times$, as described in the TT frame, where time-like and longitudinal components of the metric are eliminated. This is the main reason that the TT gauge is most often applied in the contexts that deal with GWs at the quantized level (see for instance [141]).

In the TT frame, particles that were at rest before the arrival of the wave, remain at rest even after the arrival of the wave. Thus the coordinates of test masses initially at rest as well as their coordinate distance remain unchanged. This is true when test masses are freely falling, i.e., are not under the effect of nongravitational forces. In our presented schema, we describe the EM-GWs interaction in TT gauge, assuming that the EM sender and receivers are in freely falling motion, as it could be the case for example for a drag-free satellite. Even for the Earth-bounded objects, this can be achieved thanks to different suspension mechanisms to compensate for the effect of other forces on them (which is indeed the case for ground-based GW detectors, where mirrors can be considered as freely-falling in the longitudinal direction, at least in some frequency band). Under such circumstances, we describe the EM-GWs interaction within the OMA. This framework respects the gauge invariance of the EM-GWs interaction. Let us clarify this in more detail.

Maxwell's equations Eq. (4.20) together with the constitutive relations Eq. (4.21) are just a rewriting of Maxwell's equations in the curved spacetimes, which are derived from the "gauge invariant" action

$$S \propto \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} g_{\alpha\mu} g_{\beta\nu} F^{\mu\nu} F^{\alpha\beta}. \quad (4.63)$$

Conversely, it follows that the Lagrangian describing the EM field dynamics in the magneto-dielectric media (specified by Eq. (5.7)), inherits the gauge invariance property of the EM-GWs action Eq. (4.63). On top of that, we have shown in Sec. 4.4.1 that the mode expansion of the vector potential \mathbf{A} (as well as \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B}) is in complete agreement with the residual shift of the EM field when considering geometrical optics point of view. This ensures that the mode functions $v_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ are validated to construct the quantum Hamiltonian, which is done in next chapter.

4.4.3.2 Validity of the results

As we shall see in detail in the next chapter, the EM-GWs interaction Hamiltonian, Eq. (5.15), is proportional to $\omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ which is defined by Eq.(4.45). The time evolution of the EM field operators generated by this Hamiltonian is then determined by $e^{-i/\hbar \int_{t_0}^t \hat{H}(\mathbf{x}, t') dt'} \propto e^{i \int_{t_0}^t \omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t') dt'}$. When combined with the spatial factor $e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}}$, this quantity is nothing but the residual shift, as we discussed in Sec. 4.4.1. Consequently, in the quantized version of the theory, this effect is reflected in the time evolution of the creation/annihilation operators ($\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}, \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger$), respectively. Hence, although the Hamiltonian Eq. (5.16) is not necessarily a “gauge invariant” quantity, but the overall effects concerning the phase of the EM field, such as decoherence and incoherence which will be discussed in Chapter 5, Chapter 6 and Chapter 7 are gauge invariant quantities.

So far we have investigated classical properties of the EM field, while it propagates through the GW medium. In the next chapters, we address the question of, how quantum observables of the EM field get affected by the GW medium. In the context of OMA, we have obtained the mode solutions of the EM field. We exploit these solutions to establish a quantum theory of interaction between the EM field and GWs.

4.5 Summary and conclusions

In this chapter, we described the interaction of EM field with GWs, within geometrical optics as well as OMA frameworks. Some of the main results can be summarized as follows:

- In a geometrical optics investigation, we found the null geodesics that describing the propagation of the EM field and showed that GWs induce a Doppler shift to the EM frequency, \mathcal{Z}_h , which can be measured through the rate of change of arrival time of a signal that propagates between two points.
- Then, we applied the OMA framework to solve Maxwell’s equations in the presence of GWs. We showed that GWs generally act as an inhomogeneous, anisotropic, time-dependent magneto-dielectric media, specified by the permittivity and permeability tensors $\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)/\varepsilon_0 = \mu_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)/\mu_0 = \delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$. With the help of adiabatic approximation, $\Omega_K \ll \omega_k$ and $\lambda_K \gg \lambda_k$, we could find out the mode expansion of the vector potential.
- We identified the refractive index of the GWs’ medium, which entails the physical effects of GWs on the EM frequency and phase.
- We verified that the solutions for the vector potential can properly reproduce the results of geometrical optics. Thus, we may promote the present framework to investigate the quantum field theory of EM-GWs interaction. Some remarks about the gauge invariance of the results were discussed.

- Other classical quantities of the EM field, concerning external degrees of freedom such as its polarization and orbital angular momentum, may be investigated in detail, within the presented method.

Chapter 5

Interaction between GWs and EM field: quantum version

We saw in Chapter 2 and Chapter 3 that inflationary-generated PGWs bear quantum mechanical features. That to which extent these fluctuations preserved their quantumness has been a subject of studies, and detection of the non-classicality of primordial perturbations are typically grounded on quantum information theoretical basis and its implications on the CMB observables [91, 95]. However, we shall initiate a different approach to search for the quantum nature of primordial tensor perturbations using a generic electromagnetic probe that propagates on arbitrary scales, namely from typical GWs scales up to several thousand Mpc. In Chapter 4, we investigated the propagation of EM field in the presence of GWs, at the classical level. We used the adiabatic approximation to find the mode solutions of the EM field expansion. As a result of interaction with GWs, both internal and external EM field degrees of freedom, i.e., the phase and polarization, undergo alteration. Indeed we have seen that under the adiabatic condition, the wave vector is still \mathbf{k} as implied by the spatial mode functions $\mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, while the existence of GWs changes the temporal mode functions involved in $\nu_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$. In the rest of the dissertation, we consider only the internal degree of freedom of the EM field, that is relevant to its phase.

As we finally aim at detecting *quantum* features of GWs, we should promote the description to a fully quantum mechanical one, wherein both EM and GWs (in linearized theory) are considered as quantum entities. In this chapter, following the standard QFT methods, we derive the corresponding EM-GWs interaction Hamiltonian. It follows that the EM-GWs interaction Hamiltonian reassembles the cavity opto-mechanics interaction which is fully developed in the literature of quantum optics. We try to describe the analogy in detail and benefit from well-established techniques to derive the Heisenberg equations of motion for the EM field and solve it to find the time evolution of the ladder operators of the field. Not only does the analogy help us better perceive the EM-GWs interaction, but also it suggests that one may reveal the quantum nature of GWs in the same way that the quantum mechanical behavior of mesoscopic objects has been recently revealed by means of opto-mechanical setups [142]. This analogy helps us examine quantum observables

of the EM field in different situations. As the first example of the present framework, we address the evolution of quadrature variance of the EM field in the presence of GWs placed in different states, namely vacuum fluctuations, coherent, one-mode squeezed and two-mode squeezed, and thermal states. We explicitly show that witnessing the quantum nature of GWs based on optical squeezing, as proposed in the literature, seems out of reach, firstly due to the negligibly small EM-GWs coupling strength that requires unrealistically large observation time to witness any coherent dynamics induced by PGWs, and secondly due to the fact that the EM field undergoes decoherence induced by GWs, well before any coherent dynamic can happen. This leads us to a comprehensive investigation of the temporal and spatial correlations of the EM field in the presence of GWs, in subsequent chapters.

5.1 Hamiltonian formalism

In this section, we derive the Hamiltonian of the whole system by considering EM and GW fields as two sub-systems coupled to each other, within the OMA framework. We start by the total Lagrangian density $\mathcal{L}_{\text{tot}} \equiv \mathcal{L}_{\text{gw}}^{(0)} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{em}}^{(0)} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{int}}$ where $L_{\text{tot}} = \int d^3\mathbf{x} \mathcal{L}_{\text{tot}}$ gives the total Lagrangian of the system. In the following, we shall derive an explicit expression for the Lagrangian density of the total system.

5.1.1 Canonical quantization of linearized gravitational waves

We have seen in Sec. 4.1.1 that perturbations to the Minkowski spacetime, denoted by h_{ij} , satisfy the d'Alembert equation in the TT gauge. One could equivalently start from the perturbed Einstein-Hilbert action, and derive the equation of motion for the perturbations. In this way, one may straightforwardly show that the free dynamics of GWs can be derived from the following Lagrangian density [135, 143]

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{gw}}^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{c^4}{64\pi G} \left(\frac{1}{c^2} (\dot{h}_{ij})^2 - (\partial_l h_{ij})^2 \right), \quad (5.1)$$

which results in d'Alembert equation for the tensor field h_{ij} (see Sec. 4.1.1). Indeed, this Lagrangian could also be derived from the Lagrangian of tensor perturbations in FLRW background Eq. (2.37) by substituting $d\eta = cdt/a(\eta)$, $a(\eta) = 1$ (in Minkowski spacetime) and replacing $M_{\text{pl}}^2 \rightarrow M_{\text{pl}}^2 c^2/\hbar$ and $M_{\text{pl}} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c}{8\pi G}}$. Thus, the quantization of tensor perturbations in Minkowski spacetime can be straightly done, as in Chapter 2, without further effort. However, here we introduce an equivalent way of quantization of GWs which is essentially the same procedure covered in Chapter 2. The difference comes from the choice of canonical variables describing h_{ij} . In the setup of Chapter 2, we first expanded the perturbation field h_{ij} based on Fourier modes and the quantization was directly performed on the temporal mode solutions $\chi_{\mathbf{K}}^\gamma(\eta) = a(\eta)h_{\mathbf{K}}^\gamma(\eta)$. The commutators were defined based on $\chi_{\mathbf{K}}^\gamma(\eta)$ and its conjugate momenta. It turned out that, there are two degrees of freedom

for $\chi_{\mathbf{K}}^\gamma$ corresponding to two different helicities of GWs. Here, we start by considering the field components $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ themselves as free degrees of freedom of the EM field, while we already know that a single-mode \mathbf{K} has only two degrees of freedom, i.e., the + and \times polarizations, as we discussed in Sec. 4.1.1. However, both methods give rise to the same results for the quantized tensor field \hat{h}_{ij} and hence the correlation functions of the GWs. This procedure was used in our publication [1] and here we mention it to emphasize that essentially there is no difference between these two methods.

With the help of the classical Lagrangian Eq. (5.1), one may define the canonical conjugate momentum of h_{ij} according to $\Xi_{ij} \equiv \partial \mathcal{L}_{\text{gw}} / \partial \dot{h}_{ij} = c^2 / (32\pi G) \dot{h}_{ij}$. The most general expression of $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is given by Eq. (4.5). In quantum description, one promotes h_{ij} and Ξ_{ij} to quantum operators and conventionally expands them in terms of the ladder operators

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) &= C \sum_{\gamma=+, \times} \int \frac{d^3 \mathbf{K}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \frac{e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}]}{\sqrt{2\Omega_K}} (\hat{b}_K e^{-i(\Omega t - \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x})} + \hat{b}_K^\dagger e^{i(\Omega t - \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x})}), \\ \hat{\Xi}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) &= (-i) \frac{c^2 C}{32\pi G} \sum_{\gamma=+, \times} \int \frac{d^3 \mathbf{K}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \sqrt{\frac{\Omega_K}{2}} e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] (\hat{b}_K e^{-i(\Omega t - \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x})} - \hat{b}_K^\dagger e^{i(\Omega t - \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x})}), \end{aligned} \quad (5.2)$$

where $\Omega_K = c|\mathbf{K}|$ and $K \equiv (\mathbf{K}, \gamma)$ stands for GW mode with wave vector \mathbf{K} and polarization γ , abbreviately. The ladder operators ($\hat{b}_K, \hat{b}_K^\dagger$) are associated to the mode (\mathbf{K}, γ) and the constant C has to be determined. Following the standard QFT approach, we impose the following equal time commutation relation between h_{ij} and its conjugate momentum,

$$[\hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t), \hat{\Xi}_{lk}(\mathbf{x}', t)] = i\hbar \delta_{il} \delta_{jk} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'). \quad (5.3)$$

By plugging Eq. (5.2) into Eq. (5.3) one finds the constant $C = \sqrt{16\pi c} \ell_{Pl} = \sqrt{16\pi c^3} (\hbar/E_{Pl})$, where $\ell_{Pl} = \sqrt{\hbar G/c^3}$ is the Planck length, and the bosonic commutation relation

$$[\hat{b}_{K,\gamma}, \hat{b}_{K',\gamma'}^\dagger] = \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}'), \quad (5.4)$$

outcomes. The constant C is in complete agreement with that of Eq. (2.63) (by setting $a(\eta) = 1$ in that setup), thus the field expansion Eq. (5.2) together with the commutator Eq. (5.3) provides an equivalent way of quantization of GWs. Using the Legendre transformation of the Lagrangian Eq. (5.1), one may obtain the Hamiltonian of free GWs as

$$\hat{H}_{\text{gw}}^{(0)} = \frac{1}{2} \int d^3 \mathbf{x} \left(\frac{32\pi G}{c^2} \Xi_{ij}^2 + \frac{c^4}{32\pi G} (\partial_l h_{ij})^2 \right). \quad (5.5)$$

Substituting Eq. (5.2) into the Hamiltonian Eq. (5.5), the quantized Hamiltonian in terms of the ladder operators becomes

$$\hat{H}_{\text{gw}}^{(0)} = \sum_{\gamma=+, \times} \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \hbar \Omega_K \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K},\gamma}^\dagger \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K},\gamma}, \quad (5.6)$$

which describes free evolution of GWs. Note that, the dimensionality of the ladder operators is $\dim[\hat{b}_K] = V^{1/2}$ so that the dimensionality of the Hamiltonian is energy. Thus, each GWs' mode is simply described by a harmonic oscillator the corresponding Hilbert space of which is spanned by the Fock states, as previously described in Chapter 2.

Note that throughout our investigations, we always assume GWs to evolve *freely*, in the sense that (i) we do not take into account the back-action of EM field on GWs (that means, we do not consider the possible effect of energy-momentum tensor of the EM field on the curvature of spacetime), and (ii) we ignore the expansion of the Universe while the EM field is propagating through GWs medium. Basically, the present formalism is quite general and describes any GW background in its quantum version, provided that the present state of GWs is known. However, in the dissertation, our main focus is dedicated to the inflationary-generated PGWs, and we aim to describe the effect of PGWs on the EM dynamics. We saw in Chapter 3 that when PGWs modes enter the horizon scale, their amplitude suffers decreasing by the expansion of the Universe as $1/a(\eta)$. The present spectral amplitude $h(K, \eta_H)$ of PGWs is given by Eq. (3.40). Thus, the decay of spectral amplitude during the EM-GWs interaction is proportional to the ratio $\frac{a(\eta_{em})}{a(\eta_H)}$ with $a(\eta_{em})$ and $a(\eta_H)$ being the scale factor at emission time η_{em} and detection time η_H (at the present) so that $\eta_{int} = \eta_H - \eta_{em}$ is the EM-GWs interaction in conformal time. For typical scales involved in GW detectors, this ratio is ~ 1 and there is no remarkable reduction. For sources of cosmological distances (as we target in Chapter 7), one may assume that the source is located at redshift z . By definition one has $1 + z = \frac{a(\eta_H)}{a(\eta_{em})}$. Considering the redshift range $0 \lesssim z \lesssim 10$, the present value of the spectral amplitude would be $\frac{h(K, \eta_H)}{h(K, \eta_{em})} = \frac{a(\eta_{em})}{a(\eta_H)} = \frac{1}{1+z} \sim 10\%$. However, as we discussed in Sec. 3.3, the squeezing amplitude r_K stays approximately constant, hence the graviton content of the PGWs background which turns out to be the most relevant quantity in determination of the EM field dynamics, stays constant. Consequently, we may proceed by considering the (flat) Minkowski spacetime as the background on which EM and GWs interplay, and eventually enter the effect of Universe expansion on the EM frequency shift as well as on the interaction time (or time of flight) and the propagation distance of the EM source. In other words, we assume that the squeezing parameters do not evolve during the interaction time η_{int} , and the squeezing factor is going to be determined by Eq. (3.56), throughout the EM-GWs interaction interval.

5.1.2 Quantization of the EM field in the presence of GWs

In Sec. 4.2, we formulated the EM field dynamics in the presence of GWs within the OMA framework. The effective gravitational medium is identified by the permittivity and permeability tensors Eq. (4.27). Hamiltonian dynamics of classical EM field may be initialized by the following Lagrangian density

$$\mathcal{L}_{em-gw}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{1}{2}(\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)E^i E^j - \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t)B^i B^j), \quad (5.7)$$

which is a generalization of the Lagrangian introduced in [132] to the case of inhomogeneous time-dependent medium. One may check that the Lagrangian given in Eq. (5.7) indeed reproduces the Maxwell's equations Eq. (4.20) under the adiabatic approximation ($\Omega_K \ll \omega_k$). The permittivity and permeability tensors ($\bar{\epsilon}, \bar{\mu}$) are equal and given by $\epsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)/\epsilon_0 = \mu_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)/\mu_0 = \delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ where h_{ij} is the metric perturbation component in the TT gauge. These tensors are composed of two terms, including the effect of vacuum as well as the GW background. Consequently, one may split $\mathcal{L}_{\text{em-gw}}$ into two parts, $\mathcal{L}_{\text{em-gw}} \equiv \mathcal{L}_{\text{em}}^{(0)} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{int}}$, where $\mathcal{L}_{\text{em}}^{(0)}$ describes free evolution of the EM field and \mathcal{L}_{int} accounts for the EM-GWs coupling.

In the following, we define the corresponding conjugate variable momenta of EM and GW fields and find the quantized form of the total Hamiltonian. Before doing that, we remind that (i) $\mathbf{E} = -\nabla\phi - \partial_t\mathbf{A}$, $\mathbf{B} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A}$ and the suitable gauge condition $\nabla \cdot [\bar{\epsilon}(\mathbf{x}, t)\dot{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}, t)] = 0$ excludes ϕ . Therefore the dynamical degree of freedom of the EM field is solely the vector potential \mathbf{A} ; and (ii) as mentioned before, the analogous optical medium of GWs is non-absorptive and non-dispersive in the adiabatic regime. The quantization of absorptive-dispersive magneto-dielectric media has been widely studied in the literature [144, 145, 146]. However, here we apply the standard method of quantum field theory to the linearized GWs described by the tensor field of rank 2, and the interaction of Hamiltonian outcomes naturally.

In Section 4.3 we have specified the mode expansion of the vector potential and proper spatio-temporal mode functions were obtained in the adiabatic regime, where the characteristic time-scale (length-scale) of GWs variation is large in comparison with the EM field. In a quantum description, we promote the coefficients α_k in the plane wave expansion Eq. (4.36) to quantum operators,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}, t) &= \sum_k \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2}} \left(\hat{a}_k v_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) + \hat{a}_k^\dagger v_k^*(\mathbf{x}, t) \mathbf{f}_k^*(\mathbf{x}, t) \right), \\ \hat{\mathbf{E}}(\mathbf{x}, t) = -\frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{A}}}{\partial t} &= -\sum_k \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2}} \left(\hat{a}_k \dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) + \hat{a}_k^\dagger \dot{v}_k^*(\mathbf{x}, t) \mathbf{f}_k^*(\mathbf{x}, t) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (5.8)$$

where the spatial and temporal mode functions are specified by Eqs. (4.42), (4.51), respectively. Note that the index $k \equiv (\sigma, \mathbf{k})$ labels the EM mode with wave vector \mathbf{k} and polarization σ . The canonical conjugate momentum of \hat{A}_i is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\Pi}_i(\mathbf{x}, t) &\equiv \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{\hat{A}}_i} = \epsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \dot{\hat{A}}_j(\mathbf{x}, t) \\ &= \sum_k \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2}} \left(\hat{a}_k \dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \epsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{kj}(\mathbf{x}, t) + \hat{a}_k^\dagger \dot{v}_k^*(\mathbf{x}, t) \epsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{kj}^*(\mathbf{x}, t) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (5.9)$$

Note that $v_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ satisfy the SVEA condition (see Eq. (4.37)). The Hamiltonian can be established by performing the Legendre transform on the Lagrangian $\mathcal{L}_{\text{em-gw}}$. The

resulting Hamiltonian is

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{H}_{\text{em-gw}} &= \frac{1}{2} \int d^3 \mathbf{x} [\varepsilon_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{\Pi}_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{\Pi}_j(\mathbf{x}, t) \\ &+ \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) (\nabla \times \hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}, t))_i (\nabla \times \hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}, t))_j],\end{aligned}\quad (5.10)$$

where we used the identity $\varepsilon_{ik} \varepsilon_{kl}^{-1} = \delta_{il}$. The standard canonical quantization is done by imposing the following equal time commutation relation between the Cartesian components of the conjugate variables $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{\Pi}}$ as

$$[\hat{A}_i(\mathbf{x}, t), \hat{\Pi}_j(\mathbf{x}', t)] = i\hbar P_{ij}^{\perp}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}'). \quad (5.11)$$

Here, P_{ij}^{\perp} is the generalized transverse delta-distribution which is a suitable replacement for the Dirac delta function in anisotropic media [133, 132]. Plugging Eq. (5.8) and Eq. (5.9) into the canonical commutation relation Eq. (5.11) yields the bosonic commutation relation

$$[\hat{a}_k, \hat{a}_{k'}^{\dagger}] = \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}') \delta_{\sigma\sigma'}, \quad (5.12)$$

and other commutators vanish. Now, the Hamiltonian can be obtained by inserting the Eqs. (5.8) and (5.9) into Eq. (5.10) and performing spatial integration with the help of orthogonality relation Eq. (4.41). This procedure results in the following expression for the Hamiltonian (see Appendix B.2)

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{H}_{\text{em-gw}} &= \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\hbar}{2} \sum_{\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'} \left\{ \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'} \int d^3 \mathbf{x} (\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{\mathbf{k}i} f_{\mathbf{k}'j} \dot{v}_k \dot{v}_{k'} + \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) v_k v_{k'} (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}})_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'})_j) \right. \\ &+ \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'}^{\dagger} \int d^3 \mathbf{x} (\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{\mathbf{k}i} f_{\mathbf{k}'j}^* \dot{v}_k \dot{v}_{k'}^* + \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) v_k v_{k'}^* (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}})_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'}^*)_j) \\ &+ \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^{\dagger} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'} \int d^3 \mathbf{x} (\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{\mathbf{k}i}^* f_{\mathbf{k}'j} \dot{v}_k^* \dot{v}_{k'} + \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) v_k^* v_{k'} (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}}^*)_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'})_j) \\ &\left. + \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^{\dagger} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'}^{\dagger} \int d^3 \mathbf{x} (\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{\mathbf{k}i}^* f_{\mathbf{k}'j}^* \dot{v}_k^* \dot{v}_{k'}^* + \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) v_k^* v_{k'}^* (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}}^*)_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'}^*)_j) \right\}. \quad (5.13)\end{aligned}$$

The integration over spatial coordinates is taken over the volume V where the interaction between EM field and GWs takes place. In order to calculate the spatial integration, we use the adiabatic approximation $K \ll k$. With the help of spatial mode functions $\mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ that we obtained in Sec. 4.3.2, one may calculate the integrals in the adiabatic limit. This procedure is done in Appendix B.2 and yields the following expression for the Hamiltonian

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{H}_{\text{em-gw}} &= \frac{\hbar}{4} \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \left(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k},\sigma} \hat{a}_{-\mathbf{k},\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{V} \int d^3 \mathbf{x} [\dot{v}_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) + \omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) v_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t)] \right) \right. \\ &+ \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k},\sigma}^{\dagger} \hat{a}_{-\mathbf{k},\sigma}^{\dagger} \left(\frac{1}{V} \int d^3 \mathbf{x} [\dot{v}_k^{*2}(\mathbf{x}, t) + \omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) v_k^{*2}(\mathbf{x}, t)] \right) \\ &\left. + \left(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k},\sigma}^{\dagger} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k},\sigma} + \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k},\sigma} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k},\sigma}^{\dagger} \right) \left(\frac{1}{V} \int d^3 \mathbf{x} [|\dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)|^2 + \omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) |v_k(\mathbf{x}, t)|^2] \right) \right). \quad (5.14)\end{aligned}$$

Thus, the Hamiltonian depends explicitly on time, and in general, it does not possess time-independent eigenvectors. We already discussed a time-dependent Hamiltonian and its subtleties in Chapter 2 when we considered the problem of graviton creation in the early Universe. Nevertheless, we can still define the instantaneous vacuum at a given time t_0 by $|_{(t_0)}0\rangle$, as the lowest energy state which minimizes the Hamiltonian $\hat{H}(t_0)$ at time t_0 [104]. Consequently, by minimizing the expectation value $\langle \hat{H}(t_0) \rangle$ with respect to mode function $v_k(\mathbf{x}, t_0)$, one can show that the following mode functions

$$v_k(\mathbf{x}, t_0) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t_0)}} e^{i\eta_k(\mathbf{x}, t_0)} \quad , \quad \dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}, t_0) = i\omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t_0)v_k(\mathbf{x}, t_0), \quad (5.15)$$

are the preferred mode functions that determine the vacuum at a particular moment of time t_0 (this problem is described and solved in detail in [104]). Here, $\eta_k(\mathbf{x}, t_0)$ is a function of time which, in the adiabatic approximation $\Omega_K \ll \omega_k$, coincides with the WKB solution given by Eq. (4.51). By plugging the adiabatic mode functions Eq. (4.51) into the Hamiltonian Eq. (5.14), we obtain the diagonalized Hamiltonian at a given moment of time as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}_{\text{em-gw}} &= \hbar \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \left(\frac{1}{V} \int d^3\mathbf{x} \omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \right) (\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} + \frac{1}{2}) \\ &= \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \hbar \omega_k \left(\frac{1}{V} \int d^3\mathbf{x} [1 - \frac{1}{2} \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j] \right) (\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} + \frac{1}{2}). \end{aligned} \quad (5.16)$$

in the adiabatic approximation. Here, the EM frequency in the presence of GWs $\omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is defined by Eq. (4.52). In the last equality, we used the definition of the refractive index $n_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ attributed to the GWs medium, specified by Eq. (4.49). Note that, the time dependence of the Hamiltonian Eq. (5.16) originates from the time dependence of the EM frequency in the presence of GWs, which satisfies SVEA. Moreover, integration on spatial coordinates should be performed on the volume of interaction between GWs, which depends on the spatial profile of the EM field.

In experimental situations concerning the coherent laser beam, or cavity electromagnetic, one can assume a rectangular shape for the EM profile with lengths L_x , L_y and L_z . In most practical situations, the transverse profile can be assumed a constant while the EM field has dynamics only in one direction, say the z -direction. Thus, without loss of generality, we assume that the EM wave propagates along the z -direction, while it has a transverse profile laying on the $x-y$ plane. This situation is shown in Fig. 5.1. In Fig. 5.1, $L_i \equiv x_i^f - x_i^o$ where $i = x, y, z$ and the vector $\mathbf{L} = (L_x, L_y, L_z)$ shows the size of the EM probe so that the interaction with GWs takes place within the volume $V = L_x L_y L_z$. The initial and final points are defined by \mathbf{x}^o and \mathbf{x}^f . In this way, the EM-GW Hamiltonian generally depends on \mathbf{x}^o and \mathbf{x}^f as well as t . In particular, spatial-dependence is important when the typical size of propagation of the EM field is comparable to the GWs' wavelength and time-delay effects become important (see the discussion given in Sec. 4.1.1).

Figure 5.1: The interaction between a plane wave and GWs takes place within the volume $V = L_x L_y L_z$.

Besides, note that the term $\frac{1}{2}\hbar\omega_k$ in Eq. (5.16) denotes the zero-point energy of the EM field which can be suppressed since it does not take part in quantum dynamics (we remind the Heisenberg equation $\hat{a}_k = i/\hbar[\hat{H}, \hat{a}_k]$). Using the expression Eq. (5.2) for $\hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, one has

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{1}{V} \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} \omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t) &= \frac{1}{V} \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} \omega_k \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j\right) & (5.17) \\
 &= \omega_k - \frac{\omega_k C}{2V(2\pi)^{3/2}} \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \frac{e_{ij}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}]}{\sqrt{2\Omega}} \left(\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} e^{-i\Omega t} \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} e^{i\mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x}} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} e^{i\Omega t} \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} e^{-i\mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x}} \right) \\
 &= \omega_k \left(1 - \frac{C}{2(2\pi)^{3/2}} \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \frac{e_{ij}^{\gamma}[\mathbf{K}] \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j}{\sqrt{2\Omega}} \left(\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} e^{-i\Omega t} g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. + \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} e^{i\Omega t} g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) \right) \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

Here we have defined the spatial function $g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^0, \mathbf{x}^f)$ according to

$$\begin{aligned}
g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^0, \mathbf{x}^f) &\equiv \frac{1}{V} \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}} \\
&= \frac{1}{V} \frac{e^{iK_x x^f} - e^{iK_x x^0}}{iK_x} \cdot \frac{e^{iK_y y^f} - e^{iK_y y^0}}{iK_y} \cdot \frac{e^{iK_z z^f} - e^{iK_z z^0}}{iK_z} \\
&= \frac{e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}^0}}{V} (x^f - x^0)(y^f - y^0)(z^f - z^0) \\
&\times \frac{e^{iK_x(x^f - x^0)} - 1}{iK_x(x^f - x^0)} \cdot \frac{e^{iK_y(y^f - y^0)} - 1}{iK_y(y^f - y^0)} \cdot \frac{e^{iK_z(z^f - z^0)} - 1}{iK_z(z^f - z^0)} \\
&= e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}^0} \prod_{i=1}^3 \frac{e^{iK_i(x_i^f - x_i^0)} - 1}{iK_i(x_i^f - x_i^0)} \\
&= e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}^0} \prod_{i=1}^3 g_{K_i}(x_i^f - x_i^0). \tag{5.18}
\end{aligned}$$

In the above equation, \mathbf{x}^0 and \mathbf{x}^f show the edges of the interaction volume so that $L_i = x_i^f - x_i^0$ (see Fig. 5.1). In the last line of Eq. (5.18) we have defined

$$g_{K_i}(x_i^f - x_i^0) \equiv \frac{e^{iK_i(x_i^f - x_i^0)} - 1}{iK_i(x_i^f - x_i^0)}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3. \tag{5.19}$$

In the limit that the length of the detector is small compared to GWs wavelength, one has $K_i(x_i^f - x_i^0) = K_i L_i \ll 1$ and $g_{K_i}(x_i^f - x_i^0)$ reduces to unity. As long as we consider EM probes such as laser fields, whose transverse spatial extensions are negligible with respect to the GWs wave length, one can apply the paraxial approximation and assume that the interaction volume is confined to a trajectory with starting and ending points z_0 and z_1 .

Combining Eqs. (5.16 - 5.18) yields

$$\hat{H}_{\text{em-gw}} = \hat{H}_{\text{em}}^{(0)} + \hat{H}_{\text{int}}, \tag{5.20}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{H}_{\text{em}}^{(0)} &= \sum_k \hbar \omega_k \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k, \tag{5.21} \\
\hat{H}_{\text{int}}(\mathbf{x}^0, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= -\frac{1}{2} \sum_k \hbar \omega_k \left(\frac{1}{V} \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \right) (\hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k) \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j.
\end{aligned}$$

Here, the classical field $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is replaced by the quantum operator $\hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$. The first term $\hat{H}_{\text{em}}^{(0)}$ describes free evolution of the EM field, while \hat{H}_{int} embarks the EM-GW coupling. Thus, despite the fact that the Hamiltonian is explicitly time-dependent and the vacuum state may not exist in general, in case of a slowly varying GW background the WKB approximation implies that the mode functions Eq. (4.51) diagonalize the Hamiltonian at all times and the particle creation by the GW background is negligible, as previously noted

by Kip Thorn et al [135]. From Eq. (5.21) it can be seen that the Hamiltonian commutes with the photon number operator $\hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k$. Thus, the mean number of photons in the EM field is conserved and creation/annihilation of photons does not occur, as a result of adiabatic approximation. In an adiabatic process where the frequency of a given oscillator changes slowly, the energy of the oscillator E and its frequency ω do change slowly, but the ratio E/ω remains constant, so one can say that the “number of quanta” $E/(\hbar\omega)$ in the oscillator remains fixed [49].

Accordingly, one may calculate the mean energy of the EM-GWs system, given an initial state $\hat{\rho}(t_0) = \hat{\rho}_{\text{em}}(t_0) \otimes \hat{\rho}_{\text{gw}}$. Besides the energy of the photons and gravitons which are accounted by $\langle \hat{H}_{\text{gw}}^{(0)} \rangle$ and $\langle \hat{H}_{\text{em}}^{(0)} \rangle$, the mean value of the interaction Hamiltonian may vanish or not, depending on the statistical features of the tensor perturbations. For instance, if the GWs background is composed of squeezed vacuum (as presented in Chapter 2), one has $\langle \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \rangle = 0$ and GWs do not change the mean energy of the EM field. However, the fluctuations of the energy do exist and are affected by the squeezed vacuum, as they are proportional to the quadratic correlations $\langle h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) h^{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \rangle$ that are non-vanishing for squeezed vacuum (see Sec. 2.4.2). As a result, although the energy and frequency of the EM field are changing, the adiabatic condition implies that the mean number of quanta is conserved.

The Hamiltonian Eq. (5.21) has been used in the literature for a single-mode GW propagating in z -direction [147, 148], though its expression has been given without a rigorous demonstration. In these papers, the authors considered a situation of an EM field inside a cavity whose length L is small compared to the wavelength of the GW, λ_K . Then, based on the qualitative argument that the cavity length L changes as $L \rightarrow L(1 + \frac{1}{2}h)$ in the presence of GWs, the shift of the resonant frequency of the cavity and therefore of the frequency of the EM field inside the cavity is obtained. The resulting interaction Hamiltonian then has the form of Eq. (5.21) in the small detector condition $g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) \rightarrow 1$. However, our approach is more general since it does not require the “small detector” condition ($K_i L_i \ll 1$). It is also applicable for a continuous background of GWs, and not only a single-mode GW. Finally, our result Eq. (5.21) was obtained following the standard QFT analysis, and the appearance of spacetime-dependent frequency $\omega(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is a natural consequence of the eigen-equation Eq. (4.43). Hence, not only can \hat{H}_{int} reproduce the “small detector” results, but also it entails the big detectors. This is important because in Chapter 7 we consider the EM propagation over cosmological scales which are comparable to PGWs wavelengths in the ultra-low frequency band.

So far, we have derived the EM-GWs quantum Hamiltonian which governs the EM dynamics. In the next section, we try to solve the Heisenberg equation of motion for the EM field ladder operators.

5.2 Quantum dynamics of the EM field in the presence of GWs

5.2.1 Opto-gravitational interaction

In order to proceed, we restrict our discussion to the case of a single-mode EM field $k = (\sigma, \mathbf{k})$ with \mathbf{k} and σ being its wave vector and polarization respectively, and ω_k denotes its initial frequency (i.e., in absence of GWs). Moreover, since we are interested in the internal degrees of freedom of the EM field, we may suppress the polarization index σ , assuming a predefined polarization for the EM field. Using Eq. (5.17), we may express the interaction Hamiltonian Eq. (5.21) as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}_{\text{int}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)/\hbar &= -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}} \right) \frac{\sqrt{16\pi c^3}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \sum_{\gamma=+,x} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \frac{F_\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}})}{\sqrt{2\Omega_K}} \\ &\times \left(\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K},\gamma} e^{-i\Omega_K t} g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) + \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K},\gamma}^\dagger e^{i\Omega_K t} g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) \right) \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}, \end{aligned} \quad (5.22)$$

where the function

$$F_\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) \equiv e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j, \quad (5.23)$$

accounts for the geometrical configuration of the EM-GW system. Indeed, the function $F_\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}})$ defined here is closely related to the *detector pattern function* introduced in [119] (see their Eq. (7.21) and also the discussion in the last paragraph of Sec. 4.1.3 of the dissertation). Here, we may define the detector tensor as $D_{ij} \equiv \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j$. For instance, if the EM probe propagates along the x axis one has $\hat{\mathbf{k}} = (1, 0, 0)$, $D^{11} = 1$ and other components vanish. However, throughout the rest of the thesis, we will not use the notation D_{ij} more than this. Instead, we work with the detector pattern function $F_\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}})$ directly.

In the case of a small detector where $K_i L_i \ll 1$, the spatial factors $e^{\pm i\mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x}}$ in Eq. (5.18) are equal to unity and Eq. (5.22) reduces to that of [147]. Note that the Hamiltonian Eq. (5.22) is explicitly written in the Heisenberg picture, since the time-dependence of the tensor field operator $\hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is explicitly included in \hat{h}_{ij} .

The Hamiltonian \hat{H}_{int} describes the interaction between EM and GW fields through the intensity-dependent coupling that is proportional to $\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}$. This leads to either possible nonlinear interactions $\hat{b}_K \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}$ or $\hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}$, analogous to the three-wave mixing process in nonlinear optics and reminiscent of the optomechanical coupling in the cavity optomechanics [149]. This coupling can also be viewed virtually as an intensity-dependent ‘‘displacement’’ of GWs, similar to the mechanical motion of a massive mirror induced by the radiation pressure in a cavity opto-mechanical system. The optomechanical analogy becomes more evident with the following correspondence

$$\text{GW strain field} \longleftrightarrow \text{mechanical oscillator displacement field}$$

In a similar manner to the opto-mechanical coupling, we call this interaction “opto-gravitational coupling”. As a result, the mutual interaction between EM and GWs not only influences the EM field dynamics but also the radiation pressure of the light influences the GW strain field dynamics, as discussed in a different approach recently [141]. However, as already emphasized, we will not consider those back-reaction effects. The main reason is that back-action becomes important when the EM-GWs interaction is on-resonant. In this case, the EM probe may act as a source for the production of GWs [141]. Hence, in the following chapters, we focus only on the quantum observables of the EM field induced by quantized GWs (and not the reverse).

5.2.2 Time evolution operator of the EM-GWs system

The interaction Hamiltonian Eq. (5.22) is basically written in the Heisenberg picture, since we have started from expressions for vector potential $\hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and tensor field $\hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ in the Heisenberg picture with explicit space-time dependence (see Eq. (5.2) and Eq. (5.8)). So, all the ladder operators in Eqs. (5.2 - 5.22) are their initial values, and space-time dependence is included in the mode functions. However, in the literature of optomechanics, it is convenient to start from the Hamiltonian in the Schrödinger picture, which helps us to find the time evolution operator $\hat{U}(t) \equiv e^{-i/\hbar \int_0^t dt' \hat{H}_{\text{tot}}^{(S)}}$ more easily, since the Hamiltonian is time-independent. Should one obtain the time evolution operator, the Heisenberg equation for the single-mode EM field operator, namely

$$\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} = \frac{i}{\hbar} [\hat{H}_{\text{tot}}, \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}], \quad (5.24)$$

can be provided straightforwardly according to

$$\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) = \hat{U}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(t_0) \hat{U}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t), \quad (5.25)$$

where $\hat{U}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ is the time evolution operator generated by the Hamiltonian in the Schrödinger picture, which in general depends on the length of the probe. The total Hamiltonian in the Schrödinger picture can be written as follows

$$\hat{H}_{\text{tot}}^{(S)} = \hat{H}_{\text{gw}}^{(0)} + \hat{H}_{\text{em}}^{(0)} + \hat{H}_{\text{int}}^{(S)}, \quad (5.26)$$

where $\hat{H}_{\text{gw}}^{(0)}$ and $\hat{H}_{\text{em}}^{(0)}$ are given by Eq. (5.6) and Eq. (5.21), and the interaction Hamiltonian in the Schrödinger picture is obtained from the interaction Hamiltonian in the Heisenberg picture Eq. (5.22) according to

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}_{\text{int}}^{(S)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)/\hbar &= -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}} \right) \frac{\sqrt{16\pi c^3}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \sum_{\gamma=+,x} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \frac{F_\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}})}{\sqrt{2\Omega_K}} \\ &\times \left(\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K},\gamma} g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) + \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K},\gamma}^\dagger g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) \right) \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k, \end{aligned} \quad (5.27)$$

where the time-dependence of the ladder operators \hat{b}_K and \hat{b}_K^\dagger are suppressed. Similarly, temporal mode functions like $e^{\pm i\Omega_K t}$ in the expression of $\hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ in Eq. (5.2), and $v_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ in the expression of $\hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $\hat{\mathbf{E}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ in Eq. (5.8) should be suppressed, so that they are specified by

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}) &= \sum_k \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2}} (\hat{a}_k \mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}) + \hat{a}_k^\dagger \mathbf{f}_k^*(\mathbf{x})), \\ \hat{\mathbf{E}}(\mathbf{x}) &= i \sum_k \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2}} \omega_k (\hat{a}_k \mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}) - \hat{a}_k^\dagger \mathbf{f}_k^*(\mathbf{x})), \\ \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}) &= C \sum_{\gamma=+,x} \int \frac{d^3 \mathbf{K}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \frac{e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}]}{\sqrt{2\Omega_K}} (\hat{b}_K e^{i\mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x}} + \hat{b}_K^\dagger e^{-i\mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x}}).\end{aligned}\quad (5.28)$$

where $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}) \propto e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}}$ is given by Eq. (4.42). Thus, in the Schrödinger picture the operators stay unchanged while the state of the system evolves with time. The time-evolution operator is determined by

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{U}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} \int_0^t dt' \hat{H}_{\text{tot}}^{(S)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)} = e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} t \hat{H}_{\text{tot}}^{(S)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)} \\ &= \exp \left[-i(\omega_k t) \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k - i \sum_\gamma \int d^3 \mathbf{K} (\Omega_K t) \hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{b}_K \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{i}{2\pi} \left(\frac{\hbar \omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}} \right) \sum_\gamma \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \frac{F_\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}})}{K^{3/2}} (\hat{b}_K g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) + \hat{b}_K^\dagger g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)) (\Omega_K t) \right].\end{aligned}\quad (5.29)$$

Now, we try to decompose \hat{U} into separate exponential factors. To this end, we follow the trick introduced in [150] in the case of a single-mode opto-mechanical interaction, and generalize it to the case of a continuum of GW modes with a space-dependent Hamiltonian. We define the following unitary operator \hat{T} as

$$\hat{T} \equiv e^{-\hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k \sum_\gamma \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) (\hat{b}_K^\dagger g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) - \hat{b}_K g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f))}, \quad (5.30)$$

where we have defined

$$\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \equiv \frac{1}{2\pi} \left(\frac{\hbar \omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}} \right) \left(\frac{c}{\Omega_K} \right)^{3/2} F_\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}). \quad (5.31)$$

As we shall see more clearly in Sec. 5.2.3 in the quantum dynamics of the EM field, the quantity $\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k})$ appears as a coupling strength between EM field and GWs. From this

unitary operator \hat{T} , one shows that

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{T}\hat{b}_K\hat{T}^\dagger &= e^{-\hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k\sum_\gamma\int d^3\mathbf{K}'\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K}',\mathbf{k})(\hat{b}_{K'}^\dagger g_{\mathbf{K}'}^*(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f)-\hat{b}_{K'}g_{\mathbf{K}'}(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f))}\hat{b}_K \\
&\times e^{\hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k\sum_\gamma\int d^3\mathbf{K}'\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K}',\mathbf{k})(\hat{b}_{K'}^\dagger g_{\mathbf{K}'}^*(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f)-\hat{b}_{K'}g_{\mathbf{K}'}(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f))} \\
&= \hat{b}_K - \hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k\sum_\gamma\int d^3\mathbf{K}'\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K}',\mathbf{k})\left[\hat{b}_{K'}^\dagger g_{\mathbf{K}'}^*(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f) - \hat{b}_{K'}g_{\mathbf{K}'}(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f), \hat{b}_K\right] \\
&= \hat{b}_K + \hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K},\mathbf{k})g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f). \tag{5.32}
\end{aligned}$$

Similarly, one may show that $\hat{T}\hat{b}_K^\dagger\hat{T}^\dagger = \hat{b}_K^\dagger + \hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K},\mathbf{k})g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f)$ and $\hat{T}\hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k\hat{T}^\dagger = \hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k$. For a unitary operator \hat{T} and an arbitrary function $\hat{f}(\{\hat{X}_i\})$ one has the property $\hat{T}\hat{f}(\{\hat{X}_i\})\hat{T}^\dagger = \hat{f}(\{\hat{T}\hat{X}_i\hat{T}^\dagger\})$. Using Eqs. (5.29 - 5.32), one may write

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{T}\hat{U}\hat{T}^\dagger &= e^{-i(\omega_k t)\hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k}\exp\left[-i\sum_\gamma\int d^3\mathbf{K}(\Omega_{Kt})(\hat{b}_K^\dagger + \hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K},\mathbf{k})g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f))\right. \\
&\times (\hat{b}_K + \hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K},\mathbf{k})g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f)) \\
&+ i\hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k\sum_\gamma\int d^3\mathbf{K}\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K},\mathbf{k})(\Omega_{Kt})\left((\hat{b}_K + \hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K},\mathbf{k})g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f))g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f)\right. \\
&+ \left.(\hat{b}_K^\dagger + \hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K},\mathbf{k})g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f))g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f)\right)\left. \right] \\
&= e^{-i(\omega_k t)\hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k}e^{i(\hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k)^2\sum_\gamma\int d^3\mathbf{K}\kappa_\gamma^2(\mathbf{K},\mathbf{k})|g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f)|^2(\Omega_{Kt})}e^{-i\sum_\gamma\int d^3\mathbf{K}\hat{b}_K^\dagger\hat{b}_K(\Omega_{Kt})}, \tag{5.33}
\end{aligned}$$

Thus we may write

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{T}^\dagger(\hat{T}\hat{U}\hat{T}^\dagger)\hat{T} = \hat{U} &= e^{-i\omega_k\hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k t}e^{i(\hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k)^2\sum_\gamma\int d^3\mathbf{K}\kappa_\gamma^2(\mathbf{K},\mathbf{k})|g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f)|^2(\Omega_{Kt})} \\
&\times e^{\hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k\sum_\gamma\int d^3\mathbf{K}\kappa(\mathbf{K},\mathbf{k})(\hat{b}_K^\dagger g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f)-\hat{b}_K g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f))} \\
&\times e^{-i\sum_\gamma\int d^3\mathbf{K}\hat{b}_K^\dagger\hat{b}_K(\Omega_{Kt})}e^{-\hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k\sum_\gamma\int d^3\mathbf{K}\kappa(\mathbf{K},\mathbf{k})(\hat{b}_K^\dagger g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f)-\hat{b}_K g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f))} \\
&\times e^{i\int d^3\mathbf{K}\hat{b}_K^\dagger\hat{b}_K(\Omega_{Kt})}e^{-i\int d^3\mathbf{K}\hat{b}_K^\dagger\hat{b}_K(\Omega_{Kt})}, \tag{5.34}
\end{aligned}$$

where in the last line, we have added an extra unit factor to rearrange the terms. In Eq. (5.29), terms containing $\hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k$ commute with each other. By rearranging the terms and using the property of the unitary operator $e^{-i\Omega_{Kt}\hat{b}_K^\dagger\hat{b}_K}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
&e^{-i\Omega_{Kt}\hat{b}_K^\dagger\hat{b}_K}e^{-\hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K},\mathbf{k})(\hat{b}_K^\dagger g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f)-\hat{b}_K g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f))}e^{i\Omega_{Kt}\hat{b}_K^\dagger\hat{b}_K} \\
&= e^{-\hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K},\mathbf{k})(\hat{b}_K^\dagger e^{-i\Omega_{Kt}}g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f)-\hat{b}_K e^{i\Omega_{Kt}}g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f))},
\end{aligned}$$

we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{U}(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f,t) &= e^{-i\omega_k\hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k t}e^{i(\hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k)^2\sum_\gamma\int d^3\mathbf{K}\kappa_\gamma^2(\mathbf{K},\mathbf{k})|g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f)|^2\Omega_{Kt}} \\
&\times e^{\hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k\sum_\gamma\int d^3\mathbf{K}\kappa(\mathbf{K},\mathbf{k})(\hat{b}_K^\dagger g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f)-\hat{b}_K g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f))} \\
&\times e^{-\hat{a}_k^\dagger\hat{a}_k\sum_\gamma\int d^3\mathbf{K}\kappa(\mathbf{K},\mathbf{k})(\hat{b}_K^\dagger e^{-i\Omega_{Kt}}g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f)-\hat{b}_K e^{i\Omega_{Kt}}g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o,\mathbf{x}^f))}e^{-i\int d^3\mathbf{K}\hat{b}_K^\dagger\hat{b}_K\Omega_{Kt}}. \tag{5.35}
\end{aligned}$$

In the next step, we define two operators

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{X} &\equiv \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) (\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) - \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)), \\ \hat{Y} &\equiv -\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) (\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger e^{-i\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t} g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) - \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} e^{i\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t} g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)).\end{aligned}$$

Using the Baker–Campbell–Hausdorff formula, one has $e^{\hat{X}} e^{\hat{Y}} \equiv e^{\hat{Z}}$ where $\hat{Z} = \hat{X} + \hat{Y} + \frac{1}{2}[\hat{X}, \hat{Y}] + \dots$. It turns out that

$$\frac{1}{2}[\hat{X} + \hat{Y}] = -i(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}})^2 \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \sin(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t), \quad (5.36)$$

and subsequent commutators vanish. Finally, the time-evolution operator reads

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{U}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= e^{iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}})^2} e^{\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) (\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \nu_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} \nu_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \\ &\times e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} t \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}} e^{-i \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} \Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t},\end{aligned} \quad (5.37)$$

where we have defined

$$\begin{aligned}\nu_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &\equiv (1 - e^{-i\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}) g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f), \\ E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &\equiv \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 (\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t - \sin(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t)).\end{aligned} \quad (5.38)$$

One may check that for a single-mode GW in the small-detector limit $K_i L_i \ll 1$, Eq. (5.37) and Eq. (5.38) reduce to that of [147] and Eq. (3) of [150] for the analog optomechanical system.

5.2.3 Dynamics of the field operators

Having obtained the time-evolution operator of the EM-GWs system, we now turn back to the Heisenberg picture. Time evolution of the EM field operator $\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ can be obtained from the time evolution operator as follows

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= \hat{U}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \hat{U}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \\ &= e^{i \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} \Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t} e^{i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} t} e^{-\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) (\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \nu_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} \nu_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \\ &\times e^{-iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}})^2} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} e^{iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}})^2} \\ &\times e^{\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) (\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \nu_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} \nu_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} t} e^{-i \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} (\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t)}.\end{aligned} \quad (5.39)$$

Note that the state of the system does not evolve with time. In the above equation, $\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}$ represents the field annihilation operator before the initiation of interaction with GWs, at $t_0 = 0$, which is spacetime-independent. Using the formula $e^{\hat{A}} \hat{B} e^{-\hat{A}} = \hat{B} + [\hat{A}, \hat{B}] +$

$\frac{1}{2!}[\hat{A}, [\hat{A}, \hat{B}]] + \dots$ one may show that

$$\begin{aligned}
(1) : & e^{-iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}})^2} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} e^{iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}})^2} = e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} + \frac{1}{2})} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} , \\
(2) : & e^{-\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \sum_\gamma \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) (\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \nu_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} \nu_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} + \frac{1}{2})} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \\
& \times e^{\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \sum_\gamma \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) (\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \nu_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} \nu_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \\
& = e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} + \frac{1}{2})} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} e^{\sum_\gamma \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) (\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \nu_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} \nu_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} , \\
(3) : & e^{i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} t} e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} + \frac{1}{2})} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} e^{\sum_\gamma \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) (\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \nu_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} \nu_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} t \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}} \\
& = e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} + \frac{1}{2})} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} t} e^{\sum_\gamma \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) (\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \nu_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} \nu_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} ,
\end{aligned}$$

and Eq. (5.39) can be written as follows

$$\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) = e^{-\sum_\gamma \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) (\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} + \frac{1}{2})} e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} t} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} , \quad (5.40)$$

where

$$\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \equiv (1 - e^{i\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}) g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) . \quad (5.41)$$

Here, $\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k})$ and $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ are specified by Eq. (5.31) and Eq. (5.38), respectively. Expression (5.40) is a generalization of the result of [148, 150] to the case of a continuum of GWs modes, where the spatial dependence comes from the fact that the EM field has a space-dependent frequency. To our best knowledge, this is the first time that this quantity is computed in a general situation of a continuum of GWs modes, without the small detector assumption ($K_i L_i \ll 1$) and with a general geometric configuration (coded in the detector pattern function $F_\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}})$).

The function $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ in Eq. (5.40) bears the contribution of GWs in coherent dynamics of the EM field, and is non-vanishing even in the case of vacuum fluctuations of GWs, when there are no gravitons in the field. We shall see this point explicitly later in Sec. 5.3.2 when investigating the optical variance.

Now, from the general definition of the displacement operator corresponding to a bosonic oscillator, $\hat{D}(\alpha) \equiv e^{\alpha \hat{a}^\dagger - \alpha^* \hat{a}}$, one may identify the *displacement operator* associated to GW of mode K as follows (not to be confused with the detector tensor D_{ij} introduced in Sec. 5.2.1)

$$\hat{D}_K(-\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \equiv \exp\left(-\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger + \kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}\right) . \quad (5.42)$$

where the index K is abbreviation for $K = (\gamma, \mathbf{K})$. Now, if one formally discretizes the integration over GWs modes with the help of $\int d^3 K \rightarrow \frac{(2\pi)^3}{V} \sum_{\mathbf{K}}$, Eq. (5.40) becomes

$$\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) = \left[\prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K}} \hat{D}_K(-\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \right] e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} + \frac{1}{2})} e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} t} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} , \quad (5.43)$$

where the quantity inside the brackets is nothing but the tensor product of the displacement operator of each GW mode. Hence each GW mode interacts with the EM field independently of other modes, as was expected from the Hamiltonian Eq. (5.22). The appearance of the displacement operator of the tensor field in the EM field dynamics can be justified by our intuition about the opto-mechanical system. In a cavity opto-mechanical system, a single-mode EM field couples with the vibrational mirror of the cavity, and the radiation pressure leads the mirror to vibrate. The vibration of the end mirror causes the resonant frequency of the cavity and of the EM field to change as $\omega_k = \frac{n\pi}{L} \rightarrow \frac{n\pi}{L+\Delta L} = \omega_k + \Delta\omega_k$. In the EM-GWs analog case, the strain field of GWs leads change in the EM frequency. This can be understood by noting that, in the TT gauge, the proper distance between two points of space undergoes alteration as a result of GW propagation. One may assume two imaginary end mirrors located at two points, that play the role of cavity mirrors. Hence, the TT observer perceives that the EM field frequency changes as a result of changing the cavity's proper length. Consequently, the appearance of the displacement operator of GWs in the evolution of the EM field can be understood within the opto-mechanical cavity analogy.

In general, the propagation of light through GW background is accompanied by two contributions: coherent and incoherent dynamics. Coherent dynamic is driven by the function $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ which induces coherent phase oscillations, as can be seen from Eq. (5.43). As we shall see later in detail, to determine the quantum observables of the EM field one needs to trace over GWs modes, which includes the calculation of the term inside the brackets in Eq. (5.43). As a result, even if the GWs background is in the vacuum state, the function $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ (defined by Eq. (5.38)) is still non-vanishing and therefore this function contains the contribution of non-commutative nature of the GWs bosonic operators. As we are going to see, due to the smallness of the coupling strength $\kappa_\gamma^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \sim \mathcal{O}(10^{-57})$ for optical field with frequency $\omega_k \sim 10^{15}$ Hz, it seems illusive to detect the coherent effect of quantized GWs on the EM field. On the other hand, incoherent dynamics driven by GWs may get amplified, depending on the initial quantum state of GWs. The EM observables which are quadratic in $\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}$ and $\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger$, such as two-point correlations of the EM field, are proportional to $\kappa_\gamma^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k})$. Nevertheless, as we shall see in subsequent chapters, highly squeezed PGWs generated during inflation that possess an extremely large number of gravitons induce incoherent dynamics with reasonable possibilities for detection.

Before considering the dynamics of quantum EM field observables, it is helpful to rewrite previous results in a manner that manifestly accounts for the contribution of opposite modes \mathbf{K} and $-\mathbf{K}$ in the evolution of the EM field. This step is of course not necessary, but will help us to study the effect of inflationary-generated PGWs in a coherent style with the notations of Chapter 2 and Chapter 3. In those chapters, we argued that since opposite momenta \mathbf{K} and $-\mathbf{K}$ of tensor perturbations are not independent (due to the pair particle production in both modes \mathbf{K} and $-\mathbf{K}$), it seems more easy to work in half Fourier space $\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}$, where all modes are independent. Then we expressed all relevant quantities

in terms of $\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}$ modes. We do the same procedure also for the EM observables, as follows.

5.2.4 Separation of opposite momenta \mathbf{K} and $-\mathbf{K}$ in the EM field dynamics

In this section, we aim at rewriting Eq. (5.43) in terms of GWs opposite momenta \mathbf{K} and $-\mathbf{K}$. We may start from the interaction Hamiltonian in Schrödinger picture $\hat{H}_{\text{int}}^{(S)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)$ given by Eq. (5.27), and split it into two parts,

$$\hat{H}_{\text{int}}^{(S)} \equiv \hat{H}_{\text{int}}^{(S,+)} + \hat{H}_{\text{int}}^{(S,-)}, \quad (5.44)$$

where $\hat{H}_{\text{int}}^{(S,\pm)}$ are given by Eq. (5.27) with the integral limits now limited to $\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}$ and $\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3-}$, respectively. Following the same procedure as in Sec. 5.2.2, one may show that the operator \hat{T} introduced by Eq. (5.30) can be separated into *positive* and *negative* commuting parts, $\hat{T} \equiv \hat{T}^{(+)} \otimes \hat{T}^{(-)}$ with $[\hat{T}^{(+)}, \hat{T}^{(-)}] = 0$, each part is the same as Eq. (5.30) with the integral range $\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}$ and $\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3-}$. Similarly, the time evolution operator $\hat{U}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ can be split into positive and negative parts, namely

$$\hat{U} = e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar}t(\frac{1}{2}\hat{H}_{\text{em}}^{(0)} + \hat{H}_{\text{gw}}^{(0,+)} + \hat{H}_{\text{int}}^{(S,+)} + \frac{1}{2}\hat{H}_{\text{em}}^{(0)} + \hat{H}_{\text{gw}}^{(0,-)} + \hat{H}_{\text{int}}^{(S,-)})} = \hat{U}^{(+)} \otimes \hat{U}^{(-)}, \quad (5.45)$$

where $[\hat{U}^{(+)}, \hat{U}^{(-)}] = 0$. The left hand side of Eq. (5.34) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{T}^\dagger \hat{T} \hat{U} \hat{T}^\dagger \hat{T} = \hat{U} &= \hat{T}^{(-)\dagger} \hat{T}^{(+)\dagger} \hat{T}^{(+)} \hat{T}^{(-)} \hat{U}^{(+)} \hat{U}^{(-)} \hat{T}^{(-)\dagger} \hat{T}^{(+)\dagger} \hat{T}^{(+)} \hat{T}^{(-)} \\ &= \underbrace{\hat{T}^{(+)\dagger} \hat{T}^{(+)} \hat{U}^{(+)} \hat{T}^{(+)\dagger} \hat{T}^{(+)}}_{\hat{U}^{(+)}} \otimes \underbrace{\hat{T}^{(-)\dagger} \hat{T}^{(-)} \hat{U}^{(-)} \hat{T}^{(-)\dagger} \hat{T}^{(-)}}_{\hat{U}^{(-)}}. \end{aligned} \quad (5.46)$$

Now each of $\hat{U}^{(\pm)}$ on the r.h.s is given by Eq. (5.37) in its corresponding half Fourier space, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{U}^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= e^{-\frac{i}{2}\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \omega_{\mathbf{k}} t} e^{iE^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}})^2} e^{\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) (\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \nu_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} \nu_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \\ &\times e^{-i \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} d^3 \mathbf{K} \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t)}, \\ \hat{U}^{(-)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= e^{-\frac{i}{2}\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \omega_{\mathbf{k}} t} e^{iE^{(-)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}})^2} e^{\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3-}} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) (\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \nu_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} \nu_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \\ &\times e^{-i \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3-}} d^3 \mathbf{K} \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t)} \end{aligned} \quad (5.47)$$

Now, the dynamic of EM annihilation operator is determined by

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= \hat{U}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \hat{U}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) = \hat{U}^{(-)\dagger} \hat{U}^{(+)\dagger} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \hat{U}^{(+)} \hat{U}^{(-)} \\ &= e^{-\sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) (\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}^\dagger \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma} \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{2iE^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) (\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} + \frac{1}{2})} \\ &\times e^{-\sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3-}} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) (\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}^\dagger \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma} \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{2iE^{(-)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) (\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} + \frac{1}{2})} e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} t} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}. \end{aligned} \quad (5.48)$$

With the help of the definition of the displacement operator Eq. (5.42), Eq. (5.48) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= \left[\prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathcal{R}^{3+}} \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa_{\gamma}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k})\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \otimes \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa_{\gamma}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k})\eta_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \right] \\ &\times e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^{\dagger}\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}+\frac{1}{2}})} e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}t} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}, \end{aligned} \quad (5.49)$$

where we used $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \equiv E^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + E^{(-)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ and the function $\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ is given by Eq. (5.41). Here, $\hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}$ stands for the displacement operator of the mode \mathbf{K}, γ of the GWs field. Moreover, for real polarization tensor one has $e_{ij}^{\gamma}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] = e_{ij}^{\gamma*}[\mathbf{K}] = e_{ij}^{\gamma}[-\mathbf{K}]$, and $\kappa_{\gamma}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) = \kappa_{\gamma}(-\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k})$ follows. Thus, the final result is given by the direct product of \mathbf{K} and $-\mathbf{K}$ modes, as one could expect from Eq. (5.43).

With the help of Eq. (5.49), in the rest of the dissertation we investigate optical observables. For instance, the expression of the vector potential and the electric field (given by Eq. (5.28)) in the Heisenberg picture are now determined by

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}, t) &= \sum_k \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2}} \left(\hat{a}_k(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}) + \hat{a}_k^{\dagger}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \mathbf{f}_k^*(\mathbf{x}) \right), \quad (5.50) \\ \hat{\mathbf{E}}(\mathbf{x}, t) &= i \sum_k \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2}} \omega_k \left(\hat{a}_k(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}) - \hat{a}_k^{\dagger}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \mathbf{f}_k^*(\mathbf{x}) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Note that, there is a fundamental difference between Eq. (5.8) and Eq. (5.50); the former gives a semi-classical description of the EM-GWs interaction where the EM field is quantized but GWs are treated classically, and the time evolution of the EM field is included in the temporal mode-function $v_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$, while the latter provides a full quantum mechanical description of EM-GWs, where the non-commutative nature of the GWs bosonic operators \hat{b}_K and \hat{b}_K^{\dagger} affects the EM field evolution, governed by Eq. (5.49).

Before proceeding, we first initialize different quantum states of GWs. This will help us to compare the effect of different GW states on the EM field observables, so as to search for distinctions between their imprints using electromagnetic probes.

5.2.5 Initial state of GWs

Throughout our subsequent calculations, the main effort is dedicated to finding the expectation values of the EM field observables taken over different GW's initial states and comparing the results. In this way, one will be able to separate coherent and incoherent dynamics originating from different properties of GWs. The following initial states of GWs are of main interest:

1. Vacuum state of GWs are represented by

$$\hat{\rho}_{\text{vac}} \equiv \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathcal{R}^3} |0_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}\rangle \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}| = \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathcal{R}^{3+}} |0_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}\rangle \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}|, \quad (5.51)$$

where in the last equality, we have used a representation based on the \mathfrak{R}^{3+} modes.

2. Coherent state of GWs are represented by

$$\hat{\rho}_{\text{coh}} \equiv \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} |\beta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}\rangle \langle \beta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}| = \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} |\beta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}, \beta_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}\rangle \langle \beta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}, \beta_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}|, \quad (5.52)$$

where the coherent state $|\beta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}\rangle$ is defined by the act of the displacement operator $\hat{D}(\beta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma})$ on the vacuum state, such that

$$|\beta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}\rangle \equiv \hat{D}(\beta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma})|0_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}\rangle \equiv e^{(\beta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma} \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}^\dagger - \beta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma} \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma})}|0_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}\rangle, \quad (5.53)$$

with $\beta_K \equiv |\beta_K| e^{i\theta_{\beta_K}}$ with $|\beta_K|^2 = \bar{n}_{\text{coh}}(K)$ and θ_{β_K} being the mean number of gravitons and the phase of coherent state of mode K .

3. Squeezed state of GWs are represented by

$$\hat{\rho}_{\text{sq}} \equiv \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} |\zeta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}\rangle \langle \zeta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}| = \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} |\zeta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}, \zeta_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}\rangle \langle \zeta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}, \zeta_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}|, \quad (5.54)$$

where the squeezed state $|\zeta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}\rangle$ is defined by the act of the squeezing operator $\hat{S}(\zeta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma})$ on the vacuum state, such that

$$|\zeta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}\rangle \equiv \hat{S}(\zeta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma})|0_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}\rangle \equiv e^{(\zeta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}^* \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}^2 - \zeta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma} \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}^{\dagger 2})}|0_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}\rangle, \quad (5.55)$$

with $\zeta_K \equiv r_K e^{2i\phi_K}$ being the squeezing parameter, r_K is the squeezing amplitude and ϕ_K is the squeezing angle of mode K . Note that the angle ϕ_K determines the direction of the semi-major axes of the ellipse in the phase-space representation of the squeezed state (see [151]).

4. Two-mode squeezed (TS) state represented by

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\rho}_{\text{ts}} &\equiv \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} |\text{TS}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\eta_H)\rangle \langle \text{TS}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\eta_H)|, \\ &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma} \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma} |0_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}\rangle \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}| \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}^\dagger \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}^\dagger, \end{aligned} \quad (5.56)$$

where the state $|\text{TS}_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta)\rangle$ is defined by Eq. (2.64), the two-mode squeezing and rotation operators are defined by Eq. (2.59) and Eq. (2.60), respectively. From definitions Eq. (5.54) and Eq. (5.55) it is obvious that in a typical squeezed state, a given mode \mathbf{K} is correlated only to itself, while in a two-mode squeezed state, two modes with different momenta (here with opposite momenta) are highly correlated. Moreover, as we shall touch it upon later, these correlations are imprinted in the homogeneity and isotropicity of the correlators of two-mode squeezed PGWs, which are absent in (one-mode) squeezed state.

5. Thermal state of GWs represented by

$$\hat{\rho}_{\text{th}} \equiv \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathcal{R}^3} \hat{\rho}_{\text{th}, \gamma} = \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathcal{R}^{3+}} \hat{\rho}_{\text{th}, \gamma} \otimes \hat{\rho}_{\text{th}, -\mathbf{K}, \gamma}, \quad (5.57)$$

where $\hat{\rho}_{\text{th}, \gamma}$ stands for the thermal state of GWs of mode K . The Fock state representation of the thermal state is determined by the density matrix operator $\hat{\rho}_{\text{th}, \gamma} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\bar{n}_{\text{th}}^n(K)}{1 + \bar{n}_{\text{th}}^{n+1}(K)} |n\rangle\langle n|$ with $\bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) = [\exp(\frac{\hbar\Omega_K}{k_B T}) - 1]^{-1}$ representing mean number of thermal gravitons of mode K [151].

5.3 Optical variance dynamics

In Section 5.2.1, it was explained that the opto-gravitational interaction Hamiltonian Eq. (5.22) resembles the cavity optomechanics Hamiltonian. Opto-mechanics uses high-precision control of optical or microwave fields to manipulate and read out the micro-mechanical motion of massive oscillators. Characterizing which aspects of the optical field can demonstrate the quantumness of the mechanical oscillator is of foundational interest. For instance, optomechanically generated squeezing of a single-mode optical field is investigated as a possible criterion of non-classicality of the mechanical mode [152, 153], which was previously observed in several experiments [154, 155, 156]. However, a full investigation of this problem has ruled out the optical quadrature squeezing as evidence for mechanical quantumness [157]. More precisely, it turns out that squeezing in the optical field could arise even if both optical and mechanical oscillators are considered classical objects, i.e., without considering the effect of quantum fluctuations in both fields. In the following, we first qualitatively describe the opto-mechanical induced squeezing, and then we address the question of optical squeezing induced by GWs and the possibility of its detection.

5.3.1 Optical variance in opto-mechanical system

To proceed, we consider a single-mode EM field propagating through GWs background, starting from \mathbf{x}_0 at $t_0 = 0$ conducted to \mathbf{x} . The propagation direction of the EM field is determined by \mathbf{k} . In the following calculations for the sake of abbreviation, we drop the subscript \mathbf{k} on the field operator $\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}$ denoting the EM field mode. By definition, the quadrature component of the EM field is defined by

$$\hat{\chi}_{\vartheta}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \hat{a}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)e^{-i\vartheta} + \hat{a}^{\dagger}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)e^{i\vartheta}, \quad (5.58)$$

where ϑ is a parameter that finally determines the squeezing angle. Note that here, the space-dependence of the quadrature components is included explicitly, in order for a straightforward generalization to the case of GWs, as we shall discuss in subsequent sections. However, whenever we talk about the opto-mechanical interaction, all \mathbf{x} -dependence

in the following equations should be disregarded. As before, \mathbf{x}^o and \mathbf{x}^f denote the interaction volume as depicted in Fig. 5.1. Then the *quadrature variance* is determined by

$$[\Delta\hat{\chi}_\vartheta(\mathbf{x}, t)]^2 \equiv \langle \hat{\chi}_\vartheta^2(\mathbf{x}, t) \rangle - \langle \hat{\chi}_\vartheta(\mathbf{x}, t) \rangle^2. \quad (5.59)$$

The system is said to be in a squeezed state whenever $[\Delta\hat{\chi}_\vartheta(\mathbf{x}, t)]^2 \leq 1$ for a given quadrature ϑ , meaning that the variance of the quadrature is smaller than that of the coherent state. Here, the expectation value represents the trace over opto-mechanical or opto-gravitational degrees of freedom. We take the initial state of the electromagnetic field to be a coherent laser field, described by the density matrix $\hat{\rho}_{\text{em}} \equiv |\alpha\rangle\langle\alpha|$ with $|\alpha|^2 = \bar{n}_{\text{ph}}$ giving the mean number of photons, for which $\langle\alpha|[\Delta\hat{\chi}_\vartheta]^2|\alpha\rangle = 1$ at the initial time. The variance at a given moment of time t (and at a given spatial point \mathbf{x}_1) is determined by

$$\begin{aligned} [\Delta\hat{\chi}_\vartheta(\mathbf{x}, t)]^2 &= (\langle \hat{a}^2(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle - \langle \hat{a}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle^2) e^{-2i\vartheta} \\ &+ (\langle \hat{a}^{\dagger 2}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle - \langle \hat{a}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle^2) e^{2i\vartheta} \\ &+ 2\langle \hat{a}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \hat{a}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle - 2|\langle \hat{a}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle|^2 + 1. \end{aligned} \quad (5.60)$$

The typical setup of opto-mechanical coupling is schematically shown in Figure 5.2. In panel (a), a typical Fabry-Pérot cavity with a movable mirror is shown, where the field and oscillator are described by \hat{a} and \hat{b} operators, respectively. In panel (b), the behavior of the field variance defined by Eq. (5.60) is investigated in the different schema: the blue and red curves correspond to a fully quantum mechanical and fully classical descriptions of the optomechanical interaction, respectively. In a classical description of the

Figure 5.2: Panel (a): a Fabry-Pérot cavity with one movable mirror described as a harmonic oscillator. Panel (b): field variance as a function of time for the quantum (blue, “Q”) and classical (red, “C”) description, mean-field hybrid descriptions with constant I (gray, “SC1”), Poisson random I (orange, “SC2”), and Gaussian random I (green, “SC3”). All plots use $\alpha = 20$. A line containing two alternating colors means the two corresponding descriptions predict indistinguishable results [157].

opto-mechanical system, the amplitude and phase of the EM field (that are perceived as conjugate variables) become correlated, since the mechanical oscillator provides a moving boundary condition for the EM field, which in turn affects the phase of the EM field. As a

result, even a fully classical description of opto-mechanical interactions, where both field and oscillator are governed by classical physics, predicts optical squeezing. As a result, merely observing the reduction of optical quadrature noise is not sufficient for claiming mechanical quantumness. Note that, another example of quantum squeezing induced by coupling to a time-dependent classical source that one could mention, is cosmological perturbations, extensively discussed in Chapter 2 and Chapter 3.

To describe the quantum mechanical interaction, the intracavity field can be initialized to a coherent state $|\alpha\rangle$ with α real (without loss of generality), and the mechanical oscillator to a vacuum state. The time evolution of $[\Delta\hat{\chi}_\theta(t)]^2$ in quantum description is shown in panel (b) of Fig. 5.2 by the blue curve. It is seen that the field is squeezed for the first few mechanical periods. Then the variance rapidly increases to the stable value $2|\alpha|^2+1$ as expected. At approximately $t = \frac{\pi\Omega_m}{g_0^2}$, where Ω_m and g_0 denote mechanical oscillator frequency and the opto-mechanical coupling respectively, there is a quantum revival where the variance rapidly returns to ≥ 1 for several mechanical periods before again stabilizing at $2|\alpha|^2+1$. There is another qualitatively different revival after another interval of $t \simeq \frac{\pi\Omega_m}{g_0^2}$. The quantum variance again rapidly decreases, this time below 1, indicating optical squeezing. The two quantum revivals are repeated periodically. Hence, “recurrence of optical squeezing” can be a potential witness of mechanical quantumness. In other words, revivals of optical squeezing occur only if both oscillators are considered as quantum entities possessing discrete energy levels. By “quantumness”, one means the necessity of quantization given certain experimental setups, irrespective of any non-classical features in the state as described by quantum mechanics [157].

While both fully quantum mechanical and fully classical descriptions predict optical squeezing at first mechanical oscillations, only the fully quantum mechanical description predicts the recurrence of optical squeezing after a definite time, which drastically depends on the mechanical oscillator period and the opto-mechanical coupling strength, as we described before. In addition, the orange, green, and gray curves represent three different semi-classical models where the EM field is quantized but the oscillator is treated as a classical object. However, the extent to which the mechanical oscillator feels the quantized nature of the EM field is different in each case. First, the oscillator is perturbed by only the mean field, and hence the field intensity I is given by the standard mean-field $I = \langle\alpha|\hat{a}^\dagger\hat{a}|\alpha\rangle$. This is shown by the gray line. Second, the oscillator is perturbed by the energy quanta of the field with intensity I given by a random number following the Poisson distribution with mean and variance $|\alpha|^2$, coinciding with the photon-number distribution for a coherent state. This case is shown by the orange curve. Third, the oscillator can detect fluctuations in the field intensity, but it cannot tell its energy discreteness. I is thus well approximated by a Gaussian distribution with its mean and variance $|\alpha|^2$, where the approximation holds for $\alpha \gg 1$ when the Poisson distribution of I is well approximated by a Gaussian. However, none of these semi-classical descriptions can predict squeezing or revivals of squeezing in the optical field.

The analogy between GWs and the mechanical oscillator (as we discussed in Sec. 5.2.1) suggests that one may expect that observation of revivals of optical squeezing in an opto-gravitational system could point to the quantum nature of GWs. In this case, GWs play the role of the moving end-mirror (depicted in panel (a) of Fig. 5.2) that can induce optical amplitude-phase correlations, resulting to the optical squeezing. If the quantum mechanical description of GWs is correct, the recurrence of squeezing is expected.

The first investigation of this possibility is given by [148] where it is argued that, under very specific conditions, vacuum fluctuations of GW background induce revivals of optical squeezing. In this section, we elaborate on the optical variance in the presence of GW background. We shall take different initial states for GWs, namely vacuum, coherent, squeezed, two-mode squeezed, and thermal states of GWs. We discuss different obstacles that prevent the detection of the quantumness of GWs based on the recurrence of optical squeezing. Depending on the initial state, the evolution of the optical variance will be different, as we are going to explicitly show in the following.

5.3.2 Optical variance in the presence of vacuum fluctuations of GWs

By exploiting the analytical expression for the field operator $\hat{a}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ given by Eq. (5.49), one may calculate the optical variance dynamics given by Eq. (5.60). Given the vacuum state of GWs by Eq. (5.51), one obtains (see Appendix. C for details of calculations)

$$\begin{aligned}
[\Delta\hat{\chi}_\vartheta(\mathbf{x}, t)]_{\text{vac}}^2 &= 1 + 2|\alpha|^2 \left\{ e^{-|\alpha|^2(1-\cos 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{-4\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \right. \\
&\times \cos[-2\vartheta + 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + |\alpha|^2 \sin 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + 2\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)] \\
&- e^{-2|\alpha|^2(1-\cos 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{-2\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \\
&\times \cos[-2\vartheta + 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + 2|\alpha|^2 \sin 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)] \\
&\left. + 1 - e^{-4|\alpha|^2 \sin^2 E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} e^{-2\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \right\}, \tag{5.61}
\end{aligned}$$

where the function $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ is defined by Eq. (5.38) and we have defined

$$\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) (4 \sin^2(\frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}{2})) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2. \tag{5.62}$$

Eq. (5.61) is a generalization of the result of [148, 157] to the case of a continuum of GWs in a vacuum state. We see that the function $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ defined by Eq. (5.38) represents the effect of vacuum fluctuations of the GW background, in the coherent dynamic of the variance since $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ enters into sinusoidal functions, while $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ accounts for the contribution of vacuum fluctuations in decoherent dynamics of optical variance which appears as a damping factor $\sim e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)}$ that tends to destroy coherent oscillations in the optical variance. Note that, the spatial dependence in $[\Delta\hat{\chi}_\vartheta(\mathbf{x}, t)]_{\text{vac}}^2$ is such that it depends on the distance between the initial and final points in space, namely $L_i = x_i^f - x_i^o$, because vacuum fluctuations of GWs are homogeneous and isotropic and their effect on

the EM field does not depend on the location of the detector (we touch upon this point later in Sec. 5.3.3 when we compare vacuum and coherent states).

In the case of optomechanical system, it is argued that since the optomechanical coupling strength is usually too small, one may neglect the decohering function $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ without lose of generality, which is also the case for GWs in vacuum state (note that $\kappa^2 \sim \mathcal{O}(10^{-58})$ for optical frequency). Thus, the function $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ determines the fate of optical variance, in the form of exponential factors $e^{-|\alpha|^2(1-\cos 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))}$ and $e^{-2|\alpha|^2(1-\cos 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))}$. Since in typical optical experiments $|\alpha|^2 \gg 1$, the two exponentials are non-zero only when the cosine terms are ~ 1 . In the case of an opto-mechanical system, this happens alternatively at specific periods, which is determined by the mechanical oscillation frequency and the coupling strength. However, in the case of GWs, the situation is different. Indeed, since the function $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ is too small (it is proportional to $\kappa^2 \sim 10^{-58}$), one may completely neglect the effect of $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ in Eq. (5.61). As a result, the variance starts from 1 at the beginning and remains constant at all later times, as if there is no GW background.

From definitions Eq. (5.38) and Eq. (5.60), it can be seen that both functions $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ and $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ start from zero at $t = 0$ and grow with time. While $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ stabilizes at a value of $\sim 10^{-58}$, $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ shows a monotonically increasing behavior, since the integrand in Eq. (5.38) has an asymptotic linear behavior for large $\Omega_K t$. Still, it has a negligible contribution during physical interaction times (less than the age of the Universe $\sim 10^{17}$ s). As a result, both coherent and decoherent contributions initiated from vacuum fluctuations of GWs can be disregarded.

However, in the case under consideration in [148], the expressions for $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ and $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ are derived under the small detector condition $K_i L_i \ll 1$ and the spatial factor disappears $|g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \rightarrow 1$. Hence, the time-dependent functions $E(t)$ and $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(t)$ are evaluated at two limiting cases corresponding to ultraviolet frequency $\Omega_{\text{pl}} \equiv E_{\text{pl}}/\hbar$ and infrared cut-off frequency Ω_{IR} which could be the Hubble frequency $\sim 2\pi H_0 \sim 10^{-17}$ Hz, and the continuous GWs environment is practically replaced by the modes which have the highest contribution. In this way, the expressions of $E(t)$ and $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(t)$ given by Eq. (5.38) and Eq. (5.62) reduce to

$$\begin{aligned} E(t) &\simeq \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}}\right)^2 \int_{\Omega_{\text{IR}}}^{\Omega_{\text{pl}}} d\Omega_K t = \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}}\right) \omega_k t, \\ \mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(t) &\simeq \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}}\right)^2 \int_{\Omega_{\text{IR}}}^{\Omega_{\text{pl}}} \sin^2\left(\frac{\Omega_K t}{2}\right) \frac{d\Omega_K}{\Omega_K} \\ &\leq \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}}\right)^2 \int_{\Omega_{\text{IR}}}^{\Omega_{\text{pl}}} \frac{d\Omega_K}{\Omega_K} = \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}}\right)^2 \ln\left(\frac{\Omega_{\text{pl}}}{\Omega_{\text{IR}}}\right) \sim 10^{-57} \times \ln 10^{62} \sim 10^{-55}. \end{aligned} \quad (5.63)$$

In the first equation, it is assumed that $\Omega_K t \gg 1$ so that the sinusoidal term in $E(t)$ is suppressed. Considering the frequency range $\Omega_{\text{IR}} \leq \Omega_K \leq \Omega_{\text{pl}}$, this assumption means that $\Omega_{\text{IR}} t = 2\pi H_0 t \gg 1$ that implies astronomically large observation time of around the Hubble time $t \gg H_0^{-1}$. In the second equation, one uses the fact that $0 \leq \sin^2(\frac{\Omega_K t}{2}) \leq 1$

and the worst case scenario ($\sin^2(\frac{\Omega_k t}{2}) = 1$) is considered so that the function $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(t)$ is maximized. Nevertheless, the damping factor $e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(t)}$ becomes unimportant, and only the coherent dynamics in terms of $E(t) \simeq (\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}})\omega_k t$ survive. Inserting Eq. (5.63) into Eq. (5.61) and disregarding the negligible damping induced by vacuum, the oscillatory behaviour in terms of $\propto \cos(E(t)) = \cos((\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}})\omega_k t)$ appears. For optical frequency $\omega_k \sim 10^{15}$ Hz one has $\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}} \sim 10^{-29}$, thus the needed observation time in order for observing the revivals of squeezing is of order $t \sim 10^{14}$ s. Even in this scenario, witnessing the revivals of optical squeezing is subjected to astronomically large observation times, provided that the EM field remains coherent in the meantime, which is practically impossible. As a result, witnessing “quantum nature of GWs” based on the recurrence of optical squeezing seems impossible.

5.3.3 Optical variance in the presence of coherent GWs

Continuum of GWs in coherent state is described by Eq. (5.52) where each GWs mode \mathbf{K}, γ is placed in a coherent state $|\beta_{\mathbf{K},\gamma}\rangle$. The expression of the optical variance Eq. (5.60) in this case becomes (see Appendix. C for details of calculations)

$$\begin{aligned} [\Delta\hat{\chi}_\vartheta(\mathbf{x}, t)]_{\text{coh}}^2 &= 1 + 2|\alpha|^2 \left\{ e^{-|\alpha|^2(1-\cos 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{-4\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \cos \left[-2\vartheta + 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \right] \right. \\ &+ |\alpha|^2 \sin 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + 2\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - 2C^{\text{coh}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \left. \right\} \\ &- e^{-2|\alpha|^2(1-\cos 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{-2\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \cos \left[-2\vartheta + 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \right] \\ &+ 2|\alpha|^2 \sin 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - 2C^{\text{coh}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \left. \right\} \\ &+ 1 - e^{-4|\alpha|^2 \sin^2 E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} e^{-2\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \left. \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (5.64)$$

where we have defined

$$\begin{aligned} C^{\text{coh}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &\equiv 2 \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \Im \left[\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \beta_{\mathbf{K},\gamma}^* \right] \\ &= 2 \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2}(K) \Im \left[(e^{-i\theta_{\beta_K}} - e^{i(\Omega_k t - \theta_{\beta_K})}) g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (5.65)$$

where the symbol \Im stands for the imaginary part. In the last line of Eq. (5.65), we have used Eq. (5.41) for $\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ and replaced $\beta_K = \bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2}(K) e^{i\theta_{\beta_K}}$. It is seen from Eq. (5.64) that the decoherent (damping) and coherent (oscillating) contributions of the vacuum are still present, while coherent states of GWs have a contribution *only* in the coherent dynamics of the optical variance, included in the kernel $C^{\text{coh}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ in the oscillatory terms. We shall see in Chapter 6 and Chapter 7 that the same result is also true for the two-point correlations of the EM field. This means that a collection of gravitons in coherent states does not participate in the decoherence of the EM field. The reason will be that, decoherent dynamics of the EM field are driven by *quantum fluctuations* of GWs. Hence, the coherent state of GWs which is only a displacement of vacuum fluctuations without changing the

noise area in the phase space, leaves the same decoherence effect as in the case of vacuum fluctuations.

One may estimate the order of magnitude of $C^{\text{coh}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ with $|\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k})\bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2}(K)| \sim 5.5 \times 10^{-29} \bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2}(K)$ for optical frequency $\omega_k \sim 10^{15}$ Hz. Therefore, the mean number of gravitons in the coherent state must be of the order $\bar{n}_{\text{coh}}(K) = |\beta_K|^2 \sim (10^{29})^2 = 10^{58}$ in order to compensate for extremely weak coupling strength $\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k})$ and to see a significant effect on the optical variance dynamics. Otherwise, one has $C^{\text{coh}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \ll 1$ and the optical variance reduces to that of $[\Delta\hat{\chi}_{1,\theta}(\mathbf{x}, t)]_{\text{vac}}^2$. Hence, since the effect of vacuum is negligible, we cannot distinguish with an absence of GW background.

Another distinguishing property between vacuum and coherent GWs backgrounds is the spatial dependence of the variance in the latter case through the function $g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)$. Indeed, with the help of Eq. (5.18), Eq. (5.65) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} C^{\text{coh}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= 2 \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2}(K) \mathfrak{I}[(e^{-i\theta\beta_K} - e^{i(\Omega_k t - \theta\beta_K)}) \\ &\times e^{-i\mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x}^o} \prod_{i=1}^3 \frac{e^{-iK_i(x_i^f - x_i^o)} - 1}{-iK_i(x_i^f - x_i^o)}], \end{aligned} \quad (5.66)$$

which not only depends on the propagation length of the EM field $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{x}^f - \mathbf{x}^o$, but also on the point \mathbf{x}^o which identifies the volume of interaction. This feature is an implication of the inhomogeneous nature of coherent GWs. For vacuum perturbations, spatial dependence of $[\Delta\hat{\chi}_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}, t)]_{\text{coh}}^2$ is through $|g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2$ that only depends on \mathbf{L} . The reason can be understood by noting the fact that the two-point correlation function of GWs in a vacuum state is homogeneous and isotropic. In other words, one has (see App. A for derivation)

$$\langle \{0\} | \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{h}^{ij}(\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\ell}, t) | \{0\} \rangle = \frac{8\ell_{\text{Pl}}^2}{\pi} \int dK K \frac{\sin Kl}{Kl}, \quad (5.67)$$

where we have used expression Eq. (5.2) for $\hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $C = \sqrt{16\pi c} \ell_{\text{Pl}}$ (compare with Eq. (2.77) for two-mode squeezed state). As it can be seen from Eq. (5.67), the spatial correlation function of GWs in the case of vacuum fluctuations depends only on the distance between two points, denoted by ℓ , and not on the specific location \mathbf{x} . The same is true also for GWs in a two-mode squeezed state, as it is implied by Eq. (2.77), the corresponding auto-correlation and two-point correlations of the tensor field manifest homogeneity and isotropicity. This feature (homogeneity) in the optical variance is inherited from the underlying GW background in the vacuum state. In the case of coherent GWs, it depends essentially on the process of generating them that respects linear and angular momentum conservation or not. If so, the resulting correlation functions are essentially homogeneous and isotropic and would be reflected in the EM field observables as well. However, for a generic background of coherent GWs, where there is no correlation between different

momenta, the two-point correlation function is determined by (see App. A for derivation)

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{h}^{ij}(\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\ell}, t) \rangle_{\text{coh}} &= \frac{8\ell_{\text{pl}}^2}{\pi} \int d\mathbf{K} K \frac{\sin Kl}{Kl} + \frac{4C^2}{(2\pi)^3} \int d^3\mathbf{K} |\beta_K|^2 \\ &\times \left(\cos[2\theta_{\beta_K} - 2\Omega_K t + 2\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{K} \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}] + \cos[\mathbf{K} \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}] \right), \end{aligned} \quad (5.68)$$

where we assumed the generic coherent state Eq. (5.52) that excludes any correlation between opposite momenta. The first term on r.h.s denotes the contribution of vacuum and respects homogeneity and isotropic, while the second term represents the contribution of gravitons in the coherent state in the two-point correlation function of GWs. This term is manifestly inhomogeneous and anisotropic, due to lack of correlations between opposite momenta. As a result, the inhomogeneity of GWs in a coherent state is reflected back into the EM field observables.

The kernel $C(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ can be analyzed assuming one-dimensional propagation of the EM field through GWs background, say along the z direction. In this case, one has $K_x L_x \ll 1$ and $K_y L_y \ll 1$ and Eq. (5.66) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} C^{\text{coh}}(z^o, z^f, t) &= 2 \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2}(K) \mathfrak{J} \left[(e^{-i\theta_{\beta_K}} - e^{i(\Omega_K t - \theta_{\beta_K})}) \right. \\ &\times \left. \frac{e^{-iK_z z^f} - e^{-iK_z z^o}}{-iK_z(z^f - z^o)} \right], \\ &= 2 \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2}(K) \left[\frac{\sin\left(\frac{K_z(z^f - z^o)}{2}\right)}{\left(\frac{K_z(z^f - z^o)}{2}\right)} \right] \\ &\times \left(\sin\left[\frac{K_z(z^f + z^o)}{2} + 2\theta_{\beta_K} - \Omega_K t\right] - \sin\left[\frac{K_z(z^f + z^o)}{2} + 2\theta_{\beta_K}\right] \right), \end{aligned} \quad (5.69)$$

which explicitly depends on $z^f - z^o$ as well as $z^f + z^o$. In the small detector approximation $K_z(z^f - z^o) \ll 1$ one has $K_z(z^f + z^o) \sim 2K_z z^o$ which means $z^f \simeq z^o$, and Eq. (5.69) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} C^{\text{coh}}(z^o, z^f, t) \Big|_{K_z L_z \ll 1} &\simeq 2 \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2}(K) \\ &\times \left(\sin\left[\frac{2K_z z^o}{2} + 2\theta_{\beta_K} - \Omega_K t\right] - \sin\left[\frac{2K_z z^o}{2} + 2\theta_{\beta_K}\right] \right). \end{aligned} \quad (5.70)$$

Hence, depending on the initial (or final) point in space, the result would be different. Although, it also depends on the specific spectrum of GWs. For instance, for PGWs generated during inflation, the high-frequency part of the PGWs spectrum possesses the lowest graviton content as shown in Fig 3.3, and practically does not make a significant contribution in the EM dynamics. The main contribution comes from the ultra-low frequency part $K \sim K_H \simeq 10^{-26} \text{ m}^{-1}$. In this case, in order to reveal the inhomogeneity of space, one needs to perform the experiment at two points with a distance $z_0 \sim \ell_H$, which is practically impossible. As a result, one may proceed assuming $K_z(z^f - z^o) \ll 1$ and

$K_z(z^f + z^o) \simeq 2K_z^o \ll 1$. Under this assumption, the variance is almost homogeneous on the Earth and is determined by

$$C^{\text{coh}}(t)|_{K_z L_z \ll 1} \simeq -2 \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} k_{\gamma}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2}(K) (\sin(\Omega_K t)). \quad (5.71)$$

In addition to that, the light must be kept coherent during its passage on the Earth. For the largest possible coherence time of around $\tau_{\text{coh}} \sim 1$ s, the longitudinal coherence length is $\ell_{\text{coh}} \sim 3 \times 10^8$ m, which is an order of magnitude smaller than the Earth's radius, $R_{\oplus} \sim 10^9$ m. Consequently, as long as terrestrial scales matter, spatial dependence in optical variance may not be touched. We come back to this point later in Chapter 6 when we investigate temporal correlations of the EM field.

5.3.4 Optical variance in the presence of squeezed GWs

The squeezed state of GWs is described by Eq. (5.55), where each mode \mathbf{K}, γ of GWs is placed in a squeezed state and there is no correlation between different modes. In this case, the optical variance Eq. (5.60) turns out to be given by (see Appendix C for details of calculations)

$$\begin{aligned} [\Delta \hat{\chi}_{\vartheta}(\mathbf{x}, t)]_{\text{sq}}^2 &= 1 + 2|\alpha|^2 \left\{ e^{-|\alpha|^2(1-\cos 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{-4(\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + \mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \right. \\ &\times \cos[-2\vartheta + 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + |\alpha|^2 \sin 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + 2\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)] \\ &- e^{-2|\alpha|^2(1-\cos 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{-2(\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + \mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \\ &\times \cos[-2\vartheta + 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + 2|\alpha|^2 \sin 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)] \\ &\left. + 1 - e^{-4|\alpha|^2 \sin^2 E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} e^{-2(\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + \mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \right\}. \quad (5.72) \end{aligned}$$

Compared to Eq. (5.61) for the case of vacuum fluctuations, one can see that the (one-mode) squeezed background induces *only* decoherent dynamics that appear in the decaying factor $e^{-2\mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)}$ along with the vacuum-induced decaying factor $e^{-2\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)}$. The function $\mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &\equiv \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa^2 \left\{ \sinh^2 r_K \left(4 \sin^2 \frac{\Omega_K t}{2} \right) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \right. \\ &\left. + \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K \Re \left[(e^{-2i\phi_K} - 2e^{i(\Omega_K t - 2\phi_K)} + e^{2i(\Omega_K t - 2\phi_K)}) g_{\mathbf{K}}^{*2}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) \right] \right\}, \quad (5.73) \end{aligned}$$

where the mean number of gravitons in the squeezed state is given by $\bar{n}_{\text{sq}}(K) = \sinh^2 r_K$ and ϕ_K is the squeeze angle. The kernel $\mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ depends on \mathbf{x}^o as well as on the propagation length $L_i = x_i^f - x_i^o$, as this was the case also for the coherent state (see Sec. 5.3.3). Basically, this feature is inherited from the two-point correlation function of

squeezed GWs, given by (see App. A for derivation)

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{h}^{ij}(\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\ell}, t) \rangle_{\text{sq}} &= \frac{8\ell_{\text{pl}}^2}{\pi} \int d\mathbf{K} K \frac{\sin Kl}{Kl} \\ &+ \frac{4C^2}{(2\pi)^3} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \left(\sinh^2 r_K \cos[\mathbf{K} \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}] \right. \\ &\left. - \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K \cos[2\phi_K - 2\Omega_K t + 2\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{K} \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}] \right), \end{aligned} \quad (5.74)$$

Again, the first term on r.h.s represents the contribution of vacuum, which is homogeneous and isotropic, while the second and third terms show the contribution of squeezed gravitons and are clearly \mathbf{x} -dependent. However, as we discussed before in Sec. 5.3.3, spatial dependence in the expression of $\mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ can be neglected, considering terrestrial experiments. We postpone more detailed investigation of the kernel $\mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ to Sec. 6.2.3 where decoherence induced by squeezed GWs is discussed.

As we see below, the optical variance inherits homogeneity in the case of the two-mode squeezed state, as a result of the homogeneity of the correlation function of the TS background, stemming from high correlation between opposite momenta of TS PGWs.

5.3.5 Optical variance in the presence of two-mode squeezed GWs

GWs in a two-mode squeezed state are described by Eq. (5.56) which shows the state of inflationary-generated PGWs (see Chapter 2 and Chapter 3). The optical variance Eq. (5.60) in this case turns out to be given by (see App. C for details of calculations)

$$\begin{aligned} [\Delta \hat{\chi}_\vartheta(\mathbf{x}, t)]_{\text{ts}}^2 &= 1 + 2|\alpha|^2 \left\{ e^{-|\alpha|^2(1-\cos 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{-4(\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + \mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \right. \\ &\times \cos[-2\vartheta + 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + |\alpha|^2 \sin 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + 2\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)] \\ &- e^{-2|\alpha|^2(1-\cos 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{-2(\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + \mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \\ &\times \cos[-2\vartheta + 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + 2|\alpha|^2 \sin 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)] \\ &\left. + 1 - e^{-4|\alpha|^2 \sin^2 E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} e^{-2(\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + \mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (5.75)$$

where it is seen that the two-mode squeezed PGWs only contribute to the decoherent dynamics, through the function $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$. Here, due to correlations between opposite momenta in PGWs background, the two-point correlation function of PGWs (given by Eq. (2.77)) is homogeneous and isotropic, and EM field correlations and auto-correlation inherit these features. The function $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= \sum_\gamma \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa_\gamma^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \left\{ (4\bar{n}_{\text{ts}}(K) \sin^2(\frac{\Omega_K t}{2})) \right. \\ &\left. + \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K (\cos[2\phi_K] - 2 \cos[2\phi_K - \Omega_K t] + \cos[2\phi_K - 2\Omega_K t]) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (5.76)$$

The optical variance depends only on the propagation length $L_i = x_i^f - x_i^o$ and is homogeneous. In the small detector approximation $K_i L_i \ll 1$, Eq. (5.75) and Eq. (5.76) become only time-dependent. As long as terrestrial experiments with the spatial extension of $\sim 10^8$ m (corresponding to the maximum achievable longitudinal coherence length) matters, the small detector approximation works well.

Figure 5.3: Optical variance in the presence of two-mode squeezed PGWs. In these plots, $\phi_K = 0$ for all PGWs modes, and the blue and red curves correspond to $r_{k_0} = 10^{-2}$ and $r_{k_0} = 10^{-3}$, respectively. Panel (a): time behavior of the decoherence function $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(t)$ versus time in logarithmic scale based on Eq. (5.77) (details of calculations are provided in Sec. 6.2.4). Panel (b): the optical variance $[\Delta \hat{\chi}_{1, \vartheta}(t)]_{\text{ts}}^2$ based on Eq. (5.77), where $|\alpha|^2 = 1$ is chosen for the sake of illustration.

To visualize the behavior of the optical variance in the presence of two-mode squeezed PGWs within the small detector approximation, we first set $|g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \rightarrow 1$ in the expressions of $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ and $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$, and we proceed by disregarding the vacuum contributions embedded by $E(t) \ll 1$ and $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(t) \ll 1$. In this case, Eq. (5.75) and Eq. (5.76)

reduce to the following simple form

$$\begin{aligned}
 [\Delta\hat{\chi}_\theta(t)]_{\text{ts}}^2 &= 1 + 2|\alpha|^2(e^{-2\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(t)} - 1)^2, \\
 \mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(t) &= \sum_\gamma \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa_\gamma^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \left\{ (4\bar{n}_{\text{ts}}(K) \sin^2(\frac{\Omega_K t}{2})) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K (\cos[2\phi_K] - 2 \cos[2\phi_K - \Omega_K t] + \cos[2\phi_K - 2\Omega_K t]) \right\}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{5.77}$$

Hence, the variance is always greater than one. Time behavior of $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(t)$ and $[\Delta\hat{\chi}_\theta(t)]_{\text{ts}}^2$ are shown in Fig. 5.3 based on Eq. (5.77) (details of calculation of the integrals involved in $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(t)$ are provided in Chapter 6 where we investigate decoherence induced by two-mode squeezed PGWs). The decoherence function $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(t)$ starts at zero at initial time $t = 0$ and then grows monotonically with time. It stabilizes to the highest value of $\sim 10^{52}$ after an astronomically large interaction time of the order $t \sim 10^{17}$ s. On the other hand, the variance starts from the reference value 1 at initial time $t = 0$ and undergoes sudden increase after a characteristic time scale $t \sim 10^4$ s, reaches the maximum value of $1 + 2|\alpha|^2$ and stabilizes at this value (later in Chapter 6 we shall show that this time-scale is nothing but the coherence time of EM field in the presence of two-mode squeezed PGWs). Here, $|\alpha|^2 = 1$ is chosen for the sake of illustration. With the help of the optomechanical analogy that we described in Sec. 5.3.1, stabilization of the optical variance at $1 + 2|\alpha|^2$ is a typical behavior that is initiated due to the presence of a mechanical oscillator, whether in quantum or classical description. Despite the fact that here we have suppressed the negligible contribution of the vacuum GWs (included in $E(t)$), the presence of TS PGWs leads the coherent laser field $|\alpha\rangle$ to undergo decoherence, after $\sim 10^4$ seconds, well before any revivals of optical squeezing can occur on time-scales of about $\sim 10^{14}$ s (see Sec. 5.3.2). Consequently, it seems that it is impossible to distinguish the classical or quantum nature of PGWs based on optical variance dynamics.

From an experimental perspective, observing this increase of the optical variance requires the EM field to be completely isolated from all other environmental effects, and possessing an intrinsic coherence time at least as large as $t \sim 10^4$ s.

Numerical calculations imply that changing the inflationary index β does not leave a significant effect on the variance, while reducing the tensor-to-scalar ratio shifts the curves to the right, indicating a larger coherence time. This is expected, since a smaller tensor-to-scalar ratio means a weaker PGWs spectral amplitude, hence a weaker EM-GWs coupling.

Another point is the difference between the one-mode squeezed state and the TS state. Comparing Eq. (5.73) for $\mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ with Eq. (5.76) for $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ implies that the homogeneous nature of PGWs manifests itself as the homogeneity of the optical variance, while it is not a generic feature of squeezed state of GWs. However, as we discussed in Sec. 5.3.3, spatial dependence can be ignored as long as terrestrial experiments with a typical size of Earth's radius are concerned. As a result, the two kernels coincide for small

detectors $K_i L_i \ll 1$ and $K_i x_i^o \ll 1$, which makes it challenging to distinguish between one-mode and two-mode squeezed background, by means of terrestrial experiments.

Another example of a homogeneous GW background is the thermal background, each mode of which is in a thermal state. It is well-known that a thermal source is a superposition of individual uncorrelated sources of arbitrary phase and amplitude, hence intrinsically stochastic. As we shall see below, the optical variance for such a thermal GW background is also spatially invariant.

5.3.6 Optical variance in the presence of thermal GWs

Thermal GWs can be described by the density matrix of Eq. (5.57) where each mode K of GWs is in its own thermal state possessing a mean number of thermal gravitons $\bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K)$ (see Sec. 5.2.5). The optical variance Eq. (5.60) when evaluated for the thermal state of GWs turns out to be given by (see App. C for details of calculation)

$$\begin{aligned} [\Delta \hat{\chi}_\vartheta(\mathbf{x}, t)]_{\text{th}}^2 &= 1 + 2|\alpha|^2 \left\{ e^{-|\alpha|^2(1-\cos 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{-4(\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + \mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \right. & (5.78) \\ &\times \cos[-2\vartheta + 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + |\alpha|^2 \sin 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + 2\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)] \\ &- e^{-2|\alpha|^2(1-\cos 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{-2(\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + \mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \\ &\times \cos[-2\vartheta + 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + 2|\alpha|^2 \sin 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)] \\ &\left. + 1 - e^{-4|\alpha|^2 \sin^2 E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} e^{-2(\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + \mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

where, as before, $|\alpha|^2$ denotes the mean number of photons in the coherent laser beam. We see that thermal GWs, similar to one-mode and two-mode squeezed states, contribute *only* in decoherent dynamics, captured by the function $\mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ defined by

$$\mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \equiv \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) 8 \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) \sin^2\left(\frac{\Omega_K t}{2}\right) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2. \quad (5.79)$$

Compared to Eq. (5.76) for TS state, one may check that the contribution of thermal gravitons given by $\mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ is the same as the contribution of the mean number of gravitons in TS state (and also one-mode squeezed state), which is given by the first term in $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ in Eq. (5.76). However, the fact that the squeezed state possesses a specific squeeze angle, ϕ_K , there is second contribution in $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$, which is absent in $\mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$. If one assumes a squeezed state $\zeta = r e^{2i\phi}$ for which $\langle e^{2i\phi} \rangle = \langle \cos 2\phi \rangle = \langle \sin 2\phi \rangle = 0$, similar to the phase of thermal state, one may show that the second term in $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ vanishes, and the squeezed and thermal states become identical. In other words, the spread of quantum fluctuations in the phase space becomes a circle rather than an elongated ellipse, which is similar to that of thermal fluctuations. As a result, the difference between $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ and $\mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ stems from deterministic squeeze angle in squeezed state, while it is completely indeterministic in thermal state. However, both of two-mode squeezed state and thermal state of GWs share the common property that their

two-point correlations are homogeneous, and it is reflected in optical observables. The two-point correlation function of GWs in the thermal state is given by

$$\langle \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{h}^{ij}(\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\ell}, t) \rangle_{\text{th}} = \frac{8\ell_{\text{Pl}}^2}{\pi} \int dK K \frac{\sin Kl}{Kl} + \frac{4C^2}{(2\pi)^3} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) \cos[\mathbf{K} \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}]. \quad (5.80)$$

Again, the first term shows the contribution of vacuum while the second term indicates the role of thermal gravitons in the two-point correlation function. Both terms depend only upon ℓ , thus correlations are homogeneous and isotropic. Again, we may use the small-detector approximation, and disregard the vacuum contributions in optical variance by neglecting $E(t)$ and $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(t)$. This gives rise to the following expression for optical variance

$$\begin{aligned} [\Delta \hat{\chi}_{1,\vartheta}(t)]_{\text{th}}^2 &= 1 + 2|\alpha|^2 (e^{-2\mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(t)} - 1)^2, \\ \mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(t) &\equiv \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) 8\bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) \sin^2\left(\frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}{2}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (5.81)$$

in the small-detector approximation. Eq. (5.81) is similar to Eq. (5.77) for TS state. The

Figure 5.4: Optical variance in the presence of thermal GWs based on Eq. (5.81).

behavior of $\mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(t)$ and $[\Delta \hat{\chi}_{\vartheta}(t)]_{\text{th}}^2$ versus time in logarithmic scale are shown in Fig. 5.4,

based on Eq. (5.81). Here, we have assumed that the mean number of gravitons in the thermal state is equal to that of TS state, i.e., $\bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) = e^{2r_K(\eta_H)}/4$ with $e^{r_K(\eta_H)}$ given by Eq. (3.56). For this hypothetical state, although the overall behavior of the decoherence function and optical variance reassembles to that of TS PGWs, it can be seen that the characteristic time-scale is significantly reduced to the value of $t \sim 10^{-9}$ s. In other words, thermal gravitons lead to a much more severe decoherence of the EM field, and they increase the optical variance more rapidly. This effect stems from different temporal behavior of the decoherence functions $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(t)$ and $\mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(t)$, which turns out as a result of deterministic squeezing phase in the squeezed state, which is absent in the case of the thermal state. As we shall see in detail in Chapter 6, one may use the approximation $\Omega_K t \ll 1$ for the graviton content of PGWs, since the major contribution comes from the ultra-low frequency part of the PGWs spectrum which possesses the highest graviton content. As a result, one may see that $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(t) \propto (\int d\Omega_K \bar{n}_K \Omega_K^3) t^4$ and $\mathcal{D}^{\text{th}} \propto (\int d\Omega_K \bar{n}_K \Omega_K) t^2$ (see Eqs. (6.45, 6.53). Since $\Omega_K \sim H_0$ one has $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(t) \ll \mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(t)$, and thermal gravitons induce a more rapid decoherence.

Figure 5.5: Assuming a hypothetical thermal GWs background possessing the same graviton content as two-mode squeezed PGWs, the temperature of each mode K can be obtained for each frequency. For super-Hubble modes $K \sim K_H$, the temperature can be as high as $\sim 10^{26}$ K, equivalent to $\sim 10^{12}$ Gev (note that $1^\circ \text{K} = 8.62 \times 10^{-14}$ Gev).

On the other hand, if we associate to each mode K of GWs the mean number of thermal gravitons according to $\bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) = [\exp(\frac{\hbar\Omega_K}{k_B T}) - 1]^{-1}$, and with the help of $\bar{n}(K) = \frac{e^{2r_K(\eta_H)}}{4}$ for super-Hubble scales, one can show that $T(K) = \frac{\hbar\Omega_K}{4k_B} e^{2r_K(\eta_H)}$. Figure 5.5 shows the temperature versus physical wave number today. For the ultra-low frequency part of the spectrum, corresponding to Hubble frequency, the temperature could be as high as 10^{26} K $\equiv 8.62 \times 10^{12}$ Gev. Of course, such a hot GW background in the thermal state is hardly probable to be produced in nature.

Comparing the case of thermal GWs with that of squeezed or two-mode squeezed GWs, it can be deduced that both squeezed and thermal backgrounds induce only deco-

herent dynamics and do not participate in coherent dynamics of optical variance. This result seems natural, since (as we will show in detail in Chapter 6), only fluctuations of GWs derive decoherent dynamics of the optical field, and fluctuations of GWs are amplified in squeezed, two-mode squeezed, and thermal states. On top of that, TS and thermal GW backgrounds share even more common properties stemming from their homogeneous spatial correlations. However, another distinguishing property between TS and thermal states comes from the correlations between gravitons in the TS state (and squeezed state as well), which are absent in the thermal state. Basically, in a TS state correlations of type $\langle \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K},\gamma} \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K},\gamma} \rangle \propto e^{-2i\phi_K} \sinh 2r_K$ are non-vanishing (see Eq. (2.71)), which make an important contribution in the decoherence of EM field, as implied by the second term in $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(t)$ given by Eq. (5.77). A similar argument could be applied to single-mode squeezed GWs. Consequently, while the contribution of *mean number of gravitons* whether in the thermal or squeezed state is equal and generally determined by

$$\mathcal{D}_{\bar{n}}(t) \equiv \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) 8\bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) \sin^2\left(\frac{\Omega_K t}{2}\right) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2, \quad (5.82)$$

it is the existence of *correlations between gravitons* in the squeezed state which changes temporal behavior of optical variance and determines the characteristic time-scale of the optical-variance stabilization.

In subsequent chapters, we investigate the two-point correlation function of the EM field at two different points in space-time. In search for a realizable experimental setup to reveal PGWs, in the next chapter, we examine temporal correlations of the EM field and investigate in detail the *decoherence* induced by GWs. Spatial correlations and incoherence induced by PGWs are addressed in Chapter 7.

5.4 Summary and conclusions

In this chapter, we address the quantum mechanical interaction between a generic EM probe and GW background. In summary:

- Quantum interaction Hamiltonian describing EM-GWs coupling was derived, based on the OMA formalism developed in Chapter 4. We tried to explore the implications of EM-GWs coupling with the help of analogy with cavity opto-mechanical system.
- Heisenberg equation of motion for the EM field in the presence of a generic quantum GW background was derived.
- As an explicit example, we addressed the optical variance, that deals with auto-correlations of the EM field, namely $\langle \hat{a}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle$, $\langle \hat{a}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \hat{a}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle$, $\langle \hat{a}^{\dagger}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \hat{a}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle$ and $\langle \hat{a}^{\dagger}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \hat{a}^{\dagger}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle$. It was realized that the optical variance inherits homogeneity and isotropicity of GW correlation functions. For instance,

vacuum and thermal GWs possess homogeneous correlations and this feature is reflected in EM observables as well. In the case of two-mode squeezed PGWs, it is precisely the existence of correlations between opposite momenta \mathbf{K} and $-\mathbf{K}$ that makes the correlations homogeneous, and this homogeneity is reflected in EM field observables. However, a generic background of coherent or one-mode squeezed GWs lacks homogeneity and isotropic, as discussed in App. A.

- It was realized that quantum fluctuations of GWs incorporate in decoherent dynamics of the EM field. For a coherent state of GWs, which is only a displacement of vacuum fluctuations in phase space, the induced decoherence is identical to that of vacuum fluctuations. Squeezed or thermal states for which the fluctuations are amplified, leave increased decoherence on the EM field which is of course dependent on the mean number of gravitons (that basically determines the spread of noise ellipse in phase space).
- While the contribution of vacuum fluctuations is so small that can be safely disregarded, mainly due to negligibly small EM-GWs coupling strength, coherent, squeezed, and thermal GWs may leave an observable effect on the optical variance, provided that the mean number of gravitons in the state, $\bar{n}_{\text{gw}}(K)$, is large enough to compensate for the tiny EM-GW coupling strength. This criteria could be briefly written as

$$\kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \bar{n}_{\text{gw}} \sim \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}}\right)^2 \bar{n}_{\text{gw}} \sim \mathcal{O}(1) \quad \Rightarrow \quad \bar{n}_{\text{gw}} \sim \left(\frac{E_{\text{Pl}}}{\hbar\omega_k}\right)^2 \gg 1 \quad (5.83)$$

- For two-mode squeezed PGWs with extremely large number of gravitons $\bar{n}_{\text{gw}}(K) \sim e^{2r_K(\eta_H)}/4$ with $e^{r_K(\eta_H)}$ given by Eq. (3.56), it turns out that the optical variance stabilizes at a value of $\sim 1 + 2|\alpha|^2$ after a characteristic time-scale, which crucially depends on (i) the mean number of gravitons, as well as (ii) correlations of type $\langle \hat{b}_K \hat{b}_K \rangle$ and $\langle \hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{b}_K^\dagger \rangle$ between gravitons in the state. The absence of correlations between gravitons in a thermal state drastically changes the characteristic time.
- As long as terrestrial experiments involving laser fields of maximum longitudinal coherence time $\tau_{\text{coh}} \sim 1$ s matter, one may apply the small-detector approximation $K_i(x_i^f - x_i^o) = K_i L_i \ll 1$, which cancels spatial dependence of quantum observables. In particular, it turns out that both one-mode squeezed and two-mode squeezed PGWs leave identical fingerprints on light and we cannot distinguish between these backgrounds using terrestrial experiments.

Chapter 6

PGWs-induced decoherence of light

For much of its history, experimental observation of quantum gravitational effects has been little more than an impossible dream for general relativity. In spite of extensive theoretical efforts, no one has succeeded in constructing a quantum theory of gravity. Nevertheless, whatever the final outcome of the quantum gravity riddle, one prediction seems to be rather robust: spacetime as a dynamical variable fluctuates, and these fluctuations cause decoherence in quantum systems, which can be revealed, at least in principle, in matter-wave interferometers (see for example [158, 159, 160, 161]). These fluctuations can be classical, quantum, or both. Usually, theorists explore the field of quantum gravity at Planckian energy scales, which is far beyond the capacity of the current or future particle accelerators. Besides, as a new probe of gravitons, i.e., the quantized energy packets of GWs in QFT, the noise in the arm-lengths of gravitational wave detectors is discussed recently in [161, 162].

On the other hand, cosmological observations, which probe high-energy physics, suggest that the large-scale structure of the universe originates from quantum fluctuations during the inflationary stage, and it is natural to imagine that primordial gravitational waves are also generated directly from quantum fluctuations. Hence, one possible approach to test quantum gravity is to study the non-classicality of primordial gravitational waves. However, as we discussed in Chapter 5, the PGWs background may induce decoherence of an EM probe well before any quantum feature can signify their presence (see Sec. 5.3 on optical variance dynamics).

Generally, gravitational decoherence refers to the loss of coherence in a system due to its coupling to gravity. However, most gravitational decoherence models focus on massive particles in a non-relativistic regime, i.e., the position or momentum decoherence of particles at small velocities is the subject of study. This is mainly due to the simplicity of calculations in this regime - gravitational effects are reduced to Newtonian gravity - and partly because the strength of gravitational decoherence effects is expected to increase with the particle mass. In particular, the study of the decoherence process associated with the scattering of stochastic backgrounds of gravitational waves suggests that although it has a negligible influence on atomic interferometers, it may dominate the decoherence of

macroscopic motions, such as the planetary motion of the Moon around the Earth [163].

On the other hand, investigation of the effect of GWs on the optical field has initiated another way of exploring gravitational decoherence based on quantum optical interference tests [164]. For instance, it has been shown that the quantum correlations in the form of Einstein-Podolski-Rosen (EPR), coded in the polarization of optical field, should survive the exposition to gravitational wave backgrounds, even at cosmological distances [165]. However, a systematic investigation of the decoherence induced by quantum GWs based on quantum field theoretical methods, that are capable of being adopted to various quantum observables of the optical field, is less considered in the literature.

The motivation for gravitational decoherence models is multipurpose. Firstly, the existence of a fundamental decoherence process could be a solution to the quantum measurement problem, and it could explain the emergence of a classical macroscopic world [159]. Secondly, it is a priority to encounter the decoherence induced by GWs in any proposed schema, for it would determine the ultimate possibility of witnessing quantum features of gravity. Thirdly, even if not observed experimentally, gravitational-induced decoherence may pave a new way to constrain the targeted gravitational background.

In line with these motivations, we dedicate this chapter to present a comprehensive study of the EM decoherence induced by quantum GWs, using the framework developed in Chapter 4 and Chapter 5. We have studied the auto-correlations of the EM field, which are correlations at a given moment of time and a given point in space, by monitoring the optical variance of the field. In the present and next chapter, we go one step further. In this way, we examine the behavior of two-point correlations of the EM field as it propagates through the background of GWs. After obtaining a general expression for the two-point (non-equal in time and space) correlations of the EM field, we investigate temporal correlations in detail, where GWs are assumed to be placed in (i) vacuum state, (ii) coherent state, (iii) one-mode squeezed state, (iv) two-mode squeezed state and (v) thermal state. We show that temporal correlations, i.e., correlations between the fields at two instants of time, may get ruined in the presence of GWs, depending on the state of GWs. The *decoherence* mechanism gives rise to a line-width broadening in the Fourier space. We shall derive explicit expressions for the gravitational wave-induced decoherence and line-width broadening. We conclude the chapter with a discussion on the possibility of differentiating between various GW states based on the spectrum of light. Investigation of the spatial correlations is deferred to Chapter 7.

6.1 Spatio-temporal correlation function of the EM field

Having established quantum dynamics of the EM field in the presence of a quantum GW background, we may now address the question: how do correlations of the EM field evolve in the presence of a quantum GW background?

The simplest manifestation of the existence of correlations in optical fields is the well-

known interference effects that arise when two light beams that originate from the same source are superposed. Early investigations of coherence phenomena are due to Wiener, van Citter, Zernike, Wolf, and many others' pioneering works (see [166]). The main outcome of this research field has been the introduction of a precise framework to find correlations between the fluctuating field variables at two space-time points and the formulation of dynamical laws that the correlation functions obey in free space. This stage of efforts eventually led to the formulation of the general theory of optical correlations and providing a complete statistical description of optical fields [166], which we are going to use in the following.

6.1.1 Definition of first-order correlation function

The first-order correlation function of the field, $G^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t_1; \mathbf{x}_2, t_2)$, is defined as correlations between field amplitudes at two different spacetime points as following (we adopt the notation and definitions from Chapter 4 of [151])

$$G^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t_1; \mathbf{x}_2, t_2) \equiv \langle \hat{E}^{(-)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t_1) \hat{E}^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}_2, t_2) \rangle, \quad (6.1)$$

where $\hat{E}^{(-)}(\mathbf{x}_i, t_i)$ stands for the positive frequency part of the electric field operator which contains only the creation operators. The expression of the electric field in the presence of quantum GWs is given by Eq. (5.50), from which one may easily separate the positive and negative frequency parts. Moreover, the averaging $\langle \dots \rangle$ in Eq. (6.1) represents the quantum mechanical expectation value over a given quantum state of the field and GWs. The quantity $G^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t_1; \mathbf{x}_2, t_2)$ is also called as *mutual coherence function* or *cross-correlation function* [167]. The first-order (two-point) degree of coherence is defined by [151]

$$g^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t_1; \mathbf{x}_2, t_2) \equiv \frac{G^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t_1; \mathbf{x}_2, t_2)}{\sqrt{G^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t_1; \mathbf{x}_1, t_1) G^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_2, t_2; \mathbf{x}_2, t_2)}}. \quad (6.2)$$

Depending on the configuration of the interferometric experiment, the expression of the electric field at the position of the detectors can be found. In the following, we consider the typical Young's double-slit experiment as shown in Fig. 6.1 and try to compute the first-order correlation function and the corresponding degree of coherence. Before that, we remind some basic concepts about temporal coherence.

6.1.2 Temporal coherence and longitudinal coherence length

Assume that a quasi-monochromatic beam of light is emitted from a source located at a sufficiently far distance from the two-slit apparatus (by quasi-monochromatic one means the bandwidth of the field $\Delta\omega_k$ is small compared to its mean frequency ω_k). We assume the origin of the coordinate system to be centered at the source. The radiated light is divided into two beams at two points P_1 and P_2 located at positions \mathbf{x}_1 and \mathbf{x}_2 on the two-slits screen \mathcal{A} , with a separation $d = |\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2|$. Each light ray delivers to the point P located

Figure 6.1: Schematic diagram of a simple Young's double-slit experiment. Here, the EM radiation of wave vector \mathbf{k} travels along a path for a time interval t to reach the two-slit screen with pinholes P_1 and P_2 located at a distance $d = |\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2|$ from each other. For simplification, we take the origin of coordinates at the location of the source ($\mathbf{x}_s = 0$). After the division of the wavefront, each wave reaches the observation point P located at \mathbf{x} , after passing a time interval $t_i = s_i/c$. The path difference $\Delta s = |s_2 - s_1| \equiv c\tau$ causes a time-delay τ between field amplitudes reaching P , which can be used to measure the temporal coherence of the field. The interference pattern is formed on the observation screen \mathcal{S} provided that (i) $d \leq \lambda$ and (ii) $\tau \leq (\Delta\nu)^{-1}$, where λ and $\Delta\nu$ stand for the EM wavelength and frequency bandwidth.

at \mathbf{x} on the observation screen \mathcal{S} after a path-difference $\Delta s = |s_2 - s_1| = c|t_2 - t_1| \equiv c\tau$. Here, $t_i = s_i/c$ is the time needed for light to travel from the i -th pinhole to the observation point P . Note that the distance between the two-slit screen \mathcal{A} and the observations screen \mathcal{S} is small compared to $|\mathbf{x}|$. The experimental fact is that the interference pattern is formed on the observation screen \mathcal{S} provided that (i) $d \leq \lambda$ and (ii) the time delay τ is such that $\tau\Delta\omega \leq 2\pi$. The formation of the fringes is said to be a manifestation of spatio-temporal coherence between two beams, which arise from the existence of correlations between them. Thus, the time delay $\tau \sim \frac{1}{\Delta\nu}$ is called the coherence time of the light, and $\ell_{\text{long}} \equiv c\tau$ is sometimes called the *longitudinal coherence length* [166]. For instance, the coherence time of the black-body spectrum of sunlight with temperature $T = 5777$ K is of the order of ~ 1 fs [168], while for a well-stabilized laser beam, the coherence time can be as long as $\tau \sim 10$ s [169].

In the following, we shall derive a general expression for the first-order two-point degree of coherence, based on the setup shown in Fig. 6.1. Then, we focus on pure temporal correlations by assuming $d = 0$. Investigation of pure spatial correlations is deferred to

Chapter 7.

6.2 Temporal correlations of the EM field

For our purpose, we assume that the EM field has propagated through GWs background and then illuminates two slits located at P_1 and P_2 on the plane \mathcal{A} , and the intensity is observed on the observation screen \mathcal{S} . To find the intensity at a point $P(\mathbf{x}, t)$ on the screen, we shall start with the expression for the EM field on the screen. The positive and negative frequency parts of the electric field operator at point P are a superposition of the EM field reaching from each pinhole P_i , and is given by $\hat{E}^{(\pm)}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \hat{E}_1^{(\pm)}(\mathbf{x}, t) + \hat{E}_2^{(\pm)}(\mathbf{x}, t)$. Since the EM field interacts with GWs only during the time of flight t and one may generally assume that $t \gg t_i$, hence the EM field propagates freely along s_1 and s_2 paths (or through the interferometer arms). Consequently, one may write

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{E}^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}, t) &\equiv \hat{E}^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t - t_1) + \hat{E}^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}_2, t - t_2), \\ \hat{E}^{(-)}(\mathbf{x}, t) &\equiv \hat{E}^{(-)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t - t_1) + \hat{E}^{(-)}(\mathbf{x}_2, t - t_2),\end{aligned}\quad (6.3)$$

where we have replaced $\hat{E}_i^{(\pm)}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \hat{E}^{(\pm)}(\mathbf{x}_i, t - t_i)$ since the EM-GWs interaction is neglected during $t_i \ll t$. With the help of Eq. (5.50), a single-mode linearly-polarized electric field operator is described by $\hat{E}(\mathbf{x}, t) \equiv \mathcal{E}\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}, t) + \mathcal{E}^*\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}, t)$, where \mathcal{E} is an abbreviation for the complex amplitude of the field. However, without loss of generality, we take \mathcal{E} as a real number in our calculations. The positive and negative frequency parts of the electric field are then given by

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{E}^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}_i, t - t_i) &= \mathcal{E}\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t - t_i)e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}_i}, \\ \hat{E}^{(-)}(\mathbf{x}_i, t - t_i) &= \mathcal{E}\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t - t_i)e^{-i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}_i}.\end{aligned}\quad (6.4)$$

Here, time behavior of the ladder operators $\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ and $\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ in the presence of GWs background are determined by Eq. (5.49), namely

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= \left[\prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathcal{R}^{3+}} \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k})\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \otimes \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k})\eta_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \right] \\ &\times e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} + \frac{1}{2})} e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}t} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}},\end{aligned}$$

and its Hermitian conjugate. Note that, here the position vectors \mathbf{x}^o and \mathbf{x}^f determine the interaction volume, while \mathbf{x}_1 and \mathbf{x}_2 stand for the detector points where the EM signal is

collected. The intensity at point P is then given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \hat{I}(\mathbf{x}, t) \rangle &= \langle \hat{E}^{(-)}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{E}^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}, t) \rangle & (6.5) \\
&= \langle \hat{E}^{(-)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t - t_1) \hat{E}^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t - t_1) \rangle \\
&+ \langle \hat{E}^{(-)}(\mathbf{x}_2, t - t_2) \hat{E}^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}_2, t - t_2) \rangle \\
&+ 2\Re[\langle \hat{E}^{(-)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t - t_1) \hat{E}^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}_2, t - t_2) \rangle] \\
&= G^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t - t_1; \mathbf{x}_1, t - t_1) + G^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_2, t - t_2; \mathbf{x}_2, t - t_2) \\
&+ 2\Re[G^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t - t_1; \mathbf{x}_2, t - t_2)] \\
&= I(\mathbf{x}_1, t - t_1) + I(\mathbf{x}_2, t - t_2) + 2\Re[G^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t - t_1; \mathbf{x}_2, t - t_2)],
\end{aligned}$$

where \Re stands for the real part. In the last line, we replaced the auto-correlation (correlations between the fields at the same point of spacetime) with the intensity at the point, i.e., $G^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_i, t - t_i; \mathbf{x}_i, t - t_i) \equiv I(\mathbf{x}_i, t - t_i)$. Hence, the first two terms indicate the contribution of intensity at the location of each slit. Since GW background leaves the mean number of photons conserved, i.e., the quantity $\hat{n}_{\mathbf{k}} = \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) = \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}$ is conserved, the first two terms $I(\mathbf{x}_1, t - t_1)$ and $I(\mathbf{x}_2, t - t_2)$ are indeed space-time independent (see the discussion after Eq. (5.21)). The last term in Eq. (6.5) shows the interference pattern stemming from the correlations between the fields at the location of the slits at times $t - t_1$ and $t - t_2$. Eq. (6.5) can be written in terms of the first-order degree of coherence as follows

$$\langle \hat{I}(\mathbf{x}, t) \rangle = I(1) + I(2) + 2\sqrt{I(1)I(2)}\Re[g^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t - t_1; \mathbf{x}_2, t - t_2)], \quad (6.6)$$

where $I(i)$ is abbreviation for $I(\mathbf{x}_i, t - t_i)$ with $i = 1, 2$. We used the definition Eq. (6.2), which can also be written as

$$g^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, \tau_1; \mathbf{x}_2, \tau_2) = \frac{\langle \hat{a}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_1) \hat{a}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_2) \rangle}{\langle \hat{n}_{\mathbf{k}} \rangle} e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2)}. \quad (6.7)$$

Here, for the sake of abbreviation we have defined $\tau_i \equiv t - t_i$ with $i = 1, 2$. In order to find correlations of the EM field in the presence of GWs, we first analyze the general expression of the first-order degree of coherence $g^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, \tau_1; \mathbf{x}_2, \tau_2)$ given by Eq. (6.7) with respect to different initial states of GWs. We then consider the case where $\mathbf{x}_1 = \mathbf{x}_2$ in order to examine temporal correlations and gravitational-induced decoherence of the EM field. Spatial correlations can be addressed by setting $\tau_1 = \tau_2$ (or $t_1 = t_2$) and $\mathbf{x}_1 \neq \mathbf{x}_2$ (see Chapter 7).

After obtaining the general expressions for the two-point degree of coherence, we shall limit our attention to the longitudinal coherence length of the field which is a measure of temporal coherence. We proceed by assuming that the EM field is propagated from a source located at \mathbf{x}_0 and observed at \mathbf{x} at a given time t . To achieve temporal correlations, we shall consider $\mathbf{x}_1 = \mathbf{x}_2 \simeq \mathbf{x}$, and the EM field is subjected to measurement at time t on the observation screen \mathcal{S} . When we consider spatial correlations of the field, one

may easily set $\tau_1 = \tau_2$ without effort and equal-time correlations are obtained. However, when we are interested in temporal correlations, one needs to check the stationarity of the underlying GW background. Basically, if two-time correlations of the GW background depend only on the time-difference $\tau_1 - \tau_2$, one may say that the background is stationary. In this case, the temporal correlations of GWs as well as the EM field do not depend on the origin of time, but rather on the time difference, and one may arbitrarily redefine the time origin so that $\tau_1 = t - t_1 = 0$ and $\tau_2 = t - t_2 = \tau$. Regarding typical experiments involving coherent laser beams on the Earth (and also in space), one can safely assume that the PGWs background is stationary, and is determined by its value at present time η_H . Basically, one can be sure that during the time of flight and subsequent time intervals t_i , the GWs field does not evolve drastically. However, this condition is fulfilled provided that the GWs frequency is much smaller than t^{-1} and τ^{-1} , which is truly the case for the ultra-low frequency part of the PGWs spectrum which has the major contribution in decoherence mechanism. Hence, for the inflationary-generated PGWs, the stationarity condition is met. Moreover, one may show that two-time correlations of vacuum fluctuations and thermal GWs are automatically stationary (depend only on the time-difference $\tau_1 - \tau_2$), stemming from the absence of any underlying correlations in these states. Thus, in the following discussion on temporal coherence, we assume that the GWs background is *stationary*, meaning that the major part of its spectrum is practically constant during the experiment duration so that we can set $\tau_1 = t - t_1 = 0$ and $\tau_2 = t - t_2 = \tau$ to achieve a temporal degree of coherence.

Consequently, temporal correlations are determined from the first-order degree of coherence

$$g^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}; \tau) \equiv g^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, 0; \mathbf{x}, \tau) = \frac{\langle \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, 0) \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) \rangle}{\langle \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \rangle}, \quad (6.8)$$

that essentially specifies temporal correlations of the field emitted from a source located at \mathbf{x}_0 and observed at \mathbf{x} (the location of one of the slits) at an initial time $\tau_1 = t - t_1 = 0$ and a subsequent time $\tau_2 = t - t_2 = \tau$ (the same point but at a later time τ). This quantity is of particular importance so that it makes a Fourier pair with the spectrum of the field, which will be examined in section 6.3. It is obvious that, in the absence of GWs when EM field freely propagates through spacetime, Eq. (6.8) reduces to $g^{(1)}(\tau) = e^{-i\omega_k \tau}$.

In the following, we try to find the expression of $g^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, \tau_1; \mathbf{x}_2, \tau_2)$ for different states of GWs described in Sec. 5.2.5. Details of calculations are brought into Appendix D. Here, we focus on the final results. For the sake of abbreviation, we denote by 1 and 2 the coordinates $(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_1)$ and $(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_2)$ abbreviately.

6.2.1 Temporal correlations in the case of vacuum fluctuations of GWs

Quantum fluctuations of GWs, described by the density matrix in Eq. (5.51), change the behavior of the first-order correlations of the EM field, according to (see Appendix. D for

details of calculations)

$$g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(1; 2) = e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(1; 2)} e^{-iC^{\text{vac}}(1; 2)} e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2)}, \quad (6.9)$$

where the expectation value in Eq. (6.7) is taken over the vacuum fluctuations of GWs and the state of the EM field does not matter, since only the mean value of photons appears in Eq. (6.7). The kernels are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} C^{\text{vac}}(1; 2) &\equiv \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) C_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(1; 2), \\ \mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(1; 2) &\equiv \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(1; 2), \end{aligned} \quad (6.10)$$

together with

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(1; 2) &\equiv \Im[\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_1) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_2)] \\ &= \Im[(1 - e^{i\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}\tau_1})(1 - e^{-i\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}\tau_2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2] \\ &= -\Im[2i \sin(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}\tau) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2], \\ \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(1; 2) &\equiv |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_2)|^2 \\ &= \left[4 \sin^2\left(\frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}\tau_1}{2}\right) + 4 \sin^2\left(\frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}\tau_2}{2}\right) - 2\Re(1 - e^{i\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}\tau_1} - e^{-i\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}\tau_2} + e^{i\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}(\tau_1 - \tau_2)}) \right] \\ &\times |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (6.11)$$

Thus, $C_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(1; 2)$ and $\mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(1; 2)$ represent the contribution of vacuum fluctuations in *coherent* and *decoherent* evolution of the first-order correlation function of the EM field, respectively. Temporal correlations are obtained by setting $\tau_1 = t - t_1 = 0$ and $\tau_2 = t - t_2 = \tau$, that yields

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) &= -2 \sin(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}\tau) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2, \\ \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) &= 4 \sin^2\left(\frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}\tau}{2}\right) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (6.12)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} C^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) &= - \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) (2 \sin(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}\tau)) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2, \\ \mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) (4 \sin^2\left(\frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}\tau}{2}\right)) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (6.13)$$

Both kernels depend on the propagation length $L_i = x_i^f - x_i^o$, as it should be due to the invariance under translation of the vacuum state of the GWs background. The function $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau)$ was previously obtained in Eq. (5.62), and was responsible for decoherent dynamics of the optical variance. Inserting Eq. (6.13) into Eq. (6.9), the first order degree

of (temporal) coherence is obtained

$$g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) = e^{-i(\omega_k \tau + C^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau))} e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau)}. \quad (6.14)$$

The factor $C^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau)$ affects the phase of the correlation function and changes the interference pattern periodicity. Indeed, the quantity $\Re[g^{(1)}]$ is responsible for the interference pattern in Eq. (6.6) and determines the visibility. In the absence of GWs, one would have $\Re[e^{-i\omega_k \tau}] = \cos[\omega_k \tau]$ and maxima and minima of the interference pattern are determined when this function is maximum and minimum, i.e., when $\omega_k \tau = 2n\pi$ and $\omega_k \tau = (2n+1)\pi$, respectively. However, vacuum fluctuations of GWs change this periodicity according to $\cos[\omega_k \tau + C^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau)]$. Still, $\tau = 0$ gives the first maxima as expected since $C^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau = 0) = 0$. A qualitative interpretation is that the presence of vacuum fluctuations shifts the frequency of the EM field, resulting in a shift in the periodicity of the interference pattern, which is a *coherent* (non-decaying) effect. Although this effect is a pure quantum mechanical effect, since it happens as a result of vacuum fluctuations of GWs, due to the negligibly small coupling strength $\kappa^2 \sim 10^{-58}$ for optical frequency, this effect is practically inaccessible from detection. Another contribution of vacuum fluctuations appears as the decaying factor $e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau)}$ that could limit the coherence time of the source.

To obtain the order of magnitude of these effects, first note that

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar \omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}} \right)^2 \int \frac{dK}{K} \sum_{\gamma=+, \times} \int d\phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) F_{\gamma}^2(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (6.15)$$

In order to calculate the spatial integration, we consider one-dimensional propagation of the EM field along the z direction, so that $K_x L_x \ll 1$ and $K_y L_y \ll 1$. Thus $\hat{\mathbf{k}} = (0, 0, 1)$, $\mathbf{L} \equiv (L, 0, 0)$ and $\mathbf{K} = K(\sin \Theta_K \cos \Phi_K, \sin \Theta_K \sin \Phi_K, \cos \Theta_K)$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} F_{\gamma}(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) &= e_{ij}^{\gamma}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j \rightarrow e_{33}^+ + e_{33}^{\times}, \\ |g(\mathbf{K} \cdot (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0))|^2 &= \left(\frac{\sin(\frac{K_z L}{2})}{(\frac{K_z L}{2})} \right)^2 = \left(\frac{\sin(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})}{(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})} \right)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (6.16)$$

With the help of Eq. (2.40) and Eq. (2.41) we have $e_{33}^+ = \sin^2 \Theta_K$ and $e_{33}^{\times} = 0$. Hence, $F_{\gamma}(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) = e_{33}^+ = \sin^2 \Theta_K$. With the help of Eq. (6.15) and Eq. (6.16), Eq. (6.13) reduces

to

$$\begin{aligned}
C^{\text{vac}}(L, \tau) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}} \right)^2 \int d\Phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) \sin^4 \Theta_K \quad (6.17) \\
&\times \int_{K_{\text{low}}}^{K_{\text{up}}} \frac{dK}{K} (2 \sin(Kc\tau)) \left(\frac{\sin(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})}{(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})} \right)^2, \\
\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(L, \tau) &= \frac{1}{2(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}} \right)^2 \int d\Phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) \sin^4 \Theta_K \\
&\times \int_{K_{\text{low}}}^{K_{\text{up}}} \frac{dK}{K} (4 \sin^2(\frac{Kc\tau}{2})) \left(\frac{\sin(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})}{(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})} \right)^2,
\end{aligned}$$

where K_{low} and K_{up} stand for some lower and upper limits of the integral. For instance, one may assume the lower and upper frequencies of PGWs, namely K_E and K_1 , as the lower and upper limits of the integrals. Considering the fact that for terrestrial and space-based interferometers, the small-detector condition $KL \ll 1$ is fulfilled for the ultra-low frequency part of PGWs, the spatial dependence in the kernels Eq. (6.17) disappears, and only temporal-dependence matters. Consequently, we proceed by assuming small-detector approximation. If we approximately set $K_{\text{low}} \rightarrow 0$, the integral in function $C^{\text{vac}}(\tau)$ becomes the well-known Sine Integral, $\text{Si}(x) \equiv \int_0^x \frac{\sin t}{t} dt$ with $x = K_{\text{up}}c\tau$, which does not have a closed form. The function $C^{\text{vac}}(x)$ is sketched in panel (a) of Fig. 6.2 versus $x = K_{\text{up}}c\tau$. It can be seen that, for small values $x \ll 1$, the function is linear, while for large values $x \gg 1$, the function is approximately constant. Thus, in two asymptotic regimes $C^{\text{vac}}(\tau) \propto \tau$ and $C^{\text{vac}}(\tau) \sim \pi/2$ are obtained, depending on the value of τ , which ultimately determine the behavior of the visibility as $\cos[\omega_k\tau + C^{\text{vac}}(\tau)]$. In the best case scenario that we consider the maximum of $\text{Si}(x)$ (which happens when $K_{\text{up}}c\tau \gg 1$), we may approximately write $\text{Si}(x) \simeq \pi/2$ and $C^{\text{vac}}(\tau) \propto (\hbar\omega_k/E_{\text{Pl}})^2 \sim 10^{-58}$ which is too small to be resolved by a typical interferometer. For instance, for a maximum achievable coherence time $\tau_{\text{coh}} = 10$ s, and assuming the higher PGWs wave number $K_{\text{up}} = K_1$, one obtains $x = K_1c\tau_{\text{coh}} \sim 10^8$ which is too large and fulfills the best case scenario.

Similar arguments are valid for $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\tau)$. In this case, the integral in Eq. (6.17) is determined by $\int_0^x \frac{\sin^2 t}{t} dt = 1/2(\gamma + \log 2 + \log(x) - \text{Ci}(2x))$ with $\text{Ci}(x) = -\int_x^\infty \frac{\cos t}{t} dt$ being the Cosine Integral and γ being the Euler-Mascheroni constant. The behavior of $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(x)$ versus the dimensionless parameter $x = K_{\text{up}}c\tau$ is shown in panel (b) of Fig. 6.2. Asymptotic behaviors at $x \ll 1$ and $x \gg 1$ are given by $\sim \frac{x^2}{2}$ and $\sim \log(x)$, respectively. As before, we may consider the best case scenario for large $x \gg 1$ resulting in the maximum possible decoherence effect on laser light of coherence time $\tau_{\text{coh}} = 10$ s. For $x = 10^8$ one has $\int_0^x \frac{\sin^2 t}{t} dt \propto \log(x) = \log(10^8) = 8$ which yields $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\tau) \propto (\hbar\omega_k/E_{\text{Pl}})^2 \sim 10^{-58}$ that is negligibly small.

Figure 6.2: The functions $C^{\text{vac}}(\tau)$ and $D^{\text{vac}}(\tau)$ versus the dimensionless parameter $x = K_{\text{up}}c\tau$ based on Eq. (6.17) sketched for optical frequency $\omega_k = 10^{15}$ Hz, shown in panel (a) and (b). Here, we have chosen the lower limit of the integral $K_{\text{low}} \rightarrow 0$.

6.2.2 Temporal correlations in the case of coherent GWs

A continuum of GWs in a coherent state is described by Eq. (5.52). In this case, the two-point degree of coherence Eq. (6.7) turns out to be given by (see Appendix. D for details of calculations)

$$\begin{aligned} g_{\text{coh}}^{(1)}(1; 2) &= e^{-i(C^{\text{vac}}(1;2) - C^{\text{coh}}(1;2))} e^{-D^{\text{vac}}(1;2)} e^{-i\omega_k(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2)}, \\ &= g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(1; 2) e^{iC^{\text{coh}}(1;2)}, \end{aligned} \quad (6.18)$$

where the functions $C^{\text{vac}}(1; 2)$ and $D^{\text{vac}}(1; 2)$ show the contribution of vacuum and are given by Eq. (6.10). The function $C^{\text{coh}}(1; 2)$ is defined by

$$C^{\text{coh}}(1; 2) \equiv 2 \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) C_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{coh}}(1; 2), \quad (6.19)$$

together with

$$\begin{aligned}
C_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{coh}}(1; 2) &\equiv \Im[(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_2))\beta_{\mathbf{K}}^*] \\
&= -\bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2} \Im\left[(e^{i\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}\tau_1} - e^{i\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}\tau_2})g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) e^{-i\theta_{\beta_{\mathbf{K}}}}\right] \\
&= -\bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2} \Im\left[(e^{i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}\tau_1 - \theta_{\beta_{\mathbf{K}}})} - e^{i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}\tau_2 - \theta_{\beta_{\mathbf{K}}})})g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)\right].
\end{aligned} \tag{6.20}$$

As before, we have used $\tau_1 = t - t_1$ and $\tau_2 = t - t_2$ for abbreviation. Moreover, we have used $\beta_{\mathbf{K}} = \bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2}(K)e^{i\theta_{\beta_{\mathbf{K}}}}$ with $\theta_{\beta_{\mathbf{K}}}$ being the coherence phase. Thus, Eq. (6.18) implies that in addition to the contribution of vacuum fluctuations, the effect of coherent GWs with a mean number of gravitons $\bar{n}_{\text{coh}}(K) = |\beta_{\mathbf{K}}|^2$ in mode K , appears *only* as a phase factor in the correlation function while preserving its amplitude. So one may expect an extra shift of interference pattern which depends on the multiplication $\kappa_{\gamma}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k})\bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2}(K)$. Besides, the expression depends on spatial points \mathbf{x}^o and \mathbf{x}^f and not in their relative position $\mathbf{x}^f - \mathbf{x}^o$ (see definition of $g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)$ given by Eq. (5.18)). This is a manifestation of the fact that a generic coherent background of GWs may be inhomogeneous and anisotropic, as its two-point correlation function implies (see Eq. (5.68)). This behavior is in contrast to the case of vacuum fluctuations, where only the spatial difference $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{x}^f - \mathbf{x}^o$ appears in the equations, as a result of the homogeneity of vacuum fluctuations.

Temporal correlation of the EM field is obtained by considering the correlations between the fields at a given spatial point $\mathbf{x}_1 = \mathbf{x}_2 \simeq \mathbf{x}$ at two different moments of time, by setting $\tau_1 = t - t_1 = 0$ and $\tau_2 = t - t_2 = \tau$. Thus, Eq. (6.19) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned}
C^{\text{coh}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) &= 2 \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2}(K) \Im\left[(e^{-i\theta_{\beta_{\mathbf{K}}}} - e^{i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}\tau - \theta_{\beta_{\mathbf{K}}})})\right. \\
&\quad \left. \times e^{-i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}^o} \prod_{i=1}^3 \frac{e^{-iK_i x_i^f} - e^{-iK_i x_i^o}}{-iK_i(x_i^f - x_i^o)}\right],
\end{aligned} \tag{6.21}$$

which explicitly depends on \mathbf{x}^o and \mathbf{x}^f . Eq. (6.21) is essentially the same as Eq. (5.65) which was responsible for coherent oscillations in optical squeezing. In order to obtain the order of magnitude of the effect, we proceed by assuming one-dimensional propagation of the EM field along z -direction and we set $\hat{\mathbf{k}} = (1, 0, 0)$ and $\mathbf{L} = (L, 0, 0)$ as before. Similar calculations as in Eq. (6.15) yields

$$\begin{aligned}
C^{\text{coh}}(z^o, z^f, \tau) &= \frac{1}{\pi} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}}\right) \sum_{\gamma} \int d\Phi_{\mathbf{K}} \int d(\cos \Theta_{\mathbf{K}}) F_{\gamma}(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) \int dK K^{1/2} \bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2} \left(\frac{\sin(\frac{K_z L}{2})}{(\frac{K_z L}{2})}\right) \\
&\quad \times \left(\sin\left[\frac{K_z(z^o + z^f) + 2\theta_{\beta_{\mathbf{K}}}}{2} - \Omega_{\mathbf{K}}\tau\right] - \sin\left[\frac{K_z(z^o + z^f) + 2\theta_{\beta_{\mathbf{K}}}}{2}\right]\right) \\
&= -\frac{2}{\pi} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}}\right) \sum_{\gamma} \int d\Phi_{\mathbf{K}} \int d(\cos \Theta_{\mathbf{K}}) F_{\gamma}(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) \int dK K^{1/2} \bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2} \left(\frac{\sin(\frac{K_z L}{2})}{(\frac{K_z L}{2})}\right) \\
&\quad \times \left(\sin\left(\frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}\tau}{2}\right) \cos\left[\theta_{\beta_{\mathbf{K}}} - \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}}\tau - K_z(z^o + z^f)}{2}\right]\right).
\end{aligned} \tag{6.22}$$

which not only depends on $L = z^f - z^o$, but also on $z^o + z^f$. Eq. (6.22) implies that in order to reveal the effect of coherent GWs one needs large number of gravitons so that the multiplicative $(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}})\bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2}$ takes a significant value, at least at some frequency interval. For the sake of illustration, we proceed by a hypothetical coherent GW background that possesses a large number of gravitons as in two-mode squeezed PGWs, i.e., $\bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2} \sim e^{r_K}/2$ with e^{r_K} given by Eq. (3.56). Then, one may profit from the fact that the main contribution in the integral Eq. (6.22) comes from the ultra-low frequency part of the PGWs spectrum, which contains the highest number of gravitons. Thus, for typical small-scale interferometric setups realizable on the Earth or in space, one may use the approximation $\Omega_K\tau \ll 1$ and the small-detector approximation $KL \ll 1$ and $K(z^o + z^f) \simeq 2Kz^o \ll 1$. Basically, the ultra-low frequency PGWs have astronomically large wavelengths comparable to the Hubble length, and a typical terrestrial interferometric setup designed for the measurement of temporal correlations is practically embedded in a homogeneous spacetime. In this approximation, the expression Eq. (6.22) takes the form of Eq. (5.69), and simplifies to

$$\begin{aligned} C^{\text{coh}}(\tau) &\simeq -\left[\frac{1}{\pi}\left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}}\right)\sum_{\gamma}\int d\Phi_K\int d(\cos\Theta_K)\sin^2\Theta_K\int dKK^{1/2}\bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2}\Omega_K\right]\tau \\ &\equiv -\zeta^{\text{coh}}\omega_k\tau, \end{aligned} \quad (6.23)$$

which is linear in τ . In the last line of Eq. (6.23), we have defined the dimensionless parameter ζ^{coh} which depends only on the GWs background, according to

$$\zeta^{\text{coh}} \equiv \left[\frac{1}{\pi}\left(\frac{\hbar c}{E_{\text{Pl}}}\right)\sum_{\gamma}\int d\Phi_K\int d(\cos\Theta_K)\sin^2\Theta_K\int dKK^{3/2}\bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2}(K)\right]. \quad (6.24)$$

The full expression of the temporal coherence Eq. (6.18), neglecting the vacuum contribution, becomes

$$g_{\text{coh}}^{(1)}(\tau) = e^{-i(\omega_k\tau - C^{\text{coh}}(\tau))} = e^{-i(1+\zeta^{\text{coh}})\omega_k\tau}, \quad (6.25)$$

which explicitly shows a change in the periodicity of the interference pattern, $\Re[g_{\text{coh}}^{(1)}(\tau)] = \cos[\omega_k(1+\zeta^{\text{coh}})\tau]$. That means the existence of GWs in a coherent state shifts the maxima and minima of a single-mode EM field from $\omega_k\tau = (2n+1)\pi$ to $\omega_k\tau = \frac{(2n+1)\pi}{1-\zeta^{\text{coh}}}$. The parameter ζ^{coh} depends on the inflation model parameters. For instance, if we take $(\beta = -2, \beta_s = 1, T_{\text{reh}} = 10^8 \text{ GeV})$ as usual, one has $\zeta^{\text{coh}} = 1.7 \times 10^{-5}$ for $r_{k_0} = 10^{-2}$ and $\zeta^{\text{coh}} = 5.4 \times 10^{-6}$ for $r_{k_0} = 10^{-3}$. The frequency shift in the Fourier space is determined by $\omega_k \rightarrow \omega_k(1+\zeta^{\text{coh}}) = \omega_k + \zeta^{\text{coh}}\omega_k$. For optical field of frequency $\omega_k = 10^{15} \text{ Hz}$, one has

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_k\zeta^{\text{coh}} &\sim 1.7 \times 10^{10} \text{ Hz} \quad , \quad r_{k_0} = 10^{-2} \\ \omega_k\zeta^{\text{coh}} &\sim 5.4 \times 10^9 \text{ Hz} \quad , \quad r_{k_0} = 10^{-3} \end{aligned} \quad (6.26)$$

This is basically a large frequency shift of order MHz in optical frequency. However,

this is a *global* frequency shift, in the sense that it is independent of ω_k and shifts all EM frequencies on the same foot. This renders the detection of such a coherent GW background impossible. Note that, this behavior is in contrast to the vacuum-induced frequency shift which is quadratic in ω_k as implied by Eq. (6.17).

6.2.3 Temporal correlations in the case of (uncorrelated) squeezed GWs

In this section, we calculate temporal correlations when the GW background is composed of a continuum of uncorrelated squeezed modes. We remind that, the difference between one-mode and two-mode squeezed state is the absence of correlations between different momenta in the one-mode squeezed state. This is exactly the presence of correlations between opposite momenta in the two-mode squeezed state which results in the homogeneity and isotropicity of the PGWs correlators. However, up to our knowledge, there is no astronomical or cosmological candidate that could generate squeezed state, by violating the homogeneity and isotropicity. Even though, from theoretical point of view, it is interesting for us to see how inhomogeneous-anisotropic squeezed GW manifest itself in the optical correlations.

GWs in a squeezed state are described by the density matrix Eq. (5.54) in which there is no correlation between different modes of GW field. The first-order degree of coherence Eq. (6.7) when evaluated for squeezed GWs is given by (see Appendix. D for details of calculations)

$$g_{\text{sq}}^{(1)}(1;2) = g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(1;2)e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(1;2)}. \quad (6.27)$$

Squeezed GWs contribute only in the decoherence mechanism and there is no coherent phase factor in contrast to coherent GWs. The reason is simply due to the fact that we are considering a squeezed vacuum, which has amplified noise in a certain direction, without any displacement in phase space. If one had considered a squeezed coherent state, an additional phase factor (such as C^{sq}) could also appear. The contribution of gravitons in the squeezed state in the two-point correlation function of the EM field (excluding the contribution of vacuum fluctuations) is accounted for by the decoherence function $\mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(1;2)$ given by

$$\mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(1;2) \equiv \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \left\{ \sinh^2 r_K \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(1;2) + \frac{1}{2} \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{sq-corr}}(1;2) \right\}, \quad (6.28)$$

where $\mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(1;2)$ is given by Eq. (6.11) and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{sq-corr}}(1;2) &\equiv \sinh 2r_K \Re \left[(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_2))^2 e^{-2i\phi_K} \right] \\ &= \sinh 2r_K \Re \left[(e^{i\Omega_K \tau_1} - e^{i\Omega_K \tau_2})^2 g_{\mathbf{K}}^{*2}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) e^{-2i\phi_K} \right] \\ &= \sinh 2r_K \Re \left[\left(e^{i(2\Omega_K \tau_1 - 2\phi_K)} - e^{i(2\Omega_K \tau_2 - 2\phi_K)} - 2e^{i(\Omega_K(\tau_1 + \tau_2) - 2\phi_K)} \right) g_{\mathbf{K}}^{*2}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (6.29)$$

Here, the notation $\mathcal{D}^{\text{sq-corr}}$ shows the contribution of correlations between gravitons in a single-mode of GWs in the squeezed state and is essentially the contribution of correlations like $\langle \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} \rangle$ and $\langle \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \rangle$. As before, $\tau_i \equiv t - t_i$ and (r_K, ϕ_K) represent the squeeze amplitude and angle, respectively. To obtain temporal correlations we proceed by setting $\tau_1 = t - t_1 = 0$, $\tau_2 = t - t_2 = \tau$. Moreover, we consider one-dimensional propagation of the EM field along the z direction as before, so that $L = z^f - z^o$. In this case, Eq. (6.29) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{sq-corr}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) &= \sinh 2r_K \Re \left[(e^{-2i\phi_K} - 2e^{i(\Omega_K \tau - 2\phi_K)} + e^{2i(\Omega_K \tau - \phi_K)}) \right. \\
&\times \left. \left(\frac{e^{-2iK_z z^f} + e^{-2iK_z z^o} - 2 \cos[K_z(z^f + z^o)]}{-K_z^2(z^f - z^o)^2} \right) \right] \\
&= -\frac{\sinh 2r_K}{(K_z L)^2} \Re \left\{ e^{-i(2\phi_K + 2K_z z^f)} - 2e^{-i(2\phi_K + K_z(z^f + z^o))} + e^{-i(2\phi_K + 2K_z z^o)} \right. \\
&- 2e^{i(\Omega_K \tau - 2\phi_K - 2K_z z^f)} + 4e^{i(\Omega_K \tau - 2\phi_K - K_z(z^f + z^o))} - 2e^{i(\Omega_K \tau - 2\phi_K - 2K_z z^o)} \\
&+ e^{i(2\Omega_K \tau - 2\phi_K - 2K_z z^f)} - 2e^{i(2\Omega_K \tau - 2\phi_K - K_z(z^f + z^o))} + e^{i(2\Omega_K \tau - 2\phi_K - 2K_z z^o)} \left. \right\} \\
&= -\frac{\sinh 2r_K}{(K_z L)^2} \left\{ \cos[2\phi_K + 2K_z z^f] - 2 \cos[2\phi_K + K_z(z^f + z^o)] \right. \\
&+ \cos[2\phi_K + 2K_z z^o] - 2 \cos[\Omega_K \tau - 2\phi_K - 2K_z z^f] \\
&+ 4 \cos[\Omega_K \tau - 2\phi_K - K_z(z^f + z^o)] - 2 \cos[\Omega_K \tau - 2\phi_K - 2K_z z^o] \\
&+ \cos[2\Omega_K \tau - 2\phi_K - 2K_z z^f] - 2 \cos[2\Omega_K \tau - 2\phi_K - K_z(z^f + z^o)] \\
&+ \left. \cos[2\Omega_K \tau - 2\phi_K - 2K_z z^o] \right\} \\
&= -\frac{\sinh 2r_K}{(K_z L)^2} \left(-4 \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Omega_K \tau}{2} \right) \right) \left(\cos[2\phi_K + 2K_z z^f - \Omega_K \tau] \right. \\
&- 2 \cos[2\phi_K + K_z(z^f + z^o) - \Omega_K \tau] + \cos[2\phi_K + 2K_z z^o - \Omega_K \tau] \left. \right) \\
&= \frac{\sinh 2r_K}{(K_z L)^2} \left(4 \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Omega_K \tau}{2} \right) \right) \left(-4 \sin^2 \left(\frac{K_z(z^f - z^o)}{2} \right) \right) \cos[2\phi_K - \Omega_K \tau + K_z(z^f + z^o)] \\
&= -\sinh 2r_K \left(4 \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Omega_K \tau}{2} \right) \right) \left(\frac{\sin \left(\frac{K_z L}{2} \right)}{\left(\frac{K_z L}{2} \right)} \right)^2 \cos[2\phi_K + K_z(z^f + z^o) - \Omega_K \tau],
\end{aligned} \tag{6.30}$$

and Eq. (6.27) takes the following form

$$g_{\text{sq}}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) = g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau)}, \tag{6.31}$$

together with

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) &\equiv \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \left\{ \sinh^2 r_K \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) \right. \\
&+ \left. \frac{1}{2} \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{sq-corr}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) \right\},
\end{aligned} \tag{6.32}$$

which is basically the same as Eq. (5.73) that was responsible for decoherence of optical squeezing. Eq. (6.31) thus implies that the squeezed vacuum of GWs induces *only* decoherence and does not contribute to coherent dynamics of the EM field. However,

the vacuum effect is amplified by the factor $\bar{n}_{\text{sq}}(K) = \sinh^2 r_k$ and a new contribution embarked in $\mathcal{D}^{\text{sq-corr}}$. However, EM temporal correlations are explicitly space-dependent similar to the case of coherent GWs. As described in Sec. (5.3.4), the spatial dependence of the temporal correlations is a manifestation of the fact that the (uncorrelated) squeezed GW field does not respect homogeneity, as its correlation function implies (see Eq. (5.74)). However, we shall see in Sec. (6.2.4) that correlations between opposite momenta \mathbf{K} and $-\mathbf{K}$ in the two-mode squeezed state, leads the temporal correlation of the EM field to be homogeneous, inherited from the homogeneity of the two-point correlation function of TS PGWs (see Eq. (2.77)). With the help of Eqs. (6.13, 6.15, 6.30), we may rewrite Eq. (6.32) for a one-dimensional propagation as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(z_0, z, \tau) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}} \right)^2 \int d\Phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) \sin^4 \Theta_K \int \frac{dK}{K} (4 \sin^2(\frac{\Omega_K \tau}{2})) \left(\frac{\sin(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_k}{2})}{(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})} \right)^2 \\ &\times \left\{ \sinh^2 r_K - \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K \cos [2\phi_K + K(z^f + z^o) \cos \Theta_K - \Omega_K \tau] \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (6.33)$$

In the special case of highly-squeezed GWs with large number of gravitons (as large as PGWs), one has $r_K \gg 1$, thus $\sinh^2 r_K \simeq e^{2r_K}/4$ and $\sinh 2r_K \simeq e^{2r_K}/2$, where e^{r_K} is determined by Eq. (3.56). Thus, Eq. (6.33) takes the following form

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(z_0, z, \tau) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}} \right)^2 \int d\Phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) \sin^4 \Theta_K \int \frac{dK}{K} (4 \sin^2(\frac{\Omega_K \tau}{2})) \left(\frac{\sin(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_k}{2})}{(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})} \right)^2 \\ &\times \frac{e^{2r_K}}{4} \left(2 \sin^2 \left[\frac{2\phi_K + K(z^f + z^o) \cos \Theta_K - \Omega_K \tau}{2} \right] \right). \end{aligned} \quad (6.34)$$

To evaluate the decoherence induced by (uncorrelated) highly-squeezed GWs, again we proceed by using the fact that the major contribution in the integral Eq. (6.34) is due to the ultra-low frequency part of GWs spectrum for which the graviton content is large. Thus, for typical terrestrial and space-based experiments involving coherent laser beams, one may use $\Omega_K \tau \ll 1$ (remind that the maximum coherence time so far achievable on the Earth is a few seconds [169]). Moreover, we may use the small-detector approximation by setting $KL \ll 1$ and $K(z^f + z^o) \ll 1$. Moreover, we take $\phi_K = 0$ for simplicity and use Eq. (3.56) for the squeezing amplitude. Under these assumptions, Eq. (6.34) takes the following form

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(\tau) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}} \right)^2 \int d\Phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) \sin^4 \Theta_K \int \frac{dK}{K} \frac{e^{2r_K}}{4} (8 \sin^4(\frac{\Omega_K \tau}{2})), \quad (6.35) \\ &= \left[\frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}} \right)^2 \int d\Phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) \sin^4 \Theta_K \int \frac{dK}{K} \frac{e^{2r_K}}{4} (8(\frac{\Omega_K}{2})^4) \right] \tau^4, \end{aligned}$$

which shows τ^4 -dependence. With the help of Eq. (6.35), Eq. (6.31) recasts to

$$g_{\text{sq}}^{(1)}(\tau) \equiv e^{-\left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_{\text{sq}}}\right)^4}, \quad (6.36)$$

where the decoherence time induced by one-mode squeezed GWs (under the aforementioned circumstances) is defined by

$$\tau_{\text{sq}} \equiv \left[\frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}} \right)^2 \int d\Phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) \sin^4 \Theta_K \int \frac{dK}{K} \frac{e^{2r_K} \Omega_K^4}{8} \right]^{-1/4}. \quad (6.37)$$

As we are going to show in the next section, the same behavior also appears in the case of two-mode squeezed PGWs. Indeed, although the general spatial dependence of the EM field correlations is different for one-mode and two-mode squeezed GWs, in the small-detector limit one may not be able to distinguish between these backgrounds, by means of terrestrial or even space-based experiments. The reason is simply due to the fact that the characteristic length scale of PGWs is the Hubble scale that could not be touched with small-scale probes. Consequently, the effect of both one-mode and two-mode squeezed GWs (with the same spectrum) on the temporal correlations of the EM field is indistinguishable.

However, one may note that there is no mechanism in nature that can generate this hypothetical uncorrelated one-mode squeezed GWs background. Even if such a source exists, the magnitude of the squeeze parameters of the generated GWs background depends crucially on the specific mechanism that produces the squeezed GWs, in that it respects linear momentum and other related symmetries or not. Especially, the squeezing amplitude determines the amount of squeezing of the state and its graviton content. The typical value of the mean number of gravitons in the one-mode squeezed state must be so large that compensates the negligible coupling strength $(\hbar\omega_k/E_{\text{pl}})^2$, so that meaningful observable decoherence can be observed.

6.2.4 Temporal correlations in the presence of GWs in TS state

GWs in two-mode squeezed states are described by the density matrix Eq. (5.56) in which each mode \mathbf{K} is highly correlated by the opposite momenta $-\mathbf{K}$, as a result of linear momentum conservation during their generation. Inflationary-generated PGWs are a suitable example in this regard (see Chapter 2 for an introduction to PGWs). The effect of PGWs on the correlations of the EM field defined by Eq. (6.7) is described by (see Appendix. D for details of calculations)

$$g_{\text{ts}}^{(1)}(1; 2) = g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(1; 2) e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(1; 2)}, \quad (6.38)$$

where the decoherence function $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(1; 2)$ which accounts for the decoherence induced by two-mode squeezed PGWs is defined by

$$\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(1; 2) \equiv \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \left\{ |v_K(\eta_H)|^2 \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(1; 2) + \frac{1}{2} \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{ts-corr}}(1; 2) \right\}. \quad (6.39)$$

Here, $\mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(1; 2)$ is defined by Eq. (6.11) and we have defined a new kernel

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{ts-corr}}(1; 2) &\equiv 2\Re\left[u_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H)v_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H)(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_2))\right. \\
&\quad \times \left.(\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_2))\right] \\
&= \sinh 2r_K \Re\left[\left((1 - e^{i\Omega_K\tau_1})^2 + (1 - e^{i\Omega_K\tau_2})^2 - 2(1 - e^{i\Omega_K\tau_1})(1 - e^{i\Omega_K\tau_2})\right)e^{-2i\phi_K}\right] \\
&\quad \times \left|g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)\right|^2 \\
&= \sinh 2r_K \Re\left[\left(e^{-2i\phi_K} - 2e^{i(\Omega_K\tau_1 - 2\phi_K)} + e^{2i(\Omega_K\tau_1 - \phi_K)}\right)\right. \\
&\quad + \left.\left(e^{-2i\phi_K} - 2e^{i(\Omega_K\tau_2 - 2\phi_K)} + e^{2i(\Omega_K\tau_2 - \phi_K)}\right)\right. \\
&\quad \left. - 2\left(e^{-2i\phi_K} - e^{i(\Omega_K\tau_1 - 2\phi_K)} - e^{i(\Omega_K\tau_2 - 2\phi_K)} + e^{i[\Omega_K(\tau_1 + \tau_2) - 2\phi_K]}\right)\right] \left|g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o - \mathbf{x}^f)\right|^2.
\end{aligned} \tag{6.40}$$

As before, $\tau_i \equiv t - t_i$. Moreover, $u_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)$ and $v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)$ are defined by Eq. (2.58). Thus, in addition to the decoherence induced by amplified vacuum fluctuations given by \mathcal{D}^{vac} , the function $\mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{ts-corr}}$ signifies the contribution of correlations of type $\langle \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle$ and $\langle \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}^\dagger \rangle$ in TS PGWs in optical decoherence (see also Eq. (2.71)). Although the former is identical to that of the one-mode squeezed state given by the first term in Eq. (6.28), the latter is different from $\mathcal{D}^{\text{sq-corr}}$ defined by Eq. (6.29). Indeed, the homogeneity of $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts-corr}}$ is a direct result of correlations between opposite momenta, which is absent in a one-mode squeezed state. Thus, the optical two-point correlation function depends on the relative position $\mathbf{x}^f - \mathbf{x}^o$ and not on the location of the detectors (or slits in Young's double-slit experiment).

To obtain the decoherence induced by two-modes squeezed GWs, we set $\tau_1 = t - t_1 = 0$ and $\tau_2 = t - t_2 = \tau$ as before. Thus, Eq. (6.40) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{ts-corr}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) &= \sinh 2r_K (\cos[2\phi_K] - 2\cos[2\phi_K - \Omega_K\tau] + \cos[2\phi_K - 2\Omega_K\tau]) \\
&\quad \times \left|g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)\right|^2,
\end{aligned} \tag{6.41}$$

which depends on $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{x}^f - \mathbf{x}^o$. The first-order degree of coherence Eq. (6.38) reduces to

$$g_{\text{ts}}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) = g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau)}, \tag{6.42}$$

and $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau)$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) &= \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \left|g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)\right|^2 \left\{ \sinh^2 r_K \left(4 \sin^2\left(\frac{\Omega_K\tau}{2}\right)\right) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K (\cos[2\phi_K] - 2\cos[2\phi_K - \Omega_K\tau] + \cos[2\phi_K - 2\Omega_K\tau]) \right\}.
\end{aligned} \tag{6.43}$$

For a one-dimensional propagation along the z direction and considering highly-squeezed

PGWs with $r_K \gg 1$, Eq. (6.43) reduces to the following form

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(L, \tau) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}} \right)^2 \int d\Phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) \sin^4 \Theta_K \int_{K_E}^{K_1} \frac{dK}{K} \frac{e^{2r_K}}{4} \\ &\times \left(\frac{\sin(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})}{(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})} \right)^2 \left(8 \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Omega_K \tau}{2} \right) \sin^2 \left(\frac{2\phi_K - \Omega_K \tau}{2} \right) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (6.44)$$

where we have used Eqs. (6.15, 6.16) for one-dimensional propagation of EM field along z direction. Eq. (6.44) differs from Eq. (6.33) due to different spatial dependence. In particular, \mathcal{D}^{ts} depends on $L = z^f - z^o$ and not on $z^f + z^o$. However, both kernels become identical in small-detector approximation. Assuming $\Omega_K \tau \ll 1$ corresponding to major part of PGWs spectrum and setting $\phi_K = 0$, Eq. (6.44) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(L, \tau) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}} \right)^2 \int d\Phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) \sin^4 \Theta_K \\ &\times \int_{K_E}^{K_1} \frac{dK}{K} \frac{e^{2r_K}}{4} \left(\frac{\sin(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})}{(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})} \right)^2 \left(8 \sin^4 \left(\frac{\Omega_K \tau}{2} \right) \right) \\ &= \left[\frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}} \right)^2 \int d\Phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) \sin^4 \Theta_K \right. \\ &\times \left. \int_{K_E}^{K_1} \frac{dK}{K} \frac{e^{2r_K} \Omega_K}{8} \left(\frac{\sin(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})}{(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})} \right)^2 \right] \tau^4 \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_{\text{ts}}(L)} \right)^4. \end{aligned} \quad (6.45)$$

Here, the decoherence time induced by two-mode squeezed PGWs is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{\text{ts}}(L) &= \left[\frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}} \right)^2 \int d\Phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) \sin^4 \Theta_K \right. \\ &\times \left. \int_{K_E}^{K_1} \frac{dK}{K} \frac{e^{2r_K} \Omega_K^4}{8} \left(\frac{\sin(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})}{(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})} \right)^2 \right]^{-1/4}, \end{aligned} \quad (6.46)$$

which depends on L . In the small-detector condition $KL \ll 1$, $\tau_{\text{ts}}(L)$ reduces to τ_{sq} given by Eq. (6.37). Note that, a non-vanishing squeezing angle ϕ_K may lead the integrand in Eq. (6.44) to vanish for a given value of τ and effectively increases the decoherence time induced by TS GWs. This behavior can be traced back to the correlation function of TS PGWs given by Eq. (2.73) and Eq. (2.76) (see also the discussion after Eq. (2.73)). Thus, the expression Eq. (6.46) is the worst-case scenario corresponding to maximum decoherence induced by PGWs. Applying the small-detector approximation $KL \ll 1$ which is a good approximation for the major part of PGWs spectrum regarding terrestrial and space-based interferometers, temporal correlations Eq. (6.42) becomes

$$g_{\text{ts}}^{(1)}(\tau) = g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(\tau) e^{-\left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_{\text{ts}}}\right)^4}, \quad (6.47)$$

where Eq. (6.45) is used. The time behavior of $g_{\text{ts}}^{(1)}(\tau)$ versus τ is plotted in Fig. 6.3 for two sets of parameters $\beta = -2, r_{k_0} = 10^{-2}$ and $\beta = -2, r_{k_0} = 10^{-3}$ in red and blue curves, respectively. To test the accuracy of the linear approximation, the solid curves correspond to the analytical expression Eq. (6.44), while black dots correspond to the linear approximation $\sin(\frac{\Omega_K \tau}{2}) \sim \frac{\Omega_K \tau}{2}$, based on Eq. (6.45). Both curves are plotted within the small-detector approximation $KL \ll 1$. Thus, the linear approximation works well, and the analytical expression Eq. (6.46) for $\tau_{\text{ts}}(L)$ correctly determines the decoherence time induced by two-mode squeezed PGWs.

Figure 6.3: Temporal degree of coherence in case of TS PGWs within the small detector approximation, for $(\beta = -2, \beta_s = 1, T_{\text{reh}} = 10^8)$, and $\phi_K = 0$. The red and blue curves correspond to $r_{k_0} = 10^{-2}$ and $r_{k_0} = 10^{-3}$, respectively. Solid curves show the analytical expression $g_{\text{ts}}^{(1)}(\tau)$ based on Eq. (6.44). Black dots correspond to the linear approximation where $\sin(\frac{\Omega_K \tau}{2}) \sim \frac{\Omega_K \tau}{2}$ is used, based on Eq. (6.45). It turns out that the linear approximation fits well with the full analytical expression.

According to Fig. 6.3, typical decoherence time induced by TS PGWs is as large as $\tau \sim 10^4$ s, though reducing the tensor-to-scalar ratio slightly increases the decoherence time. To detect such a big decoherence time, one needs a laser field of coherence time $\tau_{\text{coh}} \gtrsim 10^4$ s, so that any observation of decoherence during this interval can signify the existence of TS PGWs. Based on Eq. (6.46), the values $\tau_{\text{ts}} = 1.07 \times 10^4$ s for $r_{k_0} = 10^{-2}$ and $\tau_{\text{ts}} = 1.9 \times 10^4$ s for $r_{k_0} = 10^{-3}$ are found. Basically, from Eq. (6.46) one may show that $\tau_{\text{ts}} \propto r_{k_0}^{-1/4}$, hence decreasing r_{k_0} yields increasing in τ_{ts} . Considering the fact that the state of the art of ultra-stable lasers can provide $\tau_{\text{coh}} \sim 10$ s [169], one can imagine that such decoherence become detectable by future developments.

6.2.5 Temporal correlations in the presence of GWs in thermal state

A continuum of GWs in the thermal state is described by the density matrix Eq. (5.57). In this state, all modes are uncorrelated, and even more, thermal gravitons in each mode are uncorrelated with each other. The thermal state is an example of a mixed state and lacks quantum correlations. The expression of the first-order degree of coherence Eq. (6.7),

when evaluated for the thermal state, is given by (see Appendix D for details of calculations)

$$g_{\text{th}}^{(1)}(1;2) = g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(1;2)e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(1;2)}, \quad (6.48)$$

where we have defined

$$\mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(1;2) \equiv \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{X}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(1;2), \quad (6.49)$$

and $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(1;2)$ is defined by Eq. (6.11). Eq. (6.49) is in accordance with Eq. (5.77) which initiates the decaying behavior of optical squeezing. Here we have used the abbreviation $\tau_i = t - t_i$ as before. With respect to vacuum fluctuations, the thermal state possesses amplified noise in phase space. Hence, EM correlations in the presence of thermal GWs are similar to that of the vacuum fluctuations of GWs, however with an extra amplified decoherence factor stemming from the mean number of gravitons in the thermal state. Moreover, correlations depend only on the distance between the emission and reception points in space and not on the location of each point. This is a manifestation of the homogeneous nature of GWs correlations in the thermal state, which is given by (see App. A)

$$\begin{aligned} \langle h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) h^{ij}(\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\ell}, t) \rangle_{\text{th}} &= \frac{8\ell_{\text{Pl}}^2}{\pi} \int dK K \frac{\sin Kl}{KL} \\ &+ \frac{4C^2}{(2\pi)^3} \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) \cos[\mathbf{K} \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}]. \end{aligned} \quad (6.50)$$

The first term on r.h.s shows the contribution of vacuum fluctuations, while the second term represents the contribution of thermal gravitons in the two-point correlation function of GWs. However, both terms explicitly show homogeneity. As before, temporal correlations are obtained by setting $\tau_1 = t - t_1 = 0$ and $\tau_2 = t - t_2 = \tau$ in Eq. (6.49). For one-dimensional propagation of the EM field $L = z^f - z^o$ one obtains

$$g_{\text{th}}^{(1)}(L, \tau) = g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(L, \tau) e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(L, \tau)}, \quad (6.51)$$

together with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(L, \tau) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}} \right)^2 \int d\Phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) \sin^4 \Theta_K \\ &\times \int \frac{dK}{K} \left(\frac{\sin(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})}{(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})} \right)^2 \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) \left(4 \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Omega_K \tau}{2} \right) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (6.52)$$

In deriving Eq. (6.52), Eqs. (6.15, 6.16) are used. Again, the linear approximation $\Omega_K \tau \ll$

1 yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(L, \tau) &= \left[\frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}} \right)^2 \int d\Phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) \sin^4 \Theta_K \right. \\ &\quad \times \left. \int \frac{dK}{K} \left(\frac{\sin(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})}{(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})} \right)^2 \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) \Omega_K^2 \right] \tau^2 \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_{\text{th}}(L)} \right)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (6.53)$$

where the thermal-induced decoherence time is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{\text{th}}(L) &\equiv \left[\frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}} \right)^2 \int d\Phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) \sin^4 \Theta_K \right. \\ &\quad \times \left. \int \frac{dK}{K} \left(\frac{\sin(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})}{(\frac{KL \cos \Theta_K}{2})} \right)^2 \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) \Omega_K^2 \right]^{-1/2} \end{aligned} \quad (6.54)$$

In comparison with squeezed GWs, thermal GWs induce a Gaussian decoherence which is proportional to $e^{-\tau^2}$. Indeed, based on Eq. (6.51) and Eq. (6.53) in the small-detector approximation $KL \ll 1$ we obtain

$$g_{\text{th}}^{(1)}(\tau) = g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(\tau) e^{-\left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_{\text{th}}}\right)^2}, \quad (6.55)$$

where

$$\tau_{\text{th}}|_{KL \ll 1} \equiv \left[\frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}} \right)^2 \int d\Phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) \sin^4 \Theta_K \int \frac{dK}{K} \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) \Omega_K^2 \right]^{-1/2}. \quad (6.56)$$

The behavior of the temporal degree of coherence is shown in Fig. 6.4. Solid curves correspond to the full expression of $\mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(\tau)$ given by Eq. (6.52), while black dots correspond to the linear approximation $\sin(\frac{\Omega_K \tau}{2}) \sim \frac{\Omega_K \tau}{2}$ based on the analytical expression Eq. (6.53). Here, we have assumed a highly-populated thermal state as in the case of TS PGWs with $\bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) = \bar{n}_{\text{ts}}(K) \simeq e^{2r_K}/4$ and Eq. (3.56) is used. It can be seen that thermal induced decoherence time is of order $\sim 10^{-8}$ s for optical field of frequency $\omega_k = 10^{15}$ Hz, which is so small. Since typical thermal-induced decoherence time is $\sim 10^{-9}$ s, the condition $\Omega_K \tau \ll 1$ is fulfilled for $\Omega_K \lesssim 10^9$ Hz, which is in line with the previous upper bound on Ω_1 (see Sec. 3.2.2). Thus, the linear approximation works well as long as we consider the spectrum of PGWs. Note that, the results are plotted within the small-detector approximation.

With the help of Eq. (6.56), the decoherence time of the thermal background turns out to be $\tau_{\text{th}} = 1.12 \times 10^{-9}$ s for $r_{k_0} = 10^{-2}$ and $\tau_{\text{th}} = 3.6 \times 10^{-9}$ s for $r_{k_0} = 10^{-3}$. As we argued in Sec. 5.3.6, the difference between thermal and squeezed states comes from the fact that in the thermal state, the phase of gravitons is completely random. If one assumes that phase information in squeezed state is cleared in a way so that ϕ_K becomes a random variable with property $\langle e^{2i\phi_K} \rangle = \langle \cos \phi_K \rangle = \langle \sin \phi_K \rangle = 0$, then one may easily see from

Figure 6.4: Temporal degree of coherence in the case of thermal GWs for $(\beta = -2, \beta_s = 1, T_{\text{reh}} = 10^8)$. The red and blue curves correspond to $r_{k_0} = 10^{-2}$ and $r_{k_0} = 10^{-3}$, respectively. Solid curves correspond to the analytical expression Eq. (6.52) while black dots represent the linear approximation, given by Eq. (6.53). The linear approximation shows good matching with the full expression.

Eq. (6.40) that $\langle \mathcal{D}^{\text{ts-corr}}(\tau) \rangle = 0$. Here, $\langle \dots \rangle$ stands for an ensemble average corresponding to different realizations of the TS state with different random phases. Thus, $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(1; 2)$ given in Eq. (6.39) becomes identical to $\mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(1; 2)$ given by Eq. (6.49) and the bi-quadratic behavior vanishes. This is important since it highlights the role of deterministic phase ϕ_K of squeezed PGWs in optical observables and significantly changes the fate of the optical field. Of course, such a thermal background possessing an extremely large number of gravitons as in TS PGWs is only hypothetical and can be easily ruled out by means of current realizable interferometric experiments. As we discussed the temperature of thermal gravitons at the end of Sec. (5.3.6), for super-Hubble scales $K \sim K_H$ the temperature can be as high as $10^{26} \text{ K} = 8.62 \times 10^{12} \text{ GeV}$, which is not predicted by any mechanism during inflation. However, having obtained the general expression of optical correlations in the presence of a generic thermal GW background, one may put a constraint on a given scenario that predicts the existence of such a thermal background.

6.3 Spectrum of the EM field

In the previous section, we discussed temporal correlations of the EM field in the presence of GW background and showed that, depending on the state of GWs, the EM field may undergo decoherence, which causes temporal correlations to disappear after a characteristic time-scale, the inverse of which is proportional to the line-width broadening of EM spectrum in Fourier space. In this section, we calculate the power spectrum of the EM field, $S(\omega)$, which is the Fourier transform of the temporal degree of coherence $g^{(1)}(\tau)$ that we have obtained in previous sections. In particular, we compute the line-width broadening of the EM field in the case of one-mode squeezed, two-mode squeezed, and thermal GWs.

Moreover, we discuss about distinctions between these backgrounds and the possibility of detecting TS PGWs based on the EM field spectrum.

The power spectrum is obtained by taking the Fourier transform of the temporal degree of coherence Eq. (6.8) [151],

$$S(\mathbf{x}, \omega) \equiv \frac{1}{\pi} \Re \int_0^\infty g^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \tau) e^{i\omega\tau} . \quad (6.57)$$

In the following, we shall derive an expression of the optical spectrum when GWs are in the one-mode squeezed state, two-mode squeezed state, and thermal state.

6.3.1 Optical spectrum in the presence of GWs in one-mode squeezed state

The temporal degree of coherence in the presence of a one-mode squeezed state was investigated in Sec. 6.2.3. We have seen that, as a result of the inhomogeneity of the background, temporal correlations explicitly depend on \mathbf{x}^o and \mathbf{x}^f which determine the interaction volume. However, we were convinced that as far as terrestrial or space-based interferometers are concerned, the major part of the PGWs spectrum is almost homogeneous, whether in a one-mode or two-mode squeezed state. Consequently, temporal correlations of the EM field in both cases are identical, and are determined by the bi-quadratic form Eq. (6.36), namely

$$g_{\text{sq}}^{(1)}(\tau) = g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(\tau) e^{-\left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_{\text{sq}}}\right)^4} ,$$

which is the same as Eq. (6.47) for two-mode squeezed state. We examine the effect of TS PGWs on the EM spectrum in the following. The same results hold correct for the one-mode squeezed state possessing the same spectrum as PGWs.

6.3.2 Optical spectrum in the presence of TS PGWs

In the case of the so-called two-mode squeezed PGWs, temporal correlations of the EM field obey Eq. (6.47), i.e.,

$$g_{\text{ts}}^{(1)}(\tau) = e^{-\left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_{\text{ts}}}\right)^4} ,$$

where τ_{ts} is given by Eq. (6.46). The Fourier transform of $e^{-\left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_{\text{ts}}}\right)^4}$ is then given by

$$S_{\text{sq}}(\omega) = \frac{1}{\pi} \Re \int_0^\infty d\tau e^{-\left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_{\text{ts}}}\right)^4} e^{i\omega\tau} , \quad (6.58)$$

and is more complex than the standard Gaussian and does not have a simple closed-form expression in terms of the elementary functions. With the help of numerical calculations, the spectrum is calculated for two typical choices of $\tau_{\text{ts}} = 1.07 \times 10^4$ s and $\tau_{\text{ts}} = 1.9 \times 10^4$ s

corresponding to $r_{k_0} = 10^{-2}$ and $r_{k_0} = 10^{-3}$, respectively (remind that these values for tensor-to-scalar ratio correspond to current observational constraint on this parameters based on CMB surveys). Fig. 6.5 shows the plot of the optical spectrum in the presence of two-mode squeezed PGWs, where red and blue curves correspond to $r_{k_0} = 10^{-2}$ and $r_{k_0} = 10^{-3}$, respectively.

Figure 6.5: Optical spectrum in the presence of squeezed PGWs based on Eq. (6.58). Note that one-mode squeezed GWs also produce similar results. The red and blue curves correspond to $r_{k_0} = 10^{-2}$ and $r_{k_0} = 10^{-3}$, respectively. The appearance of sidebands in the spectrum is a result of the τ^4 behavior appearing in the temporal correlations.

From Fig. 6.5, it is seen that in addition to the line-width broadening induced by TS PGWs, which is proportional to the inverse decoherence time according to $\gamma_{\text{ts}} \propto (\tau_{\text{ts}})^{-1}$, the appearance of side-bands is a direct result of the τ^4 behavior of temporal correlations, induced by the TS PGW background. We remember from the discussion in Sec. 6.2.5 that the τ^4 behavior is a direct result of the deterministic phase ϕ_K in the TS state. To find the location of the side-bands in the spectrum, one may use the asymptotic behavior of the Fourier transform $\phi(k) \equiv \int_0^\infty dx e^{ikx} e^{-x^4}$ at large k [170],

$$\phi(k) \sim 2^{7/6} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{3}} \frac{1}{k^{4/3}} e^{-\frac{3}{16} 2^{1/3} k^{4/3}} \cos\left(\frac{3^{3/2} 2^{1/3}}{16} k^{4/3} - \frac{\pi}{6}\right), \quad (6.59)$$

which shows an oscillatory-decaying behavior. Here, $k = (\omega - \omega_k)\tau_c$. Since $\tau_{\text{ts}} \simeq 10^4$ s, the large- k limit is more or less satisfied when $(\omega - \omega_k) \gtrsim 10^{-4}$ Hz. Hence, the approximate location of the first sidebands can be determined by maximizing the cosine term in Eq. (6.59), i.e., by

$$\omega_{\text{side}} \simeq \omega_k \pm (\gamma_{\text{ts}}) \left(\frac{\pi/6}{3^{3/2} 2^{1/3} / 16}\right)^{3/4} \sim \omega_k \pm 1.2(\tau_{\text{ts}})^{-1}. \quad (6.60)$$

where $\gamma_{\text{ts}} = (\tau_{\text{ts}})^{-1}$ is plugged in. The parameter $\Delta\omega \equiv \omega_{\text{side}} - \omega_k$ which quantifies the separation of side-bands, increases with increasing γ_{ts} , the magnitude of which is governed by the cosmological parameters $\beta, \beta_s, T_{\text{reh}}$ and in particular, r_{k_0} . Revealing the *decoherence* induced by TS PGWs based on the interferometric schema requires laser fields with extremely large coherence times $\tau_{\text{coh}} \geq \tau_{\text{sq}} \sim 10^4$ s. On the other hand, to search for side-bands in the optical spectrum, the fractional-frequency $\Delta\omega/\omega_k = (\omega_{\text{side}} - \omega_k)/\omega_k \sim 1.2(\gamma_{\text{sq}})/\omega_k \sim 10^{-19}$ should be touched, using ultrastable lasers in near future experiments. The state-of-the-art fractional-frequency instability of 7×10^{-17} for 1064 nm laser along a 2220 km optical fiber network has been reported [171]. During the passage of light through the network, the phase fluctuations remain extremely small. This opens the room to search for the finest effects in the spectrum of light, including the appearance of sidebands, which could be a demonstration of the existence of inflationary-generated two-mode squeezed PGWs.

6.3.3 Optical spectrum in the presence of thermal GWs

The temporal degree of coherence in the case of GWs with thermal gravitons is given by Eq. (6.51). In a hypothetical schema that we consider high graviton contents as in two-mode squeezed PGWs, we could be able to use the linear approximation (where $\Omega_K \tau \ll 1$) and find a Gaussian decay of temporal correlations given by Eq. (6.55). This yields a Gaussian spectrum,

$$S_{\text{th}}(\omega) = \sqrt{\pi} \tau_{\text{th}} e^{-\left(\frac{(\omega - \omega_k)^2 (\tau_{\text{th}})^2}{4}\right)}. \quad (6.61)$$

with a broadening $\gamma_{\text{th}} \sim 2(\tau_{\text{th}})^{-1}$ with τ_{th} given by Eq. (6.56) in the small-detector limit. The spectrum is shown in Fig. 6.6. It is seen that, under the aforementioned conditions described in Sec. 6.2.5, thermal gravitons induce line-width broadening of order $\gamma_{\text{th}} \sim 10^9$ Hz for EM field of optical frequency $\omega_k = 10^{15}$ Hz, which is too large.

A larger tensor-to-scalar ratio induces a broader line-width. Indeed, from Eq. (6.56), one may show that $\tau_{\text{th}} \propto r_{k_0}^{-1/2}$. Numerically, one has $\gamma_{\text{th}} = 1.7 \times 10^9$ Hz for $r_{k_0} = 10^{-2}$ and $\gamma_{\text{th}} = 5.6 \times 10^8$ Hz for $r_{k_0} = 10^{-3}$. Of course, such a large broadening induced by the hypothetical thermal background could be revealed and ruled out by current spectral experiments. Remind that the temperature of this thermal background can be as high as $\sim 10^{12}$ GeV, which is not predicted by a possible mechanism in the early Universe.

We conclude this chapter by clarifying some point about the decoherence induced by gravitational waves. In the present framework, we have used the nomination ‘‘decoherence’’ to describe the loss of temporal correlations of the EM field induced by the GW’s environment. However, it is also convenient to use the word ‘‘decoherence’’ to imply the loss of quantum purity, defined as $\text{Tr}(\rho^2) > 1$, where $\rho(t)$ is the density matrix of the system. The two concepts bear similarities (the loss of phase coherence in a quantum state is usually associated to the increase of its purity away from unity but they are nonetheless

Figure 6.6: Optical spectrum in the presence of thermal GWs based on Eq. (6.61). It is assumed that the mean number of thermal gravitons is as high as that of TS PGWs, i.e., $\bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) = e^{2r_K}/4$ and the optical frequency $\omega_k = 10^{15}$ Hz is chosen. The red and blue curves correspond to $r_{k_0} = 10^{-2}$ and $r_{k_0} = 10^{-3}$, respectively.

distinct a priori. In the present context, one could follow the density matrix approach to find the Lindblad equation describing the evolution of the system. Regarding the two-mode squeezed PGWs, one ends up with the conclusion that the density matrix operator in the Fock state representation (and in the small-detector approximation) obeys

$$\rho_{nm}(t) = e^{-\frac{(n-m)^2}{8} \left(\frac{t}{\tau_{\text{ts}}}\right)^4} \rho_{nm}(0), \quad (6.62)$$

where τ_{ts} is given by Eq. (4.46) in the small-detector condition $KL \ll 1$. It is obvious that the populations (corresponding to $n = m$ components of the density matrix) do not change with time, while the off-diagonal elements ($n \neq m$) which show transition probabilities between two states $|n\rangle$ and $|m\rangle$ will drastically decay after τ_{ts} . Hence, one may convince that the reduction of temporal coherences is accompanied by the loss of correlations in the system, such that the EM signal evolves into a state which is completely diagonal.

6.4 Summary and conclusions

In this chapter, the decoherence of the optical field induced by quantum GWs was investigated, based on the framework we developed in previous chapters. In summary:

- General expression of the two-point correlation function of the optical field was derived, where we considered different quantum states for GWs, namely, vacuum, coherent, one-mode squeezed, two-mode squeezed, and thermal states.
- Assuming *stationarity* of GWs, we found the temporal correlation of the EM field.

We discussed the homogeneity or inhomogeneity of the correlation function and argued that these features are inherited from the two-point correlation function of GWs.

- Generally speaking, quantum fluctuations of GWs induce decoherence of the EM field. The magnitude of the effect depends on (i) the mean number of gravitons in the state and (ii) the existence or absence of a deterministic phase between gravitons in the state. On the other hand, in order to compensate for small EM-GWs coupling strength, one needs a large number of gravitons $\bar{n}_{\text{gw}} \sim (E_{\text{pl}}/\hbar\omega_k)^2$ to see an observable effect on the optical field.
- The effect of vacuum fluctuations on optical correlations is negligibly small and can be safely ignored. The coherent state of GWs induces an extra oscillating factor to the interference pattern of the optical field, which may change the periodicity of the maxima and minima in the interference pattern.
- One-mode squeezed, two-mode squeezed and thermal GWs contribute only to the decoherence of the EM field, as a result of amplified quantum noise (in phase space). However, due to the deterministic squeezing phase in squeezed GWs and the indeterministic phase in the thermal state, the temporal behavior of correlations drastically changes.
- The other vital factor in optical correlations is the homogeneity of the GWs; two-mode squeezed and thermal GWs show homogeneity, while the one-mode squeezed state lacks homogeneity. As a result, decoherence induced by two-mode squeezed and thermal gravitons depends only on the length of propagation of the EM field, while the decoherence induced by one-mode squeezed GWs depends also on the emission and reception points.
- Within the *small-detector* approximation $KL \ll 1$ which is appropriate considering the typical length-scale of terrestrial and space-based interferometers and concerning PGWs spectrum, correlations of GWs become almost homogeneous whether in one-mode or two-mode squeezed state. As a result, both backgrounds leave almost identical decoherence on temporal correlations of the EM field. In this regard, one-mode and two-mode squeezed GWs are *indistinguishable* as far as small-scale probes are concerned.
- Within the linear approximation, which is useful when considering the spectrum of PGWs determined by Eq. (3.56), we obtained simplified expressions for the decoherence time, induced by GWs. We compared the results and tried to understand the distinctions between different GW backgrounds. We argued how the decoherence induced by TS PGWs may be revealed using interferometric setups.

- Eventually, the optical spectrum was investigated. While thermal GWs show a Gaussian spectrum, one-mode, and two-mode squeezed PGWs induce secondary picks in the optical field, stemming from a deterministic squeezing phase in the squeezed state. Since thermal states do not possess this feature, observing the sidebands in the optical spectrum could point to the existence of PGWs in the squeezed state.

Chapter 7

PGWs-induced incoherence of light

In the previous chapters, we examined the possibility of detecting PGWs background with the help of EM observables, namely the optical variance (see Chapter 5) and EM temporal correlations (see Chapter 6). It was realized that detection of TS PGWs induced-decoherence is contingent upon coherent laser fields possessing coherence times of order $\tau_{\text{coh}} \gtrsim 10^4$ s, which seems challenging given the current laboratory and technical limitations. Hence, the question arises: does the GW background affect *spatial correlations* of the EM field? In contrast to temporal correlations that are highly sensitive to environmental effects, spatial correlations of a source are known to be immune to the typical environment-induced-decoherence. In particular, the van Citter-Zernike theorem implies that the correlation length of an initially spatial-incoherent source grows with distance [166]. Hence, sources at cosmological distances that have had enough time to interact with the underlying gravitational wave background seem proper candidates to explore the underlying quantum gravitational effects.

Inquiring the Planck-scale quantum features of spacetime with the help of interferometric schemes, based on the phase properties of the EM field, is an old quest [83, 84, 85, 86, 87, 172, 173, 174, 175]. For instance, the phase interferometric approach early introduced in [84] inspects the Planck-scale physics through the spacetime foam-induced *phase incoherence* of light emitted from distant objects. In fact, it has been perceived that the accumulation of tiny phase-incoherence during the long journey of light through the quantum fluctuations of the vacuum spacetime leads to the loss of the phase of radiation at large distances. This approach was elaborated in [85] to rule out or put stringent limits on some Planck-scale phenomenological models, by evidence of the diffraction pattern from the Hubble Space Telescope observations of SN 1994D and the unresolved appearance of a Hubble Deep Field galaxy at $z = 5.34$. However, further studies [176] declared that such effects “are far below what is required in this approach to shed light on the foaminess of spacetime”. Moreover, it was soon realized [177] that such an argument is only relevant for a *division of amplitude* interference (like what occurs in a Michelson interferometer) whereas in a *division of wavefront* interference, such as in the stellar interferometry, the propagation of coherence is simply governed by the van-Citter Zernike theorem [166]. The

former is connected to the notion of “temporal coherence” of a source, which we discussed in detail in Chapter 6, while the latter is relevant to its “spatial coherence”, i.e., the phase correlations of the wavefronts at two points of space. It turned out that “spatial correlations are immune to any underlying fuzzy Planck scale”, hence the Planck scale still remains inaccessible to interferometer detection with present technology [177]. Albeit, this result leaves room for quantum gravitational effects on length scales much larger than the Planck length. One important example is the relic background of inflationary-generated PGWs, as we described in detail in Chapter 2 and Chapter 3. The typical wavelength of PGWs is of the order of the Hubble scale, thus much larger than the Planck scale. PGWs are a small handful of naturally generated non-classical states of GWs, detection of which would not only confirm the inflationary scenario but also validate the quantum description of gravity at scales much larger than the Planck length.

The preceding arguments led us to examine the influence of GWs on spatial correlations of light, which are equal-time correlations between fields at two points \mathbf{x}_1 and \mathbf{x}_2 , radiated from distant objects. In line with the previous framework that we developed to describe EM-GWs interaction, in this chapter, we derive the equal-time correlation function of the EM field in the presence of GWs in different states. In particular, the possibility of detection of inflationary-generated PGWs with the help of spatial interferometric methods is investigated. To do so, we consider the experimental setup of a typical spatial interferometer, say the Michelson stellar interferometer. We find that the existence of PGWs in the two-mode squeezed state leads to the *blurring* of the EM visibility pattern, while vacuum and coherent states do not. We also examine the effect for GWs in the thermal state with the same content of gravitons as in the TS state but lacking quantum correlations that exist between gravitons in the TS state. We show how different parameters of the model, such as $\beta, \beta_s, T_{\text{reh}}$ and r_{k_0} emerge in the calculations. The main idea of the present study is to promote the use of high-precision VLBI measurement of angular size-redshift of distant sources, as a new possible way of constraining the underlying primordial background, in parallel to other surveys such as the cosmic microwave background. In particular, the present schema can pave the way to search for the effect of scalar curvature perturbations in the VLBI $\theta - z$ measurements.

7.1 Spatial correlation of EM field in free space

In this section, we present some basic formulas about the notion of spatial coherence, the van Citter-Zernike theorem, and its application to the very long baseline interferometers.

7.1.1 Spatial coherence and transverse coherence length

In Fig. 7.1, a simple schematic diagram of a typical Young’s double-slit experiment to measure spatial correlations is shown. Here, the quasi-monochromatic light from an *extended source* having radius a and located at sufficiently long distance $R = ct_{\text{int}}$ (with t_{int}

Figure 7.1: Spatial coherence illustrated by means of Young's interference experiment with light from a thermal source of radius a . Here, $\alpha \equiv \frac{d}{R}$ and $\theta \equiv \frac{2a}{R}$.

being called the time of flight or the interaction time as before), illuminates the two-slit on the screen \mathcal{A} . In this setup, it is assumed that the distance between the two-slit plane \mathcal{A} and the observation screen \mathcal{S} is much smaller than R . The incoming radiation passes through two pinholes P_1 and P_2 (which can be two telescopes in a real stellar interferometer setup or two detectors in a VLBI experiment). If the pinholes P_1 and P_2 are sufficiently close, the interference pattern will be observed in the neighborhood of the axial point P on the screen \mathcal{S} provided that $\alpha a \lesssim \lambda_k$, where α is the angle subtended by P_1P_2 when viewed from the source, i.e., $\alpha \equiv \frac{d}{R}$ and λ_k is the mean wavelength of the source (see Fig. 7.1). This condition is equivalent to saying that, the path difference between two rays emitted from distant edges of the source must be smaller than the mean wavelength of the source. The appearance of the fringes is said to be a manifestation of *spatial coherence*. Note that, the rays reach the slits simultaneously so that there is no time delay $\tau = t - t_2 - (t - t_1)$ as in the case of temporal correlations. The final interference pattern is made from the superposition of the fields emitted from all points located on the source. If R denotes the distance between the plane of source and the plane \mathcal{A} containing the pinholes, the foregoing condition implies that, in order to observe the fringes near P , the separation between pinholes d must be $d \lesssim \frac{\lambda_k}{\theta}$, where θ is the angle the source of linear size a subtends at the origin O , i.e., $\theta \sim \frac{a}{R}$. Thus, $d \sim \frac{\lambda}{\theta}$ is sometimes called the *transverse coherence length* [166].

7.1.2 Van Citter-Zernike theorem

The state of coherence of light may be appreciably changed in the process of its propagation in free space. The precise quantitative description of spatial coherence is provided on the basis of propagation of correlations, where dynamical equations for the mutual co-

herence function $G^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t_1; \mathbf{x}_2, t_2)$ is investigated [167]. One of the central theorems of the elementary theory of partial coherence was formulated earlier by van Citter (1934) and later, in a more general form, by Zernike (1938). The *van Citter-Zernike theorem* expresses the field correlations at two points in space, generated by a spatially incoherent, quasi-monochromatic, planar source. According to our previous formulation, this is nothing but $G^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t - t_1; \mathbf{x}_2, t - t_2)$ with $t - t_1 = t - t_2 \equiv t_{\text{int}}$. We may call it *mutual intensity* and denote it by

$$J(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) \equiv G^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t; \mathbf{x}_2, t). \quad (7.1)$$

where t now stands for the time of flight of the EM field through GW background. Ac-

Figure 7.2: Illustration of the van Citter-Zernike theorem. The extended source σ with radius a sends EM radiation that is going to be detected at two detectors D_1 and D_2 . Different quantities used in Eq. (7.3) are shown.

cordingly, the normalized (equal-time) mutual intensity is specified by (see Eq. (6.7))

$$g^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t; \mathbf{x}_2, t) = \frac{\langle \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle}{\langle \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \rangle} e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2)}. \quad (7.2)$$

In the free space and in the absence of GWs, the equal-time degree of coherence at two points $P_1(\mathbf{x}_1)$ and $P_2(\mathbf{x}_2)$ in the field generated by a planar, spatially incoherent, quasi-monochromatic source σ of radius a , is determined by the *Zernike's propagation law* [166]

$$J(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) \equiv G^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) = \frac{1}{[I(\mathbf{x}_1)]^{1/2} [I(\mathbf{x}_2)]^{1/2}} \left(\frac{k}{2\pi} \right)^2 \int_{\sigma} d\sigma' I(\mathbf{x}') \frac{e^{ik(R_2 - R_1)}}{R_1 R_2}, \quad (7.3)$$

where R_1 and R_2 are the distances from a typical point source $d\sigma'$ on the source to the points $P_1(\mathbf{x}_1)$ and $P_2(\mathbf{x}_2)$ (see Fig. 7.2), and k is the mean wave number of the EM field. The formula (7.3) expresses the degree of mutual intensity of the source σ in terms of the intensities $I(\mathbf{x}_1)$ and $I(\mathbf{x}_2)$ at the two field points and the intensity distribution $I(\mathbf{x}')$ across the source multiplied by the phase-difference factor $e^{ik(R_2 - R_1)}$. Usually, the observation

points $P_1(\mathbf{x}_1)$ and $P_2(\mathbf{x}_2)$ are situated in the far zone of the source and could be, for instance, the location of two telescopes on the Earth which collect the EM radiation. After performing integration in Eq. (7.3), the far-zone form of the van Citter-Zernike theorem turns out to be given by [166]

$$j(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) = \frac{2J_1(\nu)}{\nu}, \quad (7.4)$$

which is normalized to the total intensity. Here, $\nu \equiv ka|\mathbf{s}_{2\perp} - \mathbf{s}_{1\perp}|$ with $\mathbf{s}_{i\perp}$ ($i = 1, 2$) being the projection, considered as two-dimensional vector, of the three-dimensional unit vector \mathbf{s}_i onto the source plane. For instance, if the unit normal vector is $\hat{\mathbf{w}}$, the projection of \mathbf{s}_i onto the source plane has only \hat{u} and \hat{v} components, where (u, v) show two coordinates transverse to the normal vector of the plane source. Moreover, $J_1(\nu)$ is the Bessel function of the first kind and first order. In the far-zone one may take the points $P_i(\mathbf{x}_i)$ to be located at the same distance $r_1 \simeq r_2 \simeq R$ from the source and one has $\mathbf{s}_{i\perp} = (\frac{u_i}{R}, \frac{v_i}{R}, 0)$. Hence

$$\nu = k\left(\frac{a}{R}\right)\left((u_1 - u_2)^2 + (v_1 - v_2)^2\right)^{1/2} = k\left(\frac{a}{R}\right)d, \quad (7.5)$$

where d is the distance between the observation points $P_1(\mathbf{x}_1)$ and $P_2(\mathbf{x}_2)$. Note that, d is the transverse distance between \mathbf{x}_1 and \mathbf{x}_2 . The function $j(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2)$ is plotted in Fig. 7.3 versus the dimensionless parameter ν . Starting from complete coherence $j(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) = 1$ at zero distance d , correlations decrease steadily by increasing the distance between the points from $d = 0$ to $d = (3.83)k^{-1}(R/a)$ where complete incoherence $j(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) = 0$ happens for the first time. A further increase in d leads to reconstruction of coherence (in absolute value), but smaller than 0.14.

Figure 7.3: The mutual intensity $j(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) = \frac{2J_1(\nu)}{\nu}$ versus the dimensionless parameter $\nu = k\left(\frac{a}{R}\right)d$. The colored region corresponds to the coherence length $0 \leq d \leq \frac{2}{k\theta}$ where correlations decrease from unity to a value of 0.88. The mutual intensity vanishes for the first time for $\nu = 3.83$.

is collected by two or more spatially separated telescopes (Fig. 7.4). The existence of spatial correlations throughout the projected baseline of the interferometer leads to the non-vanishing visibility pattern, which is used to determine geometrical properties of the object, such as its angular diameter; The notion of spatial correlations was first used in the Hanbury Brown and Twiss intensity interferometry to infer the angular diameter of Sirius A based on spatial correlations [184].

Noticeably, VLBI imaging has found great attention in constraining cosmology. For instance, the Event Horizon Telescope (EHT) which is a VLBI array imaging supermassive black holes (SMBHs) on event horizon scales, allows tests of deviation from general relativity by performing high precision measurements of the Kerr metric [185, 186]. Moreover, the Megamaser Cosmology Project (MCP) which is based on the VLBI sub-milliarcsecond angular mapping of compact objects, has provided an independent laboratory to constrain the Hubble constant, H_0 , in parallel to other surveys such as CMB [187], likewise putting updated constraints on the mass of SMBHs [188]. In particular, the capability of the VLBI method inaccurate measurement of the angular size-redshift ($\theta - z$) of intermediate-luminosity radio quasars has led to specify AGNs as astrophysical standard rulers with intrinsic size $\ell_m \sim 11.03$ pc, that can be used to constrain cosmological parameters, namely H_0, Ω_m, w_Λ [189, 190, 191]. Recently, the capability of the stellar interferometry as a potential tool to detect GWs in the lower frequency range ($10^{-6} - 10^{-4}$) Hz has been investigated [192]. However, to our best knowledge, VLBI measurements of the angular size-redshift have not yet been used to constrain the background of PGWs. Here, we promote the idea of employing stellar interferometric methods to investigate the underlying gravitational background of PGWs.

The schematic view of a typical VLBI instrument is shown in Fig. 7.4. It consists of two telescopes that collect the incoming EM radiation from a distant source: two telescopes located at \mathbf{x}_1 and \mathbf{x}_2 collect the EM field rays $E(\mathbf{x}_1, t - t_1)$ and $E(\mathbf{x}_2, t - t_2)$, then the signals are correlated at zero time-difference so that the mutual intensity, also called as visibility in the literature of VLBI, $j(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2)$ is obtained. However, as we shall discuss in the following, the presence of PGWs appears as a decaying factor which could spoil the interference pattern, depending on the value of the tensor-to-scalar ratio.

Nevertheless, successful measurement of the angular size θ of distant objects based on visibility implies that the correlation length of the source is at least as long as the projected baseline of the VLBI instrument, say $d = b \sin \vartheta_s$, where ϑ_s denotes the angle between the line of sight and the baseline of the interferometer. Otherwise, the interference pattern vanishes as a result of vanishing visibility. Note that d given in Eq. (7.6) represents the transverse coherence length, in normal incidence when $\vartheta_s = 90^\circ$. In the following, without loss of generality, we consider the case of normal incidence, where $b = d = d_{\text{coh}} = \frac{2}{k\theta}$. In the practical situation of VLBI experiments the geometrical delay time τ_g arising from the asymmetric configuration of the instrument with respect to the line of sight of the source is usually compensated, so that the equal-time correlation of EM signals $\langle E(\mathbf{x}_1, t)E(\mathbf{x}_2, t) \rangle$

is achieved [178]. Hence, one may regard the separation length $d \equiv d_{\text{coh}} \equiv 2/(k\theta)$ as a threshold of coherence. In the following, we introduce the $\theta - z$ data measured by VLBI means, based on the existence of spatial coherence throughout the VLBI network.

Figure 7.5: The scatter plot of angular sizes of 120 compact radio quasars based on the data given in Table. 1 of Cao et al [189]. The cyan line denotes the angular size $\theta(z)$ given by Eq. (7.7) with $\ell_m = 11.03$ pc, calculated from the fiducial flat Λ CDM model with $H_0 = 67.4$ km s $^{-1}$ Mpc $^{-1}$ and $\Omega_m = 0.3$ adopted from the Planck results (Planck Collaboration et al. 2020) [191].

7.1.4 VLBI measurement of the angular size of standard ruler

The angular size-redshift relation for an object of metric size ℓ_m in the flat Λ CDM model (neglecting the radiation fractional energy density Ω_r) is given by [101]

$$\theta(z) = \frac{\ell_m}{L(z)} = \frac{\ell_m H_0 (1+z)}{c} \left(\int_0^z \frac{dz'}{\sqrt{\Omega_m (1+z')^3 + (1-\Omega_m)}} \right)^{-1}, \quad (7.7)$$

where $L(z)$ is the angular distance, ℓ_m is the proper size of the object, and other parameters are cosmological parameters previously defined in Chapter 2 (note that 1 radian is approximately 206265×10^3 mas). In principle, having standard rulers distributed over a range of redshifts is used to measure the angular diameter versus redshift relation and hence determine the cosmological parameters (here H_0 and Ω_m for example). Recently, a set of 120 milliarcsecond compact radio sources representing intermediate-luminosity quasars covering the redshift range $0.46 \leq z \leq 2.76$ has been investigated to check the possibility of using them as independent cosmological probes. These quasars observed at 2.29 GHz show negligible dependence on redshift and intrinsic luminosity, and thus represent a fixed comoving-length of a standard ruler. It is found that the compact structure in the intermediate-luminosity radio quasars could serve as a standard cosmological

ruler and could thus provide valuable sources of angular diameter-distance at high redshifts ($z \sim 3.0$), reaching beyond feasible limits of supernova studies [189, 193]. This new approach has recently used to demonstrate that these standard rulers could be helpful in the context of the current cosmological issues concerning the Hubble tension and other cosmological tensions [191]. Using a compilation of angular size-redshift data for ultra-compact radio sources from a well-known VLBI survey, the linear size of this standard ruler turns out to be $\ell_m = 11.03 \pm 0.25$ pc, which is the typical radius at which AGN jets become opaque at the observed frequency $\omega_k \sim 2$ GHz.

The scatter diagram of the observed angular size for 120 radio quasars described in [189, 190, 194] with redshift range between $z = 0.462$ and $z = 2.73$ is shown in Fig. 7.5. These objects are chosen from a well-known 2.29 GHz VLBI survey called P85 [195]. Detailed information about angular size, $\theta(z)$, and redshift, z , data are listed in Table. 1 of Cao et al [189]. In this figure, the cyan line corresponds to fiducial Λ CDM model Eq. (7.8) with $H_0 = 67.4 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ and $\Omega_m = 0.3$ adopted from the Planck results (Planck Collaboration et al. 2020 [112]). Moreover, the linear size of the standard ruler $\ell_m = 11.03$ pc is chosen [191].

What makes the preceding approach remarkable for us lies in the fact that these observations are made based on the VLBI technique, i.e., based on the notion of spatial correlations of the radio quasars. In the rest of the chapter, we try to find the incoherence induced by quantum GWs in different states, as described in Sec. 5.2.5. To do so, we first find the evolution of spherical electromagnetic waves in the presence of quantum GWs. Then, the two-point degree of coherence of the EM field is calculated for GWs in different quantum states.

7.2 EM correlations of an extended source in the presence of a generic quantum GW background

Following the same procedure pursued in Chapter 5 and Chapter 6, here we investigate the equal-time degree of coherence $g^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t; \mathbf{x}_2, t)$ when the EM field is traveling through GWs background and interacts with it. To do so, we should first generalize the formalism that we have developed for plane EM waves to the case of spherical GWs. This step is done next section.

7.2.1 Spherical EM waves in the presence of GWs

In this section, we consider the propagation of spherical waves in the presence of GWs background, as schematically shown in Fig. 7.7. The EM field is emitted from a point source located at \mathbf{x}_s from the origin of coordinate system, and is going to be observed at a distance R from it, at a time instant t . We derive the Hamiltonian and solve the Heisenberg equation governing a single-mode EM field. This step helps us investigate Glauber's

correlation functions of the EM field in the presence of such quantum background, in the next sections.

Figure 7.6: Spherical wave emission from a point source and its interaction with GWs background. The interaction takes place in a half-sphere of radius R . The vectors $\mathbf{x} = (r, \theta, \phi)$ and $\mathbf{K} = (K, \Theta_K, \Phi_K)$ are represented in spherical coordinates. The vector \mathbf{x}_s represents the location of the point source with respect to some coordinate system, and \mathbf{x} shows a typical point inside the interaction volume V , where interaction between EM field and GWs takes place.

The OMA approach can be straightforwardly generalized to obtain dynamics of spherical waves in the presence of GWs. The generalization is left to App. E.1. The spherical EM wave emitted from the point source (shown by the red circle in Fig. 7.7) propagates through spacetime while interacting with GWs. Interaction with GWs occurs in a volume V which is a semi-sphere of radius R . Dynamics of the EM field can be derived with the replacement of plane waves $\mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}} \propto e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}}$ with spherical mode functions $\mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}} \propto \frac{e^{ikr}}{r}$ in Eq. (4.36). Performing similar calculations as in Sec. 5.1.2, one ends up with the following expression for the dynamics of the EM ladder operators (see App. E.1)

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{a}_k(R, t) &= \left[\prod_{\lambda, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \lambda}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R, t)) \otimes \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \lambda}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(R, t)) \right] \\ &\times e^{2iE(R, t) (\hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k + \frac{1}{2})} e^{-i\omega_k t} \hat{a}_k, \end{aligned} \quad (7.8)$$

where the function $\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R, t)$ is defined by

$$\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R, t) \equiv (1 - e^{i\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}) \mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\lambda*}(R), \quad (7.9)$$

and is a generalization of Eq. (5.41) to spherical waves, and the spatial function $\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R)$ is a generalization of the function $g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)$ defined by Eq. (5.18) to the case of spherical waves and is defined by

$$\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R) \equiv \frac{e^{i\mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x}_s}}{2\pi R} \int d\Omega_{\hat{r}} e^{i\lambda[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j} \int_0^R dr e^{i\mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x}}. \quad (7.10)$$

In Eq. (7.10), $d\Omega_{\hat{r}} \equiv d(\cos \theta) d\phi$ is the spatial angular element with $0 \leq \phi \leq 2\pi$ and $0 \leq \theta \leq \pi$ and the unit vector \hat{r} in the spherical coordinates is specified by $\hat{r} = (\sin \theta \cos \phi, \sin \theta \sin \phi, \cos \theta)$. Moreover, the radial integration is taken from $r = 0$ to $r = R$.

7.2.2 Equal-time degree of coherence of an extended source in the presence of GWs

In this section, we compute the general expression of the correlation function appearing in the interference pattern of a typical VLBI apparatus, like the one described in Fig. 7.4. The electric field of the incoming light is collected by two detectors D_1 and D_2 located at \mathbf{x}_1 and \mathbf{x}_2 , at time t . The total electric field received at the correlator at point \mathbf{x}_C is thus determined by $\hat{E}(\mathbf{x}_C, t) = \hat{E}^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}_C, t) + \hat{E}^{(-)}(\mathbf{x}_C, t)$, where the positive and negative frequency parts of the electric field are defined by

$$\hat{E}^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}_C, t) = \hat{E}^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t - \tau_1) + \hat{E}^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}_2, t - \tau_2), \quad (7.11)$$

and its Hermitian conjugate. Here, τ_i accounts for the time delay of the EM signal through the arm $\overline{D_i P}$, with $i = 1, 2$, and $\hat{E}^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}_i, t - \tau_i)$ stands for the electric field at the location of the i -th detector at the delay time $t - \tau_i$. In the symmetric setup one has $\tau_1 = \tau_2$, which is also true in VLBI measurement thanks to the geometric delay line that ensures equal time correlation. Since we neglect the effect of the GWs background during the time delays τ_i (practically $\tau_i \ll t$), we can proceed by setting $t - \tau_1 = t - \tau_2 \equiv t$. Therefore, t will refer to the time at which the EM signal arrives at the detectors, which can also be called the time of flight or the interaction time. The expression of the intensity at point P now reads

$$I(\mathbf{x}_C, t) = \langle \hat{E}^{(-)}(\mathbf{x}_C, t) \hat{E}^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}_C, t) \rangle, \quad (7.12)$$

The electric field $\hat{E}(\mathbf{x}_C, t)$ is a superposition of spherical waves emitted from different parts of the planar disc. In order to proceed, we assume that the surface of the planar disc with area $A = \pi a^2$ is divided into N equal sub-surfaces, each of them radiating spherical waves independently. From the expression of $\hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ given in Eq. (E.1), the electric field induced by spherical waves possessing wave number k , emitted from all point sources, each of which located at \mathbf{x}' , at the observation point \mathbf{x}_i (with $i = 1, 2$) is determined by

$$\hat{E}(\mathbf{x}_i, t) = \sum_{j=1}^N \mathcal{E}_j(\hat{a}_j(R_{ij}, t) \frac{e^{ikR_{ij}}}{R_{ij}} + \text{h.c.}), \quad (7.13)$$

where \mathcal{E}_j is the electric field amplitude and is irrelevant in subsequent calculations. We can proceed by a constant amplitude for all independent point sources, $\mathcal{E}_j \equiv \mathcal{E}$, assuming a uniform radiation intensity from the source. As it can be seen from Fig. 7.2, R_{ij} stands for the distance between the j -th source element from the i -th detector. By combining Eq.(7.11) and Eq. (7.13), one can identify the positive (and negative) frequency part of the total electric field at \mathbf{x}_C , as follows

$$\hat{E}^{(+)}(\mathbf{x}_C, t) = \mathcal{E} \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\hat{a}_j(R_{1j}, t) \frac{e^{ikR_{1j}}}{R_{1j}} + \hat{a}_j(R_{2j}, t) \frac{e^{ikR_{2j}}}{R_{2j}} \right), \quad (7.14)$$

and its Hermitian conjugate. Here, R_{1j} and R_{2j} show the distance of the first and second detector with respect to the j -th source point located at \mathbf{x}'_j . The evolution of the EM field through GW background is determined by Eq. (7.8). Plugging Eq. (7.14) into Eq. (7.12), the intensity $I(\mathbf{x}_C, t)$ is determined by

$$\begin{aligned} I(\mathbf{x}_C, t) = & |\mathcal{E}|^2 \sum_{j=1}^N \left\{ \frac{\langle \hat{n}_j(R_{1j}, t) \rangle}{R_{1j}^2} + \frac{\langle \hat{n}_j(R_{2j}, t) \rangle}{R_{2j}^2} \right. \\ & \left. + 2\Re \left[\langle \hat{a}_j^\dagger(R_{1j}, t) \hat{a}_j(R_{2j}, t) \rangle \frac{e^{-ik(R_{1j}-R_{2j})}}{R_{1j}R_{2j}} \right] \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (7.15)$$

Here, cross-correlations of type $\langle \hat{a}_j^\dagger \hat{a}_{j'} \rangle = \langle \hat{a}_j^\dagger \rangle \langle \hat{a}_{j'} \rangle$ between independent modes j and j' (emitted from different point sources) vanish, assuming that each mode of the EM field is in thermal state for which $\langle \hat{a}_j \rangle = 0$. Since the EM-GWs Hamiltonian Eq. (E.40) preserves the number of photons in the adiabatic approximation, the mean number of photons is conserved and is equal to its initial value at the moment of emission. Hence, we can set

$$\langle \hat{n}_k(R_{ij}, t) \rangle \equiv \langle \hat{n}_k \rangle, \quad i = 1, 2. \quad (7.16)$$

where $\langle \hat{n}_k \rangle$ shows the mean number of photons with wave number k . The first two terms in Eq. (7.15) represent the intensity at the detectors while the last term shows the role of correlations in mode j , in the interference pattern. In absence of GWs, the annihilation operator simply reduces to the free field case, $\hat{a}_j(R_{ij}, t) \rightarrow e^{-i\omega_k t} \hat{a}_j$ (see Eq. (7.8)) and Eq. (7.15) recasts to the free-field expression. The quantity inside the brackets is closely related to the equal-time first-order degree of coherence which is usually defined by [196]

$$g_j^{(1)}(R_{1j}, t; R_{2j}, t) \equiv \frac{\langle \hat{a}_j^\dagger(R_{1j}, t) \hat{a}_j(R_{2j}, t) \rangle}{\langle \hat{n}_k \rangle} e^{-ik(R_{1j}-R_{2j})}, \quad (7.17)$$

The expectation value in Eq. (7.17) is generally taken over the total state $\hat{\rho} = \hat{\rho}_{\text{gw}} \otimes \hat{\rho}_j$, where $\hat{\rho}_{\text{gw}}$ describes the state of GWs, and $\hat{\rho}_j$ stands for the density matrix of the EM field of mode k emitted from \mathbf{x}'_j . The emission of distant objects can be assumed to be dominated by a thermal emission with a mean number of photons $\langle \hat{n}_k \rangle = [\exp(\hbar\omega_k/k_B T) - 1]^{-1}$. However, as it can be seen from Eqs. (7.15 - 7.17), the state of the EM field does not play

an important role and only the mean number of photons appears. This is one of the main features that makes spatial correlations favorable with respect to temporal correlations that drastically depend on the EM state. Thus, the degree of coherence depends *only* on the state of GWs. Combining Eqs. (7.15 - 7.17) yields

$$I(\mathbf{x}_C, t) = \frac{2|\mathcal{E}|^2\langle\hat{n}_k\rangle}{R^2} \sum_{j=1}^N \left\{ 1 + \Re[g_j^{(1)}(R_{1j}, t; R_{2j}, t)] \right\}. \quad (7.18)$$

In deriving Eq. (7.18) we have replaced in the denominators $R_{1j} \simeq R_{2j} \equiv R$, while the path difference $R_{1j} - R_{2j}$ must be kept in the phase factors as it is the originate of spatial correlations. One may check that, in the absence of GW background one has $g_j^{(1)}(R_{1j}, t; R_{2j}, t) \rightarrow e^{-ik(R_{1j}-R_{2j})}$ and Eq. (7.18) reduces to the standard interference pattern in free space (see Eq. (4.1.24) of [196]). The summation over discrete index j can be replaced by integration over the surface of the planar disc according to $\sum_{j=1}^N a_j(\mathbf{x}'_j) \rightarrow \int_{\sigma} \frac{d\sigma'}{A} a(\mathbf{x}')$ for arbitrary sequence $a_j(\mathbf{x}'_j)$, where $d\sigma'$ stands for the surface element and $A = \pi a^2$ is the area of the planar source. Thus, the expression of the intensity $I(\mathbf{x}_C, t)$ given in Eq. (7.18) is written as

$$I(\mathbf{x}_C, t) = \frac{2|\mathcal{E}|^2\langle\hat{n}_k\rangle}{R^2} \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{\pi a^2} \Re \left[\int_{\sigma} d\sigma' g^{(1)}(R_1, t; R_2, t) \right] \right\}. \quad (7.19)$$

Here, $d\sigma' = \rho' d\rho' d\phi'$ is the surface element with $0 \leq \rho' \leq a$ and $0 \leq \phi' \leq 2\pi$, and the integration is performed over the area of the disc. The two-point correlation function $g^{(1)}(R_1, t; R_2, t)$ should be evaluated from Eq. (7.17) where R_1 and R_2 are shown in Fig. (7.2). In absence of GWs Eq. (7.19) yields the van Citter-Zernike correlations,

$$I(\mathbf{x}_C, t) = \frac{2|\mathcal{E}|^2\langle\hat{n}_k\rangle}{R^2} (1 + j(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2)), \quad (7.20)$$

where the two-point function

$$j(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) \equiv \frac{\int_{\sigma} d\sigma' e^{-ik(R_1-R_2)}}{\pi a^2}, \quad (7.21)$$

is called the *mutual intensity* and bears spatial correlations in the absence of GWs background [166]. In the next section, we obtain equal-time correlations $g^{(1)}(R_1, t; R_2, t)$ defined by Eq. (7.17) in the presence of GWs in two-mode squeezed state, as predicted by inflationary scenario.

7.3 Spatial correlations in the presence of quantum GWs

7.3.1 Spatial correlations in the presence of two-mode squeezed PGWs

In this section, we consider correlation function Eq. (7.17) when GWs are placed in the two-mode squeezed state, briefly denoted by $|\text{TS}\rangle$, for which the squeezing amplitude is governed by Eq. (3.56). By inserting $\hat{a}_k(R_{ik}, t)$ from Eq. (7.8) into Eq. (7.17) one obtains

$$g_{\text{ts}}^{(1)}(1; 2) = \prod_{\lambda, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \langle \text{TS} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \lambda}^\dagger(-\kappa(K)\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1)) \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \lambda}(-\kappa(K)\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \lambda}^\dagger(-\kappa(K)\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \lambda}(-\kappa(K)\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)) | \text{TS} \rangle. \quad (7.22)$$

In the above equation, (1) and (2) are abbreviation for two points (R_1, t_1) and (R_2, t_2) . Calculation of $g_{\text{ts}}^{(1)}(R_1, t; R_2, t)$ is left to App. E.2. Here, we focus on final result and its implications. The final expression for the spatial correlation function reads as follows

$$g_{\text{ts}}^{(1)}(R_1, t; R_2, t) = e^{-iC^{\text{vac}}(R_1, t; R_2, t)} e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(R_1, t; R_2, t)} e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(R_1, t; R_2, t)}, \quad (7.23)$$

where the two-point kernels $C^{\text{vac}}(R_1, t; R_2, t)$, $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(R_1, t; R_2, t)$ and $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(R_1, t; R_2, t)$ are defined accordingly

$$\begin{aligned} C^{\text{vac}}(R_1, t; R_2, t) &\equiv \sum_{\lambda} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2(K) C_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(R_1, t; R_2, t), \\ \mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(R_1, t; R_2, t) &\equiv \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\lambda} \int_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2(K) \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(R_1, t; R_2, t), \\ \mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(R_1, t; R_2, t) &\equiv \sum_{\lambda} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2(K) \left\{ |v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)|^2 \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(1; 2) + \frac{1}{2} \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{ts-corr}}(R_1, t; R_2, t) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (7.24)$$

together with

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(R_1, t; R_2, t) &\equiv \Im[\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(R_2, t)], \\ \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(R_1, t; R_2, t) &\equiv |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_2, t)|^2, \\ \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{ts-corr}}(R_1, t; R_2, t) &\equiv 2\Re[u_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H) v_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H) (\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_2, t)) \\ &\quad \times (\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(R_2, t))]. \end{aligned} \quad (7.25)$$

In these expressions, $u_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)$ and $v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)$ are determined by Eq. (2.58), and $\kappa(K)$ and $\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R, t)$ are defined by Eq. (E.43) and Eq. (7.9). Eq. (7.23) implies that PGWs contribute to the loss of spatial correlations. Vacuum fluctuations induce both coherent and incoherent contributions, embarked in C^{vac} and \mathcal{D}^{vac} and can be encapsulated in

$$g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(R_1, t; R_2, t) = e^{-iC^{\text{vac}}(R_1, t; R_2, t)} e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(R_1, t; R_2, t)}. \quad (7.26)$$

The effect of squeezed gravitons appears only in the incoherence mechanism and is determined by \mathcal{D}^{ts} . Due to the negligible factor $\kappa^2(K) \sim (\hbar\omega_k/E_{\text{pl}})^2$ appearing in all kernels, the magnitude of the incoherence effect is automatically vanishing. However, for highly-squeezed PGWs possessing enormously large number of gravitons (as implied by Eq. (3.56)), there is a reasonable chance to overcome the tiny coupling strength $\kappa(K)$ and produce a sensible effect. In the following, we evaluate the kernel $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(R_1, t; R_2, t)$ and obtain the expression of $g_{\text{ts}}^{(1)}(R_1, t; R_2, t)$, from which the intensity $I(\mathbf{x}_C, t)$ can be found. Note that, the contribution of vacuum is negligibly small and can be disregarded safely. With the help of definition Eq. (7.9) for $\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_{ik}, t)$ one finds

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(R_1, t; R_2, t) &= 4 \sin^2\left(\frac{\Omega_K t}{2}\right) |\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_1) - \mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_2)|^2, \\ \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{ts-corr}}(R_1, t; R_2, t) &= \sinh 2r_K (\cos(2\phi_K) - 2 \cos(\Omega_K t - 2\phi_K) + \cos(2\Omega_K t - 2\phi_K)) \\ &\quad \times |\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_1) - \mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_2)|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (7.27)$$

For highly squeezed PGWs, we can proceed by replacing $\sinh^2 r_K \simeq e^{2r_K}/4$ and $\sinh 2r_K \simeq e^{2r_K}/2$. Combining Eq. (7.24) and Eq. (7.27) and inserting from Eq. (E.43) for $\kappa(K)$ one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(R_1, t; R_2, t) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}}\right)^2 \int \frac{dK}{K} \left(\frac{e^{2r_K}}{4}\right) \left(8 \sin^2\left(\frac{\Omega_K t}{2}\right) \sin^2\left(\frac{2\phi_K - \Omega_K t}{2}\right)\right) \\ &\quad \times \sum_{\lambda=+, \times} \int_0^{2\pi} d\Phi_K \int_0^\pi d(\cos \Theta_K) |\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_1) - \mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_2)|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (7.28)$$

To proceed, we first compute the spatial factor $|\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_1) - \mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_2)|^2$. This step is left to App. E.3, where it is shown that

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_1) - \mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_2)|^2 &= \left| \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} (i^\ell) \frac{2\ell+1}{2\pi} \left(\int d\Omega_{\hat{\mathbf{r}}} e^{i\ell[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}_i} \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j P_\ell(\cos \gamma) \right) \right. \\ &\quad \times \left. \left(\frac{j_\ell(KR)}{(KR)} - \frac{\int_0^{KR} j_\ell(u) du}{(KR)^2} \right) \right|^2 (K(R_1 - R_2))^2. \end{aligned} \quad (7.29)$$

In the above equation, $P_\ell(\cos \gamma)$ stands for the Legendre polynomial and γ shows the angle between $\hat{\mathbf{K}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$ (note that $\mathbf{x} = (r, \theta, \phi)$ is an integration variable scanning the interaction volume V wherein the interaction between GWs and spherical EM wave is non-vanishing, see Fig. 7.6). Moreover, $j_\ell(u)$ shows spherical Bessel function of the first kind. The distance $R_1 - R_2$ can be easily calculated from Fig. 7.2, according to

$$\begin{aligned} R_1 &= r_1 - \hat{\mathbf{s}}_1 \cdot \mathbf{x}', \\ R_2 &= r_2 - \hat{\mathbf{s}}_2 \cdot \mathbf{x}', \end{aligned} \quad (7.30)$$

where r_i shows the distance of the i -th detector with respect to some origin, say the center of the planar disc, \mathbf{x}' shows the position of the source element from the origin and $\hat{\mathbf{s}}_i$ shows

the unit vector from the source element \mathbf{x}' to the i -th detector. One has

$$R_1 - R_2 = r_1 - r_2 + (\hat{\mathbf{s}}_2 - \hat{\mathbf{s}}_1) \cdot \mathbf{x}'. \quad (7.31)$$

The path difference $r_1 - r_2$ produces a constant phase in the visibility which is irrelevant in our discussion. Moreover, for distant objects one may assume $r_1 \simeq r_2 = R$. Hence, one can define polar coordinates $\mathbf{x}' \equiv (\rho' \cos \phi', \rho' \sin \phi')$ where $0 \leq \rho' \leq a$ and $0 \leq \phi' \leq 2\pi$. Eq. (7.31) implies that only the projection of $\hat{\mathbf{s}}_2 - \hat{\mathbf{s}}_1$ onto the planar disc is encountered, and we can write $(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_{2\perp} - \hat{\mathbf{s}}_{1\perp}) \equiv (w \cos \psi, w \sin \psi)$ where $w = |\hat{\mathbf{s}}_{2\perp} - \hat{\mathbf{s}}_{1\perp}|$. Moreover, one can write $\hat{\mathbf{s}}_{i\perp} \equiv (\frac{x_i}{R}, \frac{y_i}{R}, 0)$ where (x_i, y_i) stands for the projected coordinates of the i -th detector (parallel with the planar surface). Hence, $w = \sqrt{(x_1 - x_2)^2 + (y_1 - y_2)^2}/R = \frac{d}{R}$. Consequently, we can write Eq. (7.31) as

$$R_1 - R_2 = (\hat{\mathbf{s}}_{2\perp} - \hat{\mathbf{s}}_{1\perp}) \cdot (\rho' \cos \phi', \rho' \sin \phi') = \rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi). \quad (7.32)$$

Combining Eqs. (7.28, 7.29, 7.32) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(R_1, t; R_2, t) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}} \right)^2 \int dK \left(\frac{K e^{2r_K}}{4} \right) \left(8 \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Omega_K t}{2} \right) \sin^2 \left(\frac{2\phi_K - \Omega_K t}{2} \right) \right) \quad (7.33) \\ &\times \int_0^{2\pi} d\Phi_K \int_0^\pi d(\cos \Theta_K) \sum_{\lambda=+, \times} \left| \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} (i^\ell) \frac{2\ell + 1}{2\pi} \left(\int d\Omega_{\hat{\mathbf{r}}} e_{ij}^\lambda[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j P_\ell(\cos \gamma) \right) \right. \\ &\times \left. \left(\frac{j_\ell(KR)}{(KR)} - \frac{\int_0^{KR} j_\ell(u) du}{(KR)^2} \right) \right|^2 (\rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi))^2 \\ &\equiv \xi_{\text{ts}}^{-2}(R, t) (\rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi))^2. \end{aligned}$$

In the last line, we have defined the incoherence length induced by two-mode squeezed PGWs according to

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_{\text{ts}}(R, t) &= \left[\frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}} \right)^2 \int dK \left(\frac{K e^{2r_K}}{4} \right) \left(8 \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Omega_K t}{2} \right) \sin^2 \left(\frac{2\phi_K - \Omega_K t}{2} \right) \right) \quad (7.34) \right. \\ &\times \int_0^{2\pi} d\Phi_K \int_0^\pi d(\cos \Theta_K) \sum_{\lambda=+, \times} \left| \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} (i^\ell) \frac{2\ell + 1}{2\pi} \left(\int d\Omega_{\hat{\mathbf{r}}} e_{ij}^\lambda[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j P_\ell(\cos \gamma) \right) \right. \\ &\times \left. \left. \left(\frac{j_\ell(KR)}{(KR)} - \frac{\int_0^{KR} j_\ell(u) du}{(KR)^2} \right) \right|^2 \right]^{-1/2}, \end{aligned}$$

which is a function of the distance of the source to the Earth R , and the interaction time t . Plugging Eq. (7.33) into Eq. (7.23) yields

$$g_{\text{ts}}^{(1)}(R_1, t; R_2, t) = e^{-\xi_{\text{ts}}^{-2} (\rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi))^2}, \quad (7.35)$$

where the effect of vacuum fluctuations is ignored, and Eq. (7.19) for the intensity $I(\mathbf{x}_C, t)$ becomes

$$I(\mathbf{x}_C, t) = \frac{2|\mathcal{E}|^2 \langle \hat{n}_k \rangle}{R^2} \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{\pi a^2} \Re \left[\int_0^a d\rho' \rho' \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi' e^{-\xi_{\text{ts}}^{-2} (\rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi))^2} e^{-ik\rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi)} \right] \right\}. \quad (7.36)$$

According to definition, the *visibility*, which is a measure of the sharpness of the interference fringes, is defined by [151]

$$\mathcal{V}(\mathbf{x}_C, t) \equiv \frac{I_{\max}(\mathbf{x}_C, t) - I_{\min}(\mathbf{x}_C, t)}{I_{\max}(\mathbf{x}_C, t) + I_{\min}(\mathbf{x}_C, t)}. \quad (7.37)$$

Hence, from Eq. (7.36) the visibility is determined by

$$\mathcal{V}_{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}_C, t) = \frac{1}{\pi a^2} \Re \left[\int_0^a d\rho' \rho' \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi' e^{-\xi_{\text{ts}}^{-2} (\rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi))^2} e^{-ik\rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi)} \right]. \quad (7.38)$$

The integration over ϕ' in Eq. (7.38) is calculated in App. E.4. Eventually, the expression of the visibility in Eq. (7.38) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{V}_{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}_C, t) = & 2 \Re \left\{ \int_0^1 du u e^{-\left(\frac{\nu^2}{2(k\xi_{\text{ts}})^2} u^2\right)} \left(J_0(\nu u) J_0\left(i \frac{\nu^2}{2(k\xi_{\text{ts}})^2} u^2\right) \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-i)^n J_{2n}(\nu u) J_n\left(i \frac{\nu^2}{2(k\xi_{\text{ts}})^2} u^2\right) \right) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (7.39)$$

In the above equation, $\nu = kd\theta/2$, d shows the distance between two detectors and θ stands for the angular diameter of the source. Moreover, $J_n(u)$ stands for the Bessel function of the first kind. Eq. (7.39) explicitly shows the *blurring* of the visibility induced by PGWs that could completely suppress the interference pattern. The incoherence effect depends on the interaction time t , as well as the distance of the source to the Earth R through the length-scale $\xi_{\text{ts}}(R, t)$ which depends on the squeezing parameters (r_K, ϕ_K) that, on their own, depend on the inflationary parameters such as tensor-to-scalar ratio. Thus, the order of magnitude of the incoherence depends crucially on the level of generated PGWs during inflation.

On the other hand, successful measurement of spatial correlations of most distant sources is a convincing evidence that spatial correlations have survived during their journey to the Earth. To visualize the behavior of the visibility, we first evaluate the dimensionless parameter $k\xi_{\text{ts}}$ given by Eq. (7.34). Note that, the distance of the source and the interaction time can be expressed in terms of the redshift of the source, z (see App. E.5). The plot of $k\xi_{\text{ts}}(z)$ in logarithmic scale versus the redshift z is depicted in Fig. 7.7. In this plot, the blue and orange curves correspond to two values $r_{k_0} = 0.032 \simeq 10^{-1.5}$ and $r_{k_0} \simeq 10^{-3}$ for the tensor-to-scalar ratio. At very small distance and interaction times $z \rightarrow 0$, the incoherence length takes a large value so that $g_k^{(1)}(R_1, t; R_2, t) \rightarrow e^{-ik(R_1 - R_2)}$ as it should. By increasing the redshift, the incoherence length takes smaller values, down to $k\xi_{\text{ts}} \simeq 10^6$ for $r_{k_0} = 10^{-1.5}$. For the whole redshift range $0 \leq z \leq 5$, one has $k\xi_{\text{ts}} \gtrsim 10^6$.

These plots are numerically calculated from Eq. (7.34), where only the first three terms

Figure 7.7: The dimensionless incoherence length $k\xi_{ts}(z)$ in logarithmic scale versus the redshift z , based on Eq. (7.34). The blue and orange curves correspond to two values $r_{k_0} = 0.032 \simeq 10^{-1.5}$ and $r_{k_0} \simeq 10^{-3}$ for the tensor-to-scalar ratio, respectively. For the whole range of the redshift, $k\xi_{ts}$ remains larger than $\simeq 10^6$.

corresponding to $\ell = 0, 1, 2$ in the summations are encountered since the effect of higher order-terms are negligible and can be disregarded safely. Moreover, note that the integration over the GWs wave number K should be performed between a lower and upper limit, namely K_{low} and K_{up} . In order to find the effective range of K which has the prominent contribution in integration, it is instructive to plot the integrand in Eq. (7.34), namely

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_{\text{ts}}(K, z) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}} \right)^2 \left(\frac{K e^{2r_K}}{4} \right) \left(8 \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Omega_K t(z)}{2} \right) \sin^2 \left(\frac{2\phi_K - \Omega_K t(z)}{2} \right) \right) \quad (7.40) \\
 &\times \int_0^{2\pi} d\Phi_K \int_0^\pi d(\cos \Theta_K) \sum_{\lambda=+, \times} \left| \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} (i^\ell) \frac{2\ell+1}{2\pi} \left(\int d\Omega_{\hat{r}} e^{i\ell} [\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j P_\ell(\cos \gamma) \right) \right. \\
 &\times \left. \left(\frac{j_\ell(KR(z))}{(KR(z))} - \frac{\int_0^{KR(z)} j_\ell(u) du}{(KR(z))^2} \right) \right|^2,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $t(z)$ and $R(z)$ are given by Eqs. (E.77, E.78). The plot of $f_{\text{ts}}(K, z)$ is sketched for $z = 0.5$ in Fig. 7.8 for $r_{k_0} = 0.032$. It can be seen that, the major contribution of the integrand $f_{\text{ts}}(K, 0.5)$ comes from those waves with $K \simeq K_H \sim 4 \times 10^{-26} \text{ m}^{-1}$, and the contribution of very-low frequency or very-high frequency GWs becomes negligible. In this way, depending on the length of the probe, the lower and upper wave numbers K_{low} and K_{up} which have the major contribution can be found.

With the help of Eq. (7.39) for the visibility, one can check that in the limiting case

Figure 7.8: Behavior of the integrand $f_{\text{ts}}(K, z)$ for $z = 0.5$ versus the wave number K based on Eq. (7.40). Scales with $K \simeq 4 \times 10^{-26} \text{ m}^{-1} \sim K_H$ have the highest contribution in the incoherence length $\xi_{\text{ts}}(z)$, and the effect of longer and shorter waves in $\xi_{\text{sq}}(\mathbf{R}, t)$ in Eq. (7.34) automatically vanishes.

$k \xi_{\text{ts}} \gg \nu$, the decaying factor goes to unity $e^{-\left(\frac{\nu^2}{2(k\xi)^2} u^2\right)} \rightarrow 1$ and the visibility reduces to

$$\mathcal{V}_{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}_C, t) \simeq 2 \Re \left(\int_0^1 du u J_0(\nu u) \right) = \frac{2J_1(\nu)}{\nu}, \quad k \xi_{\text{ts}} \gg k d \theta / 2 \quad (7.41)$$

which is nothing but the van Citter-Zernike correlation Eq. (7.4). Here, we have used the identities $J_0(0) = 1$, $J_n(0) = 0$ for $n \geq 1$, and $\int_0^a J_0(u) u du = a J_1(a)$. In a VLBI measurement, the visibility is non-vanishing as long as $\nu \simeq 1$ or equivalently $k d \theta / 2 \simeq 1$ (see Fig. 7.3). For typical values of the tensor-to-scalar ratio, namely $r_{k_0} \leq 0.032 \simeq 10^{-1.5}$ as constrained by *Planck PR4* [124], the PGWs induced incoherence takes large value $k \xi_{\text{ts}} \geq 10^6$, which is much higher than $\nu \simeq 1$. As a result, PGWs are too feeble to induce decaying of van Citter-Zernike correlations in VLBI measurements. This is mainly due to the very small coupling strength $\propto \left(\frac{\hbar \omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}}\right)^2$ between EM field and GWs, despite the large graviton content of the two-mode squeezed PGWs.

The situation can change when $k \xi_{\text{ts}} \sim \nu = k d \theta / 2$. This is possible whenever the coupling between the EM field and the underlying background is more strength, for instance when the EM field suffers from material fields such as primordial density perturbations. In the latter case, it is natural to think of the gravitational lensing created by matter fluctuations as a source of incoherence of the EM phase. In this regard, the present formalism can be straightforwardly generalized to encounter the incoherence induced by the density perturbations.

7.3.2 Spatial correlations in the presence of coherent GWs

Equal-time degree of coherence of the EM field when propagates through the background of GWs in coherent state is determined by

$$g_{\text{coh}}^{(1)}(1; 2) = \prod_{\lambda, \mathbf{K}} \langle \beta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \lambda}^\dagger(-\kappa(K)\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1)) \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \lambda}(-\kappa(K)\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)) | \beta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma} \rangle \quad (7.42)$$

$$\times \langle \beta_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma} | \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \lambda}^\dagger(-\kappa(K)\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \lambda}(-\kappa(K)\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)) | \beta_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma} \rangle.$$

where the coherent state $|\beta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}\rangle$ is defined by Eq. (5.53). As before, the notation (1) and (2) shows the two points (R_1, t) and (R_2, t) . Calculation of $g_{\text{coh}}^{(1)}(1; 2)$ is similar to $g_{\text{ts}}^{(1)}(1; 2)$ and is determined by

$$g_{\text{coh}}^{(1)}(R_1, t; R_2, t) = g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(R_1, t; R_2, t) e^{-iC^{\text{coh}}(R_1, t; R_2, t)}, \quad (7.43)$$

The effect of vacuum fluctuations is encapsulated in $g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t; \mathbf{x}_2, t)$ and is given by Eq. (7.26) and the net effect of coherent state is included in function $C^{\text{coh}}(R_1, t; R_2, t)$ given by

$$C^{\text{coh}}(R_1, t; R_2, t) = -2 \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa(K) C_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{coh}}(R_1, t; R_2, t), \quad (7.44)$$

where

$$C_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{coh}}(R_1, t; R_2, t) = \Im \left[(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_2, t)) \beta_{\mathbf{K}}^* \right] \quad (7.45)$$

$$= \bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2} \Im \left[(e^{-i\theta_{\beta_{\mathbf{K}}}} - e^{i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t - \theta_{\beta_{\mathbf{K}}})}) (\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma*}(R_1) - \mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma*}(R_2)) \right].$$

The spatial part $(\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma*}(R_1) - \mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma*}(R_2))$ is calculated in App. E.3 where it is shown that

$$\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma*}(R_1) - \mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma*}(R_2) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} (-i)^\ell (2\ell + 1) \left(\int d\Omega_{\hat{\mathbf{r}}} e^{i\gamma} [\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j P_\ell(\cos \gamma) \right)$$

$$\times \left\{ \frac{j_\ell(KR_2)}{KR_1} - \frac{\int_0^{KR_2} j_\ell(x) dx}{(KR_1)^2} \right\} (K(R_1 - R_2)). \quad (7.46)$$

Note that, we proceed by neglecting the phase factor $e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}_s}$. Indeed, if the GW background is homogeneous, this factor automatically vanishes since only the absolute value of the spatial function $\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma}$ appears. On the other hand, if the GW background lacks homogeneity, as in the case of coherent or one-mode squeezed GWs (which are extremely impossible due to physical conservation laws), the effect of $e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}_s}$ can be revealed provided that $K|\mathbf{x}_s| \sim 1$, which means that the experiment should be performed on different regions of space with a separation $\sim K^{-1}$. This is practically impossible, as long as we consider the spectrum of PGWs for which the major contribution comes from ultra-long wavelengths of the order of the Hubble scale ℓ_H . Hence, we neglect the phase factor $e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}_s}$ in subsequent calculations.

Thus, the effect of coherent GWs is proportional to the path difference $(R_1 - R_2)$ from

the point source to the detectors, and is vanishing whenever $R_1 = R_2$. Moreover, the effect is proportional to first power of $(R_1 - R_2)$ rather than the second power which happens for two-mode squeezed PGWs. With the help of Eq. (7.32) for $(R_1 - R_2)$, the expression of $C^{\text{coh}}(R_1, t; R_2, t)$ can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} C^{\text{coh}}(R_1, t; R_2, t) &= -2 \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \mathbf{K}(K) \bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2} \mathfrak{I} \left[(e^{-i\theta_{\beta K}} - e^{i(\Omega_K t - \theta_{\beta K})}) \right] \quad (7.47) \\ &\times \left(\frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} (-i)^{\ell} (2\ell + 1) \left(\int d\Omega_{\hat{r}} e_{ij}^{\gamma}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j P_{\ell}(\cos \gamma) \right) \right) \\ &\times K \left\{ \frac{j_{\ell}(KR_2)}{KR_1} - \frac{\int_0^{KR_2} j_{\ell}(x) dx}{(KR_1)^2} \right\} (\rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi)) \\ &\equiv \xi_{\text{coh}}^{-1}(R, t) (\rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi)). \end{aligned}$$

In the last line, we have defined the characteristic length-scale associated to coherent GWs as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_{\text{coh}}(R, t) &\equiv \left[-2 \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \mathbf{K}(K) \bar{n}_{\text{coh}}^{1/2}(K) \mathfrak{I} \left((e^{-i\theta_{\beta K}} - e^{i(\Omega_K t - \theta_{\beta K})}) \right) \right. \quad (7.48) \\ &\times \left\{ \frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} (-i)^{\ell} (2\ell + 1) \left(\int d\Omega_{\hat{r}} e_{ij}^{\gamma}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j P_{\ell}(\cos \gamma) \right) \right\} \\ &\times \left. K \left\{ \frac{j_{\ell}(KR_2)}{KR_1} - \frac{\int_0^{KR_2} j_{\ell}(x) dx}{(KR_1)^2} \right\} \right]^{-1} \\ &= \left[-\frac{1}{\pi} \left(\frac{\hbar \omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}} \right) \int_0^{2\pi} d\Phi_K \int_0^{\pi} d(\cos \Theta_K) \int_{K_{\text{low}}}^{K_{\text{up}}} dK \sqrt{K^3 \bar{n}_{\text{coh}}(K)} \right. \\ &\times \left. \mathfrak{I} \left((e^{-i\theta_{\beta K}} - e^{i(\Omega_K t - \theta_{\beta K})}) \right) \left\{ \frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} (-i)^{\ell} (2\ell + 1) \left(\int d\Omega_{\hat{r}} e_{ij}^{\gamma}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j P_{\ell}(\cos \gamma) \right) \right\} \right. \\ &\times \left. \left. \left\{ \frac{j_{\ell}(KR_2)}{KR_1} - \frac{\int_0^{KR_2} j_{\ell}(x) dx}{(KR_1)^2} \right\} \right]^{-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Plugging Eq. (7.47) into Eq. (7.43) and neglecting the effect of vacuum fluctuations, Eq. (7.19) for the intensity at point \mathbf{x}_C turns out

$$I(\mathbf{x}_C, t) = \frac{2 |\mathcal{E}|^2 \langle \hat{n}_k \rangle}{R^2} \left\{ 1 + \Re \left[\frac{\int_0^{2\pi} d\phi' \int_0^a d\rho' \rho' e^{-i(\xi_{\text{coh}}^{-1}(R, t) + k)\rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi)}}{\pi a^2} \right] \right\}. \quad (7.49)$$

Accordingly, the visibility at point \mathbf{x}_C outcomes

$$\mathcal{V}_{\text{coh}}(\mathbf{x}_C, t) = \frac{1}{\pi a^2} \Re \left[\int_0^a d\rho' \rho' \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi' e^{-i(\xi_{\text{coh}}^{-1}(R, t) + k)\rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi)} \right]. \quad (7.50)$$

Eq. (7.50) implies that coherent GWs do not participate in the incoherence of spatial correlations. Instead, they could change the (transverse) coherence length of a source, since they effectively appear as an additional term $(\xi_{\text{coh}}^{-1}(R, t) + k)$ that finally changes the coher-

ence length according to

$$d_{\text{coh}} = \frac{2}{k\theta} \rightarrow \frac{2}{(k + \xi_{\text{coh}}^{-1}(R, t))\theta} = \frac{d_{\text{coh}}}{1 + (k\xi_{\text{coh}}(R, t))^{-1}}. \quad (7.51)$$

Thus, the amount of change in the coherence length crucially depends on the graviton content of the coherent state $\bar{n}_{\text{coh}}(K)$. For instance, for a background of coherent GWs possessing graviton content as high as the two-mode squeezed PGWs, one obtains $(k\xi_{\text{coh}})^{-1} \simeq 10^{-46}$ for an object with redshift $z \sim 0.5$. Note that, in this hypothetical situation, the spectrum of coherent GWs obeys Eq. (3.56) (see Fig. 3.3) and is correct as long as the adiabatic condition $\Omega_K \ll \omega_k$ is fulfilled. One can expect that, for coherent GWs with higher frequencies, the effect may change or get amplified as a result of on-resonance coupling with EM field.

7.3.3 Spatial correlations in the presence of one-mode squeezed GWs

Equal-time correlations in the presence of one-mode squeezed GWs is determined by

$$\begin{aligned} g_{\text{sq}}^{(1)}(1; 2) &= \prod_{\lambda, \mathbf{K}} \langle \zeta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \lambda}^\dagger(-\kappa(K)\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1)) \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \lambda}(-\kappa(K)\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)) | \zeta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma} \rangle \\ &\times \langle \zeta_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma} | \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \lambda}^\dagger(-\kappa(K)\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \lambda}(-\kappa(K)\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)) | \zeta_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma} \rangle \\ &= g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(1; 2) e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(1; 2)}. \end{aligned} \quad (7.52)$$

As before, (1) and (2) stand for two points (R_1, t) and (R_2, t) , briefly. The effect of vacuum is determined by Eq. (7.26), and the effect of gravitons in one-mode squeezed state is contained in the kernel $\mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(1; 2)$ defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(R_1, t; R_2, t) &= \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa(K) \left\{ \sinh^2 r_K \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(R_1, t; R_2, t) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2} \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{sq-corr}}(R_1, t; R_2, t) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (7.53)$$

where $\mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(R_1, t; R_2, t)$ is given by Eq. (7.25) and $\mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{sq-corr}}(R_1, t; R_2, t)$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{sq-corr}}(R_1, t; R_2, t) &= \sinh 2r_K \Re \left\{ (\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_2, t))^2 e^{-2i\phi_K} \right\} \\ &= \sinh 2r_K \Re \left\{ (1 - e^{i\Omega_K t})^2 (g_{\mathbf{K}}^{\lambda*}(R_1) - g_{\mathbf{K}}^{\lambda*}(R_2))^2 e^{-2i\phi_K} \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (7.54)$$

written as

$$g_{\text{sq}}^{(1)}(R_1, t; R_2, t) = e^{-\xi_{\text{sq}}^{-2}(R, t) (\rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi))^2}, \quad (7.58)$$

where the effect of vacuum is neglected and the expression of the intensity Eq. (7.19) takes the following form

$$I(\mathbf{x}_C, t) = \frac{2 |\mathcal{E}|^2 \langle \hat{n}_k \rangle}{R^2} \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{\pi a^2} \Re \left[\int_0^a d\rho' \rho' \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi' e^{-\xi_{\text{sq}}^{-2}(\rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi))^2} e^{-ik\rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi)} \right] \right\}, \quad (7.59)$$

which is very similar to Eq. (7.36) for the case of two-mode squeezed state. Hence, the resulting visibility is the same as Eq. (7.39) with the substitution of $\xi_{\text{ts}} \rightarrow \xi_{\text{sq}}$. Comparing Eqs. (7.34, 7.57) for ξ_{ts} and ξ_{sq} , it can be seen that the first term in both equations embarks the contribution of the mean number of gravitons in the state, which leaves an identical effect in the incoherence mechanism. However, the second term in these expressions show the contribution of correlations between gravitons in two-mode and one-mode squeezed states, accordingly, which is different due to the correlations between opposite momenta in two-mode squeezed state.

Again, Eq. (7.39) suggest that, in order to see the effect of one-mode squeezed state in the VLBI experiment, it is needed that $k \xi_{\text{sq}} \simeq \nu = k d \theta / 2 \simeq 1$, unless the effect is far beyond the VLBI sensitivity. The behavior of $k \xi_{\text{sq}}(z)$ in logarithmic scale versus redshift z is shown Fig. 7.9 for two values of $r_{k_0} = 10^{-1.5}$ and $r_{k_0} = 10^{-3}$ shown by the blue and orange curves. The behavior is very similar to that of the two-mode squeezed states, and for the whole redshift range we have $k \xi_{\text{sq}} \gtrsim 10^6$, which renders its observation by VLBI means.

7.3.4 Spatial correlations in the presence of thermal GWs

The two-point correlation function of the EM field in the presence of thermal GWs is determined is given by

$$\begin{aligned} g_{\text{th}}^{(1)}(1; 2) &= \prod_{\lambda, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \langle \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \lambda}^\dagger(-\kappa(K)\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1)) \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \lambda}(-\kappa(K)\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)) \rangle_{\hat{\rho}_{\text{th}, \mathbf{K}}} \quad (7.60) \\ &\times \langle \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \lambda}^\dagger(-\kappa(K)\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \lambda}(-\kappa(K)\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)) | \zeta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma} \rangle_{\hat{\rho}_{\text{th}, -\mathbf{K}}} \\ &= g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(1; 2) e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(1; 2)}, \end{aligned}$$

where (1) and (2) stands for (R_1, t) and (R_2, t) . The effect of vacuum fluctuations is encapsulated in Eq. (7.26) and the effect of thermal gravitons is given by the kernel

$$\mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(1; 2) \equiv \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa(\mathbf{K}) \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(1, 2), \quad (7.61)$$

Figure 7.9: The dimensionless incoherence length $k \xi_{sq}(z)$ in logarithmic scale versus redshift z for squeezed GWs based on Eq. (7.57) for $\phi_K = 0$. Here, blue and orange curves correspond to $r_{k_0} = 0.032 \simeq 10^{-1.5}$ and $r_{k_0} = 10^{-3}$, respectively. Other parameters are chosen as $\beta = -2, \beta_s = 1, T_{reh} = 10^8$ Gev. The behavior is very similar to the case of two-mode squeezed GWs, as shown in Fig. 7.8. It is seen that the dimensionless parameter $k \xi_{sq}(z) \gg 1$ in whole redshift range $0 \leq z \leq 5$.

and $\mathcal{D}^{vac}(1; 2)$ is previously obtained in Eq. (7.27). Note that, as in the case of vacuum and two-mode squeezed state, \mathcal{D}^{th} is homogeneous, since it depends only on $R_1 - R_2$ (see Eq. (7.29)). Again, we may attribute this feature to the homogeneous two-point correlation function of GWs in the thermal state. Moreover, comparing \mathcal{D}^{th} with that of one-mode and two-mode squeezed states, it is realized that the contribution of thermal gravitons is identical to the contribution of the mean number of gravitons in those states. However, due to the washed-out phase information in the thermal state, the contribution of the second term is absent in the thermal case. By inserting Eq. (7.27) into Eq. (7.61) and with the help of Eq. (7.29) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{D}^{th}(R_1, t; R_2, t) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{Pl}} \right)^2 \int_{K_{low}}^{K_{up}} \frac{dK}{K} \bar{n}_{th}(K) (4 \sin^2(\frac{\Omega_K t}{2})) \int_0^{2\pi} d\Phi_K \int_0^\pi d(\cos \Theta_K) \\
&\times \sum_{\lambda=+, \times} \left| \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} (i^\ell) \frac{2\ell+1}{2\pi} \left(\int d\Omega_{\hat{r}} e^{i\lambda [\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j} P_\ell(\cos \gamma) \right) \right. \\
&\times \left. \left(\frac{j_\ell(KR)}{(KR)} - \frac{\int_0^{KR} j_\ell(u) du}{(KR)^2} \right) \right|^2 (K \rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi))^2 \\
&\equiv \xi_{th}^{-2}(R, t) (\rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi))^2, \tag{7.62}
\end{aligned}$$

where in the last, we have defined the incoherence-length induced by thermal gravitons according to

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_{\text{th}}(R, t) &\equiv \left[\frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{Pl}}} \right)^2 \int_{K_{\text{low}}}^{K_{\text{up}}} dK K \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) (4 \sin^2(\frac{\Omega_K t}{2})) \int_0^{2\pi} d\Phi_K \int_0^\pi d(\cos \Theta_K) \right. \\ &\times \sum_{\lambda=+, \times} \left| \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} (i^\ell) \frac{2\ell+1}{2\pi} \left(\int d\Omega_{\hat{r}} e_{ij}^\lambda[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j P_\ell(\cos \gamma) \right) \right. \\ &\times \left. \left. \left(\frac{j_\ell(KR)}{(KR)} - \frac{\int_0^{KR} j_\ell(u) du}{(KR)^2} \right) \right|^2 \right]^{-1/2}, \end{aligned} \quad (7.63)$$

The two-point correlation function in the presence of thermal gravitons is given by

$$g_{\text{th}}^{(1)}(R_1, t; R_2, t) = e^{-\xi_{\text{th}}^{-2}(R, t) (\rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi))^2}. \quad (7.64)$$

Therefore, the intensity and visibility given by Eq. (7.19) and Eq. (7.37) are determined by

$$I(\mathbf{x}_C, t) = \frac{2|\mathcal{E}|^2 \langle \hat{n}_k \rangle}{R^2} \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{\pi a^2} \Re \left[\int_0^a d\rho' \rho' \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi' e^{-\xi_{\text{th}}^{-2} (\rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi))^2} e^{-ik\rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi)} \right] \right\}. \quad (7.65)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{V}_{\text{th}}(\mathbf{x}_C, t) &= 2 \Re \left\{ \int_0^1 du u e^{-\left(\frac{v^2}{2(k\xi_{\text{th}})^2} u^2 \right)} \left(J_0(vu) J_0\left(i \frac{v^2}{2(k\xi_{\text{th}})^2} u^2 \right) \right. \right. \\ &\left. \left. + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-i)^n J_{2n}(vu) J_n\left(i \frac{v^2}{2(k\xi_{\text{th}})^2} u^2 \right) \right) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (7.66)$$

which is the same as Eq. (7.39) with the substitution $\xi_{\text{ts}} \rightarrow \xi_{\text{th}}$. In comparison with Eq. (7.34) for ξ_{ts} , it can be seen that the contribution of the mean number of gravitons in the thermal state is identical with that of two-mode squeezed state, however, the contribution of correlations between gravitons is absent in the case of thermal state.

The behavior of $k\xi_{\text{th}}(z)$ in logarithmic scales versus the redshift z is shown in Fig. 7.10, assuming a graviton content for thermal state as high as two-mode squeezed state, namely $\bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) = e^{2r_K}/4$ (see Eq. (3.56)) and $r_{k_0} = 10^{-1.5}$. Moreover, Fig. 7.11 shows a comparison between the incoherence induced by one-mode squeezed, two-mode squeezed and thermal states of GWs possessing the same graviton content. In general, there is only a slight difference between incoherence induced by thermal and squeezed gravitons. In other words, one may hardly distinguish between these backgrounds on the basis of the spatial incoherence of the EM probe.

Figure 7.10: The dimensionless incoherence length $k\xi_{\text{th}}(z)$ in logarithmic scale versus redshift z for thermal GWs based on Eq. (7.63). Here, blue and orange curves correspond to $r_{k_0} = 0.032 \simeq 10^{-1.5}$ and $r_{k_0} = 10^{-3}$, respectively. Other parameters are chosen as $\beta = -2, \beta_s = 1, T_{\text{reh}} = 10^8$ Gev. The behavior is very similar to the case of one- and two-mode squeezed GWs, as shown by Fig. 7.9 and Fig. 7.7. It is seen that the dimensionless parameter $k\xi_{\text{th}}(z) \gg 1$ in whole redshift range $0 \leq z \leq 5$.

7.4 Summary and conclusions

In this chapter, we investigated spatial correlations of the EM field propagating over cosmological distances, which interacts with quantum GWs in different states, namely vacuum fluctuations, coherent, one-mode squeezed, two-mode squeezed, and thermal states. The following assumptions were used:

- We assumed that during the EM-GWs interaction, the state of PGWs is stationary, in the sense that it does not change due to interaction with the EM field or other external fields such as the expanding Universe. Thus, the squeezing amplitude r_K which governs the dynamics of the EM field, stays approximately constant.
- In the case of two-mode squeezed PGWs, we have obtained all the expressions in terms of general functions $u_K(\eta_H)$ and $v_K(\eta_H)$, which are expressible in terms of the squeezing parameters. However, when numerical calculations matter, we consider the special case of $\phi_K(\eta_H) = 0$.

The following results were obtained:

- With the help of the van Citter-Zernike theorem, we infer the vital criterion that spatial correlations exist when the parameter $\nu = kd\theta/2$ is of order unity.
- In the case of two-mode squeezed PGWs, it was realized that the visibility can suffer decaying whenever the dimensionless incoherence length $k\xi_{\text{ts}}$ gets values of

Figure 7.11: Comparison of the dimensionless parameter $k\xi(z)$ in case of one-mode squeezed, two-mode squeezed, and thermal GWs, shown by dashed, solid and faded curves, respectively. Here, we have used two values for the tensor-to-scalar ratio $r_{k_0} = 10^{-1.5}$ and $r_{k_0} = 10^{-3}$. Other parameters are chosen as before. It is seen that the one-mode squeezed GWs and thermal GWs with the same number of gravitons as in the two-mode state, leave a slightly different influence on spatial coherence. In general, one may hardly distinguish between these GW backgrounds based on EM spatial correlations. In any case, it should be noted that such a one-mode squeezed or thermal background of GWs is only hypothetical and is not predicted by a plausible scenario.

order unity. However, as long as the graviton content of PGWs is determined by Eq. (3.56), it turns out that $k\xi_{ts} \geq 10^6$ for all objects with redshift range $0 \leq z \leq 6$. Hence, the incoherence induced by two-mode squeezed PGWs is far beyond the sensitivity of VLBI experiments.

- Coherent GWs may alter the (transverse) coherence length of distant objects according to $d_{\text{coh}} \rightarrow \frac{d_{\text{coh}}}{(1+(k\xi_{\text{coh}})^{-1})}$, where ξ_{coh} shows a characteristic length-scale corresponding to coherent GWs. Assuming high graviton content for coherent GWs as high as in case of two-mode squeezed state, it turns out that the change in the coherence length is too small.
- It was realized that a hypothetical background of one-mode squeezed state or thermal GWs induce incoherence of the EM field, as in case of the two-mode squeezed PGWs. The effect depends crucially on the graviton content in the state. Considering an identical graviton content in these states, the incoherence effect is almost identical that renders distinguishing between these backgrounds.

Chapter 8

Summary and conclusions

In a nutshell, in this thesis, we investigate the possibility of detecting the quantum nature of inflationary-generated primordial gravitational waves, based on interferometric schema using an electromagnetic probe.

After a comprehensive literature review in Chapter 1, in Chapter 2 the basic concept of particle creation in the expanding Universe was introduced in a general way, and then specialized to the case of tensor perturbations $\hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta)$. This procedure is done in a framework consisting of quantum field theory on one hand, and general theory of relativity on the other hand, with the help of minimal coupling prescription. This framework helps us treat metric perturbations as a quantum field theory living on the classical FLRW manifold. In this way, the Heisenberg equation of motion for the Fourier field amplitude was obtained and two asymptotic limits, corresponding to sub-Hubble and super-Hubble scales were specified. For a DS expansionary stage during inflation, we showed that the super-Hubble scales, determined by the condition $K\eta \ll 1$, undergo super-adiabatic amplification. That means the gravitational energy of the rapid expansion of the Universe turns into pair particles of the tensor field of opposite momenta. This mechanism leads to the evolution of the vacuum of the tensor field into a highly-populated two-mode squeezed vacuum, where opposite momenta of the field becomes highly entangled. Another relevant quantity of interest is the two-point correlation function of tensor perturbations $\langle \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta) \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\ell}, \eta) \rangle$, which is the main quantity when talking about detection of PGWs whether by means of GWs detectors or CMB anisotropy and polarization surveys. As we investigated in detail in the thesis, the same quantity appears in EM field correlation functions as well. Features such as homogeneity and isotropicity of EM correlations are inherited from the GW correlation function.

In Chapter 3, we considered the successive expansion of FLRW Universe, modeled by power-law scale factor $a(\eta) \propto \eta^\alpha$. Relevant model parameters were identified and theoretical and observational constraints on them were discussed. The evolution of tensorial spectral amplitude $h(K, \eta)$ (which basically determines the power spectrum of PGWs) was investigated within the successive expansion model. An approximate solution for $h(K, \eta)$ as well as the squeeze parameters r_K, ϕ_K in the super-adiabatic regime (\sim super-Hubble

scales) was obtained, starting from the quantum normalization condition that determines the initial spectral amplitude. Ultimately, the present spectrum of tensor perturbations, identified by $h(K, \eta_H)$ and $r_K(\eta_H)$, were derived in terms of four free parameters of the model $\beta, \beta_s, T_{\text{reh}}, r_{k_0}$, which determine the inflationary index, the reheating index, the reheating temperature and the tensor-to-scalar ratio, respectively. These results are used in subsequent chapters.

After providing a detailed review of PGWs generation in expanding Universe in Chapter 3, in Chapter 4 we formulated the interaction between a generic EM probe and a generic continuum of GWs, within the optical medium analogy framework. Subtleties such as gauge fixing for both EM and GWs were discussed in detail. In this way, the generalized Maxwell's equations were solved in the presence of an inhomogeneous, anisotropic, time-dependent magneto-dielectric medium mimicked by GWs. We applied the adiabatic approximation, which implies $\Omega_K \ll \omega_K$ and $\lambda_k \ll \lambda_K$, so that the slowly varying envelope approximation was used to find the temporal and spatial mode functions of the EM field. Finally, we derived the general Fresnel equation, governing the refractive index of the effective medium. It turned out that, the refractive index of the medium inherits inhomogeneity and anisotropy of GWs. Subjects such as birefringence and walk-off angle of the Poynting vector were touched upon. Eventually, it was realized that the current approach based on OMA, not only reproduces the geometrical optics results but also is capable of being promoted to a fully quantum mechanical description of EM-GWs interaction.

Chapter 5 of the thesis deals with the quantization of EM-GWs interaction. This procedure is started by establishing a Lagrangian energy density that could reproduce Maxwell's equations in the presence of GWs, within the OMA approach. In this way, the Hamiltonian dynamics of the system were derived, based on which quantum observables of the EM field can be followed. We described in detail, the analogy between EM-GWs interaction Hamiltonian with that of cavity opto-mechanics and tried to extract the similarities as much as possible. At first sight, this analogy may cause the expectation that GWs induce revivals of optical squeezing, which is a pure quantum mechanical feature in cavity opto-mechanics. However, we show that, due to significantly small EM-GWs coupling strength, the needed time to observe the effect is astronomically large, provided that the optical field maintains its coherence, which is practically impossible.

On the other hand, we showed that amplified quantum fluctuations of PGWs ruins optical coherence after a characteristic time-scale $\tau_{\text{ts}} \sim 10^4$ s, which makes it impossible to detect any revivals of optical squeezing. Thus, we conclude that witnessing the quantum nature of PGWs based on revivals of optical squeezing is ruled out, and one may not distinguish between a classical or quantum background of PGWs, as a result of stabilization of quadrature squeezing which is a common feature of both classical and quantum GWs. For comparison, we calculate the optical variance when GWs are assumed to be in vacuum, coherent, one-mode squeezed, and thermal states. It was realized that quantum

fluctuations of GWs incorporate in decoherent dynamics of the EM field. For a coherent state of GWs, which is only a displacement of vacuum fluctuations in phase space, the induced decoherence is identical to that of vacuum fluctuations. Squeezed or thermal states for which the fluctuations are amplified, leave increased decoherence on the EM field which is of course dependent on the mean number of gravitons (that basically determines the spread of noise ellipse in phase space). In any case, the mean number of gravitons must be as large as $\sim (E_{\text{pl}}/\hbar\omega_k)^2$ to compensate for small coupling strength and leave an observable effect on EM dynamics.

Chapter 6 is dedicated to investigating GWs induced-decoherence of the EM field. To do so, we first obtained general expression of the two-point correlation function of a linearly-polarized single-mode EM field, $\langle \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t_1) \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t_2) \rangle$, in the presence of GWs in different states. Then we focused on temporal correlations, assuming stationarity condition for GWs. It was shown that the EM correlations may be homogeneous or inhomogeneous, inherited from GW correlations. Generally speaking, quantum fluctuations of GWs induce decoherence, while the displacement of quantum noise in phase space may only change the periodicity of the interference pattern. Consequently, the squeezed and thermal states of GWs induce decoherence, while the coherent state of gravitons induces a change in the periodicity of interference. One-mode squeezed and two-mode squeezed states share the common property that there are correlations of type $\langle \hat{b}_K \hat{b}_K \rangle$ and $\langle \hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{b}_K^\dagger \rangle$ between gravitons, which is absent in thermal state. On the other hand, in the phase space representation, the noise ellipse is directed along a specific direction, determined by squeeze angle ϕ_K . This is in contrast to the noise of thermal gravitons, which is a circle in phase space with the spread of $1 + 2\bar{n}_{\text{th}}$, as a result of indeterministic phase in thermal state. However, spatial correlations in the one-mode squeezed state are inhomogeneous, while it is homogeneous in the two-mode squeezed state as a result of correlations between opposite momenta in the latter case. Moreover, spatial correlations are automatically homogeneous in the thermal state of GWs. Eventually, these features, namely the homogeneity or inhomogeneity of GW correlations, as well as the deterministic or indeterministic phase in the state, specify the fate of EM correlations.

In Chapter 7, spatial correlations of the EM field in the presence of GWs in various states are investigated case by case. In the absence of GWs, when the EM field propagates freely in space, spatial correlations are described by the van Citter-Zernike theorem, which expresses correlations in the field at two separated points in space. It turns out that for an extended source of radius a located at far distance R from the Earth, the EM field is coherent over a circular region of radius $d_{\text{coh}} = 2/(k\theta)$ transverse to the propagation direction. Here, $\theta = 2a/R$ defines the angular diameter of the source when viewed from the Earth. However, we show that quantum fluctuations of GWs tend to reduce the van Citter-Zernike correlations and induce incoherence (loss of spatial correlation). This effect is called blurring of the visibility induced by fluctuations of quantum PGWs. On the other hand, GWs in coherent states could change the transverse coherence length

d_{coh} , such that the magnitude of the effect depends crucially on the graviton content in the coherent state. Squeezed and thermal GWs with a large number of gravitons (hence large fluctuating noise) also cause blurring of the visibility. Thus, fluctuations of GWs in squeezed and thermal state acts an incoherence mechanism. In these cases, we found the characteristic length-scale ξ_{gr} , which depends on the characteristics of the GW, namely its homogeneity, the mean graviton number, the phase correlations and correlations between different modes. Among other things, the incoherence length induced by two-mode squeezed PGWs, ξ_{ts} , depends crucially on the tensor-to-scalar ratio. In order for the visibility to survive, as implied by current successful VLBI experiments, one needs the dimensionless parameter $k \xi_{\text{ts}} \geq k d \theta / 2$. It was realized that, for the given range of parameters of PGWs constrained by current surveys, the foregoing criteria is automatically fulfilled, meaning that the current VLBI observations are consistent with the present constraint on the tensor-to-scalar ratio, $r_{k_0} \leq 0.032$ made by Planck PR4 data [124].

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Appendix A

Spatial correlations of GWs

Here we calculate the two-point correlation of GWs in various quantum states. Quantized tensorial metric perturbations are given by Eq. (5.2), i.e.,

$$\hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) = C \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{K}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \frac{e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}]}{\sqrt{2\Omega_K}} (\hat{b}_K e^{-i(\Omega_K t - \mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x})} + \hat{b}_K^\dagger e^{i(\Omega_K t - \mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x})}). \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where $C = \sqrt{16\pi c \ell_{\text{pl}}}$. Spatial correlations of GWs are determined by

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\ell}, t) \rangle &= \frac{C^2}{(2\pi)^3} \int d^3\mathbf{K} d^3\mathbf{K}' \frac{e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] e_{ij}^{\gamma'}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}']}{\sqrt{4\Omega_K \Omega_{K'}}} \langle (\hat{b}_K e^{-i(\Omega_K t - \mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x})} + \hat{b}_K^\dagger e^{i(\Omega_K t - \mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x})}) \\ &\times (\hat{b}_{K'} e^{-i(\Omega_{K'} t - \mathbf{K}'\cdot(\mathbf{x}+\boldsymbol{\ell}))} + \hat{b}_{K'}^\dagger e^{i(\Omega_{K'} t - \mathbf{K}'\cdot(\mathbf{x}+\boldsymbol{\ell}))}) \rangle \quad (\text{A.2}) \\ &= \frac{C^2}{(2\pi)^3} \int d^3\mathbf{K} d^3\mathbf{K}' \frac{e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] e_{ij}^{\gamma'}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}']}{\sqrt{4\Omega_K \Omega_{K'}}} \{ \langle \hat{b}_K \hat{b}_{K'} \rangle e^{-i(\Omega_K + \Omega_{K'})t} e^{i(\mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}')\cdot\mathbf{x}} e^{i\mathbf{K}'\cdot\boldsymbol{\ell}} \\ &+ \langle \hat{b}_K \hat{b}_{K'}^\dagger \rangle e^{-i(\Omega_K - \Omega_{K'})t} e^{i(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}')\cdot\mathbf{x}} e^{-i\mathbf{K}'\cdot\boldsymbol{\ell}} \\ &+ \langle \hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{b}_{K'} \rangle e^{i(\Omega_K - \Omega_{K'})t} e^{-i(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}')\cdot\mathbf{x}} e^{i\mathbf{K}'\cdot\boldsymbol{\ell}} \\ &+ \langle \hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{b}_{K'}^\dagger \rangle e^{i(\Omega_K + \Omega_{K'})t} e^{-i(\mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}')\cdot\mathbf{x}} e^{-i\mathbf{K}'\cdot\boldsymbol{\ell}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

A.1 Vacuum fluctuations of GWs

Vacuum fluctuations of GWs are described by quantum state Eq. (5.51). Spatial correlations of GWs are determined by

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \hat{b}_K \hat{b}_{K'} \rangle_{\text{vac}} &= \langle \hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{b}_{K'}^\dagger \rangle_{\text{vac}} = \langle \hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{b}_{K'} \rangle_{\text{vac}} = 0 \\ \langle \hat{b}_K \hat{b}_{K'}^\dagger \rangle_{\text{vac}} &= \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}'). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Inserting Eq. (A.3) into Eq. (A.2) results in

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\ell}, t) \rangle_{\text{vac}} &= \frac{C^2}{(2\pi)^3} \int d^3\mathbf{K} d^3\mathbf{K}' \frac{e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] e_{ij}^{\gamma'}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}']}{\sqrt{4\Omega_K \Omega_{K'}}} e^{i(\Omega_K - \Omega_{K'})t} e^{-i(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}') \cdot \mathbf{x}} e^{i\mathbf{K}' \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}') \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \\
&= \frac{C^2}{(2\pi)^3} \int d^3\mathbf{K} e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] e_{ij}^{\gamma'}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \frac{e^{-i\mathbf{K} \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}}}{2\Omega_K} \\
&= \frac{8\ell_{\text{Pl}}^2}{\pi} \int dK K \frac{\sin Kl}{Kl}. \tag{A.4}
\end{aligned}$$

Here, we have used Eq. (2.39), and $\int d^3\mathbf{K} f(\mathbf{K}) \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}') = f(\mathbf{K}')$.

A.2 Coherent state of GWs

The coherent state of GWs is described by quantum state Eq. (5.52). One may write

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \hat{b}_K \hat{b}_{K'} \rangle_{\text{coh}} &= \beta_K^2 \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}'), \\
\langle \hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{b}_{K'}^\dagger \rangle_{\text{coh}} &= \beta_K^{*2} \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}'), \\
\langle \hat{b}_K \hat{b}_{K'}^\dagger \rangle_{\text{coh}} &= (1 + |\beta_K|^2) \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}'), \\
\langle \hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{b}_{K'} \rangle_{\text{coh}} &= |\beta_K|^2 \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}'). \tag{A.5}
\end{aligned}$$

With the help of Eq. (A.2) and Eq. (A.5), spatial correlations of GWs in a coherent state are determined by

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\ell}, t) \rangle_{\text{coh}} &= \frac{C^2}{(2\pi)^3} \int d^3\mathbf{K} d^3\mathbf{K}' \frac{e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] e_{ij}^{\gamma'}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}']}{\sqrt{4\Omega_K \Omega_{K'}}} \left\{ \beta_K^2 e^{-i(\Omega_K + \Omega_{K'})t} e^{i(\mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}') \cdot \mathbf{x}} e^{i\mathbf{K}' \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}} \right. \\
&+ (1 + |\beta_K|^2) e^{-i(\Omega_K - \Omega_{K'})t} e^{i(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}') \cdot \mathbf{x}} e^{-i\mathbf{K}' \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}} \\
&+ |\beta_K|^2 e^{i(\Omega_K - \Omega_{K'})t} e^{-i(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}') \cdot \mathbf{x}} e^{i\mathbf{K}' \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}} \\
&\left. + \beta_K^{*2} e^{i(\Omega_K + \Omega_{K'})t} e^{-i(\mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}') \cdot \mathbf{x}} e^{-i\mathbf{K}' \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}} \right\} \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}'). \tag{A.6}
\end{aligned}$$

Assuming $\beta_K \equiv |\beta_K| e^{i\theta_{\beta_K}}$, one obtains

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\ell}, t) \rangle_{\text{vac}} &= \frac{8\ell_{\text{Pl}}^2}{\pi} \int dK K \frac{\sin Kl}{Kl} \\
&+ \frac{4C^2}{(2\pi)^3} \int d^3\mathbf{K} |\beta_K|^2 \left(\cos[2\theta_{\beta_K} - 2\Omega_K t + 2\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{K} \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}] + \cos(\mathbf{K} \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}) \right). \tag{A.7}
\end{aligned}$$

A.3 One-mode squeezed state of GWs

The squeezed state of GWs is described by quantum state Eq. (5.54). One may write

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \hat{b}_K \hat{b}_{K'} \rangle_{\text{sq}} &= -\sinh r_K \cosh r_K e^{2i\phi_K} \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}'), \\
\langle \hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{b}_{K'}^\dagger \rangle_{\text{sq}} &= -\sinh r_K \cosh r_K e^{-2i\phi_K} \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}'), \\
\langle \hat{b}_K \hat{b}_{K'}^\dagger \rangle_{\text{sq}} &= (1 + \sinh^2 r_K) \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}') \\
\langle \hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{b}_{K'} \rangle_{\text{sq}} &= \sinh^2 r_K \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}').
\end{aligned} \tag{A.8}$$

With the help of Eq. (A.2) and Eq. (A.8), spatial correlations of GWs in one-mode squeezed state are determined by

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\ell}, t) \rangle_{\text{sq}} &= \frac{C^2}{(2\pi)^3} \int d^3\mathbf{K} d^3\mathbf{K}' \frac{e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] e_{ij}^{\gamma'}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}']}{\sqrt{4\Omega_K \Omega_{K'}}} \left\{ (-\sinh r_K \cosh r_K e^{2i\phi_K} \right. \\
&\times e^{-2i(\Omega_K - \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x})} e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}} + c.c.) + \cosh^2 r_K e^{-i\mathbf{K} \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}} + \sinh^2 r_K e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}} \left. \right\} \\
&= \frac{8\ell_{\text{pl}}^2}{\pi} \int dK K \frac{\sin Kl}{Kl} \\
&+ \frac{4C^2}{(2\pi)^3} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \left\{ -\sinh r_K \cosh r_K \cos[2\phi_K - 2\Omega_K t + 2\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{K} \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}] \right. \\
&+ \left. \sinh^2 r_K \cos(\mathbf{K} \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}) \right\}.
\end{aligned} \tag{A.9}$$

A.4 Thermal state of GWs

The thermal state of GWs is described by quantum state Eq. (5.56). One may write

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \hat{b}_K \hat{b}_{K'} \rangle_{\text{th}} &= \langle \hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{b}_{K'}^\dagger \rangle_{\text{th}} = \langle \hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{b}_{K'} \rangle_{\text{th}} = 0, \\
\langle \hat{b}_K \hat{b}_{K'}^\dagger \rangle_{\text{sq}} &= \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}').
\end{aligned} \tag{A.10}$$

With the help of Eq. (A.2) and Eq. (A.10), spatial correlations of GWs in the thermal state are determined by

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\ell}, t) \rangle_{\text{sq}} &= \frac{8\ell_{\text{pl}}^2}{\pi} \int dK K \frac{\sin Kl}{Kl} \\
&+ \frac{4C^2}{(2\pi)^3} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) \cos(\mathbf{K} \cdot \boldsymbol{\ell}).
\end{aligned} \tag{A.11}$$

Appendix B

Derivation of the EM-GWs

Hamiltonian $\hat{H}_{\text{em-gw}}$

B.1 Orthogonality relation of the mode functions $\mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$

The orthogonality equation in the manuscript is considered as (see Eq. (4.41))

$$\langle \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}} | \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'} \rangle = \int d^3 \mathbf{x} \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{ki}^*(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{k'j}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}'). \quad (\text{B.1})$$

Here, we show that although $\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is \mathbf{x} -dependent, it does not change the orthogonality equation as long as $K \ll k$. Our EM fields of interest have a frequency of radio to optical waves, which spans from \sim GHz to 10^{15} Hz so that $10 \leq k \leq 10^7 \text{ m}^{-1}$. On the other hand, PGWs span a wide range of frequency $10^{-18} \leq \Omega_K \leq 10^{10}$ Hz, so that $10^{-26} \leq K \leq 10^2 \text{ m}^{-1}$. Thus, the adiabatic condition $K \ll k$ is almost fulfilled for PGWs and radiowaves. Moreover, the high-frequency part of PGWs has a negligible graviton content, and their effect on EM observable is automatically vanishing due to the small coupling strength. Now we consider

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)/\varepsilon_0 &= \delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \\ &= \delta_{ij} - \sum_{\gamma=+, \times} \int \frac{d^3 \mathbf{K}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] (h_{\mathbf{K}}^\gamma e^{-i(\Omega t - \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x})} + c.c.). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Inserting the expression of $\mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}, t) = f(t) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}} e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}}$ (where $f(t)$ is a slowly-varying function of time as discussed in Chapter 4) and Eq. (B.2) into Eq. (B.1) results in

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}} | \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'} \rangle &= \varepsilon_0 f^2(t) \int d^3\mathbf{x} (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}'j} e^{-i(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}')\cdot\mathbf{x}} \\
&= \varepsilon_0 f^2(t) (2\pi)^3 \delta_{ij} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}'j} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}') \\
&\quad - \varepsilon_0 f^2(t) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}'j} \sum_{\gamma=+, \times} \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{K}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} e_{ij}^{\gamma}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] (h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma} e^{-i\Omega t} \int d^3\mathbf{x} e^{i(\mathbf{K} - (\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}'))\cdot\mathbf{x}} \\
&\quad + h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma*} e^{i\Omega t} \int d^3\mathbf{x} e^{-i(\mathbf{K} + (\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}'))\cdot\mathbf{x}}) \\
&= \varepsilon_0 f^2(t) (2\pi)^3 \\
&\quad - \varepsilon_0 f^2(t) (2\pi)^3 \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}'j} \sum_{\gamma=+, \times} \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{K}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} e_{ij}^{\gamma}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] (h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma} e^{-i\Omega t} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - (\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}')) \\
&\quad + h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma*} e^{i\Omega t} \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} + (\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}'))), \tag{B.3}
\end{aligned}$$

which explicitly shows the scattering of mode \mathbf{k} to \mathbf{k}' of the EM field due to the presence of GWs with momentum \mathbf{K} . Thus, the momentum conservation implies either $\mathbf{k}' = \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{K}$ or $\mathbf{k}' = \mathbf{k} + \mathbf{K}$ possibilities. Since $K \ll k$, each mode of the EM field scatters to itself, and we may set

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} - (\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}')) &\simeq \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}'), \\
\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} + (\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}')) &\simeq \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}'). \tag{B.4}
\end{aligned}$$

Indeed, these conditions are fulfilled by almost all frequency parts of the PGWs spectrum, for which $K \ll k, k'$. For all GWs with $K \ll k$, the incoming EM field of mode \mathbf{k} scatters to itself so that $\mathbf{k} \simeq \mathbf{k}'$. So, we may proceed by retaining the contribution of all PGWs modes in the integral Eq. (B.3),

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}} | \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'} \rangle &= \varepsilon_0 f^2(t) (2\pi)^3 \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}') \left(1 - \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}j} \sum_{\gamma=+, \times} \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{K}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} e_{ij}^{\gamma}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] (h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma} e^{-i\Omega t} + h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma*} e^{i\Omega t}) \right) \\
&= \varepsilon_0 f^2(t) (2\pi)^3 \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}') (1 - h_{ij}(t) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}j}) \\
&= \varepsilon_0 f^2(t) (2\pi)^3 m(t) \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}'), \tag{B.5}
\end{aligned}$$

where in the last line the function $m(t) \equiv 1 - h_{ij}(t) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}j}$ is defined. The normalization factor $f(t)$ outcomes as

$$f^2(t) = \frac{1}{\varepsilon_0 (2\pi)^3 m(t)}, \tag{B.6}$$

and spatial mode functions are determined by

$$\mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}} e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}}}{\sqrt{\varepsilon_0 (2\pi)^3 m(t)}}. \tag{B.7}$$

Note that $m(t)$ is a slowly varying function of time, as it should be. Having obtained the expression of $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ given by Eq. (4.36), we can derive the Hamiltonian.

B.2 Quantization of the Hamiltonian

The Lagrangian Eq. (5.7) correctly reproduces the Maxwell's equations in the adiabatic approximation. Moreover, one may easily show that the Lagrangian is consistent with the action $S = \frac{1}{2} \int d^4x h_{\mu\nu} T^{\mu\nu}$ (see App. B.3). Thus, the following discussion holds correct, regardless of using the optical medium analogy framework. From the Lagrangian, one may define the corresponding conjugate momenta of \mathbf{A}_i , and find the Hamiltonian. The procedure is presented in the manuscript, and we end up with Eq. (5.10), namely

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}_{em-gw} &= \frac{1}{2} \int d^3\mathbf{x} [\varepsilon_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{\Pi}_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{\Pi}_j(\mathbf{x}, t) \\ &+ \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) (\nabla \times \hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}, t))_i (\nabla \times \hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}, t))_j] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\hbar}{2} \sum_{\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'} \left\{ \int d^3\mathbf{x} \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) (\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \dot{v}_k f_{\mathbf{k}i} + \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \dot{v}_k^* f_{\mathbf{k}i}^*) (\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'} \dot{v}_{k'} f_{\mathbf{k}'j} + \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'}^\dagger \dot{v}_{k'}^* f_{\mathbf{k}'j}^*) \right. \\ &+ \int d^3\mathbf{x} \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) (\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} v_k (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}})_i + \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger v_k^* (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}}^*)_i) \\ &\left. \times (\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'} v_{k'} (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'})_j + \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'}^\dagger v_{k'}^* (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'}^*)_j) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.8})$$

In the second equality, we plugged the expression of $\hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $\hat{\Pi}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ from Eqs. (5.8, 5.9) into the Hamiltonian. Note that $v_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is also a slowly varying function of \mathbf{x} . There would be four terms in the Hamiltonian, as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}_{em-gw} &= \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\hbar}{2} \sum_{\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'} \left\{ \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'} \int d^3\mathbf{x} (\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{\mathbf{k}i} f_{\mathbf{k}'j} \dot{v}_k \dot{v}_{k'} + \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) v_k v_{k'} (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}})_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'})_j) \right. \\ &+ \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'}^\dagger \int d^3\mathbf{x} (\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{\mathbf{k}i} f_{\mathbf{k}'j}^* \dot{v}_k \dot{v}_{k'}^* + \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) v_k v_{k'}^* (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}})_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'})_j) \\ &+ \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'} \int d^3\mathbf{x} (\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{\mathbf{k}i}^* f_{\mathbf{k}'j} \dot{v}_k^* \dot{v}_{k'} + \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) v_k^* v_{k'} (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}}^*)_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'})_j) \\ &\left. + \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'}^\dagger \int d^3\mathbf{x} (\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{\mathbf{k}i}^* f_{\mathbf{k}'j}^* \dot{v}_k^* \dot{v}_{k'}^* + \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) v_k^* v_{k'}^* (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}}^*)_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'})_j) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.9})$$

In the following, we compute each term using the adiabatic approximation $K \ll k$ and derive the Hamiltonian. Note that, the spatial integration should be taken over the whole region where that the EM field interacts with GWs. The temporal mode functions $v_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ are already specified by Eq. (4.51) of the manuscript, namely

$$\begin{aligned} v_k(\mathbf{x}, t) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t)}} e^{-i \int_0^t \omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t') dt'}, \\ \dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t)}} \frac{d}{dt} e^{-i \int_0^t \omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t') dt'} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t)}} \left(-i \frac{d}{dt} \left[\int_0^t \omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t') dt' \right] \right) e^{-i \int_0^t \omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t') dt'} \\ &= -i \omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t) v_k(\mathbf{x}, t). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.10})$$

However, we proceed by keeping v_k and \dot{v}_k explicitly inside the integrals. With the help of Eq. (B.2) and Eq. (B.7), the first term in Eq. (B.9) is proportional to

$$\begin{aligned} & \int d^3\mathbf{x} \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{\mathbf{k}i} f_{\mathbf{k}'j} \dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \dot{v}_{k'}(\mathbf{x}, t) \\ &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3 m(t)} \delta_{ij} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}'j} \int d^3\mathbf{x} e^{i(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}')\cdot\mathbf{x}} \dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \dot{v}_{k'}(\mathbf{x}, t) \\ &- \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3 m(t)} \int d^3\mathbf{x} e^{i(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}')\cdot\mathbf{x}} h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}'j} \dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \dot{v}_{k'}(\mathbf{x}, t). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.11})$$

Since the function $e^{i(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}')\cdot\mathbf{x}}$ is highly oscillating for large $(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}')$, the integral averages to zero unless $(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}')$ goes to zero so that $e^{i(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}')\cdot\mathbf{x}} \sim 1$. The result of the first integral can be written as

$$\frac{\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}')}{\delta^{(3)}(0)} \int d^3\mathbf{x} \dot{v}_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) = (2\pi)^3 \frac{\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}')}{V} \int d^3\mathbf{x} \dot{v}_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad (\text{B.12})$$

where the factor $\frac{\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}')}{\delta^{(3)}(0)} = 1$ is inserted to show that the result of the integral exists for $(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}') \sim 0$. Moreover, we used

$$\int e^{i(0)\cdot\mathbf{x}} d^3\mathbf{x} = (2\pi)^3 \delta^{(3)}(0) = V \quad \rightarrow \quad \delta^{(3)}(0) = \frac{V}{(2\pi)^3}. \quad (\text{B.13})$$

The second term in Eq. (B.11) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} & -\frac{1}{(2\pi)^3 m(t)} \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} e_{ij}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}'j} \left(h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma} e^{-i\Omega t} \int d^3\mathbf{x} e^{i(\mathbf{K}+(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}')\cdot\mathbf{x})} \dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \dot{v}_{k'}(\mathbf{x}, t) \right. \\ & \left. + h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma*} e^{i\Omega t} \int d^3\mathbf{x} e^{i(-\mathbf{K}+(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}')\cdot\mathbf{x})} \dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \dot{v}_{k'}(\mathbf{x}, t) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.14})$$

Again, due to the highly oscillating factors $e^{i(\pm\mathbf{K}+(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}')\cdot\mathbf{x})}$ the integration over \mathbf{x} averages to zero unless $(\pm\mathbf{K} + (\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}')) \sim 0$, for which the value of the integral in Eq. (B.14) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} & -\frac{1}{(2\pi)^3 m(t)} \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} e_{ij}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}'j} \left(h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma} e^{-i\Omega t} \frac{\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{K} + (\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}'))}{\delta^{(3)}(0)} \int d^3\mathbf{x} \dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \dot{v}_{k'}(\mathbf{x}, t) \right. \\ & \left. + h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma*} e^{i\Omega t} \frac{\delta^{(3)}(-\mathbf{K} + (\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}'))}{\delta^{(3)}(0)} \int d^3\mathbf{x} \dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \dot{v}_{k'}(\mathbf{x}, t) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.15})$$

As before, since $K \ll k$ we may neglect \mathbf{K} in delta functions (similar to Eq. (B.4)) and Eq. (B.15) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} & -\frac{\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}')}{m(t)V} \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} e_{ij}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{-\mathbf{k}j} \left(h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma} e^{-i\Omega t} \int d^3\mathbf{x} \dot{v}_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) \right. \\ & \left. + h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma*} e^{i\Omega t} \int d^3\mathbf{x} \dot{v}_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.16})$$

Inserting Eq. (B.12) and Eq. (B.16) into Eq. (B.11) leads to

$$\begin{aligned} \int d^3\mathbf{x} \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{\mathbf{k}i} f_{\mathbf{k}'j} \dot{v}_k \dot{v}_{k'} &= \frac{\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}')}{m(t)V} \left(\int d^3\mathbf{x} \dot{v}_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) \right) (1 - h_{ij}(t) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}'j}) \\ &= \frac{\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}')}{V} \left(\int d^3\mathbf{x} \dot{v}_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.17})$$

Here, we used definition $m(t) \equiv (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}'j}$ which was defined earlier in Eq. (B.5). In a similar way, we may show that

$$\begin{aligned} \int d^3\mathbf{x} \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{\mathbf{k}i} f_{\mathbf{k}'j}^* \dot{v}_k \dot{v}_{k'}^* &= \frac{\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}')}{V} \left(\int d^3\mathbf{x} |\dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)|^2 \right), \\ \int d^3\mathbf{x} \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{\mathbf{k}i}^* f_{\mathbf{k}'j} \dot{v}_k^* \dot{v}_{k'} &= \frac{\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}')}{V} \left(\int d^3\mathbf{x} |\dot{v}_k^*(\mathbf{x}, t)|^2 \right), \\ \int d^3\mathbf{x} \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{\mathbf{k}i}^* f_{\mathbf{k}'j}^* \dot{v}_k^* \dot{v}_{k'}^* &= \frac{\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}')}{V} \left(\int d^3\mathbf{x} \dot{v}_k^{*2}(\mathbf{x}, t) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.18})$$

Next we compute the second term in the Hamiltonian Eq. (B.9), which is of the form

$$\begin{aligned} &\int d^3\mathbf{x} \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}})_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'})_j v_k v_{k'} \\ &= \int d^3\mathbf{x} \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) \varepsilon_{ilm} (\partial_l f_{\mathbf{k}m}) (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'})_j v_k v_{k'} \\ &= \int d^3\mathbf{x} \varepsilon_{ilm} \partial_l [\mu_{ij}^{-1} f_{\mathbf{k}m} (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'})_j v_k v_{k'}] - \int d^3\mathbf{x} \varepsilon_{ilm} f_{\mathbf{k}m} \partial_l [\mu_{ij}^{-1} (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'})_j v_k v_{k'}] \\ &= \int d^3\mathbf{x} \varepsilon_{mli} \partial_l [\mu^{-1} \nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'}]_i v_k v_{k'} f_{\mathbf{k}m}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.19})$$

Note that, the surface integral vanishes assuming the field vanishes at infinity. Moreover, in the last line, we have used

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_l [\mu_{ij}^{-1} (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'})_j v_k v_{k'}] &= (\partial_l \mu_{ij}^{-1}) (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'})_i v_k v_{k'} + \mu_{ij}^{-1} \partial_l [(\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'})_j] + \mu_{ij}^{-1} (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'})_j \partial_l (v_k v_{k'}) \\ &= \mu_{ij}^{-1} \partial_l [(\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'})_j]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.20})$$

In the last line, we used the fact that the functions $\mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $v_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ are slowly varying functions of \mathbf{x} and their derivative are proportional to K , which is negligible with respect to k . Thus, Eq. (B.19) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} &\int d^3\mathbf{x} \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}})_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}'})_j v_k v_{k'} \\ &= \int d^3\mathbf{x} (\nabla \times [\mu^{-1} \nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{k}}])_m f_{\mathbf{k}m} v_k v_{k'} = \int d^3\mathbf{x} \omega_{k'}^2(\mathbf{x}, t) \varepsilon_{ml}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{\mathbf{k}'l} f_{\mathbf{k}m} v_k v_{k'}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.21})$$

In the second line, we plugged in from the wave equation Eq. (4.40). Inserting \mathbf{f}_k from Eq. (B.7) into Eq. B.21 yields

$$\int d^3\mathbf{x} \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k)_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'})_j \nu_k \nu_{k'} = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3 m(t)} \int d^3\mathbf{x} e^{i(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}')\cdot\mathbf{x}} (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{ki} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k'j} \nu_k \nu_{k'}. \quad (\text{B.22})$$

A similar procedure as in Eqs. (B.11 - B.17) results in the following equation

$$\int d^3\mathbf{x} \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k)_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'})_j \nu_k \nu_{k'} = \frac{\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}')}{V} \int d^3\mathbf{x} \omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) \nu_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t). \quad (\text{B.23})$$

Similarly we may show that

$$\begin{aligned} \int d^3\mathbf{x} \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k)_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'}^*)_j \nu_k \nu_{k'}^* &= \frac{\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}')}{V} \int d^3\mathbf{x} \omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) |\nu_k(\mathbf{x}, t)|^2, \\ \int d^3\mathbf{x} \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k^*)_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'})_j \nu_k^* \nu_{k'} &= \frac{\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}')}{V} \int d^3\mathbf{x} \omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) |\nu_k(\mathbf{x}, t)|^2, \\ \int d^3\mathbf{x} \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, t) (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k^*)_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'}^*)_j \nu_k^* \nu_{k'}^* &= \frac{\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}')}{V} \int d^3\mathbf{x} \omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) \nu_k^{*2}(\mathbf{x}, t). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.24})$$

Combining Eqs. (B.17 , B.18) and Eqs. (B.23 , B.24) yields the following expression for the Hamiltonian Eq. (B.9)

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}_{em-gw} &= \frac{\hbar}{4} \sum_{\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'} \left\{ \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'} \left(\frac{\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}')}{V} \right) \int d^3\mathbf{x} (\dot{\nu}_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) + \omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) \nu_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t)) \right. \\ &+ \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'}^\dagger \left(\frac{\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}')}{V} \right) \int d^3\mathbf{x} (|\dot{\nu}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)|^2 + \omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) |\nu_k(\mathbf{x}, t)|^2) \\ &+ \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'} \left(\frac{\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}')}{V} \right) \int d^3\mathbf{x} (|\dot{\nu}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)|^2 + \omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) |\nu_k(\mathbf{x}, t)|^2) \\ &\left. + \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'}^\dagger \left(\frac{\delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}')}{V} \right) \int d^3\mathbf{x} (\dot{\nu}_k^{*2}(\mathbf{x}, t) + \omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}, t) \nu_k^{*2}(\mathbf{x}, t)) \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.25})$$

and Eq. (5.14) is recovered.

B.3 Equivalence between the optical medium analogy framework and general relativity

In this section, we show that the EM-GWs Lagrangian proposed in Eq. (5.7) within the optical medium analogy coincides with the Lagrangian obtained in general relativity. One may start from the Lagrangian Eq. (5.7) and separate it into free and interaction parts, it is easy to show that the interaction Lagrangian in the OMA framework is obtained as

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = -\frac{1}{2} h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) (\varepsilon_0 E_i E_j + \frac{1}{\mu_0} B_i B_j). \quad (\text{B.26})$$

On the other hand, the interaction action

$$S_{\text{int}}^{\text{EH}} = -\frac{1}{2} \int d^4x h_{\mu\nu} T^{\mu\nu} \quad (\text{B.27})$$

in general relativity describes the coupling between the EM field with the energy-momentum tensor $T^{\mu\nu}$ and metric perturbations $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$. Choosing the TT gauge eliminates temporal coordinates so that $\mu, \nu \rightarrow i, j$ where ij are spatial indices. The spatial sector of $T^{\mu\nu}$ is determined by

$$T^{ij} = T_{ij} = \varepsilon_0 E_i E_j + \frac{1}{\mu_0} B_i B_j - \frac{1}{2} (\varepsilon_0 E^2 + \frac{1}{\mu_0} B^2) \delta_{ij}. \quad (\text{B.28})$$

Inserting Eq. (B.28) into Eq. (B.27) and using the traceless condition $h_{ij} \delta_{ij} = 0$, one can easily obtain the interaction Lagrangian corresponding to the action Eq. (B.27) according to

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}}^{\text{EH}} = -\frac{1}{2} h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) (\varepsilon_0 E_i E_j + \frac{1}{\mu_0} B_i B_j), \quad (\text{B.29})$$

which coincides with Eq. (B.26).

Appendix C

Optical variance $[\Delta\hat{\chi}_\vartheta(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]^2$ in the presence of quantum GWs

Here we calculate optical variance, given by Eq. (5.60), assuming GWs in vacuum, coherent, one-mode squeezed, two-mode squeezed, and thermal states. In order to calculate

$$\begin{aligned} [\Delta\hat{\chi}_\vartheta(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]^2 &= (\langle \hat{a}^2(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle - \langle \hat{a}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle^2) e^{-2i\vartheta} \\ &+ (\langle \hat{a}^{\dagger 2}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle - \langle \hat{a}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle^2) e^{2i\vartheta} \\ &+ 2\langle \hat{a}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \hat{a}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle - 2|\langle \hat{a}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle|^2 + 1, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.1})$$

we should first calculate $\langle \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle$.

C.1 $\langle \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle$ in the presence of GWs

Using the expression Eq. (5.49) for $\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ one has

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \langle \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \\ &\times e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \left(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} + \frac{1}{2} \right)} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} t} \rangle \\ &\equiv M(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \langle e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \left(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} + \frac{1}{2} \right)} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} t} \rangle_{\hat{\rho}_{\text{em}}}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.2})$$

where we have defined

$$M(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \equiv \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \langle \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \rangle_{\hat{\rho}_{\text{gw}}}. \quad (\text{C.3})$$

Note that, the total density matrix of the EM-GWs system is considered as $\hat{\rho} = \hat{\rho}_{\text{em}} \otimes \hat{\rho}_{\text{gws}}$.

The expectation value over a coherent state of EM field, $\hat{\rho}_{\text{em}} = |\alpha\rangle\langle\alpha|$ is determined by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle \alpha | e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) (\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} + \frac{1}{2})} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} t} | \alpha \rangle &= \alpha e^{iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \langle \alpha | \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))^n}{n!} e^{-\frac{|\alpha|^2}{2}} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^m}{\sqrt{m!}} (\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}})^n | m \rangle \\
 &= \alpha e^{iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \langle \alpha | \sum_{n,m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)m)^n}{n!} e^{-\frac{|\alpha|^2}{2}} \frac{\alpha^m}{\sqrt{m!}} | m \rangle \\
 &= \alpha e^{iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \langle \alpha | \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} e^{-\frac{|\alpha|^2}{2}} \frac{\alpha^m e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)m}}{\sqrt{m!}} | m \rangle \\
 &= \alpha e^{iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \langle \alpha | \alpha e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \rangle \\
 &= \alpha e^{iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \exp \left[-\frac{|\alpha|^2}{2} - \frac{|\alpha e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)}|^2}{2} + \alpha^* \alpha e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \right] \\
 &= \alpha e^{iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \exp \left[-|\alpha|^2 (1 - e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)}) \right]. \tag{C.4}
 \end{aligned}$$

Now we calculate $M(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ defined by Eq. (C.3) for different states of GWs.

C.1.1 $M_{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$

With the help of the density matrix of Eq. (5.51) for vacuum fluctuations of GWs, Eq. (C.3) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) | 0_{\mathbf{K}} \rangle \langle 0_{-\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) | 0_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\
 &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}} | -\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle \langle 0_{-\mathbf{K}} | -\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle. \tag{C.5}
 \end{aligned}$$

With the help of the projection property of coherent states $\langle \alpha | \alpha' \rangle = \exp[-|\alpha|^2/2 - |\alpha'|^2/2 + \alpha^* \alpha']$, Eq. (C.5) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &\equiv \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} e^{-\frac{1}{2} [|\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)|^2 + |\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)|^2]} \\
 &= e^{-\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) (|\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)|^2 + |\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)|^2)}. \tag{C.6}
 \end{aligned}$$

In the last line of Eq. (C.6), we transformed the discrete notation to continuous notation. Note that, $\kappa_{\gamma}(-\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) = \kappa_{\gamma}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k})$ (see the definition of Eq. (5.31)). Moreover, from definition Eq. (5.41) one has

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)|^2 &= |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)|^2 = |\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)|^2 = |\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)|^2 \tag{C.7} \\
 &= 4 \sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}{2} |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2, \\
 \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^2(\mathbf{x}, t) &= (1 - 2e^{i\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t} + e^{2i\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}) g_{\mathbf{K}}^{*2}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f), \\
 \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^2(\mathbf{x}, t) &= (1 - 2e^{i\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t} + e^{2i\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}) g_{\mathbf{K}}^2(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f).
 \end{aligned}$$

Here we have used the property $g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) = g_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)$. Hence, the contribution of $\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3-}$ in the integral Eq. (C.6) would be equal to the contribution of $\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}$ and Eq. (C.6) reduces to

$$M_{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) = e^{-\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \left(4 \sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}{2} \right) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2}. \quad (\text{C.8})$$

C.1.2 $M_{\text{coh}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$

The expression of Eq. (C.3) in the case of the coherent GWs can be written as follows

$$\begin{aligned} M_{\text{coh}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \langle \beta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) | \beta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma} \rangle \\ &\times \langle \beta_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma} | \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) | \beta_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma} \rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.9})$$

With the help of the property of the displacement operator

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{D}(\alpha) \hat{D}(\beta) &= e^{i\Im(\alpha\beta^*)} \hat{D}(\alpha + \beta), \\ \hat{D}^\dagger(\beta) \hat{D}(\alpha) \hat{D}(\beta) &= e^{2i\Im(\alpha\beta^*)} \hat{D}(\alpha), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.10})$$

one has

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \beta_{\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}) | \beta_{\mathbf{K}} \rangle &= \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}^\dagger(\beta_{\mathbf{K}}) \hat{D}(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}) \hat{D}(\beta_{\mathbf{K}}) | 0_{\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\ &= e^{2i\Im(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}} \beta_{\mathbf{K}}^*)} \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}) | 0_{\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\ &= e^{2i\Im(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}} \beta_{\mathbf{K}}^*)} e^{-\frac{1}{2} |\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}|^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.11})$$

With the help of Eq. (C.11), Eq. (C.9) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} M_{\text{coh}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &\equiv \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} e^{2i\Im(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \beta_{\mathbf{K}}^*)} e^{-\frac{1}{2} |\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)|^2} \\ &\times e^{2i\Im(-\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \beta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*)} e^{-\frac{1}{2} |\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)|^2} \\ &= e^{-2i \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \Im[\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \beta_{\mathbf{K}}^* + \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \beta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*]} \\ &\times e^{-\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) (|\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)|^2 + |\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)|^2)} \\ &= M_{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) e^{-2i \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \Im[\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \beta_{\mathbf{K}}^*]}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.12})$$

C.1.3 $M_{\text{sq}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$

Eq. (C.3) in case of the one-mode squeezed GWs can be written as follows

$$\begin{aligned} M_{\text{sq}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \langle \zeta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) | \zeta_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma} \rangle \\ &\times \langle \zeta_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma} | \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) | \zeta_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma} \rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.13})$$

The squeezing operator $\hat{S}(\zeta_K)$ fulfills the property that

$$\hat{S}^\dagger(\zeta_K)\hat{D}(\beta_K)\hat{S}(\zeta_K) = \hat{D}(\beta'_K), \quad (\text{C.14})$$

where $\beta'_K = \beta_K \cosh r_K + \beta_K^* e^{2i\phi_K} \sinh r_K$. For squeezed states, one may use the following expressions

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \zeta_K | \hat{D}_K(-\kappa\eta_K) | \zeta_K \rangle &= \langle 0_K | \hat{S}^\dagger(\zeta_K) \hat{D}_K(-\kappa\eta_K) \hat{S}(\zeta_K) | 0_K \rangle \\ &= \langle 0_K | \hat{D}_K(-\kappa\eta_K \cosh r_K - \kappa\eta_K^* e^{2i\phi_K} \sinh r_K) | 0_K \rangle \\ &\equiv \langle 0_K | \hat{D}_K(-\kappa\eta') | 0_K \rangle \\ &= \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\kappa^2 |\eta'|^2\right), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.15})$$

where in the last line, we have defined

$$\eta' \equiv \eta_K \cosh r_K + \eta_K^* e^{2i\phi_K} \sinh r_K. \quad (\text{C.16})$$

We can straightforwardly show that

$$\begin{aligned} |\eta'(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)|^2 &= |\eta_K(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)|^2 (\sinh^2 r_K + \cosh^2 r_K) + 2\Re[\eta_K^2 e^{-2i\phi_K} \sinh r_K \cosh r_K] \\ &= 4 \sin^2 \frac{\Omega_K t}{2} (1 + 2 \sinh^2 r_K) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \\ &\quad + \sinh 2r_K \Re[(e^{-2i\phi_K} - 2e^{i(\Omega_K t - 2\phi_K)} + e^{2i(\Omega_K t - \phi_K)}) g_{\mathbf{K}}^{*2}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.17})$$

With the help of Eq. (C.15) and Eq. (C.17), Eq. (C.13) can be written as follows

$$\begin{aligned} M_{\text{sq}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &\equiv \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\kappa^2 (|\eta'_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)|^2 + |\eta'_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)|^2)} \\ &= \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \left\{ 4 \sin^2 \frac{\Omega_K t}{2} (1 + 2 \sinh^2 r_K) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. + \sinh 2r_K \Re[(e^{-2i\phi_K} - 2e^{i(\Omega_K t - 2\phi_K)} + e^{2i(\Omega_K t - \phi_K)}) g_{\mathbf{K}}^{*2}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)] \right\} \right) \\ &= M_{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \exp\left[-\sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \left(4 \sin^2 \frac{\Omega_K t}{2} |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. + \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K \Re[(e^{-2i\phi_K} - 2e^{i(\Omega_K t - 2\phi_K)} + e^{2i(\Omega_K t - \phi_K)}) g_{\mathbf{K}}^{*2}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)] \right) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.18})$$

C.1.4 $M_{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$

Eq. (C.3) in case of the two-mode squeezed GWs can be written as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \langle \text{TS} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) | \text{TS} \rangle \\
 &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}} | \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}} \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}} \\
 &\times \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}} \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}} | 0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle. \tag{C.19}
 \end{aligned}$$

where in the second line we have used Eq. (2.66) for definition of two-mode squeezed state $|\text{TS}\rangle$. For two-mode squeezing operator $\hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}(\zeta_{\mathbf{K}})$, we may show the following properties. For a given unitary operator \hat{V} and a function $f(\hat{A})$ of some operator \hat{A} , one may easily show that $\hat{V}f(\hat{A})\hat{V}^{\dagger} = f(\hat{V}\hat{A}\hat{V}^{\dagger})$. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}) \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}} \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}} &= \exp \left[\hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} (-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}} \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} + \kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^* \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}) \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}} \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}} \right] \\
 &= \exp \left[-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}} \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger}(\eta_H) + \kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^* \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H) \right] \\
 &= \exp \left[-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}} (u_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H) \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} + v_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H) \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^* (u_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H) \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} + v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H) \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger}) \right] \tag{C.20} \\
 &= \exp \left[-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}} u_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H) \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} + \kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^* u_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H) \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}} \right] \\
 &\times \exp \left[\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^* v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H) \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} - \kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}} v_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H) \hat{b}_{-\mathbf{K}} \right] \\
 &= \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}} u_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H)) \otimes \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}(\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^* v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)).
 \end{aligned}$$

Here, we used Eq. (2.56) and Eq. (2.62). In a similar way, we can show

$$\hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}) \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}} \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}} = \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}} u_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H)) \otimes \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^* v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)). \tag{C.21}$$

As a result, Eq. (C.19) can be written as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) u_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H)) \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)) | 0_{\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\
 &\times \langle 0_{-\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) u_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H)) | 0_{\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\
 &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \langle -\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) u_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H) | \kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H) \rangle \\
 &\times \langle \kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H) | -\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) u_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H) \rangle \\
 &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} |\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) u_{\mathbf{K}}^*|^2 - \frac{1}{2} |\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) v_{\mathbf{K}}|^2 \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \kappa^2 \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) u_{\mathbf{K}} v_{\mathbf{K}} \right] \\
 &\times \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} |\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) v_{\mathbf{K}}|^2 - \frac{1}{2} |\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) u_{\mathbf{K}}^*|^2 - \kappa^2 \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) u_{\mathbf{K}}^* v_{\mathbf{K}}^* \right] \\
 &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa^2 (|\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) u_{\mathbf{K}}^*|^2 + |\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) v_{\mathbf{K}}|^2 \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) v_{\mathbf{K}}|^2 + |\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) u_{\mathbf{K}}^*|^2 \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + 2 \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) u_{\mathbf{K}} v_{\mathbf{K}} + 2 \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) u_{\mathbf{K}}^* v_{\mathbf{K}}^* \right]. \quad (\text{C.22})
 \end{aligned}$$

With the help of Eq. (C.7), Eq. (C.22) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) (4 \sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \right] \\
 &\times \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \left\{ (4 \sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}{2}) (2 |v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)|^2) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. + 2 \Re[(1 - 2e^{i\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t} + e^{2i\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}) u_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H) v_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H)] |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \right\} \right] \\
 &= M_{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \\
 &\times \exp \left[-\sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \left\{ \sinh^2 r_{\mathbf{K}} (4 \sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}{2}) \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. + \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_{\mathbf{K}} (\cos(2\phi_{\mathbf{K}}) - 2 \cos(2\phi_{\mathbf{K}} - \Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t) + \cos(2\phi_{\mathbf{K}} - 2\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t)) \right\} \right]. \quad (\text{C.23})
 \end{aligned}$$

Here, the definitions of $u_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)$ and $v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)$ in terms of the squeezing parameters $r_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)$, $\phi_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)$ given by Eq. (2.58) are used.

C.1.5 $\langle \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle_{\text{th}}$

The expression of Eq. (C.3) in the case of the thermal GWs can be written as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{\text{th}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \langle \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \rangle_{\hat{\rho}_{\text{th}}} \quad (\text{C.24}) \\
 &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \langle \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \hat{\rho}_{\text{th}, \mathbf{K}, \gamma} \otimes \hat{\rho}_{\text{th}, -\mathbf{K}, \gamma} \rangle \\
 &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \langle \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \hat{\rho}_{\text{th}, \mathbf{K}, \gamma} \rangle \langle \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \hat{\rho}_{\text{th}, -\mathbf{K}, \gamma} \rangle.
 \end{aligned}$$

In the second line, we have used the density matrix of thermal GWs given by Eq. (5.57). In the third line, we use the fact that operators associated with opposite momenta \mathbf{K} and $-\mathbf{K}$ commute. Now, with the help of the following property of thermal states

$$\langle \hat{D}(\alpha) \rangle_{\hat{\rho}_{\text{th}}} = \exp \left[-|\alpha|^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \bar{n}_{\text{th}} \right) \right], \quad (\text{C.25})$$

one may write

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \hat{\rho}_{\text{th}, \mathbf{K}, \gamma} \rangle &= \exp \left[-|\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)|^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(\mathbf{K}) \right) \right] \quad (\text{C.26}) \\
 &= \exp \left[-\kappa^2 \left(4 \sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}{2} \right) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(\mathbf{K}) \right) \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, Eq. (C.24) recasts to the following form

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{\text{th}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \exp \left[-\kappa^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \left(4 \sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}{2} \right) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 (1 + \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(\mathbf{K}) + \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(\mathbf{K})) \right] \\
 &= \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \left(4 \sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}{2} \right) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \right] \\
 &\times \exp \left[-\sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(\mathbf{K}) \left(4 \sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}{2} \right) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \right] \\
 &= M_{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \\
 &\times \exp \left[-\sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(\mathbf{K}) \left(4 \sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}{2} \right) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \right]. \quad (\text{C.27})
 \end{aligned}$$

C.2 $\langle \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^2(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle$ in the presence of GWs

Using Eq. (5.49) for $\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ one has

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^2(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \rangle &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \langle \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \\
 &\times \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \rangle_{\hat{\rho}_{\text{gw}}} \\
 &\times \langle e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \left(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k} + \frac{1}{2}} \right)} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \left(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k} + \frac{1}{2}} \right)} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \rangle_{\hat{\rho}_{\text{em}}} \\
 &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \langle \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-2\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-2\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \rangle \\
 &\times \alpha^2 e^{4iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \exp[-|\alpha|^2 (1 - e^{4iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)})] \\
 &\equiv N(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \alpha^2 e^{4iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \exp[-|\alpha|^2 (1 - e^{4iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)})]. \tag{C.28}
 \end{aligned}$$

where in the second line we have used Eq. (C.10). The expectation value taken over the coherent state of the EM field is calculated similar to Eq. (C.4). Moreover, the function $N(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is defined by the following equation

$$N(\mathbf{x}, t) = \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \langle \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-2\kappa \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}, t)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-2\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}, t)) \rangle_{\hat{\rho}_{\text{gw}}}. \tag{C.29}$$

In comparison with Eq. (C.3) for $M(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$, one may recover the expression of $N(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ by replacing $\kappa \rightarrow 2\kappa$ in $M(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ that we have obtained in Sec. C.1. In this way, we obtain the following results

$$\begin{aligned}
 N_{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= e^{-\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} (2\kappa(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}))^2 \left(4 \sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}{2} \right) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2}, \tag{C.30} \\
 N_{\text{coh}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= N_{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) e^{-2i \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \Im \left(2\kappa(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \beta_{\mathbf{K}}^* \right)}, \\
 N_{\text{sq}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= N_{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \exp \left[- \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} (2\kappa(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}))^2 \right. \\
 &\times \left(\sinh^2 r_{\mathbf{K}} \left(4 \sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}{2} \right) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \right. \\
 &\left. + \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_{\mathbf{K}} \Re \left[\left(e^{-2i\phi_{\mathbf{K}}} - 2e^{i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t - 2\phi_{\mathbf{K}})} + e^{2i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t - \phi_{\mathbf{K}})} \right) g_{\mathbf{K}}^{*2}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) \right] \right], \\
 N_{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= N_{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \exp \left[- \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} (2\kappa(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}))^2 \left(\sinh^2 r_{\mathbf{K}} \left(4 \sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}{2} \right) \right. \right. \\
 &\left. \left. + \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_{\mathbf{K}} (\cos[2\phi_{\mathbf{K}}] - 2 \cos[2\phi_{\mathbf{K}} - \Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t] + \cos[2\phi_{\mathbf{K}} - 2\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t]) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \right) \right], \\
 N_{\text{th}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= N_{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) \exp \left[- \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} (2\kappa(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}))^2 \left(4 \sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}} t}{2} \right) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

C.3 $[\Delta\chi_\theta(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]^2$ in the presence of GWs

With the help of the results of previous sections, we can now calculate the expression of the optical variance given by Eq. (C.1), for different states of GWs.

C.3.1 $[\Delta\chi_\theta(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]_{\text{vac}}^2$

Using Eq. (C.8) and Eq. (C.30) for vacuum state of GWs, Eq. (C.1) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 [\Delta\chi_\theta(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]_{\text{vac}}^2 &= \left[\alpha^2 e^{4iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \exp[-|\alpha|^2(1 - e^{4iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)})] e^{-\frac{1}{2}\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} 4\kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega\mathbf{K}t}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} \right. \\
 &\quad - \alpha^2 e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \exp[-2|\alpha|^2(1 - e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)})] e^{-\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega\mathbf{K}t}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} \left. \right] e^{-2i\theta} \\
 &\quad + c.c. + 2|\alpha|^2 - 2|\alpha|^2 \exp[-|\alpha|^2(2 - 2\cos 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))] \\
 &\quad \times e^{-\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega\mathbf{K}t}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} + 1 \\
 &= 2\alpha^2 e^{-2\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega\mathbf{K}t}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} \exp[-|\alpha|^2(1 - \cos 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))] \\
 &\quad \times \Re\{e^{i(4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - 2\theta + |\alpha|^2 \sin 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))}\} \\
 &\quad - 2\alpha^2 e^{-\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega\mathbf{K}t}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} \exp[-2|\alpha|^2(1 - \cos 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))] \\
 &\quad \times \Re\{e^{i(2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - 2\theta + 2|\alpha|^2 \sin 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))}\} \\
 &\quad + 2|\alpha|^2(1 - \exp[-4|\alpha|^2 \sin^2 E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]) e^{-\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega\mathbf{K}t}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} + 1.
 \end{aligned} \tag{C.31}$$

With the help of definition of $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ given by Eq. (5.62), Eq. (C.31) takes the form of Eq. (5.61) of the text.

C.3.2 $[\Delta\chi_\theta(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]_{\text{coh}}^2$

Using Eq. (C.12) and Eq. (C.30) for coherent state of GWs, Eq. (C.1) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 [\Delta\chi_\theta(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]_{\text{coh}}^2 &= 2\Re\left(\alpha^2 e^{4iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \exp[-|\alpha|^2(1 - e^{4iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)})] \right. \\
 &\quad \times e^{-\frac{1}{2}\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} 4\kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega\mathbf{K}t}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} e^{-2i\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} (2\kappa\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)\beta_{\mathbf{K}}^*)} e^{-2i\theta} \left. \right) \\
 &\quad - 2\Re\left(\alpha^2 e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \exp[-2|\alpha|^2(1 - e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)})] \right. \\
 &\quad \times e^{-\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega\mathbf{K}t}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} e^{-4i\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \Im(\kappa\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)\beta_{\mathbf{K}}^*)} e^{-2i\theta} \left. \right) \\
 &\quad + 2|\alpha|^2 - 2|\alpha|^2 \exp[-|\alpha|^2(2 - 2\cos 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))] \\
 &\quad \times e^{-\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega\mathbf{K}t}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} + 1 \\
 &= 2\alpha^2 \exp[-|\alpha|^2(1 - \cos 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))] e^{-\frac{1}{2}\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} 4\kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega\mathbf{K}t}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} \\
 &\quad \times \Re\left[e^{i(4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - 2\theta + |\alpha|^2 \sin 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - 4\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \Im(\kappa\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)\beta_{\mathbf{K}}^*))}\right] \\
 &\quad - 2\alpha^2 \exp[-2|\alpha|^2(1 - \cos 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))] e^{-\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega\mathbf{K}t}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} \\
 &\quad \times \Re\left[e^{i(2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - 2\theta + 2|\alpha|^2 \sin 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) - 4\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \Im(\kappa\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)\beta_{\mathbf{K}}^*))}\right] \\
 &\quad + 2|\alpha|^2(1 - \exp[-4|\alpha|^2 \sin^2 E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]) e^{-\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega\mathbf{K}t}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} + 1.
 \end{aligned} \tag{C.32}$$

With the help of definition of $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ and $C^{\text{coh}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ given by Eq. (5.62) and Eq. (5.65), Eq. (C.32) takes the form of Eq. (5.64) of the text.

C.3.3 $[\Delta\chi_\theta(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]_{\text{sq}}^2$

Using Eq. (C.18) and Eq. (C.30) for squeezed state of GWs, Eq. (C.1) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 [\Delta\chi_\theta(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]_{\text{sq}}^2 &= 2\Re\left\{\alpha^2 e^{4iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \exp\left[-|\alpha|^2(1 - e^{4iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)})\right] e^{-\frac{1}{2}\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \mathbf{K}^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2}\right. \\
 &\times \exp\left[-4\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \mathbf{K}^2 \left\{\sinh^2 r_K (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2\right. \right. \\
 &+ \left. \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K \Re[(e^{-2i\phi_K} - 2e^{i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}-2\phi_K)} + e^{2i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}-2\phi_K)}) g_{\mathbf{K}}^{*2}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)]\right] e^{-2i\theta}\left. \right\} \\
 &- 2\Re\left\{\alpha^2 e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \exp\left[-2|\alpha|^2(1 - e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)})\right] e^{-\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \mathbf{K}^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2}\right. \\
 &\times \exp\left[-2\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \mathbf{K}^2 \left\{\sinh^2 r_K (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2\right. \right. \\
 &+ \left. \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K \Re[(e^{-2i\phi_K} - 2e^{i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}-2\phi_K)} + e^{2i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}-2\phi_K)}) g_{\mathbf{K}}^{*2}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)]\right] e^{-2i\theta}\left. \right\} \\
 &+ 2|\alpha|^2 - 2|\alpha|^2 \exp\left[-|\alpha|^2(2 - 2\cos 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))\right] e^{-\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \mathbf{K}^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} \\
 &\times \exp\left[-2\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \mathbf{K}^2 \left\{\sinh^2 r_K (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2\right. \right. \\
 &+ \left. \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K \Re[(e^{-2i\phi_K} - 2e^{i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}-2\phi_K)} + e^{2i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}-2\phi_K)}) g_{\mathbf{K}}^{*2}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)]\right] + 1 \\
 &= 2\alpha^2 \exp\left[-|\alpha|^2(1 - \cos 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))\right] e^{-2\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \mathbf{K}^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} \\
 &\times \exp\left[-4\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \mathbf{K}^2 \left\{\sinh^2 r_K (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2\right. \right. \\
 &+ \left. \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K \Re[(e^{-2i\phi_K} - 2e^{i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}-2\phi_K)} + e^{2i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}-2\phi_K)}) g_{\mathbf{K}}^{*2}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)]\right] \\
 &- 2\alpha^2 \exp\left[-2|\alpha|^2(1 - \cos 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))\right] e^{-\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \mathbf{K}^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} \\
 &\times \exp\left[-2\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \mathbf{K}^2 \left\{\sinh^2 r_K (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2\right. \right. \\
 &+ \left. \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K \Re[(e^{-2i\phi_K} - 2e^{i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}-2\phi_K)} + e^{2i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}-2\phi_K)}) g_{\mathbf{K}}^{*2}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)]\right] \\
 &+ 2|\alpha|^2 \left(1 - \exp\left[-4|\alpha|^2 \sin^2 E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)\right] e^{-\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \mathbf{K}^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2}\right. \\
 &\times \exp\left[-2\sum_\gamma \int d^3\mathbf{K} \mathbf{K}^2 \left\{\sinh^2 r_K (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2\right. \right. \\
 &+ \left. \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K \Re[(e^{-2i\phi_K} - 2e^{i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}-2\phi_K)} + e^{2i(\Omega_{\mathbf{K}t}-2\phi_K)}) g_{\mathbf{K}}^{*2}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)]\right] \left. \right) + 1.
 \end{aligned} \tag{C.33}$$

With the help of definition of $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ and $\mathcal{D}^{\text{sq}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ given by Eq. (5.62) and Eq. (5.73), Eq. (C.33) takes the form of Eq. (5.72) of the text.

C.3.4 $[\Delta\chi_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]_{\text{ts}}^2$

Using Eq. (C.23) and Eq. (C.30) for two-mode squeezed state of GWs, Eq. (C.1) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 [\Delta\chi_{1,\theta}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]_{\text{ts}}^2 &= 2\Re\left\{\alpha^2 e^{4iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \exp[-|\alpha|^2(1 - e^{4iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)})]\right. & (C.34) \\
 &\times e^{-\frac{1}{2}\sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} 4\kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_K t}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} \\
 &\times \exp\left[-4 \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \left\{ \sinh^2 r_K (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_K t}{2}) \right. \right. \\
 &+ \left. \left. \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K (\cos[2\phi_K] - 2\cos[2\phi_K - \Omega_K t] + \cos[2\phi_K - 2\Omega_K t]) \right\} e^{-2i\theta}\right] \\
 &- 2\Re\left\{\alpha^2 e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \exp[-2|\alpha|^2(1 - e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)})]\right. \\
 &\times e^{-\sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_K t}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} \exp\left[-2 \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \left\{ \sinh^2 r_K (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_K t}{2}) \right. \right. \\
 &+ \left. \left. \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K (\cos[2\phi_K] - 2\cos[2\phi_K - \Omega_K t] + \cos[2\phi_K - 2\Omega_K t]) \right\} e^{-2i\theta}\right] \\
 &+ 2|\alpha|^2 - 2|\alpha|^2 \exp[-|\alpha|^2(2 - 2\cos 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))] \\
 &\times e^{-\sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_K t}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} \exp\left[-2 \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \left\{ \sinh^2 r_K (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_K t}{2}) \right. \right. \\
 &+ \left. \left. \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K (\cos[2\phi_K] - 2\cos[2\phi_K - \Omega_K t] + \cos[2\phi_K - 2\Omega_K t]) \right\} e^{-2i\theta}\right] + 1 \\
 &= 2\alpha^2 \exp[-|\alpha|^2(1 - \cos 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))] \\
 &\times e^{-2\sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_K t}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} \exp\left[-4 \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \left\{ \sinh^2 r_K (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_K t}{2}) \right. \right. \\
 &+ \left. \left. \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K (\cos[2\phi_K] - 2\cos[2\phi_K - \Omega_K t] + \cos[2\phi_K - 2\Omega_K t]) \right\} \right] \\
 &\times \Re\left\{e^{i(-2\theta + 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + |\alpha|^2 \sin 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))}\right\} \\
 &- 2\alpha^2 \exp[-2|\alpha|^2(1 - \cos 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))] \\
 &\times e^{-\sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_K t}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} \exp\left[-2 \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \left\{ \sinh^2 r_K (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_K t}{2}) \right. \right. \\
 &+ \left. \left. \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K (\cos[2\phi_K] - 2\cos[2\phi_K - \Omega_K t] + \cos[2\phi_K - 2\Omega_K t]) \right\} \right] \\
 &\times \Re\left\{e^{i(-2\theta + 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + 2|\alpha|^2 \sin 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))}\right\} \\
 &+ 2|\alpha|^2 \left(1 - \exp[-4|\alpha|^2 \sin^2 E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]\right) \\
 &\times e^{-\sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_K t}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} \exp\left[-2 \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \left\{ \sinh^2 r_K (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_K t}{2}) \right. \right. \\
 &+ \left. \left. \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K (\cos[2\phi_K] - 2\cos[2\phi_K - \Omega_K t] + \cos[2\phi_K - 2\Omega_K t]) \right\} \right] + 1.
 \end{aligned}$$

With the help of definition of $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ and $\mathcal{D}^{\text{is}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ given by Eq. (5.62) and Eq. (5.76), Eq. (C.34) takes the form of Eq. (5.75) of the text.

C.3.5 $[\Delta\chi_{\vartheta}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]_{\text{th}}^2$

Using Eq. (C.27) and Eq. (C.30) for thermal state of GWs, Eq. (C.1) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 [\Delta\chi_{1,\vartheta}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]_{\text{th}}^2 &= 2\Re\left\{\alpha^2 e^{4iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \exp\left[-|\alpha|^2(1 - e^{4iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)})\right]\right. & (C.35) \\
 &\times e^{-\frac{1}{2}\sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} 4\kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{Kt}}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} \\
 &\times \exp\left[-4 \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{Kt}}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2\right] e^{-2i\vartheta}\left. \right\} \\
 &- 2\Re\left\{\alpha^2 e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} \exp\left[-2|\alpha|^2(1 - e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)})\right]\right. \\
 &\times e^{-\sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{Kt}}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} \\
 &\times \exp\left[-2 \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{Kt}}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2\right] e^{-2i\vartheta}\left. \right\} \\
 &+ 2|\alpha|^2 - 2|\alpha|^2 \exp\left[-|\alpha|^2(2 - 2\cos 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))\right] \\
 &\times e^{-\sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{Kt}}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2} \\
 &\times \exp\left[-2 \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 \bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) (4\sin^2 \frac{\Omega_{Kt}}{2}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2\right] + 1.
 \end{aligned}$$

With the help of definition of $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ and $\mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ given by Eq. (5.62) and Eq. (5.79), Eq. (C.35) takes the form of Eq. (5.78) of the text.

Appendix D

Two-point degree of coherence of the EM field $g^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, \tau_1; \mathbf{x}_2, \tau_2)$ in the presence of quantum GWs

In this section, we derive a general expression of the two-point degree of coherence given by Eq. (6.7), i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
 g^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, \tau_1; \mathbf{x}_2, \tau_2) &\equiv \frac{\langle \hat{a}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_1) \hat{a}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_2) \rangle}{\langle \hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a} \rangle} e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2)} \\
 &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathcal{R}^{3+}} \langle \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}^\dagger(-\kappa\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_1)) \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_2)) \rangle \\
 &\times \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}^\dagger(-\kappa\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_1)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_1)) \rangle e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}(\tau_1 - \tau_2)},
 \end{aligned} \tag{D.1}$$

where we have replaced $\hat{a}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_i)$ from Eq. (5.49), and the expectation value is taken over $\hat{\rho} = \hat{\rho}_{\text{gw}} \otimes \hat{\rho}_{\text{em}}$. For the sake of abbreviation, we take $1 \equiv (\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_1)$ and $2 \equiv (\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau_2)$ in the following.

D.1 $g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(1; 2)$

When GWs are in vacuum state, Eq. (D.1) is determined by

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(1; 2) &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathcal{R}^{3+}} \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}^\dagger(-\kappa\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1)) \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)) | 0_{\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\
 &\times \langle 0_{-\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}^\dagger(-\kappa\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)) | 0_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}(\tau_1 - \tau_2)}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{D.2}$$

With the help of Eq. (C.10), one has

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_{vac}^{(1)}(1; 2) &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}} | e^{-i\kappa^2 \mathfrak{I}(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1)\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}^\dagger(\kappa[\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)]) | 0_{\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\
 &\times \langle 0_{-\mathbf{K}} | e^{-i\kappa^2 \mathfrak{I}(\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1)\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\kappa[\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)]) | 0_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i\omega_k(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \\
 &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} e^{-i\kappa^2 \mathfrak{I}(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1)\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2) + \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1)\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} \\
 &\times \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2}\kappa^2 |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)|^2\right] \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2}\kappa^2 |\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)|^2\right] e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i\omega_k(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \\
 &= e^{-i\sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 \mathfrak{I}(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1)\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} \\
 &\times \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)|^2\right] e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i\omega_k(\tau_1 - \tau_2)}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{D.3}$$

With the help of definitions Eqs. (6.10, 6.11) for $C^{vac}(1; 2)$ and $\mathcal{D}^{vac}(1; 2)$, Eq. (D.3) takes the form of Eq. (6.9). i.e.,

$$g_{vac}^{(1)}(1; 2) = e^{-\mathcal{D}^{vac}(1; 2)} e^{-iC^{vac}(1; 2)} e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i\omega_k(\tau_1 - \tau_2)}. \tag{D.4}$$

D.2 $g_{coh}^{(1)}(1; 2)$

When GWs are in coherent state, Eq. (D.1) is determined by

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_{coh}^{(1)}(1; 2) &= \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \langle \beta_{\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}^\dagger(-\kappa\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1)) \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)) | \beta_{\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\
 &\times \langle \beta_{-\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}^\dagger(-\kappa\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)) | \beta_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i\omega_k(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \\
 &= e^{-i\sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \kappa^2 \mathfrak{I}(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1)\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i\omega_k(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \\
 &\times \langle \beta_{\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\kappa[\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)]) | \beta_{\mathbf{K}} \rangle \langle \beta_{-\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\kappa[\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)]) | \beta_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle.
 \end{aligned} \tag{D.5}$$

With the help of Eq. (C.10) we have $\hat{D}^\dagger(\beta)\hat{D}(\alpha)\hat{D}(\beta) = e^{2i\mathfrak{I}(\alpha\beta^*)}\hat{D}(\alpha)$, hence

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_{coh}^{(1)}(1; 2) &= e^{-iC^{vac}(1; 2)} \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} e^{2i\mathfrak{I}(\kappa\beta_{\mathbf{K}}^*[\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)])} \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\kappa[\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)]) | 0_{\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\
 &\times e^{2i\mathfrak{I}(\kappa\beta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*[\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)])} \langle 0_{-\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\kappa[\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)]) | 0_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i\omega_k(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \\
 &= e^{-iC^{vac}(1; 2)} e^{2i\sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \mathfrak{I}(\kappa\beta_{\mathbf{K}}^*[\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)])} e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i\omega_k(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \\
 &\times \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa^2 |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)|^2\right].
 \end{aligned} \tag{D.6}$$

With the help of definitions of $\mathcal{D}^{vac}(1; 2)$ and $C^{coh}(1; 2)$ given by Eqs. (6.11, 6.19), Eq. (D.6) recasts to Eq. (6.18) of the text, i.e.,

$$g_{coh}^{(1)}(1; 2) = g_{vac}^{(1)}(1; 2) e^{iC^{coh}(1; 2)}. \tag{D.7}$$

D.3 $g_{sq}^{(1)}(1; 2)$

When GWs are in squeezed state, Eq. (D.1) is determined by

$$g_{sq}^{(1)}(1; 2) = e^{-i \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \kappa^2 \mathfrak{G}(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} e^{-i \mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i \omega_{\mathbf{k}}(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \quad (\text{D.8})$$

$$\times \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \langle \zeta_{\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\kappa[\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)]) | \zeta_{\mathbf{K}} \rangle \langle \zeta_{-\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\kappa[\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)]) | \zeta_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle.$$

With the help of Eq. (C.14 - C.16), one has

$$\langle \zeta | \hat{D}(\beta) | \zeta \rangle = \langle 0 | \hat{S}^\dagger \hat{D}(\beta) \hat{S} | 0 \rangle = \langle 0 | \hat{D}(\beta') | 0 \rangle = \exp[-\frac{1}{2} |\beta'|^2], \quad (\text{D.9})$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \beta &\equiv \kappa(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)), \\ \beta' &\equiv \beta \cosh r + \beta^* e^{2i\phi_{\zeta}} \sinh r \\ &= \kappa([\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)] \cosh r + [\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2)] e^{2i\phi_{\zeta}} \sinh r). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.10})$$

Combining Eqs. (D.9 , D.10), one has

$$\begin{aligned} \exp[-\frac{1}{2} |\beta'|^2] &= \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2} \kappa^2 [|\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)| \cosh r_K + |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2)| e^{2i\phi_{\zeta}} \sinh r_K]^2\right] \\ &= \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2} \kappa^2 (1 + \sinh^2 r_K) |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)|^2 + \sinh^2 r_K |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2)|^2\right. \\ &\quad \left.+ 2 \Re[\sinh r_K \cosh r_K e^{2i\phi_{\zeta}} (\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)) (\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))] \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.11})$$

With the help of Eqs. (D.9 - D.11), Eq. (D.8) recasts to the following form

$$g_{sq}^{(1)}(1; 2) = e^{-i \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \kappa^2 \mathfrak{G}(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} e^{-i \mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i \omega_{\mathbf{k}}(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \quad (\text{D.12})$$

$$\times \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa^2 \left\{ (1 + 2 \sinh^2 r_K) |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)|^2 \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. + \sinh^2 r_K \Re[e^{2i\phi_{\zeta}} (\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2))^2] \right\} \right]$$

$$= g_{vac}^{(1)}(1; 2) e^{-\mathcal{D}^{sq}(1; 2)},$$

where in the last line we have used the definition of $\mathcal{D}^{sq}(1; 2)$ given by Eq. (6.28), and Eq. (6.27) of the text is obtained.

D.4 $g_{ts}^{(1)}(1; 2)$

When GWs are in two-mode squeezed state, Eq. (D.1) is determined by

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_{ts}^{(1)}(1; 2) &= e^{-i\sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \kappa^2 \mathfrak{J}(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1)\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \\
 &\times \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}} | \hat{R}^{\dagger} \hat{S}^{\dagger} \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\kappa[\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)]) \hat{S} \hat{R} \\
 &\times \hat{R}^{\dagger} \hat{S}^{\dagger} \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\kappa[\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)]) \hat{S} \hat{R} | 0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle.
 \end{aligned} \tag{D.13}$$

With the help of Eq. (C.20 , C.21), one has

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_{ts}^{(1)}(1; 2) &= e^{-i\sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \kappa^2 \mathfrak{J}(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1)\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \\
 &\times \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(\kappa u_{\mathbf{K}}^*[\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)]) \otimes \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa v_{\mathbf{K}}[\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2)]) \\
 &\times \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}(\kappa u_{\mathbf{K}}^*[\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)]) \otimes \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa v_{\mathbf{K}}[\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(2)]) | 0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\
 &= e^{-i\sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \kappa^2 \mathfrak{J}(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1)\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \\
 &\times \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger}(-\kappa u_{\mathbf{K}}^*[\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)]) \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa v_{\mathbf{K}}[\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(2)]) | 0_{\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\
 &\times \langle 0_{-\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger}(\kappa v_{\mathbf{K}}[\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2)]) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}(\kappa u_{\mathbf{K}}^*[\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)]) | 0_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\
 &= e^{-i\sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \kappa^2 \mathfrak{J}(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1)\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \\
 &\times \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \langle -\kappa u_{\mathbf{K}}^*[\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)] | -\kappa v_{\mathbf{K}}[\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(2)] \rangle \\
 &\times \langle \kappa v_{\mathbf{K}}[\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2)] | \kappa u_{\mathbf{K}}^*[\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)] \rangle \\
 &= e^{-i\sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \kappa^2 \mathfrak{J}(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1)\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \\
 &\times \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \exp[-\frac{1}{2}\kappa^2 |u_{\mathbf{K}}|^2 |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)|^2] \exp[-\frac{1}{2}\kappa^2 |v_{\mathbf{K}}|^2 |\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(2)|^2] \\
 &\times \exp[\kappa^2 u_{\mathbf{K}} v_{\mathbf{K}} (\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2)) (\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(2))] \\
 &\times \exp[-\frac{1}{2}\kappa^2 |v_{\mathbf{K}}|^2 |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2)|^2] \exp[-\frac{1}{2}\kappa^2 |u_{\mathbf{K}}|^2 |\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)|^2] \\
 &\times \exp[\kappa^2 u_{\mathbf{K}}^* v_{\mathbf{K}}^* (\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)) (\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2))] \\
 &= e^{-i\sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \kappa^2 \mathfrak{J}(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1)\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \\
 &\times \exp[-\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa^2 (|u_{\mathbf{K}}|^2 + |v_{\mathbf{K}}|^2) |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)|^2] \\
 &\times \exp[\sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa^2 \mathfrak{R}\{u_{\mathbf{K}} v_{\mathbf{K}} (\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(1) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(2))\}].
 \end{aligned} \tag{D.14}$$

With the help of definition of u_K and v_K in terms of the squeezing parameters, given by Eq. (2.58), and using the condition $|u_K|^2 - |v_K|^2 = 1$, Eq. (D.14) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_{ts}^{(1)}(1; 2) &= e^{-i \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} \kappa^2 \mathfrak{I}(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} e^{-i \mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i \omega_k (\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \\
 &\times \exp \left[- \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa^2 \{ (1 + 2|v_K|^2) \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(1; 2) - \mathcal{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{ts-corr}}(1; 2) \} \right] \\
 &= g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(1; 2) e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(1; 2)}, \tag{D.15}
 \end{aligned}$$

where in the last line, we have used the definition of \mathcal{D}^{ts} given by Eq. (6.39). Thus, Eq. (6.38) of the text is derived.

D.5 $g_{th}^{(1)}(1; 2)$

When GWs are in thermal state, Eq. (D.1) is determined by

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_{th}^{(1)}(1; 2) &= e^{-i \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} \kappa^2 \mathfrak{I}(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} e^{-i \mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i \omega_k (\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \tag{D.16} \\
 &\times \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \langle \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(\kappa[\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)]) \rangle_{\hat{\rho}_{\text{th}, \mathbf{K}, \gamma}} \langle \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}(\kappa[\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)]) \rangle_{\hat{\rho}_{\text{th}, -\mathbf{K}, \gamma}} \\
 &= e^{-i \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} \kappa^2 \mathfrak{I}(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} e^{-i \mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i \omega_k (\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \exp \left[- \kappa^2 |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)|^2 (\bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) + \frac{1}{2}) \right] \\
 &\times \exp \left[- \kappa^2 |\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)|^2 (\bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) + \frac{1}{2}) \right] \\
 &= e^{-i \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} \kappa^2 \mathfrak{I}(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} e^{-i \mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) - i \omega_k (\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \exp \left[- \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa^2 (\bar{n}_{\text{th}}(K) + \frac{1}{2}) \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\text{vac}}(1; 2) \right] \\
 &= g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(1; 2) e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(1; 2)}.
 \end{aligned}$$

In the last line, we used definition of $\mathcal{D}^{\text{th}}(1; 2)$ given by Eq. (6.49).

Appendix E

Preliminaries for evaluation of spatial degree of coherence $g^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t; \mathbf{x}_2, t)$

E.1 Dynamics of spherical EM waves in the presence of GWs

In this section, we investigate the evolution of spherical EM waves propagating through GWs background. We follow the same procedure introduced for plane waves in Chapter 4 and Chapter 5, based on the optical medium analogy. We may start by a single point source, located at \mathbf{x}_s with respect some coordinate system, which emits spherical EM waves (see Fig. 7.6). In the adiabatic approximation $\Omega_k \ll \omega_k$ the vector potential fulfills Eq. (4.35). In order to solve Eq. (4.35) and find the local field $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ at a typical point \mathbf{x}_P , we proceed by considering an spherical wave expansion of the vector potential as follows

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) = \sum_k \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2}} (\alpha_k \nu_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) + \alpha_k^* \nu_k^*(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \mathbf{f}_k^*(\mathbf{x}_P, t)). \quad (\text{E.1})$$

Here, k denotes different modes of the EM field possessing different wave numbers. Although the quantum pre-factor \hbar is included intentionally, at the classical level one can substitute $\alpha_k \sqrt{\hbar} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_k$. The time-harmonic behavior of $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ is included in the temporal mode function $\nu_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ which recasts to $e^{\pm i\omega_k t}$ in the vacuum case, i.e., when there is no gravitational background. However, we let this function be \mathbf{x}_P -dependent as well, since the gravitational background is \mathbf{x}_P -dependent through $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$. That means, $\nu_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ is a slowly varying function of \mathbf{x}_P . The spatial mode function $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ contains the spatial factor which recasts to the spherical waves in the absence of GWs, and again we let it to have a slowly varying envelope as well since the gravitational medium is time-dependent. Thus we may consider

$$\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \rightarrow \mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \equiv \hat{\mathbf{u}}_k(\theta, \phi) f(t) \left(\frac{e^{ikr}}{r} \right), \quad (\text{E.2})$$

with $f(t)$ being a slowly varying function of time and $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_k(\theta, \phi)$ a unit vector denoting the polarization of the electric field, which is orthogonal to \mathbf{x} at each point P (see Fig. 7.6). Note that r is the distance between point P and the source element located at \mathbf{x} , as depicted in Fig. 7.6. Here, the position vector $\mathbf{x} = (r, \theta, \phi)$ shows the location at which one monitors the EM field, in spherical coordinates. In the following, we take a constant unit vector $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_k$ and neglect its variation in the vicinity of the observation point \mathbf{x}_P (this assumption holds true for observation points much further than the source). The slowly varying envelope approximation (SVEA) implies that [134]

$$\left| \frac{\dot{\mathbf{f}}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)} \right| \ll \left| \frac{\dot{\mathbf{f}}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)} \right| \ll \omega_k \quad , \quad \left| \frac{\nabla^2 v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)}{\nabla v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)} \right| \ll \left| \frac{\nabla v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)}{v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)} \right| \ll k. \quad (\text{E.3})$$

Note that since $\mathbf{x}_P = \mathbf{x}_s + \mathbf{x}$, derivatives with respect to \mathbf{x}_P and \mathbf{x} can be interchanged. Eq. (E.3) implies that temporal change of the spatial mode function due to the existence of GWs happens in a time scale much larger than the characteristic oscillatory behavior of the EM wave. Similarly, spatial change of the temporal mode functions induced by GW medium happens at scales much larger than the typical wavelength of the EM field. Inserting $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ into the field expansion Eq. (E.1) and using the wave equation Eq. (4.35), one can show that

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \times (\bar{\mu}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)) &= -k^2 f(t) \left(\frac{e^{ikr}}{r} \right) \hat{\mathbf{r}} \times [\bar{\mu}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) (\hat{\mathbf{u}}_k \times \hat{\mathbf{r}})] + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{r^2}\right) \\ &= -\left(\frac{\ddot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)}{v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)} \right) \bar{\epsilon}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_k f(t) \left(\frac{e^{ikr}}{r} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{E.4})$$

Here, $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$ shows the unit vector from the source to the point P . In derivation of Eq. (E.4), we have neglected spatial derivative of $\bar{\mu}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ and $v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$, as well as time derivative of $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ under the adiabatic approximation $K \ll k$ and $\Omega_K \ll \omega_k$, implied by Eq. (E.3). Moreover, one can neglect higher order terms $\propto \mathcal{O}(\frac{1}{r^2})$ that vanish fast at large distances. Thus, Eq. (E.4) contains the second-order spatial derivative of $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ on the left-hand side, and second-order time derivative of $v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ on the right-hand side. To solve Eq. (E.4), we proceed by assuming the following time behavior for the temporal mode functions,

$$\ddot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \equiv -\omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t). \quad (\text{E.5})$$

Firstly, note that the \mathbf{x}_P -dependence of temporal mode function $v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ must satisfy the SVEA condition Eq. (E.3). In the following, we shall see that this is indeed the case. On the other hand, in the proposed form Eq. (E.5) a friction term is absent in the time evolution of the EM field, while its frequency may be affected by the underlying GWs background. This assumption intuitively supports the fact that the GW background does not produce or annihilate photons, under the adiabatic approximation $\Omega_K \ll \omega_k$. This means that the GW medium is not dispersive and absorptive in the optical range since the EM-GWs interaction is off-resonant. In the corresponding quantum field theory, this

assumption implies that EM-GWs interaction does not create or annihilate photons, and the mean number of photons in the EM field is conserved. This point was first noted by Kip. Thorne [135] in the case of a slowly varying GW background.

Now, inserting Eq. (E.5) into Eq. (E.4) yields

$$\left[\omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \varepsilon_{il}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) + k^2 \varepsilon_{ijr} \varepsilon_{mnl} \hat{r}_j \hat{r}_n \mu_{rm}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \right] \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,l} = 0, \quad (\text{E.6})$$

with $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,l}$ being the l -th component of the polarization vector $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_k$ and ε_{ijr} representing the Levi-Civita symbol. Now, if we define a new quantity

$$n_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \equiv \frac{\omega_k}{\omega_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)}, \quad (\text{E.7})$$

where $\omega_k = ck$ is the EM frequency in the vacuum (in the absence of GWs), combining Eq. (E.6) and Eq. (E.7) yields

$$\left[\varepsilon_{il}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) + \frac{n_k^2(\mathbf{x}_P, t)}{c^2} \varepsilon_{ijr} \varepsilon_{mnl} \hat{r}_j \hat{r}_n \mu_{rm}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \right] \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,l} = 0. \quad (\text{E.8})$$

Eq. (E.8) is also obtained in [136] for plane waves, where it turns out that the quantity $n_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ is nothing but the refractive index of the GWs medium. The existence of eigen-solutions for $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_k$ leads to the *generalized Fresnel equation*

$$n_k^2(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j - \det(\bar{\bar{\varepsilon}}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)) = 0. \quad (\text{E.9})$$

Eq. (E.9) identifies the refractive index of the effective medium according to

$$n_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) = \sqrt{\frac{\det(\bar{\bar{\varepsilon}}(\mathbf{x}_P, t))}{\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j}}, \quad (\text{E.10})$$

which is consistent with Eq. (14) of [136]. With the help of Eq. (4.27), one can check that $\det(\bar{\bar{\varepsilon}}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)) = 1$ in the linear order $\mathcal{O}(h)$, and Eq. (E.10) simplifies to

$$\begin{aligned} n_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) &= (\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j)^{-1/2} = (\delta_{ij} \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j)^{-1/2} \\ &= 1 + \frac{1}{2} h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{E.11})$$

Consequently, the EM frequency in the presence of GW background is determined by Eq. (E.7), namely

$$\omega_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) = \omega_k \left(\delta_{ij} - \frac{1}{2} h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \right) \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j, \quad (\text{E.12})$$

and the temporal mode functions $\nu_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ are determined by Eq. (E.5). Having identified the expression of $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ given by Eq. (E.1), in the following we construct the Hamiltonian of the EM-GWs system. Before doing so, it is useful to specify the orthogonality relation

of the spatial mode functions $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$.

E.1.1 Orthogonality relation of the spherical mode functions $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$

With the help of the optical medium analogy, it is convenient to define the orthogonality equation of the spatial mode functions $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ in the presence of anisotropic media according to

$$\langle \mathbf{f}_k | \mathbf{f}_{k'} \rangle \equiv \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) f_{k,i}^*(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{k',j}(\mathbf{x}, t) \equiv \delta_{k,k'}. \quad (\text{E.13})$$

(see [197] and references therein). Here, $f_{k,i}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ denote the i -th component of the spatial mode function $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$. Note that since the medium is spacetime dependent, in general, the integration in Eq. (E.13) may not produce the Kronecker delta function $\delta_{k,k'}$. However, as we shall see, the orthonormality relation Eq. (E.13) holds in the adiabatic limit $K \ll k$. Firstly note that our EM field of interest could have a frequency range of radio to optical waves, which span from \sim GHz to 10^{15} Hz so that $10 \leq k \leq 10^7 \text{ m}^{-1}$. On the other hand, PGWs span a wide range of frequency $10^{-18} \leq \Omega_K \leq 10^{10}$ Hz, so that $10^{-26} \leq K \leq 10^2 \text{ m}^{-1}$. Thus, the adiabatic condition $K \ll k$ is almost fulfilled for PGWs and radio waves. Moreover, the high-frequency part of PGWs has a negligible graviton content (see Fig. 3.3), and their effect on the EM observables is automatically vanishing due to small coupling strength. Inserting the expression of $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) = f(t) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_k(\frac{e^{ikr}}{r})$ into Eq. (E.13), and with the use of Eq. (4.27), one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathbf{f}_k | \mathbf{f}_{k'} \rangle &= \varepsilon_0 f^2(t) \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j} \left(\frac{e^{-i(k-k')r}}{r^2} \right) \\ &= \varepsilon_0 f^2(t) \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} \left(\frac{e^{-i(k-k')r}}{r^2} \right) \delta_{ij} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j} \\ &\quad - \varepsilon_0 f^2(t) C \sum_{\lambda=+, \times} \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{K}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \left\{ \frac{h_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda e^{-i(\Omega t - \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}_s)}}{\sqrt{2\Omega_K}} \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} (e_{ij}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j}) \frac{e^{-i(k-k'-K \cos \gamma)r}}{r^2} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\lambda*} e^{i(\Omega t - \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}_s)}}{\sqrt{2\Omega_K}} \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} (e_{ij}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j}) \frac{e^{-i(k-k'+K \cos \gamma)r}}{r^2} \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{E.14})$$

Here, we replaced $\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x} = Kr \cos \gamma$, where γ denotes the angle between \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{x} . The radial integration can be performed using

$$\lim_{R \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^R dr r^2 \left(\frac{e^{-i(k-k')r}}{r^2} \right) = R \delta_{k-k',0}. \quad (\text{E.15})$$

Thus, Eq. (E.14) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \mathbf{f}_k | \mathbf{f}_{k'} \rangle &= \varepsilon_0 f^2(t) \int d^2\Omega_{\hat{r}} (\delta_{ij} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j}) R \delta_{k-k',0} \\
&- \varepsilon_0 f^2(t) C \sum_{\lambda=+,\times} \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{K}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \left\{ \frac{h_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda e^{-i(\Omega t - \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}_s)}}{\sqrt{2\Omega_K}} \int d^2\Omega_{\hat{r}} (e_{ij}^\lambda[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j}) R \delta_{k-k',K \cos \gamma} \right. \\
&+ \left. \frac{h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\lambda*} e^{i(\Omega t - \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}_s)}}{\sqrt{2\Omega_K}} \int d^2\Omega_{\hat{r}} (e_{ij}^\lambda[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j}) R \delta_{k-k',-K \cos \gamma} \right\}.
\end{aligned} \tag{E.16}$$

Here, the symbol $d^2\Omega_{\hat{r}} = d(\cos \theta) d\phi$ stands for the spatial angular element. Thus, Eq. (E.16) explicitly shows the scattering of mode k to k' of the EM field due to the presence of GWs with momentum K . Thus, the momentum conservation implies either possibilities $k' = k - K \cos \gamma$ or $k' = k + K \cos \gamma$. Since $K \ll k$, each mode of the EM field scatters to itself, and we may set

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta_{k-k',K \cos \gamma} &\simeq \delta_{k-k'}, \\
\delta_{k-k',-K \cos \gamma} &\simeq \delta_{k-k'}.
\end{aligned} \tag{E.17}$$

Indeed, these conditions are fulfilled by almost all frequency parts of the PGWs spectrum, for which $K \ll k, k'$. For all GWs with $K \ll k$, the incoming EM field of mode k scatters to itself so that $k \simeq k'$. So, we may proceed by retaining the contribution of all PGWs modes in the integral Eq. (E.16), such that

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \mathbf{f}_k | \mathbf{f}_{k'} \rangle &= \varepsilon_0 f^2(t) R \delta_{k,k'} \int d^2\Omega_{\hat{r}} (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_s, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j} \\
&\equiv \varepsilon_0 f^2(t) R \delta_{k,k'} m(t),
\end{aligned} \tag{E.18}$$

where the slowly varying function $m(t)$ is defined by

$$m(t) \equiv \int d^2\Omega_{\hat{r}} (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_s, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,j}. \tag{E.19}$$

Comparing Eq. (E.18) with definition Eq. (E.13), the normalization factor $f(t)$ outcomes

$$f^2(t) = \frac{1}{R m(t) \varepsilon_0}, \tag{E.20}$$

and spatial mode functions are determined by

$$\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{u}}_k(\theta, \phi)}{\sqrt{R m(t) \varepsilon_0}} \left(\frac{e^{ikr}}{r} \right). \tag{E.21}$$

E.1.2 Derivation of the interaction Hamiltonian $\hat{H}_{\text{em-gw}}$ in the adiabatic limit

As we have discussed in Sec. 5.1.2, the following Lagrangian density

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{L}_{\text{em-gw}}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) &= \mathcal{L}_{\text{em}}^{(0)} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)E^i(\mathbf{x}_P, t)E^j(\mathbf{x}_P, t) - \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)B^i(\mathbf{x}_P, t)B^j(\mathbf{x}_P, t)).\end{aligned}\quad (\text{E.22})$$

correctly describes the dynamics of the EM field in the presence of GWs, where the permittivity and permeability tensors are identified by Eq. (4.27). Following the standard second quantization procedure, one promotes the vector potential $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ to the Hermitian quantum field operator $\hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$. Thus, the expansion coefficients (α_k, α_k^*) in the field expansion Eq. (E.1) become bosonic operators $(\hat{a}_k, \hat{a}_k^\dagger)$ satisfying the bosonic commutation relation $[\hat{a}_k, \hat{a}_k^\dagger] = \delta_{k,k'}$. The canonical conjugate momentum of the canonical variable $\hat{A}_i(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ is defined by

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\Pi}_i(\mathbf{x}_P, t) &\equiv \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_{\text{em-gw}}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)}{\partial \dot{\hat{A}}_i(\mathbf{x}_P, t)} = \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)\dot{\hat{A}}_j(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \\ &= \sum_k \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2}} \left(\hat{a}_k \dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) f_{k,j}(\mathbf{x}, t) + \hat{a}_k^\dagger \dot{v}_k^*(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) f_{k,j}^*(\mathbf{x}, t) \right).\end{aligned}\quad (\text{E.23})$$

Note that $v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ and $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ satisfy the SVEA condition Eq. (E.3). The Hamiltonian can be established by performing the Legendre transform on the Lagrangian $\mathcal{L}_{\text{em-gw}}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$. The resulting Hamiltonian is

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{H}_{\text{em-gw}} &= \frac{1}{2} \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} [\varepsilon_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \hat{\Pi}_i(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \hat{\Pi}_j(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \\ &\quad + \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) (\nabla \times \hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}_P, t))_i (\nabla \times \hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}_P, t))_j],\end{aligned}\quad (\text{E.24})$$

where the identity $\varepsilon_{ik}\varepsilon_{kl}^{-1} = \delta_{il}$ is used. Here, spatial integration $\int_V d^3 \mathbf{x}$ is performed over the volume V wherein the EM-GWs interaction takes place. Plugging the expressions of $\hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ and $\hat{\Pi}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ from Eqs. (E.1, E.23) into the Hamiltonian Eq. (E.24) yields

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{H}_{\text{em-gw}} &= \frac{1}{2} \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} [\varepsilon_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \hat{\Pi}_i(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \hat{\Pi}_j(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \\ &\quad + \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) (\nabla \times \hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}_P, t))_i (\nabla \times \hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}_P, t))_j] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\hbar}{2} \sum_{k,k'} \left\{ \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) (\hat{a}_k \dot{v}_k f_{k,i} + \hat{a}_k^\dagger \dot{v}_k^* f_{k,i}^*) (\hat{a}_{k'} \dot{v}_{k'} f_{k',j} + \hat{a}_{k'}^\dagger \dot{v}_{k'}^* f_{k',j}^*) \right. \\ &\quad + \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) (\hat{a}_k v_k (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k)_i + \hat{a}_k^\dagger v_k^* (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k^*)_i) \\ &\quad \times (\hat{a}_{k'} v_{k'} (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'})_j + \hat{a}_{k'}^\dagger v_{k'}^* (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'}^*)_j) \left. \right\}.\end{aligned}\quad (\text{E.25})$$

Re-arranging the terms, there would be four terms in the Hamiltonian, as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{H}_{em-gw}(t) &= \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\hbar}{2} \sum_{k,k'} & (E.26) \\
&\times \left\{ \hat{a}_k \hat{a}_{k'} \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} (\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) f_{k,i} f_{k',j} \dot{v}_k \dot{v}_{k'} + \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_k v_{k'} (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k)_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'})_j) \right. \\
&+ \hat{a}_k \hat{a}_{k'}^\dagger \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} (\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) f_{k,i} f_{k',j}^* \dot{v}_k \dot{v}_{k'}^* + \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_k v_{k'}^* (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k)_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'}^*)_j) \\
&+ \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_{k'} \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} (\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) f_{k,i}^* f_{k',j} \dot{v}_k^* \dot{v}_{k'} + \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_k^* v_{k'} (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k^*)_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'})_j) \\
&\left. + \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_{k'}^\dagger \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} (\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) f_{k,i}^* f_{k',j}^* \dot{v}_k^* \dot{v}_{k'}^* + \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_k^* v_{k'}^* (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k^*)_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'}^*)_j) \right\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Note that, the spherical EM wave emitted from a point source located on the surface of a star, propagates into a sphere with radius R until it is received on the Earth, and R is the distance of the source to the Earth. Then the interaction with GWs takes place within the volume encompassed in the half-sphere of radius R . The resulting Hamiltonian thus depends on the interaction time t as well as on the distance R , which is indeed the characteristic length of the probe. In the following, we compute each term in Eq. (E.26) using the adiabatic approximation $K \ll k$ and derive the explicit form of the interaction Hamiltonian.

With the help of definition Eq. (4.27) for $\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$, the first term in Eq. (E.26) contains a terms like

$$\begin{aligned}
&\int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) f_{k,i}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{k',j}(\mathbf{x}, t) \dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \dot{v}_{k'}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) & (E.27) \\
&= \frac{1}{R m(t)} \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} (\delta_{ij} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j}) \left(\frac{e^{i(k+k')r}}{r^2} \right) \dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \dot{v}_{k'}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \\
&- \frac{1}{R m(t)} \sum_{\lambda=+, \times} \int \frac{d^3 \mathbf{K}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \left\{ \frac{h_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda e^{-i(\Omega t - \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}_s)}}{\sqrt{2\Omega_K}} \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} \left(\frac{e^{i(k+k'+K \cos \gamma)r}}{r^2} \right) \right. \\
&\left. + \frac{h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\lambda*} e^{i(\Omega t - \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}_s)}}{\sqrt{2\Omega_K}} \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} \left(\frac{e^{i(k+k'-K \cos \gamma)r}}{r^2} \right) \right\} (e_{ij}^\lambda[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j}) \dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \dot{v}_{k'}(\mathbf{x}_P, t).
\end{aligned}$$

In the second line, we used the expression of $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$ given by Eq. (E.21). Note that the function $e^{i(k+k' \pm K \cos \gamma)r}$ is highly oscillating for large values of its argument, hence the radial integral averages to zero unless $(k + k' \pm K \cos \gamma)r \rightarrow 0$, so that $e^{i(k+k' \pm K \cos \gamma)r} \rightarrow 1$. Moreover, taking into account that $K \ll k$, the result of the integral can be approximately written as

$$\begin{aligned}
&\int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) f_{k,i}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{k',j}(\mathbf{x}, t) \dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \dot{v}_{k'}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) & (E.28) \\
&= \frac{\delta_{k+k',0}}{R m(t)} \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_s, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j} \left(\frac{\dot{v}_k^2(\mathbf{x}_P, t)}{r^2} \right).
\end{aligned}$$

Similarly, one may show that

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) f_{k,i}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{k',j}^*(\mathbf{x}, t) \dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \dot{v}_{k'}^*(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \\
&= \frac{\delta_{k-k',0}}{R m(t)} \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_S, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j} \left(\frac{|\dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)|^2}{r^2} \right), \\
& \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) f_{k,i}^*(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{k',j}(\mathbf{x}, t) \dot{v}_k^*(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \dot{v}_{k'}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \\
&= \frac{\delta_{k-k',0}}{R m(t)} \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_S, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j} \left(\frac{|\dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)|^2}{r^2} \right), \\
& \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) f_{k,i}^*(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{k',j}^*(\mathbf{x}, t) \dot{v}_k^*(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \dot{v}_{k'}^*(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \\
&= \frac{\delta_{k+k',0}}{R m(t)} \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_S, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j} \left(\frac{\dot{v}_k^{*2}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)}{r^2} \right).
\end{aligned} \tag{E.29}$$

Next, we compute the second term in the first line of Eq. (E.26), which is of the form

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t))_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'}(\mathbf{x}, t))_j v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_{k'}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \\
&= \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \epsilon_{ilm} (\partial_l f_{k,m}(\mathbf{x}, t)) (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'})_j v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_{k'}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \\
&= \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} \epsilon_{ilm} \partial_l [\mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) f_{k,m}(\mathbf{x}, t) (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'})_j v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_{k'}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)] \\
&\quad - \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} \epsilon_{ilm} f_{k,m}(\mathbf{x}, t) \partial_l [\mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'})_j v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_{k'}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)] \\
&= \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} \epsilon_{mli} \partial_l [\mu^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'}(\mathbf{x}, t)]_i v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_{k'}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) f_{k,m}(\mathbf{x}, t) \\
&= \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} (\nabla \times [\mu^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'}(\mathbf{x}, t)])_m f_{k,m}(\mathbf{x}, t) v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_{k'}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \\
&= \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} \omega_{k'}^2(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \varepsilon_{il}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) f_{k',i}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_{k,m}(\mathbf{x}, t) v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_{k'}(\mathbf{x}_P, t).
\end{aligned} \tag{E.30}$$

Here, ϵ_{ilm} stands for the Levi-Civita symbol. Note that, a surface integral vanishes assuming the EM field vanishes at the infinity. Moreover, we have omitted derivatives of the slowly varying functions, such as $\partial_l \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ and $\partial_l v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$, which are proportional to K and are much smaller than k . In the last line of Eq. (E.30), we used the wave equation Eq. (E.4). With the help of Eq. (E.21) for the spatial mode functions $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t)$, Eq. (E.30) can be written as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t))_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'}(\mathbf{x}, t))_j v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_{k'}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \\
&= \frac{1}{R m(t)} \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_S, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j} \left(\frac{e^{i(k+k')r}}{r^2} \right) v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_{k'}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \omega_{k'}^2(\mathbf{x}_P, t).
\end{aligned} \tag{E.31}$$

Again, the integral in Eq. (E.31) is non-vanishing whenever $e^{i(k+k')r} \rightarrow 1$, for which the

integral can be approximated by

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t))_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'}(\mathbf{x}, t))_j v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_{k'}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \quad (\text{E.32}) \\ &= \frac{\delta_{k+k'}}{Rm(t)} \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_s, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j} (\omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \frac{v_k^2(\mathbf{x}_P, t)}{r^2}). \end{aligned}$$

Similar procedure can be done for other terms in Eq. (E.26). The result is

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x}, t))_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'}^*(\mathbf{x}, t))_j v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_{k'}^*(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \quad (\text{E.33}) \\ &= \frac{\delta_{k-k'}}{Rm(t)} \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_s, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j} (\omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \frac{|v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)|^2}{r^2}), \\ & \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k^*(\mathbf{x}, t))_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'}(\mathbf{x}, t))_j v_k^*(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_{k'}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \\ &= \frac{\delta_{k-k'}}{Rm(t)} \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_s, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j} (\omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \frac{|v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)|^2}{r^2}), \\ & \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} \mu_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_k^*(\mathbf{x}, t))_i (\nabla \times \mathbf{f}_{k'}^*(\mathbf{x}, t))_j v_k^*(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_{k'}^*(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \\ &= \frac{\delta_{k-k'}}{Rm(t)} \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_s, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j} (\omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \frac{v_k^{*2}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)}{r^2}). \end{aligned}$$

Inserting Eqs. (E.28 , E.29) and Eqs. (E.32 , E.33) into the Hamiltonian Eq. (E.26) results in the following expression

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}_{em-gw}(t) &= \frac{\hbar}{4} \sum_{k,k'} \left\{ \hat{a}_k \hat{a}_{k'} \frac{\delta_{k+k',0}}{Rm(t)} \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_s, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j} \left(\frac{\dot{v}_k^2(\mathbf{x}_P, t) + \omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_k^2(\mathbf{x}_P, t)}{r^2} \right) \right. \\ &+ \hat{a}_k \hat{a}_{k'}^\dagger \frac{\delta_{k-k',0}}{Rm(t)} \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_s, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j} \left(\frac{|\dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)|^2 + \omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}_P, t) |v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)|^2}{r^2} \right) \\ &+ \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_{k'} \frac{\delta_{k-k',0}}{Rm(t)} \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_s, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j} \left(\frac{|\dot{v}_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)|^2 + \omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}_P, t) |v_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)|^2}{r^2} \right) \\ &+ \left. \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_{k'}^\dagger \frac{\delta_{k+k',0}}{Rm(t)} \int_V d^3\mathbf{x} (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_s, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k',j} \left(\frac{\dot{v}_k^{*2}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) + \omega_k^2(\mathbf{x}_P, t) v_k^{*2}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)}{r^2} \right) \right\}. \quad (\text{E.34}) \end{aligned}$$

Each term in the Hamiltonian Eq. (E.34) represents the scattering of photons mediated by long wavelength GWs (since $K \ll k$ is assumed). Terms proportional to $\hat{a}_k \hat{a}_{k'}$ and $\hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_{k'}^\dagger$ correspond to photon creation by the GWs field, while other terms like $\hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k$ represent the scattering of each mode to itself in the presence of GWs. The temporal mode functions $v_k(\mathbf{x}_C, t)$ are already specified by Eq. (E.5) in the adiabatic approximation $\Omega_K \ll \omega_k$. One

can easily show that the following mode functions

$$\begin{aligned}
\nu_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\omega_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)}} e^{-i \int_0^t \omega_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t') dt'} , \\
\dot{\nu}_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\omega_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)}} \frac{d}{dt} [e^{-i \int_0^t \omega_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t') dt'}] \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\omega_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)}} \left(-i \frac{d}{dt} \left[\int_0^t \omega_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t') dt' \right] \right) e^{-i \int_0^t \omega_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t') dt'} \\
&= -i \omega_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \nu_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t) .
\end{aligned} \tag{E.35}$$

satisfy Eq. (E.5). Note that this solution is valid within the adiabatic approximation $\Omega_K \ll \omega_k$. Substitution of the mode functions Eq. (E.35) into the Hamiltonian Eq. (E.34) resets the contribution of $\hat{a}_k \hat{a}_k$ and $\hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k^\dagger$ to zero, and Eq. (E.34) reduces to

$$\hat{H}_{em-gw}(t) = \hbar \sum_k \left(\hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k + \frac{1}{2} \right) \frac{\delta_{k-k',0}}{Rm(t)} \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} (\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_s, t)) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,j} \frac{\omega_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)}{r^2} . \tag{E.36}$$

Consequently, under the adiabatic condition $\Omega_K \ll \omega_k$ (and $K \ll k$), particle creation by GWs background is negligible, and the EM-GW coupling is intensity-dependent, i.e., proportional to $\hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k$. One could alternatively derive the Hamiltonian Eq. (E.36) by energy consideration. Indeed, Eq. (E.26) implies that the Hamiltonian of the system is explicitly time-dependent and, in the corresponding quantum field theory, the vacuum state of the field is not well-defined. Nevertheless, one may define *instantaneous* vacuum, by finding suitable mode functions $\nu_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ such that the energy of the system, determined by the mean value of the Hamiltonian Eq. (E.26), is minimized at each moment. The minimization procedure yields the adiabatic mode functions Eq. (E.35), and the Hamiltonian Eq. (E.36) outcomes.

In order to obtain explicit form of the interaction Hamiltonian $\hat{H}_{int}(t)$ given by Eq. (E.36), we insert from Eq. (E.12) the expression of $\omega_k(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ into $\hat{H}_{int}(t)$. For simplicity, we consider only one mode of the EM field, specified by wave number k . By neglecting the vacuum energy $\frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k$, one has

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{H}_{em-gw}(t) &= \hbar \omega_k \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k \frac{1}{Rm(t)} \int_V d^3 \mathbf{x} ([\delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_s, t)] \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,j}) (\delta_{ab} - \frac{1}{2} h_{ab}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)) \frac{\hat{r}_a \hat{r}_b}{r^2} \\
&= \hbar \omega_k \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k \frac{1}{Rm(t)} \int_V \frac{d^3 \mathbf{x}}{r^2} (1 - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_s, t) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,j} - \frac{1}{2} h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j) .
\end{aligned} \tag{E.37}$$

Note that, a, b are spatial indices and \hat{r}_a represents the a -the Cartesian component of the unit vector \hat{r} . In the second line, we used the identity $\delta_{ij} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,i} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{k,j} = 1$, and we retain terms up to $\mathcal{O}(h_{ij})$ in the linear approximation. Inserting from Eq. (E.19) for $m(t)$ and keeping terms up to $\mathcal{O}(h_{ij})$, it is easy to show that the Hamiltonian reads as follows

$$\hat{H}_{em-gw}(t) = \hbar \omega_k \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k \left(1 - \frac{1}{4\pi R} \int_V \frac{d^3 \mathbf{x}}{r^2} h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j \right) . \tag{E.38}$$

The first term in the parentheses describes free evolution of the EM field. The second term shows the EM-GWs interaction Hamiltonian, which can be written as

$$\hat{H}_{\text{int}}(R, t) = -\frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k \left(\frac{1}{2\pi R} \int_0^R dr \int d\Omega_{\hat{r}} h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j \right). \quad (\text{E.39})$$

The fully quantum version of the interaction Hamiltonian can be obtained by inserting from Eq. (5.2) the quantum field operator $\hat{h}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_P, t)$ into the Hamiltonian Eq. (E.39),

$$\hat{H}_{\text{int}}(R, t) = -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\hbar \omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}} \right) \frac{\sqrt{16\pi c^3}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \sum_{\lambda=+, \times} \int \frac{d^3 \mathbf{K}}{\sqrt{2\Omega_K}} (\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}, \lambda} e^{-i\Omega_K t} \mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R) + \text{h.c.}) \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k, \quad (\text{E.40})$$

where the function $\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}(R)$ is defined by

$$\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R) \equiv \frac{e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}_s}}{2\pi R} \int d\Omega_{\hat{r}} e^{i_{ij}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}]} \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j \int_0^R dr e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}}. \quad (\text{E.41})$$

which bears the effect of the size of the probe (the distance of the source, in our case). The Hamiltonian Eq. (E.40) describes the quantum interaction between a spherical EM field and GWs, propagated from a point source located at a distance R from the Earth. With the help of Hamiltonian the Eq. (E.40), one can proceed to solve the Heisenberg equation of motion and find the dynamics of the ladder operators $\hat{a}_k(t)$ and $\hat{a}_k^\dagger(t)$. This step is similar to what we have done in Sec. 5.2.3 for plane EM waves, and gives rise to the following expression

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{a}_k(R, t) &= \left[\prod_{\lambda, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \lambda}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R, t)) \otimes \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \lambda}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(R, t)) \right] \\ &\times e^{2iE(R, t) (\hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k + \frac{1}{2})} e^{-i\omega_k t} \hat{a}_k. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{E.42})$$

Here, we have used the half-Fourier space representation where $\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}$, which turns out to facilitate the computations concerning two-mode squeezed PGWs. Here, $\hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \lambda}$ stands for the displacement operator of GWs as defined in Eq. (5.42). The coupling strength $\kappa(K)$ and the functions $E(R, t)$ and $\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R, t)$ are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa(K) &\equiv \frac{1}{2\pi} \left(\frac{\hbar \omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}} \right) K^{-3/2}, \quad (\text{E.43}) \\ E(R, t) &\equiv \sum_{\lambda=+, \times} \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa^2(K) |\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R)|^2 (\Omega_K t - \sin(\Omega_K t)), \\ \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R, t) &\equiv (1 - e^{i\Omega_K t}) \mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\lambda*}(R). \end{aligned}$$

E.2 Derivation of the two-point correlation function $g_{ts}^{(1)}(1; 2)$

In this section, we derive Eq. (7.23). The two-mode squeezed state of PGWs $|TS\rangle$ is defined in Eq. (2.64). Thus, Eq. (7.22) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
g_{ts}^{(1)}(1; 2) &= \prod_{\lambda, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}} | \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \lambda}^{\dagger}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1)) \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \lambda}(-\kappa \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)) \\
&\quad \times \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \lambda}^{\dagger}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \lambda}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)) \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}} \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}} | 0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\
&= e^{-i \sum_{\lambda} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} \kappa^2(K) \Im(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} e^{-i \omega_{\mathbf{K}}(t_1 - t_2)} \\
&\quad \times \prod_{\lambda, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}} | \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \lambda}(\kappa(K) [\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)]) \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}} \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}} \\
&\quad \times \hat{R}_{-\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} \hat{S}_{-\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \lambda}(\kappa(K) [\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)]) \hat{S}_{-\mathbf{K}} \hat{R}_{-\mathbf{K}} | 0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle.
\end{aligned} \tag{E.44}$$

Using the multiplication property of the displacement operator \hat{D} , namely $\hat{D}(\alpha)\hat{D}(\beta) = e^{i\Im(\alpha\beta^*)}\hat{D}(\alpha + \beta)$, one has

$$\hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1)) \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)) = e^{-i\kappa^2(K) \Im(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(\kappa(K) [\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)]). \tag{E.45}$$

together with a similar expression for $-\mathbf{K}$. In order to write Eq. (E.45) in a separated form, we may use the following identities

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}) \hat{S}_{\mathbf{K}} \hat{R}_{\mathbf{K}} &= \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{\mathbf{K}} u_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H)) \otimes \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}(\kappa(K) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^* v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)), \\
\hat{R}_{-\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} \hat{S}_{-\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger} \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}) \hat{S}_{-\mathbf{K}} \hat{R}_{-\mathbf{K}} &= \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}} u_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H)) \otimes \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(\kappa(K) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^* v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)).
\end{aligned} \tag{E.46}$$

With the help of Eq. (E.46), Eq. (E.44) can be written as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
g_{ts}^{(1)}(1; 2) &= e^{-i \sum_{\lambda} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} \kappa^2(K) \Im(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} e^{-i \omega_{\mathbf{K}}(t_1 - t_2)} \\
&\quad \times \prod_{\lambda, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(\kappa(K) u_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H) [\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)]) \\
&\quad \otimes \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa(K) v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H) [\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2)]) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}(\kappa(K) u_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H) [\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)]) \\
&\quad \otimes \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa(K) v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H) [\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(2)]) | 0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\
&= e^{-i \sum_{\lambda} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} \kappa^2(K) \Im(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} e^{-i \omega_{\mathbf{K}}(t_1 - t_2)} \\
&\quad \times \prod_{\lambda, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger}(-\kappa(K) u_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H) [\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)]) \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa(K) v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H) [\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(2)]) | 0_{\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\
&\quad \times \langle 0_{-\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger}(\kappa(K) v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H) [\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2)]) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}(\kappa(K) u_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H) [\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)]) | 0_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\
&= e^{-i \sum_{\lambda} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} \kappa^2(K) \Im(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} e^{-i \omega_{\mathbf{K}}(t_1 - t_2)} \\
&\quad \times \prod_{\lambda, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \langle -\kappa(K) u_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H) [\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)] | -\kappa(K) v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H) [\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(2)] \rangle \\
&\quad \times \langle \kappa(K) v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H) [\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2)] | \kappa(K) u_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H) [\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)] \rangle.
\end{aligned} \tag{E.47}$$

Using the projection property of coherent states, $\langle \alpha | \alpha' \rangle = e^{-\frac{1}{2}|\alpha|^2 - \frac{1}{2}|\alpha'|^2 + \alpha^* \alpha'}$, Eq. (E.47) reads

$$\begin{aligned}
g_{ts}^{(1)}(1; 2) &= e^{-i \sum_{\lambda} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} \kappa^2(K) \Im(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} e^{-i \omega_{\mathbf{K}}(t_1 - t_2)} \\
&\times \prod_{\lambda, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \kappa^2(K) |u_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)|^2 |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)|^2 \right] \\
&\times \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \kappa^2(K) |v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)|^2 |\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(2)|^2 \right] \\
&\times \exp \left[\kappa^2(K) u_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H) v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H) (\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2)) (\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(2)) \right] \\
&\times \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \kappa^2(K) |v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)|^2 |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2)|^2 \right] \\
&\times \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \kappa^2(K) |u_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)|^2 |\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)|^2 \right] \\
&\times \exp \left[\kappa^2(K) u_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H) v_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\eta_H) (\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)) (\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(2)) \right] \\
&= e^{-i \sum_{\lambda} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} \kappa^2(K) \Im(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2))} e^{-i \omega_{\mathbf{K}}(t_1 - t_2)} \\
&\times \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\lambda} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa^2(K) (|u_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)|^2 + |v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)|^2) |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(2)|^2 \right] \\
&\times \exp \left[\sum_{\lambda} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa^2(K) \Re \{ u_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H) v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H) (\eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(1) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(1) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(2) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(2)) \} \right].
\end{aligned} \tag{E.48}$$

In the last equality we transformed to the continuum notation, and used the normalization property $|u_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)|^2 - |v_{\mathbf{K}}(\eta_H)|^2 = 1$ for two-mode squeezed states. If one resumes the calculations for GWs in vacuum state, namely $\hat{\rho}_{\text{vac}} = \prod_{\mathbf{K}} |0_{\mathbf{K}}\rangle \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}}|$, it can be verified that the contribution of vacuum fluctuations are already involved in the contribution of two-mode squeezed state. In this case one has

$$\begin{aligned}
g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(R_1, t; R_2, t) &= \prod_{\lambda, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t)) \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_2, t)) \\
&\times \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(R_2, t)) | 0_{\mathbf{K}}, 0_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\
&= \prod_{\lambda, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t)) \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_2, t)) | 0_{\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\
&\times \langle 0_{-\mathbf{K}} | \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}^{\dagger}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t)) \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}(-\kappa(K) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(R_2, t)) | 0_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle.
\end{aligned} \tag{E.49}$$

With the help of the property $\hat{D}^{\dagger}(\alpha) \hat{D}(\beta) = e^{-i \Im \alpha \beta^*} \hat{D}(\beta - \alpha)$ for displacement operator, Eq. (E.49) is rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned}
g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(R_1, t; R_2, t) &= \prod_{\lambda, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} \langle 0_{\mathbf{K}} | e^{-i \kappa^2 \Im(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(R_2, t))} \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}}(\kappa(K) [\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_2, t)]) | 0_{\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\
&\times \langle 0_{-\mathbf{K}} | e^{-i \kappa^2 \Im(\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(R_2, t))} \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}}(\kappa(K) [\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(R_2, t)]) | 0_{-\mathbf{K}} \rangle \\
&= \prod_{\lambda, \mathbf{K} \in \mathfrak{R}^{3+}} e^{-i \kappa^2 \Im(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(R_2, t) + \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t) \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}^*(R_2, t))} \\
&\times \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \kappa^2(K) |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_2, t)|^2 \right] \\
&\times \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \kappa^2(K) |\eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t) - \eta_{-\mathbf{K}}(R_2, t)|^2 \right].
\end{aligned} \tag{E.50}$$

Using the continuous notation, Eq. (E.50) reads

$$g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(R_1, t; R_1, t) = e^{-i \sum_\lambda \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa(K) \Im(\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t) \eta_{\mathbf{K}}^*(R_2, t))} \quad (\text{E.51})$$

$$\times \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \sum_\lambda \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3 \mathbf{K} \kappa^2(K) |\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_1, t) - \eta_{\mathbf{K}}(R_2, t)|^2 \right].$$

With the help of definitions Eq. (7.24, 7.25), we may rewrite Eq. (E.51) as follows

$$g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(R_1, t; R_2, t) = e^{-i C^{\text{vac}}(R_1, t; R_2, t)} e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(R_1, t; R_2, t)}. \quad (\text{E.52})$$

Combining Eqs. (E.48, E.50) and with the help of Eqs. (7.24, 7.25), Eq. (7.23) outcomes.

E.3 Derivation of the spatial factor $|\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_1) - \mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_2)|^2$

In order to calculate the expression $|\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_1) - \mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_2)|^2$, first note that the phase factor $e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}_s}$ in Eq. (7.10) vanishes and does not play a role, as a result of homogeneity of the PGWs background. Using the plane wave expansion in terms of the spherical Bessel functions,

$$e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}} = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} (i^\ell) (2\ell + 1) j_\ell(Kr) P_\ell(\cos \gamma), \quad (\text{E.53})$$

the definition Eq. (7.10) for $\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R)$ can be expanded as follows

$$\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R) \equiv \frac{e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}_s}}{2\pi R} \int d\Omega_{\hat{r}} e^{i\lambda} e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}} \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j \int_0^R e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}} dr \quad (\text{E.54})$$

$$= \frac{1}{2\pi(KR)} \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} (i^\ell) (2\ell + 1) \left(\int_0^{KR} j_\ell(u) du \right) \left(\int d^2 \Omega_{\hat{r}} e^{i\lambda} e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}} \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j P_\ell(\cos \gamma) \right).$$

In this way, integrations over the radial and spatial variables are decoupled. Here, $\hat{r} = (\sin \theta \cos \phi, \sin \theta \sin \phi, \cos \theta)$ and $\hat{\mathbf{K}} = (\sin \Theta_K \cos \Phi_K, \sin \Theta_K \sin \Phi_K, \cos \Theta_K)$ show the unit vectors in spherical coordinates, $d\Omega_{\hat{r}} = d(\cos \theta) d\phi$ and γ represents the angle between \hat{r} and $\hat{\mathbf{K}}$. Before proceed, it is useful to obtain an asymptotic expression for $\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R)$ in case of a small detector, for which $KR \ll 1$. The radial part of Eq. (E.54) can be written as

$$\frac{\int_0^{KR} j_\ell(u) du}{(KR)} \quad (\text{E.55})$$

In the small-detector approximation, we take $\epsilon = KR \ll 1$ and expand the spherical Bessel $j_\ell(u)$ around $u = 0$, which gives rise to

$$j_\ell(u) \simeq j_\ell(0) + j'_\ell(0)(u - \epsilon) + j''_\ell(0) \frac{(u - \epsilon)^2}{2!} + \dots \quad (\text{E.56})$$

Plugging the expansion Eq. (E.56) into Eq. (E.55) yields

$$\lim_{KR \ll 1} \left(\frac{\int_0^{KR} j_\ell(u) du}{(KR)} \right) \simeq j_\ell(0) = \begin{cases} 1 & , \ell = 0 \\ 0 & , \ell \neq 0 \end{cases} \quad (\text{E.57})$$

and Eq. (E.54) reduce to

$$\lim_{KR \ll 1} \mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda \simeq \frac{\int d\Omega_{\hat{\mathbf{r}}} e_{ij}[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j}{2\pi}. \quad (\text{E.58})$$

which is a constant factor and independent of KR .

With the help of Eq. (E.54) we can write

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_1) - \mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_2) &= \frac{e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}_s}}{2\pi} \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} (i^\ell)(2\ell+1) \left(\int d\Omega_{\hat{\mathbf{r}}} e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j P_\ell(\cos \gamma) \right) \\ &\times \left(\frac{1}{(KR_1)} \int_0^{KR_1} j_\ell(u) du - \frac{1}{(KR_2)} \int_0^{KR_2} j_\ell(u) du \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{E.59})$$

The radial part of Eq. (E.59) can be expanded as

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{(KR_1)} \int_0^{KR_1} j_\ell(u) dxu - \frac{1}{(KR_2)} \int_0^{KR_2} j_\ell(u) du \\ &= \frac{1}{(KR_1)} \int_0^{KR_1} j_\ell(u) du - \frac{1}{K(R_2 - R_1 + R_1)} \int_0^{KR_2} j_\ell(u) du \\ &= \frac{1}{K} \left[\frac{1}{R_1} \int_0^{KR_1} j_\ell(u) du - \frac{1}{R_1 + (R_2 - R_1)} \int_0^{KR_2} j_\ell(u) du \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{K} \left[\frac{1}{R_1} \int_0^{KR_1} j_\ell(u) du - \frac{1}{R_1(1 + \frac{R_2 - R_1}{R_1})} \int_0^{KR_2} j_\ell(u) du \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{K} \left[\frac{1}{R_1} \int_0^{KR_2} j_\ell(u) du + \frac{1}{R_1} \int_{KR_2}^{KR_1} j_\ell(u) du \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{1}{R_1} \int_0^{KR_2} j_\ell(u) du - \left(\frac{R_1 - R_2}{R_1} \right) \frac{1}{R_1} \int_0^{KR_2} j_\ell(u) du \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{E.60})$$

In the last equality, the integral from 0 to KR_1 is split into two sub-intervals 0 to KR_2 and KR_2 to KR_1 . Moreover, we have used the fact that $(R_2 - R_1) \ll R_1$. Hence, Eq. (E.60) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{(KR_1)} \int_0^{KR_1} j_\ell(u) du - \frac{1}{(KR_2)} \int_0^{KR_2} j_\ell(u) du \\ &= \frac{1}{(KR_1)} \int_{KR_2}^{KR_1} j_\ell(u) du - \frac{K(R_1 - R_2)}{(KR_1)^2} \left(\int_0^{KR_2} j_\ell(u) du \right) \\ &\equiv \mathcal{G}_1(R_1, R_2) - \mathcal{G}_2(R_1, R_2), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{E.61})$$

where in the last line we have defined

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{G}_1(R_1, R_2) &\equiv \frac{1}{(KR_1)} \left(\int_{KR_2}^{KR_1} j_{\ell}(u) du \right) \\ \mathcal{G}_2(R_1, R_2) &\equiv \frac{K(R_1 - R_2)}{(KR_1)^2} \left(\int_0^{KR_2} j_{\ell}(u) du \right).\end{aligned}\quad (\text{E.62})$$

The function $\mathcal{G}_1(R_1, R_2)$ can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{G}_1(R_1, R_2) &= \frac{1}{(KR_1)} \int_{KR_2}^{K(R_1 - R_2 + R_2)} j_{\ell}(u) du, \\ &= \frac{1}{(KR_1)} \int_{KR_2}^{KR_2 + K(R_1 - R_2)} j_{\ell}(u) du.\end{aligned}\quad (\text{E.63})$$

Taking $y = KR_2$ and $\epsilon = K(R_1 - R_2)$ so that $\epsilon \ll y$, and using the Taylor series expansion of $j_{\ell}(u)$ around y , we obtain

$$j_{\ell}(u) \simeq j_{\ell}(y) + j'_{\ell}(y)(u - y) + \frac{j''_{\ell}(y)}{2!}(u - y)^2 + \dots \quad (\text{E.64})$$

Inserting Eq. (E.64) into Eq. (E.63) yields

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{G}_1(R_1, R_2) &= \frac{1}{(KR_1)} \int_y^{y+\epsilon} (j_{\ell}(y) + j'_{\ell}(y)(u - y) + \frac{j''_{\ell}(y)}{2!}(u - y)^2 + \dots) du \\ &= \frac{1}{(KR_1)} j_{\ell}(y) \epsilon + \frac{1}{(KR_1)} j'_{\ell}(y) \frac{\epsilon^2}{2} + \dots \\ &\simeq \frac{j_{\ell}(KR_2)}{(KR_1)} (K(R_1 - R_2)) + \frac{j'_{\ell}(KR_2)}{(KR_1)} \frac{(K(R_1 - R_2))^2}{2}.\end{aligned}\quad (\text{E.65})$$

The second term in Eq. (E.65) is proportional to $\epsilon^2 = (K(R_1 - R_2))^2$. From Eq. (7.32) one has $|\epsilon| = |K(R_1 - R_2)| \leq K\rho'w = K(\rho'/a)a(d/R) = Kd(\theta/2)(\rho'/a) \leq Kd\theta/2$ where $w = d/R$ is used. In a typical VLBI interferometer performing on the Earth, the detector separation d can be as large as the Earth's radius and the measured θ is of the order of 10^{-8} rad. Thus one may use $|\epsilon| \ll 1$ concerning the spectrum of PGWs. Therefore, we proceed by keeping terms up to $\mathcal{O}(K(R_1 - R_2)) = \epsilon$ and neglecting higher order terms. Combining Eqs. (E.61, E.62, E.65) yields

$$\begin{aligned}&\frac{1}{(KR_1)} \int_0^{KR_1} j_{\ell}(u) du - \frac{1}{(KR_2)} \int_0^{KR_2} j_{\ell}(u) du \\ &= \left\{ \frac{j_{\ell}(KR_2)}{(KR_1)} - \frac{\int_0^{KR_2} j_{\ell}(u) du}{(KR_1)^2} \right\} (K(R_1 - R_2)).\end{aligned}\quad (\text{E.66})$$

Inserting Eq. (E.66) into Eq. (E.59) results in

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_1) - \mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_2) &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} (i^\ell)(2\ell + 1) \left(\int d\Omega_{\hat{\mathbf{r}}} e^{i\gamma} [\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j P_\ell(\cos \gamma) \right) \quad (\text{E.67}) \\ &\times \left\{ \frac{j_\ell(KR_2)}{(KR_1)} - \frac{\int_0^{KR_2} j_\ell(u) du}{(KR_1)^2} \right\} (K(R_1 - R_2)). \end{aligned}$$

Using Eq. (7.32) for $R_1 - R_2$, one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_1) - \mathcal{G}_{\mathbf{K}}^\lambda(R_2)|^2 &= \left| \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} (i^\ell) \frac{(2\ell + 1)}{2\pi} \left(\int d\Omega_{\hat{\mathbf{r}}} e^{i\gamma} [\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j P_\ell(\cos \gamma) \right) \quad (\text{E.68}) \right. \\ &\times \left. \left(\frac{j_\ell(KR)}{(KR)} - \frac{\int_0^{KR} j_\ell(u) du}{(KR)^2} \right) \right|^2 (K\rho' w \cos(\phi' - \psi))^2. \end{aligned}$$

and Eq. (7.33) for $\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(R_1, t; R_2, t)$ outcomes.

E.4 Derivation of the visibility $\mathcal{V}_{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}_C, t)$

The integration over the polar coordinate ϕ' in Eq. (7.38) for the visibility $\mathcal{V}(\mathbf{x}_C, t)$ can be written in the following compact form

$$\begin{aligned} I_{\phi'} &\equiv \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-A^2 \cos^2 \phi'} e^{-ik\xi_{\text{ts}}A \cos \phi'} d\phi' \quad (\text{E.69}) \\ &= \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-\frac{A^2}{2} - \frac{A^2}{2} \cos 2\phi'} e^{-ik\xi_{\text{ts}}A \cos \phi'} d\phi', \end{aligned}$$

where we have defined $A \equiv \xi_{\text{ts}}^{-1} \rho' w$ and replaced $\phi' - \psi \rightarrow \phi'$. With the help of the Jacobi-Anger identity

$$e^{iz \cos \phi'} = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} i^m J_m(z) e^{im\phi'}, \quad (\text{E.70})$$

Eq. (E.69) can be written as

$$I_{\phi'} = e^{-\frac{A^2}{2}} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-\frac{A^2}{2} \cos 2\phi'} J_m(-k\xi_{\text{ts}}A) e^{im\phi'} d\phi'. \quad (\text{E.71})$$

Substituting the expression

$$e^{-\frac{A^2}{2} \cos 2\phi'} = e^{i(i\frac{A^2}{2} \cos 2\phi')} = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} i^n J_n(i\frac{A^2}{2}) e^{i2n\phi'}, \quad (\text{E.72})$$

into Eq. (E.71) and using the properties $J_m(-x) = (-1)^m J_m(x)$ and $J_n(ix) = i^n I_n(x)$ where $I_n(x)$ stands for the modified Bessel function of the first kind, one ends up with

$$I_{\phi'} = (2\pi) e^{-\frac{A^2}{2}} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} J_{2m}(k\xi A) I_m\left(\frac{A^2}{2}\right). \quad (\text{E.73})$$

Inserting Eq. (E.73) into Eq. (7.38) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{V}_{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}_C, t) &= \frac{2\pi}{\pi a^2} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \int_0^a \rho' e^{-\left(\frac{w^2}{2\xi_{\text{ts}}^2} \rho'^2\right)} J_{2m}(k w \rho') I_m\left(\frac{w^2}{2\xi_{\text{ts}}^2} \rho'^2\right) d\rho' \\ &= \frac{2}{a^2} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} (-i)^m \int_0^a \rho' e^{-\frac{w^2}{2\xi_{\text{ts}}^2} \rho'^2} J_{2m}(k w \rho') J_m\left(i \frac{w^2}{2\xi_{\text{ts}}^2} \rho'^2\right) d\rho' \\ &= \frac{2}{a^2} \int_0^a \rho' e^{-\frac{w^2}{2\xi_{\text{ts}}^2} \rho'^2} \left(J_0(k w \rho') J_0\left(i \frac{w^2}{2\xi_{\text{ts}}^2} \rho'^2\right) + 2 \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (-i)^m J_{2m}(k w \rho') J_m\left(i \frac{w^2}{2\xi_{\text{ts}}^2} \rho'^2\right) \right) d\rho'. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{E.74})$$

In the last line, we have used the symmetry properties of the Bessel functions. Changing the variable $\rho' \rightarrow \rho'/a$ results in Eq. (7.39).

E.5 Expression of the time of flight t and distance R versus redshift z

Typical quasars detected by VLBI means are located at cosmological distances. Hence, it seems necessary to express physical quantities in terms of the redshift of the source, z , rather than the time of flight t . These objects are located at the redshift range $0.46 \leq z \leq 2.73$, so during their journey to the Earth, they have been affected not only by PGWs background but also by the expansion of the Universe. One may incorporate the expansion of the Universe by expressing time, distance, and frequency in terms of the redshift. In particular, one may replace the redshifted EM frequency according to $\omega_k \rightarrow \omega_k/(1+z)$. The light detected today was emitted at some earlier time. The time of flight $t(z)$, i.e., the time interval between emission at time t_z , corresponding to the redshift z , and detection at present t_{z_H} , is determined by [101],

$$t(z) = t_{z_H} - t_z = \int_{z_H}^z \frac{dz'}{(1+z')H(z')}, \quad (\text{E.75})$$

where $H(z')$ is the Hubble parameter at redshift z and $z_H = 0$ is the redshift at the present. We proceed assuming a flat Universe comprising only cold dark matter and a cosmological constant, so that $\Omega_\Lambda + \Omega_m = 1$. The Hubble parameter versus redshift is thus determined by

$$H(z) = H_0 \sqrt{(1 - \Omega_m) + \Omega_m(1+z)^3}. \quad (\text{E.76})$$

By plugging Eq. (E.76) into Eq. (E.75) and setting $z_H = 0$, the time of flight $t(z)$ turns out

$$t(z) = H_0^{-1} \int_0^z \frac{dz'}{\sqrt{(1 - \Omega_m)(1 + z')^2 + \Omega_m(1 + z')^5}}, \quad (\text{E.77})$$

Moreover, the angular diameter distance $R(z)$ of an object located at redshift z is determined by [101]

$$R(z) = \frac{c}{H_0(1 + z)} \left(\int_0^z \frac{dz'}{\sqrt{\Omega_m(1 + z')^3 + (1 - \Omega_m)}} \right). \quad (\text{E.78})$$

خلاصه‌ی فارسی

1 پیش‌گفتار

پیش‌بینی‌های موفقیت‌آمیز نظریه‌ی نسبیت عام، گواه محکمی بر این مدعا است که پدیده‌های گرانشی را می‌توان با در نظر گرفتن انحنای فضا-زمان، به درستی فهمیده و توصیف کرد. در نسبیت عام، اثرات گرانشی ماده در قالب انحنای فضا-زمان ظاهر شده و انتشار ذرات و میدان‌ها در این پس‌زمینه‌ی خمیده صورت می‌پذیرد. در این سطح از بررسی، میدان گرانشی را کلاسیکی در نظر گرفته و روش‌های معمول نظریه میدان‌های کوانتومی در فضا-زمان مینکوفسکی، تا جای ممکن مورد تعمیم و توسعه قرار می‌گیرند. این تعمیم سراسر است، منجر به پیش‌بینی پدیده‌های فیزیکی غنی و جالب توجهی شده که دیدگاه ما را نسبت به طبیعت گرانش و وسعت بخشیده است.

از مهم‌ترین نتایج فیزیکی این ادغام، خلق ذرات در فضا-زمان‌های کیهان شناختی است. به عبارت دیگر، پیش‌بینی می‌شود که میدان گرانشی بسیار قوی فضا-زمان منبسط‌شونده منجر به تولید گراویتون‌ها، بسته‌های انرژی میدان گرانشی کوانتیده، می‌شود. در این فرایند، نوسانات کوانتومی خلأ به اصطلاح دچار کشیدگی شده و نهایتاً منجر به تولید ذرات در حالت چلانده‌ی دو-مدی می‌شود. به علاوه، نشان داده می‌شود که گراویتون‌های خلق‌شده در حالت قویاً درهم‌تنیده هستند. به این ترتیب، انتظار می‌رود که پس‌زمینه‌ای از امواج گرانشی اولیه، از زمان کودکی دنیا (زمان انبساط تورمی) تا کنون، در سرتاسر کیهان گسترده شده باشند که امروزه باید در حالت چلانده یافت شوند. به علاوه، این امواج گرانشی اولیه، خصوصیات امواج گرانشی تصادفی را از خود بروز می‌دهند. تولید و تحول امواج گرانشی اولیه که در دوره‌ی تورمی به وجود آمده‌اند، به عواملی مانند زمان خروج از افق در دوره‌ی تورمی، زمان ورود به افق در دوره‌های پس از تورم و نحوه‌ی تحول خود کیهان در این میان بستگی دارد. بنابراین، آنچه امروزه از این امواج گرانشی به دست می‌آید می‌تواند اطلاعات ارزنده‌ای از شرایط وقوع دوره‌ی تورمی و تحول کیهان پس از آن در اختیار قرار دهد. به خصوص، امواج گرانشی اولیه‌ی تصادفی اطلاعات منحصر به فردی درباره‌ی فیزیک انرژی‌های بسیار بالا در طول دوره‌ی تورم با خود به همراه دارند، چرا که بر خلاف سایر ذرات، گراویتون‌ها خیلی سریع از سایر میدان‌ها واجفتیده شده و پس از تولدشان به طور آزادانه در جهان اولیه پخش شده‌اند. بنابراین حامل اطلاعاتی پیش از زمان واجفتیدگی تابش پس‌زمینه‌ی کیهانی هستند.

بنابراین، آشکارسازی امواج گرانشی اولیه‌ی تصادفی، به جد و جهد گرفته شده و جزء خطوط اصلی اهداف آشکارسازهای امواج گرانشی کنونی و در حال توسعه، هر کدام در پنجره‌ی بسامدی خود، قرار گرفته است: رصدخانه‌ی امواج گرانشی تداخل سنج لیزری، LIGO، VIRGO، GEO، AIGO، LCGT و ET که همگی در بازه‌ی بسامدی $(10^2 - 10^3)$ هرتز فعالیت می‌کنند، تداخل سنج‌های فضایی نظیر آنتن فضایی تداخل سنج لیزری LISA که در بازه‌ی بسامدی $(10^{-1} - 10^{-4})$ هرتز حساسیت دارد، رصدخانه‌ی بیگ بنگ BBO و رصدخانه‌ی امواج گرانشی تداخل سنج دسی هرتز DECIGO که هر دو در بازه‌ی بسامدی $(10 - 0.1)$ هرتز فعال هستند و آرایه‌ی زمان سنج تپ‌اختر که شامل PPTA و SKA می‌شود که هر دو در بازه‌ی بسامدی $(10^{-6} - 10^{-9})$ هرتز کار می‌کنند. علاوه بر این، طرح‌واره‌های متعددی برای آشکارسازی امواج گرانشی اولیه با بسامدهای بالا، بر مبنای آشکارسازهای موجبر، آشکارساز پرتوی میزری گاؤسی در محدوده‌ی $(1 - 100)$ مگاهرتز ارائه شده است. از سوی دیگر، بخش بسامدهای فوق کوتاه امواج گرانشی اولیه، که متناظر با ابعاد 10^4 تا 10^4 مگاپارسک است، مسئول ناهمسانگردی و قطبش تابش پس‌زمینه‌ی کیهانی بوده که انتظار می‌رود توسط کاوشگر ناهمسانگردی

ریزموجی ویلکینسون¹، ماهواره ی پلانک²، ماهواره ی لایتبرد³ و تلسکوپ کیهان شناسی آتاکاما⁴ ثبت شود. آشکارسازی امواج گرانشی اولیه، نه تنها دلالت بر راستی نظریه ی تورمی است، بلکه می تواند مهر تأییدی باشد بر درستی توصیف کوانتومی میدان گرانشی در ابعاد بزرگتر از طول پلانک. در کیهان شناسی استاندارد، تصور می شود که دوره ی تورمی پس از دوره ی گرانش کوانتومی رخ داده است، با این وجود هنوز تأیید تجربی مستقیم برای تصدیق این مدعا وجود ندارد. هم چنین، صحت نظریه ی گرانش کوانتومی هنوز به محک آزمایش کشیده نشده است. از این منظر، امواج گرانشی اولیه برخاسته از نوسانات کوانتومی خلاء در دوره ی تورمی، آزمایشگاه تجربی بی نظیری برای تأیید این نظریه ها به شمار می آید. در این راستا، چندین طرحواره برای آشکارسازی سرشت کوانتومی امواج گرانشی اولیه، بر مبنای ماهیت چلانده ی این امواج، توسط آشکارسازهای امواج گرانشی زمینی و فضایی و نیز ردیابی آثار حک شده بر ناهمسانگردی و قطبش تابش پس زمینه ی کیهانی، مورد بررسی قرار گرفته اند. با این وجود، آشکارسازی سرشت کوانتومی این امواج هنوز خارج از دسترسی تجربی قرار دارد.

با الهام از مباحثی که در بالا بدانها اشاره شد، پایان نامه ی حاضر به این موضوع می پردازد که چطور می توان ماهیت کوانتومی امواج گرانشی اولیه را توسط آشکارسازهای مبتنی بر امواج الکترومغناطیسی، نظیر تداخل سنج های لیزری و تداخل سنج خط پایه ی بسیار طولانی، بر ملا ساخت. برای نیل بدین منظور، ابتدا به برپایش چارچوب نظری برای توصیف اندرکنش میان امواج الکترومغناطیسی و امواج گرانشی مبادرت می کنیم. استفاده از مفهوم مانستگی محیط نوری در این میان، منجر به سهولت حل معادلات ماکسول و نیز درک پدیده های گرانشی در قالب مفاهیم آشنای نوری می شود. به علاوه، گذار به سطح بررسی کوانتومی به طور سراسر با ارتقای هامیلتونی کلاسیکی به کوانتومی صورت می پذیرد. به خصوص، نشان داده می شود که هامیلتونی توصیف کننده ی اندرکنش میان امواج الکترومغناطیسی و گرانشی، مانسته ی اندرکنش کاواک اپتومکانیک بوده و ازین رو، باب جدیدی برای کشف ماهیت کوانتومی امواج گرانشی، از طریق مانسته سازی با معادل اپتومکانیک آن، گشوده می شود. با بررسی مفصل این موضوع، کاشف به عمل می آید که امواج گرانشی اولیه موجب واهمدوسی (از بین رفتن همبستگی های زمانی) موج الکترومغناطیسی شده و این موضوع به نوبه ی خود، آشکارسازی تحولات همدوس میدان الکترومغناطیسی برخاسته از ویژگی های کوانتومی امواج گرانشی را، تحت الشعاع قرار می دهد. با این وجود، نشان می دهیم که همبستگی های فضایی تابش الکترومغناطیسی گسیل شده از چشمه های بسیار دوردست، نظیر تابش ریزموج تپ اخترهای دور، چگونه می تواند اطلاعات ارزنده ای درباره ی امواج گرانشی اولیه که در پس زمینه ی انتشار امواج الکترومغناطیسی قرار دارند، فراهم کند.

در ادامه ی این بخش، ابتدا مرور مختصری بر امواج گرانشی اولیه برخاسته از نوسانات خلاء در دوره ی تورمی خواهیم داشت و ویژگی هایی نظیر دامنه ی طیفی این امواج بر حسب بسامد و دامنه ی چلانده ی مدهای مختلف را، در زمان کنونی، معرفی خواهیم کرد. در بخش بعدی، مفاهیمی نظیر مانستگی محیط نوری، هامیلتونی برهمکنش و دینامیک میدان الکترومغناطیسی در حضور پس زمینه ای از امواج گرانشی کوانتیده مد نظر قرار می گیرند که سنگ بنای اصلی برای محاسبات بعدی به شمار می روند. مباحثی نظیر واهمدوسی و ناهمدوسی برخاسته از گرانش در بخش های بعدی از نظر گذرانده می شود. این خلاصه را با تأکید بر نتایج نوین حاصل از پژوهش کنونی و ارائه ی چشم اندازی برای بررسی های بیشتر، به پایان می رسانیم.

2 امواج گرانشی اولیه برخاسته از نوسانات کوانتومی دوره ی تورمی

امواج گرانشی، اختلالات $h_{\mu\nu}(x)$ بر متریک فضا زمان هستند

$$g_{\alpha\beta} = \bar{g}_{\alpha\beta} + h_{\alpha\beta}, \quad |h_{\alpha\beta}| \ll 1, \quad \alpha, \beta = 0, 1, 2, 3. \quad (1.ه)$$

¹Wilkinson Microwave Anisotropy Probe

²Planck satellite

³LiteBIRD satellite

⁴Atacama Cosmology Telescope

در عبارت بالا، $\bar{g}_{\mu\nu}$ نشان دهنده ی متریک زمينه ی فضا زمان است که اختلالات $h_{\mu\nu}$ بر روی آن در حال انتشار بوده و برای مثال، می تواند متریک مینکوفسکی یا متریک جهان منبسط شونده باشد. با نوشتن معادلات اینشتین، می توان نشان داد که اختلالات متریک از معادله ی دالامبرین پیروی می کنند. بنابراین، نظریه ی نسبیت عام اینشتین، وجود امواج گرانشی، یعنی اختلالاتی در فضا زمان که با سرعت نور منتشر می شوند، را پیش بینی می کند. با بررسی جزئیات دقیق تر می توان نشان داد که امواج گرانشی، به مثابه میدان تانسوری مرتبه دو، دارای دو حالت قطبشی مجزا بوده که متناظر با دو دستینگی⁵ در نظریه ی میدان کوانتومی است. در پیمانه ی عرضی-بی رد، امواج گرانشی بر حسب امواج تخت به صورت زیر قابل بیان هستند:

$$h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta) = \sum_{\gamma=+, \times} \int \frac{d^3 \mathbf{K}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}} [e^{\gamma} \hat{K}] (h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma}(\eta) e^{i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}} + h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma*}(\eta) e^{-i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x}}). \quad (2.ه)$$

در عبارت بالا، $i, j = 1, 2, 3$ اندیس های فضایی، \mathbf{K} بردار موج گرانشی و Ω_K بسامد موج گرانشی هستند. تانسور فضایی $e^{\gamma} [\hat{\mathbf{K}}]$ تانسور قطبش موج گرانشی با قطبش $\gamma = +, \times$ است. کمیت $h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma}(\eta)$ دامنه ی میدان فوریه ای نام دارد که با طیف توان موج گرانشی در ارتباط است. در این جا، η نشان دهنده ی مختصات زمانی است. اگر اختلالات متریک فضا زمان مینکوفسکی مد نظر باشد، η همان مختصه ی زمانی t است. اگر اختلالات متریک جهان منبسط شونده مد نظر باشد، η می تواند زمان همدیس باشد. برای توصیف اختلالات متریک در جهان منبسط شونده ی همگن و همسانگرد، متریک فریدمن-رابرتسون-واکر مختل شده به صورت زیر معرفی می شود

$$ds^2 = a^2(\eta) \left[-d\eta^2 + (\delta_{ij} + h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta)) dx^i dx^j \right], \quad (3.ه)$$

که در آن، $a(\eta)$ عامل مقیاس نام داشته و معیاری از بزرگی اندازه ی جهان به دست می دهد و دینامیک انبساط جهان با دینامیک این عامل در ارتباط است. کمیت $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \eta)$ اختلالات تانسوری پیمانه-ناوردا هستند که ویژگی عرضی-بدون رد دارند، یعنی $\partial^j h_{ij} = \delta^{ij} h_{ij} = 0$. بسط عمومی معادله (2.ه) می تواند توصیف کننده ی اختلالات تانسوری متریک فریدمن باشد. در این صورت، معادلات اینشتین-فریدمن که تحولات متریک و اختلالات متریک را تعیین می کنند، ایجاب می کند که

$$h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma''}(\eta) + 2 \frac{a'(\eta)}{a(\eta)} h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma'}(\eta) + K^2 h_{\mathbf{K}}^{\gamma}(\eta) = 0. \quad (4.ه)$$

بنابراین، علاوه بر عامل نوسانی که با ضرب K^2 مشخص می شود، انبساط جهان، که در اینجا با عامل $\mathcal{H} \equiv a'(\eta)/a(\eta)$ ظاهر شده است، می تواند دینامیک دامنه ی میدان امواج گرانشی را به طور کلی دستخوش تغییر کند. کمیت \mathcal{H} چیزی نیست جز پارامتر هابل در مختصات همدیس. امواج زیر-هابل⁶ که برای آنها $\mathcal{H} \ll K$ ، تحول عادی خود را در جهان منبسط شونده سپری می کنند که همراه با افت دامنه ی موج گرانشی متناسب با $1/a(\eta)$ است. برای امواج فوق-هابل⁷ $\mathcal{H} \gg K$ ، دامنه ی میدان گرانشی نه تنها دچار فروافت نشده، بلکه مادامی که رژیم فوق-هابل برقرار باشد، دامنه ثابت خواهد ماند. می توان نشان داد که معادله (4.ه) یک نوسانگر واداشته را توصیف می کند که بسامد آن وابسته به زمان است. در دیدگاه کلاسیکی، این به معنی تبادل انرژی میان سامانه و محیط پیرامون آن، در اینجا موج گرانشی در حضور فضا زمان منبسط شونده، است. از نقطه نظر مکانیک کوانتومی، این موضوع ارتباط مستقیم با تولید ذرات امواج گرانشی، یعنی گراویتون ها، توسط موتور پمپ کننده ی جهان منبسط شونده، دارد. این پدیده ای است که تحت عنوان "تولید ذرات در فضا زمان های کیهان شناختی" به تفصیل مورد بررسی قرار گرفته است. در این بخش، ما صرفاً بر نتایج این پدیده و کاربرد آن در مسائل مد نظر خود تمرکز کرده و جزئیات محاسبات را به متن اصلی پایان نامه واگذار می کنیم.

⁵Chirality

⁶Sub-Hubble

⁷Super-Hubble

کمیت دیگری که معمولاً در ادبیات امواج گرانشی اولیه مورد توجه است، دامنه ی طیفی نام داشته و با $h(K, \eta)$ نشان داده می شود، که با دامنه ی میدان $h_K(\eta)$ متناسب است. بدین ترتیب، می توان نشان داد که دامنه ی طیفی امواج گرانشی اولیه با منشاء کوانتومی، امروزه به صورت زیر خواهد بود

$$h(\eta_H, K) = \begin{cases} A \left(\frac{K}{K_H}\right)^{2+\beta} & , \quad K \leq K_E \\ A \left(\frac{K}{K_H}\right)^{\beta-\gamma} \zeta_E^{-\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}} & , \quad K_E \leq K \leq K_H \\ A \left(\frac{K}{K_H}\right)^{\beta} \zeta_E^{-\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}} & , \quad K_H \leq K \leq K_2 \\ A \left(\frac{K}{K_H}\right)^{1+\beta} \left(\frac{K_H}{K_2}\right)^{-\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}} \zeta_E^{-\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}} & , \quad K_2 \leq K \leq K_s \\ A \left(\frac{K}{K_H}\right)^{1+\beta-\beta_s} \left(\frac{K_s}{K_H}\right)^{\beta_s} \left(\frac{K_H}{K_2}\right)^{-\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}} \zeta_E^{-\frac{2+\gamma}{\gamma}} & , \quad K_s \leq K \leq K_1, \end{cases} \quad (5.ه)$$

که در آن، اعداد موج مشخصه ی K_E, K_H, K_2, K_s, K_1 در متن اصلی به طور کامل تعریف و مشخص شده اند. بنابراین، با در دست داشتن طیف امواج گرانشی اولیه، می توانیم دامنه ی چلانگی، r_K ، مربوط به هر مد K از امواج گرانشی اولیه را به دست آوریم. نشان داده می شود که دامنه ی چلانگی در رابطه ی زیر صدق می کند

$$e^{r_K} = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{K}{K_1}\right)^{1+\beta} \left(\frac{K_2}{K_E}\right)^2 \left(\frac{K_s}{K_1}\right)^{-\beta_s} \left(\frac{K_1}{K_2}\right) \left(\frac{K_H}{K_E}\right)^{\gamma} & , \quad K \leq K_E \\ \left(\frac{K}{K_1}\right)^{1+\beta} \left(\frac{K_1}{K_H}\right) \left(\frac{K_2}{K_H}\right) \left(\frac{K_E}{K_H}\right)^{-(2+\gamma)} \left(\frac{K_s}{K_1}\right)^{-\beta_s} & , \quad K_E \leq K \leq K_H \\ \left(\frac{K}{K_2}\right)^{\beta-1} \left(\frac{K_2}{K_1}\right)^{\beta} \left(\frac{K_s}{K_1}\right)^{-\beta_s} & , \quad K_2 \leq K \leq K_H \\ \left(\frac{K}{K_s}\right)^{\beta} \left(\frac{K_s}{K_1}\right)^{\beta-\beta_s} & , \quad K_s \leq K \leq K_2 \\ \left(\frac{K}{K_1}\right)^{\beta-\beta_s} & , \quad K_1 \leq K \leq K_s \\ 1 & , \quad K \geq K_1. \end{cases} \quad (6.ه)$$

با در دست داشتن این کمیت، می توانیم تعداد میانگین گراویتون های تولید شده در هر مد K را از طریق $\bar{n}(K) = \sinh^2 r_K \simeq e^{2r_K}/4$ به دست آوریم. توجه شود که عبارت بالا برای مدهایی صادق است که در رژیم فوق-هابل سر کرده اند و برای آن ها دامنه ی چلانگی $r_K \gg 1$ است.

چارچوب نظری توصیف اندرکنش الکترومغناطیسی-گرانشی

در پژوهش حاضر، از چارچوب مانستگی محیط مادی جهت توصیف اندرکنش امواج الکترومغناطیسی-گرانشی بهره برداری شده است. در این چارچوب، آثار گرانشی به طور مؤثر در قالب یک محیط ناهمگن و ناهمسانگرد مغناطو-دی الکتریک ظاهر شده که تانسورهای تراوایی الکتریکی و مغناطیسی آن توسط مؤلفه های متریک فضا زمان مشخص می شوند. بدین ترتیب، برای فضا زمان مینکوفسکی مختل شده، که انتشار امواج گرانشی را توصیف می کند، تانسورهای الکتریکی و مغناطیسی با یکدیگر برابر بوده و داریم:

$$\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)/\varepsilon_0 = \mu_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)/\mu_0 = g_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \delta_{ij} - h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t). \quad (7.ه)$$

که در آن، $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ بسطی مشابه رابطه (2.ه) دارد. با این تفسیر، گام بعدی یافتن ویژه-پاسخ های معادلات ماکسول در این محیط مادی است که توسط امواج گرانشی $h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ ایجاد می شود. در این میان، استفاده از تقریب پوش کند-تغییر در ساده سازی معادلات کمک شایانی می کند. این تقریب، بر این واقعیت فیزیکی استوار است که آهنگ تغییر موج الکترومغناطیسی که با بسامد موج الکترومغناطیسی یعنی ω_k مشخص می شود، از آهنگ تغییرات پس زمینه ی امواج

گرانشی که با بسامد موج گرانشی یعنی Ω_K تعیین می شود، بسیار بیشتر است. به عبارت دیگر، زمان مشخصه تحول میدان الکترومغناطیسی بسیار کوچکتر از زمان مشخصه موج گرانشی است و در بازه ی زمانی ای که میدان الکترومغناطیسی نوسان می کند، میدان گرانشی عملاً ثابت است. با توجه به کران بالایی که بر بسامد امواج گرانشی اولیه وجود دارد، یعنی $f_1 \lesssim 4 \times 10^{10} \text{Hz}$ ، این تقریب برای امواج الکترومغناطیسی با بسامد ناحیه ی نوری قابل استفاده است. با این وجود، باید خاطر نشان کرد که دامنه ی طیفی امواج گرانشی اولیه با افزایش بسامد (یا عدد موج) کاهش می یابد، به طوری که بخش عمده ی آثاری که بر میدان الکترومغناطیسی برجای می ماند ناشی از بخش بسامدهای فوق کوتاه امواج گرانشی اولیه است که در شرط کند-تغییر به خوبی صدق می کنند. از سوی دیگر، بخش بسامدهای بالاتر امواج گرانشی اولیه دارای محتویات گراویتونی ناچیزی بوده به طوری که اثر ناچیزی در تحولات میدان الکترومغناطیسی برجای می گذارند. بنابراین، تقریب پوش کند-تغییر قابل تعمیم به بخش امواج رایویی با بسامدهای از مرتبه ی گیگاهرتز نیز هست. بدین ترتیب، حل معادلات ماکسول به حل معادله ی فرنل تعمیم یافته کاهش می یابد که پاسخ آن ضریب شکست محیط را به صورت زیر به دست می دهد

$$n_k(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sqrt{\frac{\det(\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t))}{\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j}}. \quad (8.ه)$$

در این رابطه، تانسور تراوایی الکتریکی توسط روابط (2.ه، 7.ه) داده می شود، و $\hat{\mathbf{k}}_i$ مؤلفه ی i ام بردار موج الکترومغناطیسی \mathbf{k} را نشان می دهد. بدین ترتیب، ویژه توابع مُدی زمانی و فضایی به صورت زیر به دست می آیند

$$\begin{aligned} v_k(\mathbf{x}, t) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t)}} e^{\pm i \int_0^t \omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t') dt'}, \\ \mathbf{F}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) &= \frac{\hat{\mathbf{u}} e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}}}{(2\pi)^{3/2} \sqrt{m(t)}}, \end{aligned} \quad (9.ه)$$

که در آن، بسامد وابسته به زمان میدان الکترومغناطیسی به صورت زیر تعریف شده است

$$\omega_k(\mathbf{x}, t) = \omega_k \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} h_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j\right). \quad (10.ه)$$

و در آن، ω_k بسامد اولیه ی موج الکترومغناطیسی، در عدم حضور پس زمینه ی امواج گرانشی است. با این تفسیر، حضور امواج گرانشی موجب تغییر بسامد موج الکترومغناطیسی به صورت بالا می شود، و این موضوع ویژه توابع زمانی و فضایی را به صورت رابطه (9.ه) تغییر می دهد. روابط بالا، در غیاب امواج گرانشی، به پاسخ های مورد انتظار در فضای تهی کاسته می شوند. بنابراین، بررسی آثار گرانشی در سطح توصیف کلاسیکی، با کمک روابط پیشین میسر می شود. به عنوان مثال، آثاری نظیر "جابجایی باقیمانده"، که به معنای جابجایی بسامد موج الکترومغناطیسی در حضور امواج گرانشی بوده و پیشتر در ادبیات امواج گرانشی در چارچوب اپتیک هندسی و معادلات ژئودزی به دست آمده است، اکنون در چارچوب اپتیک موجی و با به کارگیری چارچوب مانستگی محیط نوری، بازیابی می شود. علاوه بر آن، ویژگی هایی نظیر قطبش موج الکترومغناطیسی نیز در چارچوب کنونی قابل بررسی هستند. برای مثال، می توان نشان داد که محیط مؤثر امواج گرانشی به مثابه یک محیط دوشکستی رفتار کرده و بسته به قطبش موج فرودی، ضریب شکست محیط متفاوت خواهد بود. با داشتن ویژه-پاسخ های معادلات ماکسول در حضور امواج گرانشی، برپایش لاگرانژی سامانه و هامیلتونی متناظر با آن به روش استاندارد صورت می پذیرد. به ویژه، در سطح بررسی کوانتومی، می توان نشان داد که هامیلتونی توصیف

کننده ی اندرکنش میدان تک-مُد الکترومغناطیسی با پیوستاری از امواج گرانشی با رابطه ی زیر داده می شود

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}_{\text{int}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)/\hbar &= -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}} \right) \frac{\sqrt{16\pi c^3}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \sum_{\gamma=+, \times} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \frac{F_\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}})}{\sqrt{2\Omega_K}} \\ &\times \left(\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma} e^{-i\Omega_K t} g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) + \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}^\dagger e^{i\Omega_K t} g_{\mathbf{K}}^*(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f) \right) \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}, \end{aligned} \quad (11.هـ)$$

که در آن عملگرهای بوزونی $(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}, \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger)$ و $(\hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger)$ به ترتیب نشان دهنده ی عملگرهای نردبانی تک-مُد میدان الکترومغناطیسی، با بردار موج و قطبش $k \equiv (\sigma, \mathbf{k})$ و نیز موج گرانشی با بردار موج و قطبش $K \equiv (\gamma, \mathbf{K})$ است. هم چنین، تابع الگوی آشکارساز به صورت زیر تعریف شده است

$$F_\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}) \equiv e_{ij}^\gamma[\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{\mathbf{k}}_i \hat{\mathbf{k}}_j, \quad (12.هـ)$$

که دربرگیرنده ی جهت گیری و پیکربندی سامانه ی الکترومغناطیسی نسبت به امواج گرانشی در حال انتشار است. همان طور که از شکل هامیلتونی رابطه (11.هـ) بر می آید، جفت شدگی الکترومغناطیسی-گرانشی وابسته به شدت است، یعنی به عملگر تعداد فوتونی $\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}$ وابسته است. هم چنین، این جفت شدگی به دلیل وجود جملات نظیر $\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}^\dagger$ و $\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} \hat{b}_{\mathbf{K}}$ مشابه پدیده ی اختلاط سه-موجی در اپتیک غیر خطی و نیز یادآور جفت شدگی کاواک اپتومکانیک است. در کاواک اپتومکانیک، فشار تابشی میدان الکترومغناطیسی درون کاواک منجر به حرکت نوسانی آینه ی انتهایی کاواک شده و این حرکت به نوبه ی خود منجر به مدوله شدن ویژه-بسامدهای کاواک می شود. بدین ترتیب، میدان الکترومغناطیسی با آینه با جرم میکروسکوپی جفت شدگی وابسته به شدت پیدا کرده و تحول یکدیگر را رقم می زنند. در مورد جفت شدگی الکترومغناطیسی-گرانشی رابطه (11.هـ)، امواج گرانشی به طور مؤثر به مثابه ی آینه ی انتهایی متحرک کاواک، باعث مدوله شدن بسامد موج الکترومغناطیسی می شود. از این منظر، می توان مانستگی زیر را میان موج گرانشی و آینه ی انتهایی متحرک کاواک اپتومکانیک برقرار کرد:

دامنه ی میدان نوسانی موج گرانشی \longleftrightarrow دامنه ی جابجایی نوسانگر مزوسکوپی در کاواک اپتومکانیک

با الهام گرفتن از تلاش هایی که پیش تر در زمینه ی اپتومکانیک به منظور دست یازیدن به رفتار کوانتومی نوسانگر مزوسکوپی صورت گرفته است، اکنون می توان انتظار داشت که مانستگی بالا بتواند راهی جدید برای آشکارسازی رفتار کوانتومی امواج گرانشی بگشاید. به عنوان یک مثال خاص برای سامانه ی کاواک اپتومکانیک، این طرح واره مطرح شده است که جفت شدگی میدان تابشی با نوسانگر مزوسکوپی تنها در صورتی می تواند موجب احیای چلانگی مؤلفه های کوادراتوری میدان الکترومغناطیسی شود که نوسانگر مزوسکوپی سرشت کوانتومی داشته باشد و رفتار آن در چارچوب مکانیک کوانتومی توصیف و تحلیل شود. در غیر این صورت، احیای چلانگی مؤلفه های کوادراتوری میدان الکترومغناطیسی به وقوع نخواهد پیوست. از این رو، پیشنهاد می شود هرگاه بتوان این رفتار میدان الکترومغناطیسی را در آزمایشگاه مورد تأیید قرار داد، ماهیت کوانتومی نوسانگر مزوسکوپی تصدیق خواهد شد. به منظور بررسی و تعمیم این نکته به مورد جفت شدگی الکترومغناطیسی-گرانشی، باید دینامیک میدان الکترومغناطیسی را بررسی کنیم.

با کمک هامیلتونی رابطه (11.هـ) و با حل معادلات هایزنبرگ، کاشف به عمل می آید که عمگر نردبانی نابودگر میدان الکترومغناطیسی توسط رابطه ی زیر تعیین می شود

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= \left[\prod_{\gamma, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+}} \hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k})\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \right. \\ &\otimes \left. \hat{D}_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(-\kappa_\gamma(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k})\eta_{-\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)) \right] \\ &\times e^{2iE(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)(\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} + \frac{1}{2})} e^{-i\omega_k t} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}. \end{aligned} \quad (13.هـ)$$

در رابطه ی بالا، عملگر $\hat{D}_{\mathbf{K}, \gamma}(\zeta)$ نشان دهنده ی عملگر جابجایی مد $K \equiv (\gamma, \mathbf{K})$ میدان امواج گرانشی است و

سایر کمیت‌ها نظیر $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ ، $\eta_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ و $\kappa_{\gamma}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k})$ در متن اصلی پایان‌نامه تعریف شده‌اند. بدین ترتیب، در حالی که جمله‌ی پایانی در عبارت (ه.13) حاوی تحول آزاد میدان الکترومغناطیسی در غیاب امواج گرانشی است، سایر جملات در بردارنده‌ی آثار اندرکنش میان امواج گرانشی با میدان الکترومغناطیسی هستند. حاصل محاسبه‌ی مشاهده پذیرهای میدان الکترومغناطیسی، به حالت اولیه‌ی میدان امواج گرانشی وابسته است. در پژوهش حاضر، کمیت‌های مورد بحث را به ازای حالت‌های مختلف میدان امواج گرانشی محاسبه کرده‌ایم، از جمله: پیوستار خلاء میدان گرانشی، امواج گرانشی در حالت همدوس، امواج گرانشی در حالت چلانده‌ی تک-مُدی و حالت چلانده‌ی دومدی و نیز حالت گرمایی. به طور مثال، واریانس مؤلفه‌های کوادراتوری میدان الکترومغناطیسی در حالتی که امواج گرانشی در حالت چلانده‌ی دومدی و میدان الکترومغناطیسی در حالت همدوس $|\alpha\rangle$ به سر برند، با رابطه‌ی زیر داده می‌شود

$$\begin{aligned} [\Delta\hat{\chi}_{\vartheta}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]_{\text{is}}^2 &= 1 + 2|\alpha|^2 \left\{ e^{-|\alpha|^2(1-\cos 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{-4(\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + \mathcal{D}^{\text{is}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \right. \\ &\times \cos[-2\vartheta + 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + |\alpha|^2 \sin 4E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + 2\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)] \\ &- e^{-2|\alpha|^2(1-\cos 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} e^{-2(\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + \mathcal{D}^{\text{is}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \\ &\times \cos[-2\vartheta + 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + 2|\alpha|^2 \sin 2E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)] \\ &\left. + 1 - e^{-4|\alpha|^2 \sin^2 E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} e^{-2(\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) + \mathcal{D}^{\text{is}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t))} \right\}, \quad (\text{ه.14}) \end{aligned}$$

که در آن ϑ پارامتر تنظیم‌کننده‌ی فاز مؤلفه‌های کوادراتوری بوده و توابع دیگر به صورت زیر تعریف شده‌اند

$$\begin{aligned} E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &\equiv \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 (\Omega_K t - \sin(\Omega_K t)), \quad (\text{ه.15}) \\ \mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) (4 \sin^2(\frac{\Omega_K t}{2})) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2, \\ \mathcal{D}^{\text{is}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t) &= \sum_{\gamma} \int_{\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^3} d^3\mathbf{K} \kappa_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \left\{ (4\bar{n}_{\text{is}}(K) \sin^2(\frac{\Omega_K t}{2})) \right. \\ &\left. + \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K (\cos[2\phi_K] - 2 \cos[2\phi_K - \Omega_K t] + \cos[2\phi_K - 2\Omega_K t]) \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

در روابط بالا، $E_{\text{PI}} = 1.9561 \times 10^9 \text{ J}$ انرژی پلانک، r_K و $2\phi_K$ به ترتیب نشان‌دهنده‌ی دامنه و فاز چلانده‌ی امواج گرانشی اولیه است. نسبت تعیین‌کننده‌ی $(\hbar\omega_k / E_{\text{PI}})^2$ (که درون ضریب κ_{γ} قرار دارد) قدرت اندرکنش را مشخص می‌کند. برای بسامدهای نوری $\omega_k \sim 10^{15} \text{ Hz}$ ، این نسبت از مرتبه‌ی $\sim 10^{-58}$ است که بسیار ناچیز است. بنابراین، آشکارسازی آثار کوانتومی امواج گرانشی توسط پوششگرهای الکترومغناطیسی، منوط به شرایطی است که جفت‌شدگی بسیار ضعیف الکترومغناطیسی-گرانشی به صورت مؤثر تقویت شده باشد. اگرچه برای بسامدهای بالاتر میدان الکترومغناطیسی این جفت‌شدگی قوی‌تر است، با این حال هنوز بسیار ضعیف است. همان‌گونه که از روابط بالا پیداست، توابع $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ و $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ هر دو هم در تحولات همدوس و هم ناهمدوس میدان الکترومغناطیسی مشارکت داشته، در حالی که تابع رفتار نوسانی و احیای چلانده‌ی واریانس را رقم بزند، با توابع $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ و $\mathcal{D}^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ مشخص می‌شود، که متأسفانه در مورد سامانه‌ی الکترومغناطیسی-گرانشی این دو عامل بسیار ناچیز و در عمل قابل چشمپوشی هستند. در مقابل، تابع $\mathcal{D}^{\text{is}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ که نشان‌دهنده‌ی مشارکت ماهیت چلانده‌ی دومدی امواج گرانشی اولیه در واریانس میدان است، می‌تواند اثری مشاهده‌پذیر بر واریانس میدان برجای گذارند، منوط به آن‌که تعداد میانگین گرویتون‌ها آن قدر زیاد باشد که جفت‌شدگی ناچیز را بهبود بخشد. به عبارت دیگر، هرگاه $\bar{n}_{\text{is}}(K) \sim 10^{58}$ ، آثار امواج گرانشی اولیه بر میدان قابل رؤیت خواهد بود، هر چند این آثار در واقع موجب واهمدوسی میدان الکترومغناطیسی می‌شوند. هم‌چنین، در رابطه (ه.15) دیده می‌شود که علاوه بر تعداد میانگین گرویتون‌ها، هم‌بستگی‌های کوانتومی بین گرویتون‌ها در حالت چلانده‌ی دومدی،

که از نوع $\langle \hat{b}_K \hat{b}_K^\dagger \rangle$ و $\langle \hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{b}_K \rangle$ بوده و متناسب با $\sinh 2r_K$ هستند، سهم مضاعفی در واهمدوسی ایفا می کنند. در نهایت، با چشم پوشی از آثار ناچیز ناشی از خلاء میدان گرانشی که توسط دو تابع $E(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ و $D^{\text{vac}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)$ داده می شود، می توان رابطه (ه.14) را به صورت زیر بازنویسی کرد

$$[\Delta \hat{\chi}_\theta(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)]_{\text{ts}}^2 = 1 + 2|\alpha|^2 (e^{-2\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, t)} - 1)^2. \quad (\text{ه.16})$$

بنابراین، واریانس میدان از مقدار ابتدایی $[\Delta \hat{\chi}_\theta(t=0)]_{\text{ts}}^2 = 1$ شروع به افزایش کرده، با گذشت زمان به مقدار نهایی $1 + 2|\alpha|^2$ رسیده و در همین وضعیت مانا باقی می ماند. به طور معادل، در سامانه ی کاواک اپتومکانیک، این رفتار مشابه با حالتی است که نوسانگر مزوسکوپیک در حالت گرمایی با تعداد میانگین فونون های گرمایی \bar{n}_{th} و میدان الکترومغناطیسی در حالت همدوس $|\alpha\rangle$ باشد. در آن جا نیز، واریانس میدان از مقدار ابتدایی $[\Delta \hat{\chi}_\theta(t=0)]_{\text{th}}^2 = 1$ صعود کرده و در مقدار نهایی $1 + 2|\alpha|^2$ مانا است. بدین ترتیب، واریانس همواره مقداری بزرگتر از 1 اختیار کرده و امکان چلانندی، که متناظر با شرط $[\Delta \hat{\chi}_\theta(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)]_{\text{ts}}^2 < 1$ بوده، منتفی است. بدین ترتیب، به نظر می رسد آشکارسازی سرشت کوانتومی امواج گرانشی اولیه با برقراری مانستگی با سامانه ی کاواک اپتومکانیک، راه گشا نخواهد بود.

3 واهمدوسی ناشی از امواج گرانشی

یکی از وجوه اجتناب ناپذیر اندرکنش الکترومغناطیسی-گرانشی، واهمدوسی ناشی از گرانش است. به عبارت دیگر، همان طور که به تفصیل در متن پایان نامه بدان پرداخته شده است، اندرکنش میدان الکترومغناطیسی با پیوستاری از امواج گرانشی کوانتومی موجب از بین رفتن هم بستگی های زمانی میدان الکترومغناطیسی می شود. به طور کلی، هم بستگی های فضایی-زمانی میدان الکترومغناطیسی در حضور پس زمینه ی امواج گرانشی، نه تنها به حالت کوانتومی میدان امواج گرانشی بستگی دارد، بلکه خصوصیات آماری و هم بستگی های فضایی-زمانی میدان امواج گرانشی را نیز به ارث می برد. به طور مثال، اگر میدان امواج گرانشی بصورت آماری خصوصیات یک میدان تصادفی را داشته باشد، یعنی اختلالات فضا زمان به صورت آماری همگن، همسانگرد و غیرقطبیده باشند، این ویژگی ها در توابع هم بستگی میدان الکترومغناطیسی نیز نگاشته می شود.

به عنوان مثال، امواج گرانشی اولیه که در حالت چلانده ی دو مودی به سر می برند، خصوصیات امواج تصادفی را از خود نشان می دهند. در این مورد، نشان می دهیم که تابع هم بستگی زمانی مرتبه ی اول میدان الکترومغناطیسی (در حد تطابق مکانی) در حضور امواج گرانشی اولیه در حالت چلانده ی دو مودی، توسط رابطه ی زیر مشخص می شود

$$g_{\text{ts}}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) = g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) e^{-\mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau)}, \quad (\text{ه.17})$$

که در آن $g_{\text{vac}}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau)$ در بردارنده ی آثار ناشی از نوسانات کوانتومی میدان امواج گرانشی بوده که در عمل بسیار ناچیز و قابل چشم پوشی است. بخش دوم رابطه ی بالا، دلالت بر رفتار فروافتی هم بستگی های زمانی دارد که ناشی از سرشت امواج گرانشی در حالت چلانده ی دو مودی است و توسط رابطه ی زیر تعیین می شود

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}^{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f, \tau) = & \sum_{\gamma} \int d^3 \mathbf{K} \mathbf{K}_{\gamma}^2(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{k}) |g_{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}^o, \mathbf{x}^f)|^2 \left\{ \sinh^2 r_K \left(4 \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Omega_K \tau}{2} \right) \right) \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{1}{2} \sinh 2r_K (\cos[2\phi_K] - 2 \cos[2\phi_K - \Omega_K \tau] + \cos[2\phi_K - 2\Omega_K \tau]) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{ه.18})$$

با در نظر گرفتن $\phi_K = 0$ و نیز در شرایط آشکارسازهای کوچک که طول آنها از طول موج امواج گرانشی کوتاهتر بوده،

رابطه ی بالا به صورت زیر ساده می شود

$$\mathcal{D}^{is}(\tau) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{Pl}} \right)^2 \int d\Phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) \sin^4 \Theta_K \quad (19.هـ)$$

$$\times \int_{K_E}^{K_1} \frac{dK}{K} \frac{e^{2r_K}}{4} \left(8 \sin^4 \left(\frac{\Omega_K \tau}{2} \right) \right),$$

که در آن، فرض دامنه ی چلانگی بسیار بزرگ $1 \gg r_K$ برای امواج گرانشی اولیه اعمال شده است. برای محاسبه ی این انتگرال، رابطه (6.هـ) برای جای گذاری عبارت e^{2r_K} استفاده می شود. هم چنین، برای تخمین انتگرال و به دست آوردن حاصل انتگرال به صورت تحلیلی، می توان از این واقعیت بهره جست که سهم عمده در انتگرال بالا، مربوط به بسامدهای بسیار ریز یا طول موج های بسیار بلند است که حاوی مقادیر هنگفت محتوای گراویتونی هستند و در نتیجه می توانند آثاری مشاهده پذیر بر جای گذارند. محاسبه ی دقیق عبارت (19.هـ) این نتیجه را به دست می دهد که هم بستگی های زمانی برای زمان های تأخیر $\tau \lesssim 10^4$ s وجود داشته و برای زمان های تأخیر بیشتر از آن، هم بستگی وجود ندارد. بنابراین، تقریب $1 \ll \Omega_K \tau$ به معنای انتخاب کران بالای بسامدی $\Omega_K \lesssim 10^{-4} \text{s}^{-1}$ است. با به کارگیری این تقریب، عبارت بالا به صورت زیر ساده می شود

$$\mathcal{D}_{\phi_{K=0}}^{is}(\tau) \simeq \left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_{ts}} \right)^4, \quad (20.هـ)$$

که در آن، زمان واهمدوسی ناشی از امواج گرانشی اولیه در حالت چلانده ی دوّمدی، به صورت زیر تعریف شده است

$$\tau_{ts} = \left[\frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{Pl}} \right)^2 \int d\Phi_K \int d(\cos \Theta_K) \sin^4 \Theta_K \int_{K_E}^{K_1} \frac{dK}{K} \frac{e^{2r_K} \Omega_K^4}{8} \right]^{-1/4}. \quad (21.هـ)$$

مقدار عددی عبارت بالا، با جای گذاری رابطه (6.هـ) برای e^{2r_K} حاصل می شود. دامنه ی چلانگی r_K امواج گرانشی اولیه به پارامترهای دوره ی تورمی، نظیر نسبت تانسور به اسکالر r_{k_0} (با دامنه ی چلانگی اشتباه نشود) و نیز با اندیس تورمی β تعیین می شود. در حد آشکارسازهای کوچک $KL \ll 1$ ، زمان واهمدوسی به ازای مقدار $\beta = -2$ که توصیف گر فضازمان دوسپته در زمان تورمی است، و مقادیر $r_{k_0} = 10^{-2}$ و $r_{k_0} = 10^{-3}$ به ترتیب برابر است با $\tau_{ts} = 1.07 \times 10^4$ s و $\tau_{ts} = 1.9 \times 10^4$ s. بنابراین، افزایش نسبت تانسور به اسکالر منجر به کاهش زمان واهمدوسی می شود. این نتیجه قابل انتظار است، چرا که افزایش نسبت تانسور به اسکالر به معنای افزایش دامنه ی میدان امواج گرانشی اولیه بوده و این به صورت مؤثر اندرکنش قوی تر با میدان الکترومغناطیسی را در پی دارد. بنابراین، آثار واهمدوسی ناشی از اندرکنش گرانشی نیز سریع تر رخ می نمایند.

بدین ترتیب، انتظار می رود که اگر بتوان آزمایش تداخل سنجی ای را تدارک دید که در آن، چشمه ی میدان همدوس لیزری زمان همدوسی بیشتر از 10^4 s داشته باشد، و سپس این پویشگر به مدت 10^4 s در فضا پویش کرده و سپس هم بستگی های میدان میان لحظه ی ابتدایی و انتهای اندازه گیری شود، علی الاصول می توان رد پای امواج گرانشی اولیه را به صورت عامل واهمدوس کننده ی میدان الکترومغناطیسی، ثبت کرد. البته، این نتیجه منوط بر آن است که میدان الکترومغناطیسی در تمامی طول مدت از سایر چشمه های واهمدوسی کننده منزوی شده باشد.

از سوی دیگر، واهمدوسی گرانشی موجب ایجاد پهن شدگی پهنای خط لیزری می شود. این پهن شدگی به طور معکوس با زمان واهمدوسی در ارتباط است و برای $\tau_{ts} \sim 10^4$ s مقداری از مرتبه ی 10^{-4} Hz $\gamma_{ts} \sim$ اختیار می کند، که بسیار کوچک است. آشکارسازی چنین پهن شدگی کوچکی نیازمند ابزار دقیق با قدرت تفکیک بالا است. علاوه بر پهن شدگی طیفی، اثر دیگری که خاص امواج گرانشی اولیه در حالت چلانده ی دوّمدی است، ظهور و بروز نوارهای جانبی در طیف

الکترومغناطیسی است. مکان تقریبی وقوع این نوارهای جانبی توسط رابطه‌ی زیر به دست می‌آید

$$\omega_{\text{side}} \sim \omega_k \pm 1.2\gamma_{\text{ts}}. \quad (22)$$

به این ترتیب، پارامتر $\gamma_{\text{ts}} \sim |\omega_{\text{side}} - \omega_k| \equiv \Delta\omega$ که فاصله‌ی نوارهای جانبی با قله‌ی مرکزی طیف را مشخص می‌کند، با کاهش زمان واهمدوسی وابسته به محدوده‌ی تغییرات پارامترهای تورمی نظیر نسبت تانسور به اسکالر r_{k0} و اندیس تورمی β است. البته محدوده‌ی تغییرات این پارامترها چندان وسیع نبوده و در مجموع، نهایتاً یک مرتبه‌ی بزرگی در زمان واهمدوسی تغییر ایجاد می‌شود. با این وجود، جستجوی نوارهای جانبی در طیف الکترومغناطیسی توسط لیزرهای فوق پایدار که قابلیت تفکیک کسر بسامدی از مرتبه‌ی کوچکی $10^{-19} \sim (\gamma_{\text{ts}}/\omega_k) = \Delta\omega/\omega_k$ را دارا هستند، در آینده امکان‌پذیر است.

4 ناهمدوسی ناشی از امواج گرانشی

همان‌گونه که در بالا اشاره شد، آشکارسازی سرشت کوانتومی امواج گرانشی اولیه بر اساس ایده‌ی احیای چلانگی مؤلفه‌های کوادراتوری میدان الکترومغناطیسی عملاً ناممکن بوده، و آشکارسازی آن بر مبنای اثر واهمدوسی هم‌بستگی‌های زمانی یا از طریق پهن‌شدگی طیف توان و یا نمایان ساختن نوارهای جانبی در طیف توان، عمدتاً منوط به فناوری‌های پیشرفته و شرایط آزمایشگاهی کنترل‌شده برای منزوی کردن سامانه از سایر عوامل ناهمدوس‌کننده‌ی محیطی است. در سوی مقابل، هم‌بستگی‌های فضایی میدان الکترومغناطیسی این خاصیت منحصر به فرد را دارند، که نه تنها نسبت به نوفه‌های محیطی مقاوم هستند، بلکه با افزایش فاصله از چشمه‌ی ساطع‌کننده، این هم‌بستگی‌ها نیز گسترش می‌یابند. در چارچوب نظریه‌ی همدوسی در اپتیک، قضیه‌ی ون-سیتر-زرنیک برای توصیف هم‌بستگی‌های فضایی میدان الکترومغناطیسی ساخته و پرداخته شده است. بدین ترتیب، تابش الکترومغناطیسی از نواحی مختلف یک چشمه‌ی گسترده که در ابتدا کاملاً ناهمدوس و ناهم‌فاز است، در فواصل دوردست منجر به تشکیل طرح تداخلی می‌شود. قضیه‌ی ون-سیتر-زرنیک، بیان دقیق و فرمول‌بندی‌شده از هم‌بستگی‌های میدان الکترومغناطیسی در دو نقطه‌ی فضایی (اما هم‌زمان) را ارائه می‌کند، که ناشی از امواج تابشی از یک چشمه‌ی گسترده واقع در دوردست است که در ابتدا هیچ نوع هم‌بستگی با یکدیگر ندارند. بر این پایه، در نواحی دوردست و در نزدیکی راستایی که عمود بر سطح چشمه است، نور تابشی از چشمه‌ای قرصی با شعاع a ، در ناحیه‌ای با قطر تقریبی $d_{\text{coh}} \approx 2/(k\theta)$ اصطلاحاً همدوس است. در این رابطه، k طول موج مرکزی چشمه‌ی شبه-تک‌رنگ و $\theta = 2a/R$ قطر زاویه‌ای چشمه است که از زمین دیده می‌شود. هم‌چنین، R فاصله‌ی چشمه تا زمین است. در نتیجه، اگر تابش الکترومغناطیسی در فضای آزاد منتشرشده و در فاصله‌ی رسیدن تا زمین دستخوش تغییر و اندرکنشی نشود که هم‌بستگی‌ها را تضعیف کند، طرح تداخلی قابل رؤیت است.

استفاده از مفهوم هم‌بستگی‌های فضایی، در ابتدا به منظور اندازه‌گیری قطر زاویه‌ای ستاره‌ی ساگیتاریوس در آزمایش تداخل سنجی هانبری-براون-توئیس مورد استفاده قرار گرفت. امروزه، تداخل سنج‌های خط پایه‌ی بسیار طولانی، به منظور اندازه‌گیری ویژگی‌های ظاهری اجرام بسیار دوردست نظیر تپ‌اخترها، بر اساس اندازه‌گیری هم‌بستگی‌های فضایی امواج الکترومغناطیسی رادیویی تابشی از آن‌ها، به طور گسترده مورد بهره‌برداری قرار گرفته است. فراتر از آن، در سال‌های اخیر استفاده از شگرد تصویربرداری توسط تداخل سنج‌های خط پایه‌ی بسیار طولانی، در مباحث کیهان‌شناسی نیز جایگاه ویژه‌ای پیدا کرده است. به عنوان مثال، تلسکوپ افق رویداد که برای تصویربرداری از سیاه‌چاله‌های فوق سنگین طراحی شده است، با اندازه‌گیری دقیق متریک کر، انحراف از نسبت عام را می‌سنجد. از سوی دیگر، پروژه‌ی کیهان‌شناختی مگامیزر، که از فناوری تداخل سنجی خط پایه‌ی بسیار طولانی برای نگاشت موقعیت اجرام فشرده در آسمان با دقت زیر-میلی ثانیه‌ی قوسی بهره می‌برد، آزمایشگاهی جدید، در ترازوی با سایر نقشه‌برداری‌های متداول بر مبنای تابش زمینه‌ی کیهانی، برای مقید کردن ثابت هابل و نیز به‌روزرسانی قیدهای کنونی بر جرم سیاه‌چاله‌های فوق سنگین ارائه کرده است. به ویژه، توانایی موشکافانه‌ی تداخل سنج خط پایه‌ی بسیار طولانی در اندازه‌گیری قطر زاویه‌ای-قرمزگرایی ($\theta - z$) تپ‌اخترها، این نتیجه‌ی شگفت‌انگیز را به دنبال داشته است که می‌توان هسته‌های کهکشانی فعال را به عنوان خط‌کش‌های استاندارد

با ابعاد ذاتی $11.03 \text{ pc} \sim \ell_m$ در نظر گرفت که به نوبه‌ی خود در مقید کردن پارامترهای کیهان‌شناختی نظیر ثابت هابل، پارامتر چگالی ماده‌ی تاریک و انرژی تاریک، سودمند است. با این وجود، تا کنون تلاشی برای به‌کارگیری داده‌های اندازه‌گیری شده‌ی قطر زاویه‌ای-فرم‌گراییِ تپ‌اخترها توسط تداخل‌سنج‌های خط پایه‌ی بسیار طولانی، به منظور مقید کردن امواج گرانشی اولیه انجام نشده است. این موضوع مخصوصاً از این نظر حائز اهمیت است که تابش رادیویی این اجرام به مدت کافی در معرض برهم‌کنش با میدان امواج گرانشی پس‌زمینه بوده است و بنابراین آثار این برهم‌کنش می‌باید بر هم‌بستگی‌های فضایی تابش الکترومغناطیسی ثبت شده باشد.

بدین ترتیب، با بهره‌گیری از چارچوبی که برای توصیف اندرکنش الکترومغناطیسی-گرانشی برپا ساخته‌ایم، به بررسی هم‌بستگی‌های فضایی تابش اجرام دور دست پرداخته و نشان می‌دهیم که امواج گرانشی اولیه در حالت چلانده‌ی دوّمُدی می‌توانند باعث از بین رفتن این هم‌بستگی‌ها شوند. این پدیده را اصطلاحاً ناهمدوسی ناشی از امواج گرانشی می‌نامیم. با انجام محاسبات، نشان می‌دهیم که تابع نمایانی به صورت نمایی با فاصله‌ی میان دو آشکارساز افت می‌کند، که از رابطه‌ی زیر به دست می‌آید

$$\mathcal{V}_{\text{ts}}(\mathbf{x}_C, t) = 2 \Re \left\{ \int_0^1 du u e^{-\left(\frac{\nu^2}{2(k\xi_{\text{ts}})^2} u^2\right)} (J_0(\nu u) J_0\left(i \frac{\nu^2}{2(k\xi_{\text{ts}})^2} u^2\right) + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-i)^n J_{2n}(\nu u) J_n\left(i \frac{\nu^2}{2(k\xi_{\text{ts}})^2} u^2\right)) \right\}. \quad (23.ه)$$

که در آن، $\nu = kd\theta/2$ ، d فاصله‌ی میان دو آشکارساز و θ قطر زاویه‌ای ستاره بوده و ξ_{ts} نشان‌دهنده‌ی طول ناهمدوسی ناشی از امواج گرانشی اولیه در حالت چلانده‌ی دوّمُدی، به صورت زیر تعریف شده است

$$\xi_{\text{ts}}(R, t) = \left[\frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{E_{\text{pl}}}\right)^2 \int dK \left(\frac{K e^{2r_K}}{4}\right) \left(8 \sin^2\left(\frac{\Omega_K t}{2}\right) \sin^2\left(\frac{2\phi_K - \Omega_K t}{2}\right)\right) \right. \\ \times \int_0^{2\pi} d\Phi_K \int_0^\pi d(\cos \Theta_K) \sum_{\lambda=+, \times} \left| \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} (i^\ell) \frac{2\ell+1}{2\pi} \left(\int d\Omega_{\hat{r}} e^{i\lambda} [\hat{\mathbf{K}}] \hat{r}_i \hat{r}_j P_\ell(\cos \gamma) \right) \right. \\ \left. \times \left(\frac{j_\ell(KR)}{(KR)} - \frac{\int_0^{KR} j_\ell(u) du}{(KR)^2} \right) \right]^2 \Big]^{-1/2}, \quad (24.ه)$$

به این ترتیب، تعداد میانگین گراویتون‌ها و نیز هم‌بستگی‌های کوانتومی از نوع $\langle \hat{b}_K \hat{b}_K \rangle$ و نیز $\langle \hat{b}_K^\dagger \hat{b}_K^\dagger \rangle$ در حالت چلانده‌ی دوّمُدی، در فرایند ناهمدوسی مشارکت دارند. همان‌طور که پیداست، این طول مشخصه به زمان اندرکنش میان موج الکترومغناطیسی و امواج گرانشی بستگی دارد. برای اجرامی که در فواصل کیهانی از ما فرار گرفته‌اند، مانند تپ‌اخترها و هسته‌های کهکشانی فعال، می‌توانیم زمان و فاصله را بر حسب فرم‌گرایی ستاره z ، به صورت زیر بیان کنیم

$$t(z) = H_0^{-1} \int_0^z \frac{dz'}{\sqrt{(1 - \Omega_m)(1 + z')^2 + \Omega_m(1 + z')^5}}, \quad (25.ه)$$

$$R(z) = \frac{c}{H_0(1+z)} \left(\int_0^z \frac{dz'}{\sqrt{\Omega_m(1+z')^3 + (1 - \Omega_m)}} \right).$$

در این رابطه، Ω_m و Ω_Λ به ترتیب کسر چگالی انرژی تاریک و ماده‌ی تاریک را نشان می‌دهند. بنابراین، طول ناهمدوسی ξ_{ts} بر حسب فرم‌گرایی چشمه قابل بیان است.

آشکارسازی موفقیت‌آمیز اجرام دور دست توسط روش‌های تداخل‌سنجی، گواهی بر این مدعا است که برهم‌کنش با امواج گرانشی پس‌زمینه نتوانسته است هم‌بستگی‌های فضایی میدان را، در طول فضایی d_{coh} از بین ببرد. به عبارت دیگر،

همان طور که از رابطه‌ی (ه.23) پیداست، آثار ناهمدوسی ناشی از امواج گرانشی اولیه در صورتی قابل مشاهده است که

$$k \xi_{\text{is}}(z) \gtrsim \nu = k d \theta / 2. \quad (\text{ه.26})$$

طول مشخصه‌ی ناهمدوسی $\xi_{\text{is}}(z)$ با کمیت تانسور به اسکالر r_{k_0} مرتبط است که در واقع شدت جفت‌شدگی با امواج گرانشی اولیه را تنظیم می‌کند. با توجه به حد بالای این کمیت، $r_{k_0} \lesssim 0.032$ ، که توسط ماهواره‌ی پلانک به ثبت رسیده است، کاشف به عمل می‌آید که مقدار کمیت بدون بُعد $k \xi_{\text{is}}$ در محدوده‌ی قرمزگرایی $0 \leq z \leq 5$ همواره مقداری بیشتر از 10^6 اختیار کرده و بنابراین اثر ناهمدوسی امواج گرانشی اولیه به قدری ضعیف بوده که قابلیت آشکارسازی آن‌ها بر اساس تداخل‌سنج‌های خط پایه‌ی بسیار طولانی⁸ امکان‌پذیر نیست. البته باید خاطر نشان کرد که در بررسی کنونی، اثر ناهمدوسی ناشی از اختلالات نرده‌ای فضا‌زمان بر هم‌بستگی‌های فضایی میدان الکترومغناطیسی نادیده گرفته شد. این امر ممکن است نتایج کنونی را تغییر دهد، چرا که انتظار می‌رود همگرایی گرانشی ایجاد شده توسط اختلالات مادی به‌عنوان سازوکاری در جهت ناهم‌فازی میدان الکترومغناطیسی عمل کنند. در این راستا، چارچوب حاضر را می‌توان به‌طور مستقیم تعمیم داد تا ناهم‌فازی القاشده توسط اختلالات چگالی اولیه را نیز در بر بگیرد.

از سوی دیگر، برهم‌کنش امواج گرانشی اولیه با میدان‌های مادی، در دوران‌های پس از تولید آن‌ها در زمان تورمی، می‌تواند حالت کوانتومی امواج گرانشی اولیه را تغییر داده و آن‌ها را به حالت‌های همدوس تبدیل کند. از این رو، اثر برهم‌کنش‌های بعدی بر امواج گرانشی اولیه نیازمند بررسی‌های بیشتری است که می‌توان آن را در چارچوب کنونی مورد مطالعه قرار داد.

⁸Very long baseline interferometers